

Review and testing methods for Harmful Algal Blooms, invasive species, jellyfish blooms, and top predators

Deliverable 5.2

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1. GES4SEAS Project Summary

Human activities at sea (e.g., maritime transport, extraction of living and non-living resources, etc.) and coastal areas (e.g., agriculture, leisure, and recreation, etc.) have expanded considerably, leading to an increased level of pressures and subsequent degradation of ocean health and, ultimately, human health. Single and cumulative impacts of these activities are likely to increase, driven by human demands and enhanced by climate change.

Human activities evolve following socio-economic drivers leading to pressures, which often are studied in isolation from each other even though their impacts on marine ecosystems can interact, making the effects cumulative (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic or a combination). Knowledge on these interactions and their cumulative effects in the marine environment has increased in recent years, but huge challenges remain to be solved. Thus, there is little predictability with which to inform decision-making processes, especially on ecological tipping points, which, if exceeded, could lead to a point of no-return for the system, i.e. a regime shift. In this context, an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach to the management of human activities at sea and on land should ensure that the combined pressure of such activities is kept within levels compatible with the requirements of Good Environmental Status (GES) (within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive – MSFD), against a background of climate change. This means that the capacity of marine and coastal ecosystems to respond to human-induced changes is not compromised, enabling the sustainable use of marine goods and services by present and future generations.

Thus, the main objective of GES4SEAS is to inform and guide marine governance in minimizing human pressures and their impacts on marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning while maintaining the sustainable delivery of ecosystem services. This will be achieved through developing an innovative and flexible toolbox, tested, validated, demonstrated and upscaled in the context of an adaptive EBM approach. The toolbox will allow competent authorities to assess and predict the effect of multiple stressors (including climate change) and pressures from human activities, at the national, sub-regional, regional and European levels. Ultimately, this will help achieving GES, and support different policies at national, European and global levels (e.g., Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), Biodiversity Strategy 2030, United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)).

Stakeholders and the key competent authorities (including national, regional and European levels) are integrated in a Practitioner Advisory Board (PAB) to co-create and validate the toolbox and the EBM

approach. This will result in a real problem-solving approach with iterative and incremental development steps.

GES4SEAS will also rely on existing EU and non-EU multi-actor networks to involve and engage with stakeholders. This multi-actor approach will ensure that the research and deliverables are relevant to marine managers all around the world. Lastly, it is important to highlight that the toolbox will be tested and demonstrated at 11 Learning Sites (LSs) covering all European regional seas (also overseas). Thus, it is expected that GES4SEAS will achieve Technological and Societal Readiness Levels 6. This will be achieved by the participation of 20 partners, covering the four European regional seas and Canada.

It is expected that GES4SEAS will:

- Operationalise integrative and holistic solutions for EBM based on a software toolbox for analysing, assessing and mapping cumulative pressures, GES and ecosystem services.

- Provide evidence and training to key stakeholders of the benefits of using the toolbox that will be developed in GES4SEAS for assessing the environmental status of marine waters and the ecosystem services considering the effects of multiple pressures, so opt for using it.

- Ensure the EBM approach and provide guidelines for the management of Invasive Alien Species (IAS), Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), jellyfish outbreaks, and top predators.

- Investigate the best ways to obtain thresholds of GES and tipping points (system breaking points) using models.

- Reach and engage a wider society, and specifically young people and educators, on key messages stemming from this project, so GES4SEAS contributes to societal ocean literacy and responsible behaviours.

2. Deliverable 5.2 executive summary

Deliverable 5.2 aims to develop, refine, and implement a suite of innovative methods to assess and manage HABs, invasive species, jellyfish blooms, and top predators—stressors of increasing concern across European marine ecosystems, which were developed in Deliverable 2.2². The objective is to enhance the capacity of EBM to address these issues by using an integrative methodological framework that combines cutting-edge monitoring, modelling, and analytical tools. This includes:

1. **Satellite remote sensing** to detect and map spatial-temporal dynamics of phytoplankton blooms, turbidity, sea surface temperature, and other indicators related to HABs and jellyfish events.
2. **Lagrangian particle tracking models** assimilating Copernicus products to simulate the transport of invasive species, HABs, and jellyfish under current and future (2050) climate scenarios.
3. **Molecular tools** (e.g. eDNA) to assess species identification, distribution, population structure, and ecological interactions, and compare them with conventional monitoring approaches.
4. **Cumulative impact assessment** based on an expanded version of the **CIMPAL** framework to quantify ecological risks across all European seas by integrating species-habitat relationships and impact strength.
5. **Biologging and telemetry** of top predators to assess spatiotemporal overlaps with human pressures, thereby identifying high-risk areas and informing spatial management strategies

Deliverable 5.2 operationalizes EBM by producing ready-to-use, scalable, and scientifically validated methodologies that tackle key biological components and stressors affecting marine ecosystems. It integrates state-of-the-art modelling and observation techniques to predict, map, and manage

² Katsanevakis S, Sagarminaga Y, Fortuna CM, Amorim E, Birchenough SNR, Boicenco L, Borrello P, Bosch-Belmar M, Brasseur S, Bresnan E, Bueno-Pardo J, Camp J, Coll M, Claver C, de Angelis R, Doyle T, Ferrer L, Fernández-Corredor E, France J, Fortibuoni T, Franco A, Frascchetti S, Fumarola LM, Garcés E, Garcia-Garin O, Giménez J, Holland MM, Jakobsen HH, Jaspers C, Knudsen SW, Kobos J, Lanzén A, Leone A, Leoni V, Louzao M, Lynam CP, Magaletti E, Mazaris AD, Machairopoulou M, Montero N, Nikolaou A, Olenin S, Pagou K, Peck MA, Pedrajas A, Piraino S, Puntilla-Dodd R, Raicevich S, Ramírez F, Ransijn J, Reñé A, Revilla M, Rilov G, Rodríguez GJ, Russell DJF, Sampedro N, Sbragaglia V, Serena F, Spada E, Stæhr PAU, Stern R, Stranga Y, Teixeira H, Tidbury HJ, Tsirintanis K, Tsirtsis G, van Leeuwen A, Papadopoulou N, Elliott M, Borja A, 2023. GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.2. Technical report on the state-of-the-art in support of Ecosystem-Based Management approaches to address Harmful Algal Blooms, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators. 337 pp.

ecological risks. This task is essential for delivering spatially explicit risk assessments and management options that align with the MSFD, EU Biodiversity Strategy, and SDGs. The methodologies developed support proactive, adaptive management and foster cross-regional harmonization—cornerstones of modern EBM. This deliverable presents 25 case studies across the four European regional seas (Baltic, North-East Atlantic, Mediterranean, and Black Sea).

Chapter four evaluated the application of satellite imagery processing and analysis to map HABs, invasive species distributions, and jellyfish bloom events through five case studies:

Case Study 1: Risk assessment of Harmful Phytoplankton Blooms in the NW Mediterranean Sea

This study assessed HABs risk along the Catalan coast (NW Mediterranean) by analyzing long-term phytoplankton monitoring data from harbours (2000–2012) and beaches (2000–2023), using species-specific abundance thresholds to classify bloom incidence. Results revealed that all harbours exhibited some bloom risk, with high-risk sites scattered along the coast and dominated by toxin-producing dinoflagellates, while beach risk was more spatially heterogeneous, with high-risk zones mainly in the north of the Catalan coast due to high-biomass species. Seasonal risk peaked in spring and summer, especially in confined harbour environments that promote water column stability and bloom development. The study highlights the importance of local environmental conditions and anthropogenic pressures in shaping HABs dynamics and demonstrates that risk-based site classification is a practical tool for guiding monitoring and management.

Case Study 2: Cyanobacteria bloom interpretation and forecasting in the Baltic Sea

This study developed a machine learning-based model—specifically a random forest classifier—to forecast summer cyanobacterial blooms in the northern Baltic Sea, including the Gulf of Bothnia, using satellite-derived bloom data (2003–2023) as the response variable and winter nutrient concentrations (DIN, DIP), May air temperature, and spatial coordinates as predictors. The model achieved high accuracy (87.3%) and identified DIP as the most influential factor, with bloom risk highest in the Gulf of Finland, Northern Baltic Proper, Archipelago Sea, and southern Bothnian Sea. Visual validation against 2024 satellite composites showed good agreement, albeit with some spatial overestimations near the Swedish coast. Sensitivity analysis indicated that even modest nutrient reductions could meaningfully lower bloom risk. The findings highlight the potential of machine learning for spatially explicit forecasting of harmful algal blooms in data-rich but process-model-limited marine environments.

Case Study 3: Environmental drivers of HABs in Black Sea and Aegean coastal waters: Critical thresholds for increased risk of HAB formation

This study applied the Random Forest (RF) machine learning algorithm to identify key environmental drivers of HABs in the western Black Sea and Aegean Sea, using data on nutrient concentrations (DIN, DIP), temperature, and salinity to predict phytoplankton presence and abundance at the genus level. Across both regions, temperature and salinity were consistently the most important predictors, with salinity dominating in the more variable Black Sea and temperature in the relatively stable Aegean. For specific harmful genera (e.g., *Dinophysis*, *Prorocentrum*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*), thresholds for high-biomass risk were derived, showing species- and site-specific preferences for environmental conditions. Despite regional differences, RF proved effective in establishing interpretable risk thresholds, suggesting its utility in integrated ecological status assessments and predictive tools for marine management.

Case study 4: Critical thresholds of environmental drivers of HABs in Danish waters (Learning Site 3): the role of time lags in the prediction of HABs

This study applied the RF machine learning algorithm to identify environmental drivers of HABs in Danish coastal waters, using data from five long-term monitoring stations. Temperature and salinity emerged as the most important predictors of phytoplankton presence and abundance, with nutrients (DIN and DIP) contributing less consistently. For HAB-forming genera (*Prorocentrum*, *Pseudochattonella*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Skeletonema*), threshold conditions for high biomass were derived, with *Prorocentrum* and *Pseudochattonella* showing consistent responses to environmental variables across stations. Time-lag analyses revealed that species-specific delays (from one week to one month) between environmental change and bloom development improve model correlations, suggesting physiological or ecological inertia. These results highlight the importance of incorporating species traits and time lags into early warning tools for HAB management.

Case study 5: Satellite data to generate Chl-a indicators in the Romanian coast

This study assessed eutrophication status in Romanian Black Sea waters using the 75th percentile (P75) of chlorophyll-a concentrations derived from both satellite and in-situ data (2010–2022), applying the MSFD D5.2.1 indicator. Results showed strong agreement between the two data sources in open marine waters (R^2 up to 0.78), moderate correlation in transitional ($R^2 = 0.38$) and coastal waters ($R^2 = 0.26$), and no statistically significant differences in P75 means across all water body types. Satellite-derived chlorophyll-a values tended to overestimate concentrations slightly, particularly in optically complex nearshore areas, but overall remained within ecological thresholds, indicating acceptable trophic status. Transitional waters emerged as the most variable and closest to exceeding thresholds, underscoring their vulnerability. The study supports integrating satellite and in-situ data

in MSFD monitoring, while stressing the need for continued algorithm refinement and validation in dynamic coastal zones.

Chapter five explores the use of Lagrangian particle tracking models to simulate and predict the transport and dispersal pathways of marine organisms, with applications to jellyfish blooms, habitat limitation, and coral larval connectivity through three case studies:

Case study 6: Lagrangian model to estimate the origin of jellyfish blooms along the Spanish coast

This study used backward Lagrangian particle tracking simulations to reconstruct the origin and drift path of a Portuguese man-of-war (*Physalia physalis*) swarm that stranded along the Galician coast in February 2014. By modelling trajectories with the SOFT tool using various wind drag coefficients ($CD = 0.02, 0.04, 0.06$) and drift angles ($\pm 50^\circ$), the researchers found that the swarm likely originated in the open North Atlantic Ocean, probably south of 49.76° N—consistent with the subtropical habitat of *P. physalis* and suggesting most individuals were right-handed. The model showed that drift trajectories were largely shaped by the sequence of intense storms that struck Western Europe in winter 2013–14. The study highlights the sensitivity of trajectory predictions to wind drag coefficients and supports the use of wind-driven drift models to understand jellyfish-like organism dispersal and inform early-warning systems.

Case study 7: Substrate availability as a limiting factor in the distribution of adult jellyfish (Scyphozoa) in the North Sea

This modelling study assessed how the expansion of offshore structures, especially wind farms, may alter the distribution of *Aurelia aurita* jellyfish in the North Sea by simulating ephyrae dispersal under three scenarios: natural coarse sediments, existing (2023) anthropogenic structures, and projected 2050 offshore wind developments. Results showed that natural substrates largely explain current jellyfish distributions, with dense aggregations in the western and central North Sea. While artificial structures present by 2023 contributed modestly to jellyfish presence, future wind farm expansion is projected to increase jellyfish density notably in the northern and southern North Sea, shifting spatial patterns. These findings support the hypothesis that ocean sprawl could enhance jellyfish blooms, but further work is needed to quantify polyp densities across substrates and assess interannual variability.

Case study 8 - Estimating Larval Dispersal of the Cold-Water Coral *Lophelia pertusa* in the Gulf of Cádiz: Enhancing Distribution Understanding and Conservation Strategies

This study used biophysical modeling to investigate larval dispersal and connectivity of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* in the Gulf of Cádiz, a key biogeographic transition zone. Simulations

incorporating larval behavior and temperature-dependent pelagic larval duration (PLD) showed that while active dispersal allowed some larvae to reach the Mediterranean and Canary Islands, most settled near their release sites, revealing strong local retention. Settlement success was highest in the Gulf of Cádiz and Moroccan Margin, particularly at sites like Cádiz-Diapiric Ridge and Pompeia Coral Mound, while connectivity between regions remained low. The Vulcões de Lama area and Cabo de São Vicente emerged as potential connectivity hubs, reinforcing the need for a strategically connected MPA network. Findings emphasize that under climate change, reduced PLD may further limit connectivity, underscoring the vulnerability of isolated coral populations and the importance of protecting known reefs and identifying yet-undiscovered ones.

Chapter 6 demonstrates how molecular techniques, particularly eDNA metabarcoding, can complement or enhance traditional monitoring methods for assessing marine biodiversity, harmful algal blooms, and non-indigenous species through five case studies:

Case study 9: Comparing 18S metabarcoding and microscopy for HAB monitoring in the Bay of Biscay

This study compared traditional light microscopy with 18S rRNA-based eDNA metabarcoding to monitor HAB taxa at two time-series stations off the Basque coast in the Bay of Biscay. While microscopy identified more species-level taxa, metabarcoding revealed far greater overall diversity and detected certain genera (e.g. *Karlodinium*, *Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis*) more frequently, especially in the larger size fraction (3–200 µm), reflecting higher sensitivity for HAB surveillance. Both methods captured key HAB-forming genera like *Heterosigma* and *Lingulodinium*, but some species were only detected by one method, highlighting their complementarity. The study also noted the overlooked detection of picoplanktonic HAB species such as *Aureococcus anophagefferens* in microscopy surveys. Overall, eDNA metabarcoding offers a scalable and sensitive tool for routine HAB monitoring, particularly when combined with targeted qPCR assays and improved reference databases.

Case study 10: Non-indigenous species screening using DNA metabarcoding of coastal and estuarine bulk community samples

This study explored the use of COI-based metabarcoding on bulk macrobenthic invertebrate samples from the Basque coast (2018–2024) to detect non-indigenous species (NIS), comparing results with morphology-based monitoring and reference databases. Of 60 NIS flagged, 32 were confirmed as non-native to Western Europe, with six species—three new to the Bay of Biscay—detected for the first time in the region (e.g. *Blackfordia virginica*, *Moerisia inkermanica*, *Chaetogammarus ischnus*). Only five of these metabarcoding detections overlapped with historical morphological records, while 20 known NIS were missed by metabarcoding, highlighting both complementarity and current

limitations. The results support metabarcoding as a promising tool for early detection of benthic NIS, though they also stress the need for improved taxonomic reference databases and targeted validation to avoid misidentifications.

Case study 11: Testing the use of eDNA as a complementary tool to underwater transect surveys

This case study explores the integration of eDNA metabarcoding with traditional visual census methods to enhance biodiversity monitoring in key Mediterranean sites. Three study areas were proposed: Cap de Creus (a Natura 2000 site), urban beaches in Barcelona, and offshore habitats for highly mobile pelagic species. Despite limited initial funding, the Cap de Creus site has secured support through collaborations with the “HumanFear” project and the Marie Curie “PETRIFY” fellowship. The upcoming fieldwork (2025–2027) will combine water and sediment eDNA sampling with fish and invertebrate visual censuses to assess the ecological effects of no-take Marine Protected Areas. The study aims to demonstrate the feasibility of using eDNA metabarcoding to complement existing monitoring frameworks and support adaptive conservation planning.

Case study 12: Exploring the potential of eDNA metabarcoding for assessing phytoplankton diversity and abundance in coastal environments

This study assessed phytoplankton diversity in coastal Mediterranean waters using both traditional microscopy and eDNA metabarcoding targeting the 18S rDNA V4 region. Seasonal and bloom-related samples revealed that metabarcoding excels at detecting small, cryptic dinoflagellates (e.g. *Ansanella*, *Heterocapsa*), showing higher genus- and species-level concordance in bloom samples (up to 94.1% and 74.2%, respectively). However, discrepancies were found due to factors such as ribosomal gene copy number variation, primer biases, extracellular DNA, and incomplete reference databases. While some taxa were uniquely detected by each method, overall, the study demonstrates that eDNA metabarcoding is a robust and complementary tool for improving the resolution and sensitivity of phytoplankton monitoring in marine ecosystems.

Case study 13: Metabarcoding of eDNA to assess NIS and hazardous phytoplankton in three Italian ports

This study applied a multi-marker eDNA metabarcoding approach (targeting 18S rRNA V4, V7, V9, COI, and rbcL) to water and sediment samples from three major Italian ports, comparing results with classical morphological methods to assess biodiversity and detect NIS. Metabarcoding identified 1,484 species (including 31 NIS and 44 hazardous phytoplankton species), significantly more than the 752 species detected morphologically, although only 5.5% overlapped between the two methods. While metabarcoding proved more sensitive—especially for cryptic, early-stage, or previously

undocumented taxa—it also faced limitations related to the incompleteness of reference databases, PCR biases, and the potential for false positives due to eDNA persistence. The study supports eDNA metabarcoding as a powerful, complementary tool for NIS early detection and biodiversity surveillance in port monitoring, while underscoring the need for improved barcode coverage and integration with RNA-based methods for better inference of organism viability.

Chapter 7 presents the new developments in the CIMPAL family of indices for mapping cumulative (positive or negative) impacts of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms on biodiversity or ecosystem services through eight case studies:

Case study 14: Expansion of CIMPAL to account for the impacts of HABs and jellyfish blooms

This study introduces and applies an extended version of the CIMPAL index—CIMPAL-JH—to assess the cumulative ecological impacts of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms in the Aegean Sea. The new index incorporates interspecific interactions and accounts for cumulative impacts across 10 habitat types. Findings reveal that cumulative impacts are greatest in shallow coastal areas, particularly the Thermaikos and Saronikos Gulfs, with IAS contributing the most, followed by jellyfish blooms and HABs. Key impactful taxa include *Mnemiopsis leidy*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Rhizostoma pulmo*, and *Mesodinium rubrum*. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating multiple invasion drivers and ecological interactions into impact assessments, providing a scalable tool for ecosystem-based management and spatial planning. It also calls for enhanced data on bloom dynamics and interspecific interactions to refine future applications.

Case study 15: New developments in CIMPAL

This study presents a major expansion of the CIMPAL index within the GES4SEAS project, transforming it into a flexible, modular tool implemented in R for assessing cumulative impacts of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms. Key innovations include the integration of multiple data formats (point occurrences and polygons), incorporation of variable Magnitude of Impact (MoI) per observation, and the inclusion of biotic interactions using GloBI data. The workflow also supports automated visualisation and calculation of species-specific impact indices, enhancing reproducibility and usability. Tested across GES4SEAS Learning Sites, the new R-based CIMPAL package—soon to be publicly available via GitHub and Zenodo—offers a versatile, scalable platform for evidence-based marine management under complex, data-rich scenarios.

Case study 16: Implementation of expanded CIMPAL in the European Seas – LS10

This pan-European study represents the most comprehensive assessment to date of the cumulative negative impacts of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms on marine biodiversity across European seas using the expanded CIMPAL framework. It integrates high-resolution spatial data, updated species distributions, and a novel consideration of interspecific biotic interactions to generate impact maps across 15 marine habitat types. Findings reveal that while HABs affect less than 1% of the area (primarily in the Aegean and Black Seas), jellyfish blooms impact nearly 10%, with hotspots in the Black Sea and Northern Adriatic. The implementation of automated, standardised workflows for data harmonisation, impact scoring, and spatial analysis marks a significant advancement in reproducible and policy-relevant cumulative impact assessments, paving the way for improved support to MSFD, regional conventions, and national biodiversity strategies.

Case study 17: Implementation of CIMPAL in the Gulf of Bothnia (LS1)

This study applied the CIMPAL method to assess cumulative impacts of invasive species and HABs in the Gulf of Bothnia (LS1), using 7 NIS and 1 HAB layer over 14 habitat types. *Marezzelleria* spp. accounted for 75% of the total impact, dominating 10 of the 14 habitat types, followed by *Cercopagis pengoi* (12%) and cyanobacteria blooms (11%). The most impacted areas were the southern Finnish coast, with minor hotspots along the Swedish side. The study emphasizes that while some invasive species (e.g., *Marezzelleria* spp.) may have neutral or even beneficial roles, others, such as *Neogobius melanostomus* and *Rhithropanopeus harrisi*, pose significant ecological threats; thus, proactive management should focus on preventing new introductions and evaluating species-specific impacts for targeted restoration efforts.

Case study 18: Implementation of CIMPAL in LS9

This study applied the CIMPAL index to assess cumulative ecological impacts of invasive jellyfish (*Mnemiopsis leidyi*, *Beroe ovata*) and tintinnid species in the Romanian Black Sea from 2018–2023, revealing distinct hotspots of invasion pressure—especially near the Danube Delta and the ports of Constanța and Mangalia. These areas face compounded risks from maritime traffic, ballast water discharge, nutrient inputs, and hydrological conditions that favour opportunistic NIS. *M. leidyi* emerged as a major disruptor of trophic dynamics, while *B. ovata*—though initially restorative—also introduced ecological complexity. The findings highlight the need for strengthened monitoring, ballast water regulation, and habitat restoration to bolster resilience. While the CIMPAL framework proved effective for visualizing spatial patterns of invasion, the study recommends refining impact estimates

with empirical data and expanding assessments to include benthic habitats and food web dynamics for a more comprehensive management approach.

Case study 19: CIMPAL+: accounting for cumulative positive impacts on biodiversity

This study introduces CIMPAL+, a novel framework expanding the original CIMPAL index to assess and map the *positive* cumulative impacts of NIS on native biodiversity, using the Aegean Sea as a case study. Sixteen NIS were evaluated, revealing that coastal habitats in the South Aegean, particularly shallow soft and hard substrates, experienced the highest positive impacts, with the non-indigenous seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* demonstrating the highest positive cumulative impacts. Positive impacts arose mainly from habitat creation and food provision, though these do not offset negative impacts, which remain higher overall. CIMPAL+ also incorporated interspecific interactions, improving impact resolution. While offering a more balanced impact view, the study emphasizes that positive effects should be considered independent, not compensatory to negative impacts, guiding nuanced and evidence-based marine biodiversity management.

Case study 20: CIMPAL-ES⁻ and CIMPAL-ES⁺: accounting for cumulative impacts on ecosystem services

This study introduces CIMPAL-ES, a novel spatially explicit index designed to assess and map both the *negative* and *positive* cumulative impacts of IAS on marine ecosystem services. Applied to the Mediterranean and Aegean Seas, the index integrates species distribution data, habitat associations, and standardized impact weights across 14 ecosystem services. Results reveal high spatial heterogeneity, with hotspots of negative impacts (e.g., food provision and lifecycle maintenance) concentrated in shallow coastal areas, particularly in the southern Aegean and Adriatic regions, while positive impacts (e.g., coastal protection, cognitive effects) are more widespread in the Aegean-Levantine Sea. Species such as *Caulerpa cylindracea* demonstrated both high positive and negative scores, highlighting complex ecological roles. While the framework offers a transparent, scalable tool for management prioritization and policy, limitations include assumptions of spatially constant impacts, gaps in offshore data, and simplified treatment of human infrastructure. The authors advocate future enhancements including monetary valuation, integration of impact synergies, and application in cost-benefit scenarios to inform adaptive, ecosystem-based IAS management.

Case study 21: Implementation of CIMPAL for the impacts of jellyfish blooms, IAS and HABs in the Adriatic Sea

This study applied the CIMPAL index to assess the cumulative impacts of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs across the Italian Adriatic Sea, identifying 530 impacted 1×1 km grid cells, with the highest

cumulative scores concentrated in the northern and central coastal zones. The most impacted habitats were pelagic waters—mainly from jellyfish (e.g., *Rhizostoma pulmo*, *Mnemiopsis leidyi*) and invasive bivalves (*Magallana gigas*, *Ruditapes philippinarum*)—followed by shallow soft substrates and lagoons affected by IAS and *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*. *M. leidyi*, *A. transversa*, and *M. gigas* emerged as the top-ranking IAS based on extent and impact intensity. Jellyfish blooms, particularly in the north, exerted widespread and consistent pressure on fish recruitment and trophic dynamics, while *O. cf. ovata* caused intense but spatially limited ecological stress. The study demonstrates the utility of integrating citizen science with standardised spatial impact assessments to identify ecological hotspots and inform adaptive marine management, though it highlights persistent gaps in field-based data and impact validation.

Chapter 8 presents the use of biologging for top predators monitoring, recent advances, and applications through four case studies:

Case study 22: Analysing bycatch risk of the European shag (*Gulosus aristotelis*) in small-scale Basque fisheries through integration of species tracking and AIS data

This case study assessed bycatch risk to juvenile European shags (*Gulosus aristotelis*) from small-scale fisheries in the Basque Country by integrating GPS and dive tracking of 14 tagged birds with AIS-based fishing effort data. Core foraging zones for shags overlapped spatially with key artisanal fishing grounds—particularly those used by netters and longliners—highlighting high-risk coastal areas, especially around the Bilbao estuary, the coastal stretch from the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve to Mutriku, and along the eastern Basque coast. The study identified spatially explicit zones of high, medium, and low risk of incidental capture, revealing potential for gear-specific interactions and underscoring the vulnerability of juveniles. It offers the first risk map for shag bycatch in this region, demonstrating the utility of biologging combined with AIS for informing targeted mitigation strategies and spatial management, though limitations remain due to voluntary vessel tracking and the need for broader adult data and behavioural context.

Case study 23: Identification of critical areas for the Balearic shearwater and overlap with fisheries

This study assessed spatial overlap between fishing activity and the non-breeding distribution of the Critically Endangered Balearic shearwater (*Puffinus mauretanicus*) using geolocator data from 53 tagged individuals (88 annual tracks) between 2017–2022. Three core at-sea areas were identified: the western Mediterranean, western Iberian Peninsula, and Bay of Biscay, with significant migration via the Strait of Gibraltar. Between 2018–2021, ~650,000 mW fishing hours occurred across these areas—93.5% in the Bay of Biscay—mainly from bottom otter trawls (63%). Notably, over half of this

effort occurred within Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), exposing shearwaters to bycatch risk even in designated conservation zones. The study highlights both industrial and artisanal fisheries as critical threats and calls for urgent integration of bycatch risk into MPA management, strengthened monitoring, and gear-specific mitigation, aligning with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and broader ecosystem-based management objectives.

Case study 24: Identification of critical areas for Audouin’s gull and overlap with fisheries

This study presents the most comprehensive spatial analysis to date of Audouin’s gull (*Ichthyaetus audouinii*) foraging behaviour across its Western Mediterranean breeding range, using GPS tracking of 71 individuals from five colonies. It reveals that gulls extensively exploit anthropogenic food subsidies, especially fishing discards and urban waste, with terrestrial habitats (notably urban areas and fishing ports) used slightly more than marine habitats overall. However, marine areas that were both highly productive and subject to intense fishing—especially by trawlers—were heavily used at sea, with significant spatiotemporal co-occurrence between gulls and both purse seiners (especially in northern colonies) and trawlers (southern colonies). Foraging behaviour varied by colony and time of day, reflecting high behavioural plasticity that supports the species’ ongoing expansion, but potentially creates ecological traps due to low-quality or hazardous human-derived food sources. The findings underscore the dual-edged role of fisheries and urbanization in supporting opportunistic seabirds and call for integrated conservation policies—particularly in light of EU discard bans and changing waste management practices—that consider both the benefits and risks of anthropogenic food subsidies.

Case Study 25. Biologging as a tool for the conservation/management of protected and conservation-interest species

This study explores the use of satellite telemetry to investigate the movement ecology of cetaceans, focusing on two case studies: killer whales in the Ross Sea and fin whales in the Mediterranean. Using LIMPET and transdermal tags, researchers revealed area-restricted search behaviour linked to foraging in both species and identified key habitats, including Closs Bay for killer whales and the Pelagos Sanctuary and Lampedusa for fin whales. While telemetry provides crucial, observer-independent data on behaviour and habitat use essential for conservation, the study highlights the ethical and welfare concerns linked to invasive tagging, advocating for rigorous adherence to the “three Rs” (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) in study design and deployment. Ultimately, the research highlights the balance between scientific gain and animal welfare in marine conservation practice.

In summary, Deliverable D5.2 studied critical challenges for marine ecosystems, i.e. HABs, IAS, jellyfish blooms, and the decline of top predators. Drawing on case studies and cross-cutting analyses, the report generated a suite of targeted **recommendations** aimed at enhancing monitoring strategies and improving management responses. These recommendations stress the need for integrated, adaptive, and technologically advanced approaches to better detect, understand, and mitigate the ecological and socio-economic impacts of these complex phenomena.

Satellite data offer significant advantages for monitoring extensive and dynamic marine and coastal areas, especially in remote regions with limited field resources, by enabling the detection of seasonal patterns, anomalies, extreme events, and phenological shifts. To ensure effective use, reliable in-situ data are essential for validating satellite products, a current limitation in turbid and shallow waters that calls for expanded monitoring and data sharing. Progress is being made in detecting phytoplankton groups and some HABs through improved satellites and algorithms, but validated products are still lacking. Continued collaboration between remote sensing and plankton experts is crucial for generating quality data relevant to food webs, eutrophication, HABs, and gelatinous zooplankton under MSFD descriptors. Further research is needed to develop algorithms capable of identifying jellyfish aggregations. Moreover, integrating satellite-derived parameters into machine learning models could enhance understanding of ecosystem spatial dynamics, though these models also depend on robust ground-truth datasets for validation.

Lagrangian models are valuable tools for assessing the spatial and temporal dynamics of drifting ecosystem components—such as plankton, seaweed, litter, and oil spills—by capturing how their impacts and ecosystem services manifest along their trajectories rather than at their sources. These models enhance understanding of connectivity across ecosystems, including benthic-pelagic and land-sea interactions, and are particularly useful in large or data-poor areas. However, their effectiveness depends on robust calibration and validation using reliable ground data, as well as a thorough understanding of the physical and biological traits of the components being modelled.

eDNA metabarcoding, based on high-throughput sequencing, offers a powerful means of characterizing molecular diversity in environmental samples, enabling the detection of cryptic, low-abundance, or morphologically indistinct taxa and providing higher taxonomic resolution than traditional methods. It shows promise for early detection of rare or harmful species, including non-indigenous taxa, and has been proposed as a tool for biomonitoring and GES assessment. However, its application is limited by the lack of standardization across protocols, susceptibility to methodological biases, semi-quantitative outputs, and issues such as false positives and negatives due to incomplete reference databases and sequencing artefacts. As such, eDNA metabarcoding should

be employed as a complementary approach alongside conventional techniques, with results interpreted cautiously and validated against traditional taxonomic methods.

The **CIMPAL** framework is recommended as a versatile tool for assessing the cumulative impacts of NIS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms. Future applications are advised to incorporate both negative and positive impacts, account for interspecific interactions, and evaluate the effects on ecosystem services. High-resolution spatial analyses (e.g., 1 km²) are essential for identifying impact hotspots, guiding management actions, and enabling upscaling for broader assessments. CIMPAL also supports cross-border coordination, stakeholder engagement, and alignment with policy targets such as the MSFD and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Its effectiveness depends on robust, fine-scale data and impact evidence, necessitating improved monitoring, adaptive strategies in light of climate change, and adequate investment in data collection and assessment.

Biologging is a valuable tool for monitoring marine top predators, offering detailed insights into habitat use and enabling spatially explicit assessments of their overlap with anthropogenic pressures. It supports the design of targeted management measures by highlighting risk areas, especially for endangered or migratory species, and provides complementary data on human activities at sea, such as fishing effort. To enhance conservation outcomes, interactions between predators and human activities should be assessed both at sea and on land, including in non-EU waters to support transboundary management. In data-poor regions, biologging can be supplemented with alternative methods, such as video monitoring, and is particularly useful for detecting ecological tipping points through observed changes in predator distribution and abundance.

In conclusion, Deliverable D5.2 provides a scientifically robust, operationally feasible, and policy-relevant framework to support ecosystem-based management of some of the most pressing biological stressors in European seas. By integrating advanced tools—including satellite remote sensing, Lagrangian modelling, molecular techniques, cumulative impact indices, and biologging—this work enables more precise, scalable, and adaptive assessments of ecological risk. The 25 case studies (plus an additional in the Annexes) illustrate how these methodologies can be effectively applied across diverse regional contexts, providing actionable insights for spatial planning, early warning systems, and targeted conservation efforts. Collectively, the deliverable advances the capacity of European marine governance to respond proactively to complex and dynamic environmental challenges.

3. Introduction

The **fourth outcome indicated in the Horizon Europe proposal call** [HORIZON-CL6-DEC-2021-00-00: Assess and predict integrated impacts of cumulated direct and indirect stressors on coastal and marine biodiversity, ecosystems and their services], in which the project GES4SEAS is included, **aims to identify and interrogate the current EBM approaches and policy measures for activities to reduce pressures to ensure that GES can be achieved thereby enabling the sustainability of coastal and marine ecosystems to deliver services and societal goods and benefits while at the same time being resilient to rapid climate and environmental changes.**

In this context, **Deliverable 2.1, titled “Ecosystem management approaches based on a review of the activity–pressures–effects chain towards achieving Good Environmental Status in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive”**, was submitted on 31st May 2023. It constituted a foundational step toward developing practitioner-oriented proposals and guidance on EBM under the MSFD. This deliverable set the conceptual and methodological groundwork for subsequent tasks and work packages by (i) outlining the current understanding of EBM and its underpinning principles, (ii) identifying and describing tools relevant to testing each principle, and (iii) assessing how these tools can be integrated into a coherent toolbox for EBM implementation. Particular emphasis was placed on incorporating EBM into international and regional legal frameworks, marine assessment strategies, EU directives, and national instruments.

Building upon this foundation, **Deliverable 2.2, titled “State-of-the-art in support of Ecosystem-Based Management approaches to address Harmful Algal Blooms, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators”** expanded the scope of analysis by addressing four critical and emerging ecological challenges—invasive species, the decline of top predators, jellyfish blooms, and HABs. This task provided a comprehensive review of the scientific knowledge concerning the drivers–pressure–state–impact relationships of these stressors under climate change and socio-economic change scenarios. It also examined their implications for ecosystem functioning and the provision of ecosystem services, with a focus on societal goods and human health. Furthermore, the task synthesised current knowledge gaps and evaluated available approaches for monitoring, forecasting, and managing these phenomena, thus informing the development of targeted solutions within the broader EBM framework.

The review of IAS revealed the complex and growing threat posed by biological invasions in marine ecosystems, driven primarily by human activities and exacerbated by climate change. It emphasized the need for reliable data infrastructures (e.g., EASIN, AquaNIS), early warning systems, and

harmonized monitoring protocols—especially in high-risk areas such as ports. Despite the availability of risk screening tools and ballast water treatment technologies, inconsistencies in assessment methodologies and insufficient pathway knowledge continue to hinder effective management. The report recommends a comprehensive suite of measures, including expanding the List of IAS of Union Concern, enhancing biosecurity, supporting predictive tools, and adopting a more nuanced view that considers the potential functional roles of some alien species in warming ecosystems.

In addressing the decline of marine top predators, Deliverable 2.2 examined their pivotal ecological roles and the cascading consequences of their reduction. It evaluated a wide range of monitoring techniques—spanning traditional field methods to satellite tracking and eDNA analysis—and assessed their utility in capturing trends in distribution, abundance, and ecological impact. The synthesis revealed how anthropogenic pressures and environmental changes have destabilized predator populations and, by extension, trophic dynamics. Recommendations focused on implementing coordinated monitoring strategies, strengthening conservation governance, and embedding predator protection more explicitly within EBM to restore balance and resilience in marine food webs.

The section on jellyfish recognized the dual nature of these organisms as both disruptors and contributors to marine ecosystems. It traced the rise in jellyfish-related research and proposed practical monitoring strategies—including citizen science, acoustic detection, and remote sensing—to better integrate gelatinous zooplankton into GES assessments. The review argued for a paradigm shift from reactive local responses to proactive, predictive management grounded in defined criteria, indicators, and thresholds. It also explored the potential of jellyfish as ecosystem service providers and called for increased ocean literacy to mitigate human-jellyfish conflicts.

Finally, the section on HABs highlighted their multidimensional impacts—ranging from biodiversity loss to public health threats—and advocated for a more integrated and anticipatory management approach. Two novel decision-support tools, the GES4HABs decision tree and the MAMBO matrix, were introduced to facilitate context-specific responses to bloom events and their underlying drivers. These tools, combined with updated monitoring indicators and international cooperation, form a robust foundation for improving the inclusion of HABs in MSFD implementation.

Together, the analyses presented in Deliverable 2.2 stress the urgency of advancing a systems-based, cross-sectoral, and anticipatory framework for managing these complex and interacting stressors. The insights and tools generated provide an essential knowledge base to inform toolbox development, stakeholder engagement, and scenario modelling in subsequent work packages. They also represent

a significant contribution to refining EBM strategies under the MSFD, and to shaping future policy adaptations that reflect the realities of a rapidly changing marine environment.

Subsequently, Task 5.2 built directly upon the findings and gaps identified in Deliverable 2.2 by developing, refining, and testing methodological approaches to assess and manage IAS, the decline of top predators, jellyfish outbreaks, and HABs, while also advancing operational tools to support EBM. This task focused on enhancing the spatial and temporal resolution of monitoring, improving predictive capacity, and strengthening the evidence base for effective and adaptive management interventions across European regional seas.

Specifically, Deliverable 5.2 describes the refinement and application of several key methods. These include the development of satellite imagery processing routines to map the occurrence of phytoplankton blooms and identify oceanographic conditions associated with HABs, jellyfish events, and IAS distributions across European seas, expanding on insights from Task 2.2. Existing Lagrangian particle tracking models were configured and tuned to simulate the transport pathways of these biological components, enabling spatial risk forecasting. Molecular techniques such as eDNA were employed to support enhanced monitoring and to unravel cause-effect pathways linked to population structures and species assemblages. Additionally, the CIMPAL framework for cumulative impact assessment was adapted and expanded to assess impacts from jellyfish and HABs, positive impacts from alien species, and impacts on ecosystem services, allowing improved mapping of ecological risks and benefits across Learning Sites (LSs). The use of biologging and telemetry was also advanced to improve the monitoring and management of top predators, contributing to spatially explicit management recommendations.

The relevance of these issues—IAS, declining top predators, jellyfish outbreaks, and HABs—to EBM cannot be overstated. Each represents a critical and complex pressure on marine ecosystems, affecting ecological integrity and the delivery of ecosystem services central to achieving GES under the MSFD.

- **Invasive Alien Species (IAS):** Widely acknowledged as a major global threat to biodiversity, marine IAS disrupt ecosystems functioning through mechanisms such as altered nutrient cycling, competitive exclusion, and habitat transformation. These impacts from this MSFD Descriptor 2 directly influence other descriptors such as D1 (biodiversity) and D6 (seafloor integrity).
- **Decline of Top Predators:** As keystone species, top predators regulate community structure and food web stability. Their loss—often a consequence of overexploitation and habitat

degradation—can trigger trophic cascades with profound implications for ecosystem function and resilience, thus affecting D1 (biodiversity) and D4 (food webs).

- **Jellyfish Outbreaks:** Increasingly frequent and widespread, jellyfish blooms signal ecological imbalances often linked to anthropogenic pressures. Their impacts on fisheries, tourism, and trophic dynamics make them pertinent to descriptors such as D3 (commercial fish and shellfish) and D4 (food webs), with indirect links to eutrophication and biodiversity loss.
- **Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs):** Intensified by nutrient enrichment and climate change, HABs compromise water quality, ecosystem health, and public safety. Effective monitoring and management are essential for GES descriptors, including D5 (eutrophication), D3 (commercial fish and shellfish), D4 (food webs), and increasingly, D1 (biodiversity).

Incorporating these components into the EBM framework is critical for shifting from fragmented, pressure-specific management to an integrated, systems-oriented approach. Traditional monitoring often fails to capture the complexity and cumulative effects of these stressors. In contrast, EBM accommodates multiple interacting pressures, accounts for ecological thresholds, and supports adaptive management. By integrating advanced monitoring methods and predictive tools for IAS, top predators, jellyfish, and HABs, Deliverable 5.2 significantly advances the capacity of marine managers to detect early warning signals, assess environmental status more holistically, and implement targeted, evidence-based interventions. This comprehensive and forward-looking approach reinforces the potential of EBM to deliver resilient, sustainable marine ecosystems under accelerating global change.

4. Satellite imagery processing and analysis to map HABs, invasive species distribution, and jellyfish bloom events

4.1 Introduction

Remote sensing technologies on board aerial and satellite platforms can provide useful information for indicators or drivers related to some species' spatio-temporal distributions. These include Sea Surface Temperature (SST) from infrared sensors and ocean-color-based products, such as Chl-a and turbidity. These parameters are measured over large areas at higher temporal ranges and frequencies, that can assess temporal dynamics (seasonality, anomalies, extreme events, trends, etc.), and spatial distribution and evolution (i.e., blooms and river plumes extensions). The main limitation of remote sensing is that cloud or ice coverage obscures image acquisition in some areas and seasons (above all in winter and in northern and equatorial latitudes), and lack of subsurface data.

In addition, whilst parameters like SSTs are reliable, the estimation of chlorophyll-a and other ocean-color metrics are often uncertain in optically complex waters found mainly near the coast. New algorithms and processing methods are continuously being proposed to overcome these difficulties and provide improved products not only for chlorophyll-a but also for the identification of risk areas for specific species like HABs, jellyfish or marine mammals.

Besides physico-chemical parameters, other remote sensing products can be useful to support indicators on human print like coastline changes, location of aquaculture and other human infrastructures from high resolution true-color images, or vessel densities and fishing effort from Automatic Identification Systems (AIS).

In-situ and remote monitoring approaches are often integrated in modelling tools than can help to (i) investigate, characterize and quantify the links between different parameters, ecosystem components and their impacts, (ii) discern the contribution of natural vs. anthropogenic causes, (iii) delineate areas with higher risks for HABs based on historical data, (iv) predict, in real- or near real-time, the risk of HABs, and (v) make climatic projections.

There are a multitude of different **model types** and, such as ecological and food web models, biogeochemistry models, statistical and machine learning models, physical numerical models, Lagrangian particle tracking models, spatial plan models, etc. These models can, at different reliability levels, assess areas with the highest risk likelihood of different impacts, help to optimize monitoring plans (e.g., with less sampling effort in situations of low probability of HABs), assess/manage the compatibility of different marine uses, aid the preparedness for contingency responses, or

extrapolate *in situ* observations/indicators within the grid to better depict the spatio-temporal variability of the pelagic habitat.

Although models can be very practical tools, it is important to bear in mind that they cannot substitute monitoring data. Models are a form of secondary monitoring that use multiple data sources. Their reliability depends on accurate and representative data for their development and calibration, implementation, and validation.

4.2 Case study 1: Risk assessment of Harmful Phytoplankton Blooms in the NW Mediterranean Sea

Nagore Sampedro, Albert Reñé, Esther Garcés, Jordi Camp

4.2.1 Introduction

Unlike other marine regions — such as the Baltic Sea, where extensive cyanobacterial blooms regularly occur, often covering large areas visible from satellite imagery and associated with broad-scale pressures — large-scale events are generally not observed in the NW Mediterranean. Instead, the Mediterranean Sea typically experiences small, localized coastal blooms that are often undetectable by satellites and driven by more localized factors. Although the Mediterranean is predominantly oligotrophic, its coastal areas receive nutrient inputs from various sources, resulting in locally elevated nutrient concentrations. These coastal zones are also subject to multiple pressures, largely due to the high population density concentrated along the Mediterranean shoreline.

Coastal HABs in the Mediterranean are a widespread issue. They can pose risks to public health and interfere with recreational coastal activities. Moreover, they lead to significant economic losses, particularly in the aquaculture and tourism sectors. While HABs are natural phenomena, their frequency and intensity are exacerbated by intense coastal exploitation. Assessing the risk of harmful phytoplankton blooms along the coast—and understanding its spatial and temporal variability—is a critical first step toward identifying the specific pressures affecting high-risk areas. Such assessments can help competent authorities implement more effective management strategies to mitigate anthropogenic impacts.

The scientific literature offers a range of methodologies for HAB risk assessment. Different authors apply distinct approaches, including the use of environmental variables such as nutrient concentrations or temperature (e.g., Hou et al., 2022), or integrating multiple variables into composite risk indices (e.g., Gianella et al., 2025).

In this case study, the proposed risk assessment is based on phytoplankton cell counts, with species-specific thresholds established to define levels of potential adverse effects. Historical bloom records provide a valuable dataset, especially given the high recurrence of HABs in the region.

Bloom risk varies spatially and temporally—most notably by season—and depends on the characteristics of the coastal environment. Confined areas, such as harbors generally experience reduced water exchange and greater water column stability compared to open waters. These

conditions favor the proliferation of certain taxa, especially dinoflagellates, which include the majority of toxic or harmful phytoplankton species.

Since 2000, the Toxic and Harmful Phytoplankton Monitoring Plan in Catalonia has provided essential long-term data on species' occurrence and abundance. In Catalonia, monitoring in confined waters serves as an early warning system for harmful algal blooms to protect shellfish production zones (Furones, 2004), whereas beaches have been sampled for compliance with bathing water control and for the implementation of the WFD (Water Framework Directive).

This case study aims to assess the risk of HABs in two different coastal environments—beaches and harbours— identifying high-risk areas along the Catalan coast (NW Mediterranean Sea, LS6), and evaluate seasonal variability in bloom risk.

4.2.2 Methods

The study area

This study focuses on the Catalan coast (NW Mediterranean Sea) (Figure 4.2.1), located in the northeast of the Iberian Peninsula. The southern area is influenced by the Ebro River and the rice fields in its delta, which contribute high loads of nitrates, while the central coast is affected by urban discharges from the city of Barcelona, which contribute significant amounts of ammonium and phosphate (Flo, 2011).

Figure 4.2.1. Study area along the Catalan coast in the NW Mediterranean Sea. Maps show sampling sites distributed along the coastline, including (A) harbours and (B) beaches. The inset provides the geographical context of the study within the Mediterranean basin. Riverine inflows and major urban areas are also indicated.

Data Sources

Phytoplankton monitoring data were obtained from various monitoring programs conducted under contracts with the Catalan Water Agency (ACA) of the Government of Catalonia. These programs were designed to comply with several European directives related to food safety, environmental quality, and bathing water monitoring.

- Harbour data: collected between 2000 and 2012 from 16 different harbours along the Catalan coast with 1–4 samples per month.
- Beach data: collected from 2000 to 2023 at 25 beaches, with sampling frequency varying depending on the site and the year. Some beaches were monitored year-round for up to eight years, while others were sampled only from May to September.

Risk Index Calculation

To assess the risk of HABs, specific risk thresholds were defined (Table 4.2.1) for each phytoplankton species and for each environment type. These thresholds were based on the abundance levels at which the species are known to cause adverse effects and were defined for toxic species (health risk), species harmful to marine life, and those that degrade water quality and affect tourism.

Table 4.2.1. Thresholds used for each harmful species and for each coastal environment.

Negative impacts	Species	Abundances (cells/L)	
		Beaches	Harbours
Human health risks			
Consumption of contaminated shellfish			
<i>ASP</i>			
	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp	> 2·10 ⁵	> 2·10 ⁵
<i>DSP</i>			
	<i>Dinophysis</i> sps	> 2000	> 5000
	<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>	> 2000	> 5000
	<i>Prorocentrum rathymum</i>	> 2000	> 5000
<i>PSP</i>			
	<i>Alexandrium</i> sps.	> 1·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
Producers of yessotoxin			
	<i>Lingulaulax polyedra</i>	> 1·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Prorocentrum reticulatum</i>	> 1·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
Inhalation of toxic aerosols			
Respiratory syndrome			
	<i>Ostreopsis</i> sps	> 5000	> 1·10 ⁴
Economic impacts			
Tourism losses due to poor water quality or visible blooms			
High biomass blooms with discoloration			
	<i>Alexandrium taylorii</i>	> 1·10 ⁵	> 1·10 ⁵
	Gymnodinioids (<i>G.litoralis</i> , <i>L. fissa</i> , <i>B. branvensis</i>)	> 1·10 ⁵	> 1·10 ⁵
Mucilage or foam producers			
	<i>Gymnodinium impudicum</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Gonyaulax fragilis</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Phaeocystis</i> spp	>1·10 ⁶	>1·10 ⁷
Toxicity to marine organisms			
Mortality of fish.			
	<i>Chatonella</i> spp	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Dictyocha fibula</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Dictyocha speculum</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Fibrocapsa japonica</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Karlodinium</i> spp	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴
	<i>Prorocentrum cordatum</i>	> 5·10 ⁴	> 5·10 ⁴

At each site, the number of samples with harmful species present at abundances exceeding at least one of the established thresholds was recorded. Subsequently, the percentage of bloom-positive samples was calculated, resulting in an **incidence score** for each site.

$$\left(\frac{\text{N}^\circ \text{ of samples with blooms}}{\text{N}^\circ \text{ of samples}} \right) * 100 = \text{Incidence Score}$$

For interpretability, scores were translated into four qualitative risk levels.

Incidence Score=0	Risk level 0: Very low
Incidence Score: 0.1-3	Risk level 1: Low
Incidence Score: 3.1-10	Risk level 2: Moderate
Incidence Score>10	Risk level 3: High

To ensure comparability, beach risk maps were restricted to May to September data, as for some beaches only summer-season data were available. Including year-round data for some locations while limiting others to summer months would have introduced bias in the calculation of bloom frequency percentages. Standardizing the temporal window allowed consistent risk assessment across all sampling sites.

4.2.3 Results

The evaluation of HAB risk in harbours from 2000 to 2012 exhibited that all harbours presented positive incidence scores (Figure 4.2.2A). Arenys, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Tarragona, and Sant Carles de la Ràpita exhibited a high incidence of HABs, with notable seasonal variation (Figure 4.2.3). These elevated bloom frequencies were primarily associated with toxin-producing species: *Alexandrium minutum* and *Dinophysis sacculus* in Arenys and Vilanova harbours; *Alexandrium pacificum* and *Gymnodinium impudicum* in Tarragona; and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. in Sant Carles de la Ràpita. Moderate-risk harbors included L’Estartit, Port Olímpic, Barcelona, Cambrils, and L’Ampolla, while low-risk sites were Roses, Empuriabrava, Palamós, Blanes, Premià, Torredembarra, and L’Ametlla.

Beach monitoring (2000–2023) identified high-risk zones in the northern coast (from Empuriabrava to Sant Feliu) and some central beaches (Figure 4.2.2B). In contrast, Picordia and Riumar had very low risk, illustrating the spatial heterogeneity of bloom incidence.

Figure 4.2.2. Risk assessment of harmful algal blooms in harbours (A) and beaches (B) along the Catalan coast. Symbols represent four risk levels based on historical data: 0 (very low), 1 (low), 2 (moderate), and 3 (high).

The dominant species responsible for high-risk areas varied by location:

In northern beaches, elevated risk levels were due to high-biomass bloom producers *Alexandrium taylori* and gymnodinioid species such as *Gymnodinium litoralis*, *Levanderina fissa*, and *Barrufeta bravensis*.

In Lllavaneres and Terramar, the main contributor was the toxic species *Ostreopsis* spp.

Figure 4.2.3. Seasonal HAB risk in harbours. Risk categories range from 0 (very low) to 3 (high).

Seasonal analysis of risk in harbours revealed highest risk in spring and summer. Beach data were insufficient to evaluate the risk level for each yearly season, but available results suggest a similar trend.

4.2.4 Discussion

Methodological aspects

The establishment of abundance thresholds to calculate bloom frequency has also been applied in some studies aiming to assess the ecological quality of coastal waters under the Water Framework Directive (WFD). For example, in Revilla et al. (2009), specific thresholds were established for each of two phytoplankton size classes used in their classification scheme.

However, choosing appropriate thresholds for risk assessment requires knowledge of the abundance at which a species becomes potentially harmful in a given environment. For instance, the abundance at which toxic species pose a threat can vary greatly between taxa. While species of the genus *Dinophysis* can contaminate bivalves even at very low cell densities (Yasumoto et al., 1985) other toxic taxa such as *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. often require much higher abundances in the water column to produce similar contamination risks (e.g. Whyte et al., 2023).

In the case of non-toxic species, very high abundances are generally needed to cause water discoloration or negatively impact tourism-related activities. Furthermore, the impact of a bloom also depends on the characteristics of the coastal environment. In open waters, where shellfish production zones are located, a bloom may directly affect seafood safety. In contrast, blooms occurring inside harbours may not pose an immediate risk to consumers, as shellfish harvesting is typically not permitted in these areas. However, a high abundance of a toxic species in a harbour could potentially spread to production areas in open waters, especially if oceanographic conditions are favourable (Vila et al., 2001a).

Classifying sites by risk level based on bloom frequency percentages is a more intuitive approach for managers and decision-makers, but it requires adequate sampling effort. A minimum of 33 samples per site or season was necessary to differentiate risk categories, since a single bloom in 33 samples corresponds to the 3% threshold used to define “low risk.”

Although thresholds must be tailored to local species and environments, this method provides a useful tool for identifying high-risk areas guiding to identify sites that require closer monitoring and where local pressures should be studied in more detail to understand the possible causes of the observed risk.

Effect of the environment in the HAB risk

HAB risk patterns varied significantly between harbours and beaches:

All harbours exhibited some level of bloom risk, while certain beaches remained unaffected

The spatial distribution of risk also differed between harbours and beaches. On beaches, risk was primarily concentrated in the northern part of the Catalan coast, whereas high-risk harbours were scattered along the entire coastline, rather than being limited to a specific area.

Dominant bloom-forming species varied by environments, indicating distinct ecological drivers.

These differences highlight the influence of hydrological changes and physical modifications—particularly those resulting from human activities such as harbour construction—which may enhance the frequency and diversity of harmful algal blooms in confined coastal waters. Furthermore, the contrasting spatial risk pattern suggests that localized environmental conditions and anthropogenic pressures play a critical role in shaping the frequency and intensity of HABs. These findings underscore the need for further site-specific investigations to better understand the pressures driving bloom dynamics across different coastal settings.

Influence of seasonality on HAB risk

The seasonal pattern of HAB risk observed in most coastal locations should be considered when optimizing monitoring efforts and allocating resources. Such seasonality could be due to several aspects but mainly related to optimal environmental conditions allowing the growth of phytoplankton species, e.g., high water temperature, water column stability or nutrient inputs. In addition, this seasonality should be considered when investigating the environmental and anthropogenic pressures that influence bloom occurrence.

4.2.5 References

- Davidson, K., Gowen, R. J., Harrison, P. J., Fleming, L. E., Hoagland, P., & Moschonas, G. (2014). Human health impacts of harmful algal blooms in a changing world: A special emphasis on Europe. *Ocean and Coastal Management*, 102, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2014.03.010>
- Flo, E., Garcés, E., Manzanera, M., & Camp, J. (2011). Coastal inshore waters in the NW Mediterranean: Physicochemical and biological characterization and management implications. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 93(4), 279–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.04.002>
- Furones, D., Vila, M., Garcés, E., Sampedro, N., Arin, L., Masó, M., ... & Diogene, J. (2004). The monitoring programme for marine toxins and harmful phytoplankton in the Catalan coastline, North Western Mediterranean, Spain. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety: Harmful Algal Bloom Events and Biotxin Contamination* (pp. 197–205).
- Gianella, F., Burrows, M. T., & Davidson, K. (2025). Risk assessment of harmful algal blooms in salmon farming: Scotland as a case study. *Toxins*, 17(1), 35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins17010035>
- Hou, J., Wang, Z., Li, D., & Chen, J. (2022). Harmful algal bloom risk in the Changjiang River Estuary. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, Article 916497. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.916497>
- Revilla, M., Franco, J., Bald, J., Laza-Martínez, A., Seoane, S., Orive, E., ... & Borja, Á. (2009). Assessment of the phytoplankton ecological status in the Basque Country's estuarine and coastal waters using

chlorophyll-a and phytoplankton community composition. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 58(1), 85–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2008.09.005>

Vila, M., Garcés, E., Masó, M., & Camp, J. (2001a). Is the distribution of the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* expanding along the NW Mediterranean coast? *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 222, 73–83. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps222073>

Whyte, C., Swan, S. C., Turner, A. D., Hatfield, R. G., Mitchell, E., Lafferty, S., ... & Davidson, K. (2023). The presence of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* in North Atlantic aquaculture sites: Implications for monitoring amnesic shellfish toxins. *Toxins*, 15(9), 554. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins15090554>

Yasumoto, T., Murata, M., Oshima, Y., Sano, M., Matsumoto, G., & Clardy, J. (1985). Diarrhetic shellfish toxins. *Tetrahedron*, 41(6), 1019–1025. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020\(01\)96620-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020(01)96620-0)

4.3 Case study 2: Cyanobacteria bloom interpretation and forecasting in the Baltic Sea

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4.3.1 Introduction

Marine HABs can be produced by a wide range of micro-organisms, most often planktonic microalgae. In the Baltic Sea, cyanobacterial blooms constitute a major problem from environmental, ecological, human health and ecosystem services perspectives (e.g., Karjalainen et al., 2007, 2008). Those blooms induce losses of recreational values of the sea and beaches due to accumulations of foul-smelling, potentially toxic cyanobacteria, and because their nitrogen fixation adds large amounts of potentially biologically available nitrogen to a eutrophicated and largely nitrogen-limited sea (Horstmann, 1975; Larsson et al., 2001; Kahru, 2020).

While blooms of cyanobacteria typically occur in freshwater ecosystems, the conditions in the Baltic Sea characterized with low salinity enable cyanobacteria to flourish, especially as currently cultural eutrophication supports phytoplankton growth. Cyanobacterial blooms may always have occurred in the Baltic Sea, occasionally even in its pristine state before major disturbance from changes in land use, industrialization and global climatic change (Zillen and Conley, 2010). However, during the last 2-3 decades massive blooms have become an annual phenomenon in large areas in warmest time of the year. The excessive nutrient loads leading to eutrophication and rapid warming of the sea have been deemed as the main factors behind the extensive blooms (Zillen and Conley, 2010). Warming mainly acts by stabilizing the water column and decreasing the mixing depth, thereby increasing the light irradiance needed for the growth of cyanobacteria and allowing the blooms to accumulate on surface (Stal et al., 2003).

How to forecast cyanobacterial blooms?

Different methodologies could be used for forecasting of HABs, including statistical and process-based models. Flynn and McGillicuddy (2018) found out that statistical models have proven effective for hindcasts and near-term forecasts, the statistical relationships become less predictable as forcing conditions shift outside the range of past observations, while process-based models may be robust for projecting HAB response under novel environmental conditions, if the key processes remain unchanged under a different set of forcing conditions.

Cyanobacteria blooms in lakes and reservoirs have been modelled in many studies, also with the above mentioned two model types which Rousso et al. (2020) define as process-based and data-driven

models. In the Baltic Sea earlier process-based modeling include Janssen et al. (2004) and Roiha et al. (2010). Anyhow, especially the northern Baltic Sea has been found as a challenging environment for dynamic, spatially accurate biogeochemical models. Several studies with process-based physical-biogeochemical models have been carried out to estimate the carbon and nutrient fluxes in the Baltic Sea but none of these models have been able to realistically reproduce the carbon fixation and the nutrient uptake by primary production (Fransner et al., 2018 and references therein). As there was not any reliable operational process-based biogeochemical model available for the forecasting of cyanobacterial blooms in the GES4SEAS learning site 1 (Gulf of Bothnia in the Baltic Sea), it was reasoned that machine learning which does not demand process descriptions but can fluently incorporate information different data sources could provide a useful alternative for modelling of these blooms. The current study applied machine learning with datasets produced with monitoring cruises and FerryBox-devices, climate reanalysis data, weather forecasts and remote sensing interpretations of blooms.

4.3.2 Methods

The research area

The geographic area for this study covers the northern part of the Baltic Sea, Gulf of Bothnia (Fig. 1). The total area of the Gulf of Bothnia is 117 000 km². It can be further divided to Bothnian Sea (63650 km²), Bothnian Bay (33224 km²), the Quark (4509 km²), Åland Sea (4433 km²) and the Archipelago Sea (11077 km²) (<https://maps.helcom.fi/website/mapservice/>). All these basins are on shallow, the average depths ranging from 19 m in the Archipelago Sea to 75 m in the Åland Sea, but there are also locations deeper than 200 m in the Bothnian Sea. The topography is very complex in large areas including e.g. tens of thousands of small and larger islands, but also wide offshore areas. In addition to the Gulf of Bothnia, the northern part of the Baltic Proper and the Gulf of Finland were also included in the modelling work in this deliverable because bloom forecasts covering whole this area would be useful for supporting marine ecosystem management.

The salinity in the Gulf of Bothnia is determined by precipitation to and evaporation from the sea, the abundant freshwater input from the large drainage basin and variable inflows of water with higher salinity from the Baltic Proper bordering our research area in the south. The salinity in the surface water is below 2 in the northernmost part of the Bothnian Bay where there are estuaries of several large rivers, and 5-6 in the southern parts of then Bothnian Sea. There is a permanent salinity stratification in the Baltic Proper whereas in the Gulf of Bothnia the salinity stratification is less profound because a shallow sill delimits the more saline water inflow from the deeper water layer in

the Baltic Proper (Zillen and Conley, 2010). Variations in the depth and steepness of the halocline and salinity in the water flowing in this basin contribute to the salinity variations.

Profound temperature stratification develops during summer, even if weather conditions determine the mixing layer steepness and depth. Summertime maximum temperatures in the offshore areas are 15-20 °C while in winter the northern parts are annually ice-covered more than 6 months. Warming due to climate change is rapid even compared to any of the other large marine ecosystems (Belkin 2009).

Anthropogenic effects are profound in the Baltic Sea. It has been stated that the Baltic Sea is affected by levels of warming, acidification, nutrient pollution, and deoxygenation that most coastal areas will experience only in the future, especially the interaction of perturbations that the Baltic ecosystem is subjected to is among the strongest for any marine region (Reuch et al., 2018). Anyhow, the Gulf of Bothnia is more oligotrophic than the other basins of the Baltic Sea, even if also there e.g., the cyanobacterial blooms have increased during the last two decades especially in the southern parts and become more extensive and long-lasting.

The data

Current study applied several data sources with different types of data to forecast the blooms. This study covers the years 2003-2024, as this was the period from which suitable satellite data was available (see below). Datasets for this study were compiled from the northern Baltic Sea with latitude 58° N as the southern border.

The nutrient concentrations data for this study were compiled from the Finnish and Swedish marine monitoring data bases VESLA and SHARKWEB, respectively. Besides, we also applied nutrient concentration data from FerryBox (<https://eurogoos.eu/regional-operational-oceanographic-systems/>), i.e., data collected with through-flow systems installed by the Marine Research Laboratory of the Finnish Environment Institute in two ships (M/S Finnmaid and M/S Silja Serenade) in commercial marine traffic making frequent trips across the Baltic Sea. These systems measure automatically, continuously, and unattended several marine biogeochemical variables.

In the nutrient concentrations the variables of interest were dissolved inorganic phosphorus and nitrogen in the surface water in the 0-15 m depth layer (monitoring cruises) and at c. 5 m depth (FerryBox data where water intake is at c. 5 m depth). These data were included from the 1st of January to the end of March.

There are both ecological and practical reasons for utilizing winter nutrient concentration in modelling and in forecasting of blooms in summer. The potential for summertime cyanobacterial blooms is determined already as early as February by the DIN and DIP concentrations in the surface layer (Janssen et al., 2004). The onset of the spring bloom is related to salinity stratification and warming of the surface water (Spilling et al., 2018). Depending on the DIN to DIP ratio (dissolved inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus, respectively), spring bloom typically depletes one of these essential nutrient species from the surface water. The spring bloom in the Baltic Sea (except in the Bothnian Bay that is P-limited) is terminated when inorganic nitrogen has been depleted, i.e., the phytoplankton community is N-limited (Spilling et al., 2018). Depletion of DIN leads to low DIN to DIP ratio. Such conditions are favorable for cyanobacteria which through diazotrophy (nitrogen-fixation) can utilize molecular nitrogen unlike eucaryotic phytoplankton. Currently, the cultural eutrophication in many areas of the Baltic Sea favor cyanobacteria during summer and enable extensive surface blooms to develop.

The practical reasons for using wintertime nutrient data relate to the availability of data after the spring bloom. Usually, there are not enough nutrient concentration data available for spatial modelling between the short and variable period between the end of spring bloom and the beginning of summer bloom.

For the modelling, all nutrient concentration data from the national monitoring datasets and Ferrybox were combined, and spatial interpolation was conducted for the datasets of each year using Fixed Rank Kriging (FRK, Zammit-Mangion and Cressie, 2024, https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/FRK/vignettes/FRK_intro.pdf), to produce concentration raster layers for the northern Baltic Sea. The raster layers were produced with a spatial resolution of 0.1 longitude degrees and 0.2 latitude degrees corresponding to grid cells of ca. 5*5 km.

As it was hypothesized that temperature could contribute to the blooms of cyanobacteria, the air temperature was included as an explanatory factor to the modelling framework. Temperatures in the surface water closely follow the air temperatures. Climate reanalysis generates consistent time series of climate variables as a combination of past observations and models (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-reanalysis>). These reanalysis data about monthly temperatures in 2 m height over surface were downloaded covering the years 2003-2023 and the months May, June, July, and August. For the forecasts, seasonal weather forecasts (51 forecasts in total) were also downloaded in April 2024 from Copernicus Climate Change Service for year 2024 covering the same months as the reanalysis data (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/seasonal-forecasts>).

The satellite data raster maps on surface blooms (<https://ckan.ymparisto.fi/dataset/itameren-vuosittainen-levakooste-sentinel-3-sentinel-2-landsat-8-9-2017-yearly-algae-compo-2017>) were applied as the response variable data in the machine learning models. The annual composite of phytoplankton surface blooms is made from daily surface algal bloom observations during the summer period. The algal rafts are converted into a four-class interpretation map representing the probability of the occurrence of surface algal blooms in a particular area. The algal classes are (1) none, (2) potential, (3) likely, and (4) evident surface algae. Seasonal composites represent the maximal state of the algae blooms from June to August. The composites since 2018 are at ground resolution of $\sim 0.003^\circ$ (approx. 370 m \times 180 m). The composite of 2017 is of coarser ground resolution (0.009° , approx. 1,000 m \times 500 m). Surface algae bloom areas can be separated from non-algal areas based on the reflectance observed by the Sentinel-3 satellite series OLCI-instrument. The method uses various wavelength bands observed by the satellite, which differ between cyanobacterial areas and areas without cyanobacteria. Since 2020, the composite has also included material from the Sentinel-2 MSI satellite instrument. Starting in 2022, the composite has also been supplemented with interpretations made from data from the OLI and OLI-2 instruments of the Landsat-8 and Landsat-9 satellites. This allows the dataset to cover the areas closer to shoreline better. Before 2017 there were some differences in the instruments and processing of the satellite data, and these can be read in Finnish Environment Institute's data description (<https://ckan.ymparisto.fi/dataset/itameren-vuosittainen-levakooste-sentinel-3-sentinel-2-landsat-8-9-2017-yearly-algae-compo-2017>).

Modelling methods

We applied machine learning to evaluate how the selected explanatory variables could influence the cyanobacterial biomass during summer (June, July, August), and to forecast surface blooms during summer 2024. The annual satellite data composites of phytoplankton surface blooms in the years 2003-2023 in four categories were applied as the response data. Satellite data composite for the summer 2024 become available in September 2024 and was used for model performance evaluation. It was reasoned that decision tree methods which are in principle well suited for categorical data, would be applicable in this classification study as the response data for in four bloom biomass categories, whereby we selected random forest (RF) for this task.

The explanatory variables in the final RF model included longitude, latitude, DIN, DIP, average air temperature in May, and year. An alternative configuration where the variable year was converted to 5 categories (each covering c. 4 years) was also explored as it was assumed that with the random forest there could be challenges in extrapolating beyond the observed range of years. Also, including the temperature data from June, July, and August as well as averages from these months were

explored as an alternative to May temperature. The RF model was fitted with the `r` package `caret` (<https://topepo.github.io/caret/>). The data was divided in learning and test sets. Confusion matrix was applied as the most important tool to find the best models.

Spatial bloom level forecasts for the summer 2024 were made for the Northern Baltic Sea including the Guld of Bothnia with the fitted model using water quality raster about DIN and DIP estimated from the winter 2024 monitoring survey and Ferrybox data. Additionally, seasonal temperature forecasts from Copernicus for May were applied. The categorical bloom forecasts values were first converted to integers from 1 to 4, and spatial smoothing was applied to enable printing a forecast map with continuous gradient colours (blue, yellow, orange, red) corresponding the bloom categories. Also, the grid was somewhat extended to make it cover the nearshore areas which were lacking from the original modelling results due to lack of satellite data from these areas. The results were compared with the composite of phytoplankton surface blooms made in autumn from daily surface algal blooms observed in the summer period of the year 2024 as described above. The sensitivity of this model was tested by exploring the responses in bloom risk forecasts produced by inducing changes in nutrient concentrations. Model forecasts were run by inducing gradual changes in both nutrients in the range of -50 to +50% (a square matrix with dimension 21*21) compared with the concentrations in winter 2024.

4.3.3 Results

The map produced of the RF modelling results (Figure 4.3.1) supported that in summer 2024 there will be a high risk for cyanobacterial blooms in the Gulf of Finland, Northern Baltic Proper, Archipelago Sea and the offshore areas of the Southern Bothnian Sea. Low risk was forecasted for the northern parts of the Bothnian Sea, the Quark and the Bothnian Bay.

Figure 4.3.1. The forecasted surface bloom risks in the Northern Baltic Sea in the summer 2024. The risk categories in forecast correspond to categories none, potential, likely, and evident in the observational (satellite) data.

The final RF model had a good overall fit with the test data as the confusion matrix indicated an accuracy of 87.3%. The variance importance (Figure 4.3.2) indicated that the DIP concentration was by far the most important factor to contribute to the bloom risk.

Figure 4.3.2. The variance importance in the final RF model indicating that the DIP concentration was clearly the most important factor to contribute the blooms. On the vertical axes the explanatory variables t2m_May represents the reanalysis estimates of the air temperature on 2 m high from the surface.

The forecast was visually validated against the seasonal composite image of satellite interpretations (Figure 4.3.3) the bloom level categories in the forecast corresponding to categories none, potential, likely, and evident in the observational (satellite) data. The fit between the model and the observations was judged good, even if there are more spatial details in the satellite data and a few overestimated bloom risk areas were found from the Swedish coast of the Bothnian Sea (compare to Figure 4.3.1).

Figure 4.3.3. The surface blooms of cyanobacteria in the summer 2024 as a seasonal composite image from satellite data (<https://tarkka.syke.fi/>). Bloom categories as in Figure 4.3.1.

4.3.4 Discussion

Nutrients, DIP in particular, contributed strongly to the magnitude and distribution of the blooms. Compared to the composite of phytoplankton surface blooms from satellite data (Figure 4.3.3), there were less spatial details in the fitted model. In this deliverable, we did not make profound statistical testing of the model results against the bloom composites from satellite images. The visual comparison, however, indicated good match with the satellite-based composite image. Satellite time series of blooms of cyanobacteria are much more reliable in indicating bloom occurrence than the traditional monitoring which typically samples a few fixed stations with large temporal gaps (Kahru and Elmgren, 2014). The largest difference in the satellite composite compared with the forecast with RF model was close the Swedish coasts in the western Bothnian Sea, where forecasting somewhat overestimated the bloom risk.

The bloom model can be used to estimate how changes in DIN and DIP concentrations could influence the bloom occurrence (Figure 4.3.3). For example, a simultaneous decrease of 10-15% DIP and circa 20% DIN, would significantly decrease the risk of blooms. This visualized response is naturally valid only for the studied site, and comparable visualizations could be made in multiple areas to get useful management advice from the model.

We showed that the main variables determining the bloom occurrence are DIP, latitude, year and DIN (Figure 4.3.2). Kahru et al. (2020) analysed the impacts of multiple environmental variables on cyanobacterial blooms separating annual and decadal time scales. They found that the longer time moving averages of environmental variables better explained the variations in the blooms than the annual values. Anyhow, this might be linked to the quality of the data as incorporating data over several years could e.g., increase the coverage and quality of spatial data. Kahru et al. (2020) also found out that sediment-bound reserves of DIP and DIN as well as the ratio between these reserves, and extent of the hypoxic area in deep water were good predictors for bloom occurrence. However, Kahru et al. (2020) had a different aim in the study as they sought correlations between surface blooms and environmental variables while we wanted to develop a system for spatial forecasting in which we also utilized spatial coordinates. To our knowledge modelling studies for cyanobacterial bloom forecasting with machine learning and a comparable choice of data sources have not been published for the northern Baltic Sea. This study supports that machine learning could be a feasible alternative for modelling of harmful algal blooms in the northern Baltic Sea and potentially in other areas relatively rich with data but lacking reliable spatial dynamic marine ecosystem models.

4.3.5 References

- Belkin, I.M. (2009). Rapid warming of Large Marine Ecosystems. *Progress in Oceanography* 81 207–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2009.04.011>
- Flynn, K.J. and McGillicuddy, D.J., (2018). Modeling Marine harmful algal blooms: current status and future prospects. *Harmful Algal Blooms*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp. 115–134. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118994672.ch3>
- Fransner, F., Gustafsson, E., Tedesco, L., Vichi, M., Hordoir, R., Roquet, F., Nycander, J. (2018). Non-Redfieldian dynamics explain seasonal pCO₂ drawdown in the Gulf of Bothnia. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 123, 166–188. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC013019>
- Janssen, F., Neumann, T., Schmidt, M., (2004). Inter-annual variability in cyanobacterial blooms in the Baltic Sea controlled by wintertime hydrographic conditions. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 275, 59–68.
- Kahru, M., Elmgren, R., Kaiser, J., Wasmund, N., Savchuk, O. (2020). Cyanobacterial blooms in the Baltic Sea: Correlations with environmental factors. *Harmful Algae*. 92, 101739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101739>
- Kahru, M. and Elmgren, R. (2014). Multidecadal time series of satellite-detected accumulations of cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea. *Biogeosciences*, 11, 3619–3633. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-3619-2014>
- Karjalainen, M., Engström-Öst, J., Korpinen, S., Peltonen, H., Pääkkönen, J.-P., Rönkkönen, S., Suikkanen, S. and Viitasalo, M. (2007): Ecosystem consequences of cyanobacteria in the northern Baltic Sea. *Ambio* 36(2-3): 195-202.
- Karjalainen, M., Pääkkönen, J.-P., Peltonen, H., Sipiä, V., Valtonen T. and Viitasalo, M. (2008). Nodularin concentrations in Baltic Sea zooplankton and fish during a cyanobacterial bloom. *Marine Biology* 155: 483–491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-008-1046-4>
- Spilling K, Olli K, Lehtoranta J, Kremp A, Tedesco L, Tamelander T, Klais R, Peltonen H and Tamminen T (2018). Shifting Diatom—Dinoflagellate Dominance During Spring Bloom in the Baltic Sea and its Potential Effects on Biogeochemical Cycling. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 5:327. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00327>
- Stal, L. J., Albertano, P., Bergman, B., von Bröckel, K., Gallon, J. R., Hayes, P. K., Sivonen, K., and Walsby, A. E. (2003): BASIC: Baltic Sea cyanobacteria. An investigation of the structure and dynamics of water blooms of cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea – responses to a changing environment, *Cont. Shelf Res.*, 23, 1695–1714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2003.06.001>
- Zillén, L. and Conley, D.J., 2010. Hypoxia and cyanobacteria blooms - are they really natural features of the late Holocene history of the Baltic Sea? *Biogeosciences*, 7, 2567–2580. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-7-2567-2010>

4.4 Case study 3: Environmental drivers of HABs in Black Sea and Aegean coastal waters: Critical thresholds for increased risk of HAB formation

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4.4.1 Introduction

The increasing size and frequency of HABs in coastal waters is often associated with cultural eutrophication (Heisler et al., 2008; Xiao et al., 2019) and warming due to the recent climatological changes (Kudela et al., 2008), although the relationship is complex and not always so straight-forward (Glibert et al., 2008). It is widely known that the main cause of eutrophication is inorganic nutrient enrichment, mainly in the forms of nitrogen and phosphorus, resulting in the growth of high algal biomass. However, for the development of HABs, the composition, and not the total quantity of nutrient pool, is mostly important (Heisler et al., 2008), reflecting the fact that the development of a HAB is a species-specific procedure boosted in a chemical environment suitable for each species physiological requirements. Moreover, a HAB is not necessarily linked with the development of high algal biomass, for example, some *Dinophysis* species, even in low populations, may have toxic effects on other organisms (e.g. Anderson et al., 2008). Physical factors, including temperature and salinity, have also been identified as important drivers for HAB formation (Tamvakis et al., 2021), affecting either directly or indirectly the size, frequency and changes in seasonality of HABs (Xiao et al., 2019). Many statistical methods have been applied, aiming to associate HAB formation and development with eutrophication or environmental drivers, including modern data processing methods, as machine learning (Tamvakis et al., 2021). These methods may lead to the establishment of cause-and-effect relationships between environmental variables and HABs development, providing the basis for forecasting and defining possible thresholds for the good ecological state of coastal waters. The Random Forest (RF) algorithm has recently gained significant attention in marine ecology as a robust tool for analyzing complex ecological data and revealing the interactive relationships of the driving forces in difficult ecological problems. Its utility in this field is underscored by its ability to handle high-dimensional datasets and its effectiveness in identifying key environmental variables that crucially influence marine ecosystems. Furthermore, studies have shown that RF outperforms traditional modelling techniques in various prediction projects, reinforcing its status as a leading machine learning method (Boulesteix et al., 2012).

The application of Random Forest (RF) algorithm in marine ecology extends to habitat mapping and biodiversity assessments. For instance, it has been employed to predict the distribution of various

species based on habitat characteristics, demonstrating its robustness in handling correlated variables and modelling complex interactions (Wei et al., 2010; Rather et al., 2020). The main advantage of RF algorithm is that offers valuable insights into the factors influencing species distributions and ecosystem dynamics. Its ensemble learning approach, coupled with its ability to assess variable importance, makes it particularly suitable for the complexities of ecological data. As marine ecosystems face increasing pressures from climate change and human activities, the application of RF will likely play a crucial role in supporting conservation strategies and enhancing our understanding of marine biodiversity.

In the current study, an attempt is made to identify the main environmental drivers of HABs in coastal waters of the western Black Sea (Learning Site 9, LS9) and Aegean Sea (LS8) by applying the RF machine learning algorithm. Nutrient concentrations (Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN and Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus, DIP), as well as temperature and salinity, are used as cause variables to predict (a) the presence/absence of phytoplankton at genus level and (b) low/high density of phytoplankton at genus level. For certain genera already known as harmful or potentially harmful, further analysis is applied, aiming to define thresholds of environmental drivers above or below which the risk of HAB formation is high. Finally, the establishment of common rules on the risk of HAB formation for certain species in the study areas is examined, aiming to further assess the possibility to include those thresholds in integrated tools for management of the good ecological state of European waters.

4.4.2 Methods

The Databases

Western Black Sea (LS9)

Data were collected from three areas, Sulina close to the Danube River outflow, Est-Constanta and Mangalia (Figure 4.4.1). Five stations with a maximum depth of 20 m were sampled in Sulina, a total of 34 samples from 2008-2018, from May to September. In Est-Constanta, 7 stations were sampled with a maximum depth of 80 m, a total of 140 samples from 2009-2018, from May to September. Finally, at Mangalia, 55 samples were collected from 2008-2018, from May to August, at 6 stations with a maximum depth of 90 m.

Figure 4.4.1. Location of sampling stations in the western Black Sea in Sulina (5 stations) close to the Danube river outflow, Est-Constanta (7 stations) and Mangalia (6 stations).

The biotic information includes phytoplankton data at the species level, both abundance and wet biomass, and environmental information includes PO_4 (DIP), NO_3 , NO_2 , NH_4 , temperature and salinity. DIN was calculated by adding NO_3 , NO_2 and NH_4 .

Aegean coastal waters (LS8)

The dataset includes 701 field samples from coastal areas of the Aegean Sea in Eastern Mediterranean (Figure 4.4.2), representing a wide range of productivity. At each station, repetitive sampling was carried out covering at least a full annual cycle mostly on a monthly basis. Detailed information about the sampling sites and data collection are provided in Spatharis et al. (2008). Inner Saronikos Gulf (S, 2 stations), near Athens is characteristic of eutrophic conditions (Simboura et al., 2005). Outer Saronikos Gulf (S, 7 stations), Gera Gulf (G, 8 stations) and Rhodes coastal (R1, 10 stations) are more typical of mesotrophic conditions (Arhonditsis et al., 2000), while offshore stations in Rhodes Island (R2, 5 stations) have been characterized as oligotrophic (Kitsiou et al., 2002). Finally, the 2 stations in the Strait of Mytilene (M) fall in the range from eutrophication to mesotrophy. A detailed account on the eutrophication level and ecological status of these areas is provided in Spatharis and Tsirtsis (2010).

The available biotic information includes phytoplankton abundance at species level identified in an inverted microscope and environmental information includes DIP and DIN concentrations, temperature and salinity.

Figure 4.4.2. Location of sampling sites in Aegean Sea, W. Mediterranean, in Saronikos (9 stations) close to the Metropolitan area of Athens, Gera Gulf (8 stations) and Strait of Mytilene (2 stations) in the island of Lesbos, Rhodes offshore waters (5 stations) and Rhodes coastal waters (10 stations) in the island of Rhodes.

Summary statistics of the environmental variables for the two Learning Sites are shown in Table 1. Temperature has almost the same range and mean in the two study sites, whereas salinity is much lower in Black Sea compared to the Aegean. DIN is also much higher in Black Sea, whereas DIP is not considerably different in the two LSs.

Table 4.4.1. Summary statistics of environmental variables in Aegean Sea (LS8) and Black Sea (LS9): temperature in oC, salinity in o/oo, DIN Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen in μM , DIP Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus in μM .

Statistic	temperature	salinity	DIN	DIP
<u>LS8. Aegean Sea</u>				
min	9.9	27.98	0.12	0.01
max	27.6	40.28	37.95	6.00
mean	19.3	38.67	1.93	0.14
<u>LS9. Black Sea</u>				
min	7.2	0.11	1.39	0.01
max	27.3	20.30	82.75	4.00
mean	19.5	15.11	12.01	0.31

Analyses applied: the Random Forest algorithm

General principles

RF operates on the principle of ensemble learning, where multiple decision trees are constructed from random data subsets. Each tree contributes to the final prediction, which is typically achieved through majority voting for classification tasks or averaging for regression tasks (Wei et al., 2010; Rather et al., 2020).

The key steps involved in the RF algorithm are the following:

Bootstrap Sampling: For each tree, a random sample of the training data is selected with replacement.

Feature Subsampling: At each node of the decision tree, a random subset of the available features is selected for consideration.

Tree Growing: A decision tree is grown using the selected subset of features and the corresponding bootstrap sample.

Aggregation: The predictions from all the individual trees are combined, typically through majority voting (for classification) or averaging (for regression), to obtain the final prediction.

The use of multiple decision trees in the RF algorithm mitigates overfitting, a common issue with single decision trees, thereby enhancing the model's generalization capabilities. In marine ecology, this characteristic is particularly beneficial due to the often noisy and complex nature of ecological data, where multiple interacting factors can obscure clear patterns (Kitsiou and Karydis, 2020).

Parameter tuning is essential for optimizing the RF model. Key hyperparameters include the number of trees in the forest, the number of variables tested in each split, and the minimum number of samples required to split a node. Increasing the number of trees generally enhances model accuracy, although also increases computational demands (Rather et al., 2020). Adjusting the hyperparameters can control overfitting; shallower trees may generalize better, while deeper trees can capture more complex relationships within the data. Additionally, the minimum samples per leaf (terminal nodes) can influence the model's sensitivity to noise, making it crucial to balance these parameters for optimal performance (Wei et al., 2010). The values of the hyperparameters of RF applied in the current study are shown in [Table 4.4.2](#).

Table 4.4.2. Values of the hyperparameters used in RF training in the current study.

Random Forest hyperparameter	Value
Number of trees	500
Number of variables tried at each split	Sqrt of the number of input variables
Minimum size of terminal nodes	1
Maximum number of terminal nodes trees in the forest	Maximum possible

Measuring the importance and interaction of the explanatory variables

The algorithm's ability to assess variable importance is another significant advantage, allowing researchers to discern which physicochemical or other factors most influence ecosystem dynamics, e.g. species occurrence, abundance or distribution. This is particularly relevant in marine ecology, where understanding the impact of variables such as temperature, salinity, and nutrient availability is crucial for conservation and management efforts (Bremner, 2008).

RF quantifies variable importance through different metrics, providing insights that can guide ecological research and policy decisions (Fox et al., 2017). Among these metrics, the mean decrease of node impurity was selected to measure the changes of node purity after splits on each input variable and to offer insights to the local adjustments. Moreover, the importance of the input variables to the global structure of the forest was approached using the one-sided binomial test result that tests whether the number of nodes of a splitting variable exceeds the theoretical number of the corresponding random selection. Finally, the most significant interaction among the input variables was estimated as the most frequent ordered pair of consecutive nodes that appears in the tree forest.

Data processing was performed within the R environment (R Core Team, 2025). For Random Forest analyses, the packages `randomForest` and `randomForestExplainer` were used.

4.4.3 Results

RF algorithm was applied in the western Black Sea (LS9 Romania) database for the prediction of (a) the presence-absence and (b) low-high abundance of each genus based on environmental variables (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity). To have enough instances to train the algorithm, a minimum of 10 cases per genus was set. Therefore, presence-absence was predicted for 62 genera, using 26-142 instances for absence and 10-126 instances for presence. For low-high abundance, a limit of 10000 cells/L was set, and prediction was made for 21 genera, using 81-142 instances for low and 10-71 instances for high abundance.

The classification errors for the prediction of presence-absence and low-high abundance are shown in [Figure 4.4.3](#). Classification errors are higher for presences and high abundances due to the much lower number of instances that were used to train the RF algorithm. Nevertheless, the two errors are complementary for each genus and counter-balanced since there are only two possible classes (presence-absence, low-high abundance) in the analysis implemented.

Figure 4.4.3. Classification errors of the RF algorithm for the prediction of presence-absence (left) and low-high abundance (right) at genus level for the western Black Sea (LS9 Romania).

The % contribution of environmental variables based on Gini decrease (loss of information if the variable under consideration is removed from the analysis) in the prediction process is shown in [Figure 4.4.4](#). The contribution of the four variables is almost identical in both cases. Salinity has the highest contribution, followed by temperature. The contribution of nutrients is lower compared to the physical variables and almost equal for DIN and DIP.

Figure 4.4.4. % contribution of environmental variables (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity) in the prediction of (a) presence-absence (left) and (b) high-low abundance (right) at genus level for the western Black Sea (LS9 Romania).

The analyses above were also performed for LS8, Aegean coastal waters. By setting a minimum number of 10 cases per genus, to have enough instances to train the algorithm, presence-absence was predicted for 66 genera, using 36-464 instances for absence and 10-438 instances for presence. For low-high abundance a limit of 10000 cells/L was set, and prediction was made for 13 genera, using 412-462 instances for low and 12-62 instances for high abundance.

As it was observed in the analysis for the Black Sea, the classification errors are higher for presences and high abundances due to the much lower number of instances that were used to train the RF algorithm (Figure 4.4.5). Nevertheless, the two errors are complementary and counter-balanced, and therefore they do not affect further analyses.

Figure 4.4.5. Classification error of the RF algorithm for the prediction of presence-absence (left) and low-high abundance (right) at genus level for Aegean coastal waters (LS8).

The % contribution of environmental variables based on Gini decrease (loss of information if the variable under consideration is removed from the analysis) in the prediction process is shown in (Figure 4.4.6). The % contribution of the four variables is almost the same, either for presence-absence or for high-low abundance. Temperature is identified as the most important predictor, whereas DIN and salinity have almost equal effect. The effect of DIP is lower in both cases.

Figure 4.4.6. % contribution of environmental variables (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity) in the prediction of (a) presence-absence (left) and (b) high-low abundance (right) at genus level for Aegean coastal waters (LS8).

Moreover, the importance of environmental variables on the blooming of specific genera in the two Learning Sites and the limits above or below which a bloom is favored, were quantified by the Random Forest algorithm. Specifically, for each genus, two classes of abundance were set (high-low abundance) and the contribution of each variable in the class prediction was estimated. For the variables with the highest contribution in the prediction (based on the Gini index decrease, i.e. loss of information when the variable is removed from the analysis), limits were also estimated separating the two classes. For Black Sea waters, the method was applied for *Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis*, *Gonyaulax*, *Lingulodinium*, *Prorocentrum* and *Pseudo-nitzschia*, characterized as Potentially Toxic Species in this area (Boicenco, pers. comm), although their toxicity and the potential to develop harmful algal blooms have not been identified so far. The limits characterizing high-low abundance in cells/L for each genus were 500 for *Alexandrium*, 200 for *Dinophysis*, 1000 for *Gonyaulax*, 1 000 for *Lingulodinium*, 500 for *Prorocentrum* and 200 000 for *Pseudo-nitzschia*, based on the corresponding

warning limits set in several European countries in the report of the EU Working Group on Toxin-producing Phytoplankton Monitoring in Bivalve Mollusc Harvesting Areas (2019).

For each genus and each pair of environmental variables, a heat map is produced by RF showing the variable ranges where the risk of bloom formation is high. As an example, the heat map for the risk of high abundance of *Prorocentrum* in relation to temperature and salinity for the Black Sea is shown in Figure 4.4.7. Red areas show increased risk of high abundance (higher than 500 cells/L) and blue areas show low risk. Therefore, in the Black Sea temperatures higher than 18°C and salinity higher than 13 favor a high abundance of *Prorocentrum*. The information from the heat maps for the various genera in the two sites are summarized in [Tables 4.4.3](#) (Black Sea) and [4.4.4](#) (Aegean Sea).

Figure 4.4.7. Heat map showing the risk of high (in red) and low (in blue) abundance of *Prorocentrum* in the Black Sea, calculated by the RF algorithm.

The results of the Random Forest algorithm in the Black Sea (LS9) are shown in [Table 4.4.3](#). For each genus, limits are shown only for variables identified by the method as significant. The two variables having the highest contribution in the prediction of high-low abundance (based on Gini decrease, i.e. information loss when the variable is removed from the analysis) are written in bold.

Table 4.4.3. Limits of environmental variables that determine the growth of high biomass for each genus in Black Sea waters (LS9 Romania). The two variables with the highest effect are shown in bold. Dashes show variables with no effect.

genus	salinity (‰)	temperature (°C)	DIN (μM)	DIP (μM)
<i>Alexandrium</i>	<15	>25	-	-
<i>Dinophysis</i>	13-18	<17	<20	<0.3
<i>Gonyaulax</i>	>18	>28	>75	-
<i>Lingulodinium</i>	14-15	12-14	-	-
<i>Prorocentrum</i>	>13	>18	-	-
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i>	-	<19	15-60	0.3-0.8

As it was generally found in the analysis for all phytoplankton genera, temperature and salinity seem to be the most important predictors of high biomass for the six potentially toxic genera under consideration (Table 4.4.4). Regarding the limits above or below which high biomass may grow, the results are species specific, some showing preference for high values, others for low, and others for values in rather narrow ranges.

A similar analysis was performed for Aegean coastal waters (LS8) for the genera analyzed above in Black Sea (except for *Alexandrium*, which was found in very low densities in the Aegean) for comparison and additional genera causing HABs in the Aegean (unpublished data), that is *Noctiluca*, *Chatonella* and *Gymnodinium*. The limits for low-high abundances were set as 500 for *Gymnodinium*, *Karenia* and 5 000 for *Noctiluca*.

Table 4.4.4. Limits of environmental variables that determine the growth of high biomass for each genus in Aegean coastal waters (LS8). The two variables with the highest effect are shown in bold. Dashes show variables with no effect.

genus	salinity (‰)	temperature (°C)	DIN (μM)	DIP (μM)
<i>Dinophysis</i>	<39	16-18	>10	<2
<i>Gonyaulax</i>	-	~13	>2	>0.2
<i>Lingulodinium</i>	-	12-14	-	>0.2
<i>Prorocentrum</i>	<38	>24	-	-
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i>	<38	15-17	-	-
<i>Gymnodinium</i>	~38	-	<1	>0.4
<i>Karenia</i>	<38	14-20	-	>0.5
<i>Noctiluca</i>	<37	>24	>1	>0.3

Temperature and salinity are the variables with the highest effect on abundance growth for most genera in Aegean coastal waters, as was also observed for the Black Sea. Regarding the environmental values, temperature in the range of 12-20 °C and DIP values above 0.2 μM seem to favor most genera. Salinity is generally high in Aegean coastal waters when compared to the Black Sea.

4.4.4 Discussion

The RF machine learning algorithm was applied to estimate the most important environmental predictors for phytoplankton growth in the western Black Sea (LS9 Romania) and Aegean Sea coastal waters (LS8). Physical variables (temperature and salinity) were identified as the most important predictors for both presence-absence and low-high abundance at the genus level in the Black Sea when compared with nutrients (DIN and DIP). In Aegean coastal waters, temperature was also identified as the most important predictor, followed by DIN, salinity and DIP, their effects being almost equal. The role of physical variables as drivers of phytoplankton growth has also been identified in the past in similar studies (Tamvakis et al., 2014, 2021; Lazar et al., 2024). Although temperature and salinity do not necessarily have a direct effect on phytoplankton growth, indirect effects as the vertical movement of the pycnocline is identified as an important triggering factor for phytoplankton growth either in the open ocean (Mann and Lazier, 2013) or in coastal areas affected by terrestrial freshwater runoff (Spatharis et al., 2007). Salinity, identified as the main predictor for phytoplankton growth in the Black Sea, is not so important in Aegean Sea. This is possibly due to the relatively narrow salinity range observed in the Aegean (28-40) when compared to Black Sea waters (0-20), which are heavily influenced by freshwater inputs from the Danube River. These findings also suggest that the Black Sea may be particularly vulnerable to climate change, as rising temperatures and alterations in Danube River hydrology, marked by alternating periods of drought and flooding, could further impact ecosystem stability.

For selected harmful algal genera, an attempt was made to estimate environmental conditions increasing the risk of HAB formation. Physical variables (temperature and salinity) were mostly found as the most important predictors of increased abundance in both Black Sea and Aegean coastal waters, although salinity has a relatively narrow range in the Aegean when compared to the Black Sea. Inorganic nutrients seem to also affect growth in both sites, mostly DIP in the Aegean and DIN in the Black Sea. Regarding the identified limits for high risk of bloom formation, the results are species specific, some showing preference for high values, other for low, and other for values in rather narrow ranges.

When attempting to compare the environmental conditions increasing the risk of blooms for toxic or potentially toxic genera analyzed in both sites (*Dinophysis*, *Gonyaulax*, *Lingulodinium*, *Prorocentrum*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*), some conclusions can be drawn, although not always safely. Salinity which is an important predictor in the Black Sea due to its broad range, does not provide useful information in the Aegean, so interesting comparisons can be made only for temperature. *Dinophysis* in both sites is favored by temperatures lower than 18°C and DIN in the range 10-20 µM. *Lingulodinium* is favored by temperature in the narrow range of 12-14°C in both sites, whereas DIP, for which high values are required in the Aegean, is not important in the Black Sea. *Prorocentrum* is favored by salinities in the range of 13-38 and temperatures higher than 18°C. *Pseudo-nitzschia* shows high risk for blooms at temperatures lower than 19°C and high DIN concentrations. Finally, *Gonyaulax* requires high nutrient concentrations of nutrients in both sites, although for temperature, the identified limits are not in agreement.

In conclusion, the Random Forest machine learning algorithm can be effectively used for the prediction of HABs from environmental variables. Although the conditions for HAB formation are always species specific and often site specific (Gilbert et al., 2008), some general rules and thresholds for increased risk of bloom formation can be established using RF, at the genus level. Those thresholds may be further included in integrated tools for the management of the good ecological state of European waters.

4.4.5 References

- Anderson, D.M., Burkholder, J.M., Cochlan, W.P., Glibert, P.M., Gobler, C.J., Heil, C.A., Kudela, R.M., Parsons, M.L., Rensel, J.E.J., Townsend, D.W., Trainer, V.L., and Vargo, G.A. (2008). Harmful algal blooms and eutrophication: Examining linkages from selected coastal regions of the United States. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 39-53. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.017>
- Arhonditsis, G., Tsiirtsis, G., Angelidis, M., and Karydis, M. (2000). Quantification of the effects of nonpoint nutrient sources to coastal marine eutrophication: applications to a semi-enclosed gulf in the Mediterranean Sea. *Ecological Modelling*, 129, 209-227. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800\(00\)00239-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800(00)00239-8)
- Boulesteix, A.-L., Janitza, S., Kruppa, J. and König, I.R. (2012). Overview of random forest methodology and practical guidance with emphasis on computational biology and bioinformatics. *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 2(6): 493-507. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1072>
- Bremner, J. (2008). Species' traits and ecological functioning in marine conservation and management. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 366(1-2): 37-47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2008.07.007>
- EU Working Group on Toxin-producing Phytoplankton Monitoring in Bivalve Mollusc Harvesting Areas (2019). European Union Reference Laboratory for Marine Biotoxins Monitoring of Toxin-

- producing Phytoplankton in Bivalve Mollusc Harvesting Areas. Guide to Good Practice: Technical Application, 44 pp.
- Fox, E.W., Hill, R.A., Leibowitz, S.G., Olsen, A.R., Thornbrugh, D.J., Weber, M.H. (2017). Assessing the accuracy and stability of variable selection methods for random forest modeling in ecology. *Environmental Monitor. & Assessment* 189, 316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-017-6025-0>
- Glibert, P.M., Burkholder, J.M., Graneli, E., and Anderson, D.M. (2008). Advances and insights in the complex relationships between eutrophication and HABs: Preface to the special issue. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 175-181. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.013>
- Heisler, J., Glibert P.M., Burkholder, J.M., Anderson, D.M., Cochlan, W., Dennison, W.C., Dortch, Q., Gobler, C.J., Heil, C.A., Humphries, E., Lewitus, A., Magnien, R., Marshall, H.G., Sellner, K., Stockwell, D.A., Stoecker, D.K., and Suddleson, M. 2008. Eutrophication and harmful algal blooms: A scientific consensus. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 3-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.006>
- Kitsiou, D., Coccossis, H., and Karydis, M. (2002). Multi-dimensional evaluation and ranking of coastal areas using GIS and multiple criteria choice methods. *Science of the Total Environment*, 284(1-3), 1-17. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697\(01\)00851-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697(01)00851-8)
- Kitsiou, D., Karydis, M. (2011). Coastal marine eutrophication assessment: A review on data analysis. *Environmental International* 37(4): 778-801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2011.02.004>
- Kudela, R.M., Lane, J.Q., and Cochlan, W.P. (2008). The potential role of anthropogenically derived nitrogen in the growth of harmful algae in California, USA. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 103-110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.019>
- Lazar, L.; Boicenco, L.; Pantea, E.; Timofte, F.; Vlas, O.; Bişnicu, E. Modeling Dynamic Processes in the Black Sea Pelagic Habitat—Causal Connections between Abiotic and Biotic Factors in Two Climate Change Scenarios. *Sustainability* 2024, 16, 1849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16051849>
- Mann, K.H., and Lazier, J.R.N. (2013). *Dynamics of Marine Ecosystems*. 3rd ed. Malden, M.A. & Oxford, UK, Blackwell Publishing, 496 pp.
- Rather, T.A., Kumar, S., Khan, J.A. (2020). Multi-scale habitat selection and impacts of climate change on the distribution of four sympatric meso-carnivores using random forest algorithm. *Ecological Processes* 9(60). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-020-00265-2>
- R Core Team (2025). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Spatharis, S., G. Tsirtsis, D. Danielidis, T. Do Chi and D. Mouillot, 2007. Effects of pulsed nutrient inputs on phytoplankton assemblage structure and blooms in an enclosed coastal area. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Science*, 73, 807-815, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2007.03.016>
- Spatharis, S., Mouillot, D., Danielidis, D., Karydis, M., Do Chi, T., and Tsirtsis, G. (2008). Influence of terrestrial runoff on phytoplankton species richness-biomass relationships: a double stress hypothesis. *Journal of Marine Biology and Ecology*, 362, 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2008.06.003>
- Spatharis, S., and Tsirtsis, G. (2010). Ecological quality scales based on phytoplankton for the implementation of Water Framework Directive in Eastern Mediterranean. *Ecological Indicators*, 10(4), 840-847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2010.01.005>
- Simboura, N., Panayotidis, P., and Papathanassiou, E. (2005). A synthesis of the biological quality elements for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive in the Mediterranean ecoregion: the case of Saronikos Gulf. *Ecological Indicators*, 5, 253-266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2005.03.006>

- Tamvakis, A., Spatharis, S., Trygonis, V., Myritzis, J., and Tsirtsis, G. (2014). Optimizing biodiversity prediction from abiotic parameters. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 53, 112-120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.12.001>
- Tamvakis, A., Tsirtsis, G., Karydis, M., Patsidis, K., and Kokkoris, G.D. (2021). Drivers of harmful algal blooms in coastal areas of Eastern Mediterranean: a machine learning methodological approach. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 18(5), 6484-6505, <https://doi.org/10.3934/mbe.2021322>
- Wei, C.-L., Rowe, G.T., Escobar-Briones, E, Boetius, A., Soltwedel, T., Caley, M.J., et al. (2010) Global Patterns and Predictions of Seafloor Biomass Using Random Forests. *PLoS ONE* 5(12): e15323. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0015323>
- Xiao, X., Agustí, S., Pan, Y., Yu, Y., Li, K., Wu, J., and Duarte, C.M. (2019). Warming Amplifies the Frequency of Harmful Algal Blooms with Eutrophication in Chinese Coastal Waters. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2019, 53, 13031–13041. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b03726>

4.5 Case study 4: Critical thresholds of environmental drivers of HABs in Danish waters (Learning Site 3): the role of time lags in the prediction of HABs

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4.5.1 Introduction

The size and frequency of HABs in coastal waters are increasing, often associated with cultural eutrophication (Heisler et al., 2008; Xiao et al., 2019) and warming due to the recent climatic changes (Kudela et al., 2008). A review of the possible relationships as well as of the main environmental factors related to the development of HABs has been given in Chapter 4.4. In the same Chapter, the advantages of the use of machine learning methods, and specifically Random Forest (RF), in studying marine ecological processes, including HABs, have been reviewed and revealed.

In the current study, RF machine learning algorithm is used to identify the main environmental drivers of HABs in a number of stations in Danish waters (Learning Site 3, LS3). Nutrient concentrations (Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN and Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus, DIP), as well as temperature and salinity, are used as cause variables to predict (a) presence/absence and (b) low/high abundance of phytoplankton at the genus level. For certain genera already known as harmful or potentially harmful, further analysis is applied, aiming to define thresholds of environmental drivers above or below which, the risk of HAB formation is high. Finally, the role of time lags between selected cause (environmental) and response (phytoplankton abundance) variables is investigated aiming to increase the understanding of a complex and often site and species-specific process as HAB development (Anderson et al., 2008).

4.5.2 Methods

The database

Data were compiled from 43 stations in Danish waters, LS3 (Figure 4.5.1) sampled from the column of 0-10 m, on a monthly or more frequent basis, each station at different time periods. For some stations, long time series exist for example, from 1978 to 2021 or from 1985 to 2021, whereas for others the sampling frequency is high (e.g. 4 samples per month), although the length of the time series is relatively short (for example, 2 years). The biotic information includes phytoplankton abundance data at the species level, whereas environmental information is available for DIN, DIP, salinity and temperature.

Figure 4.5.1. Location of the 43 sampling stations in Danish waters (LS3) sampled on a monthly or more frequent basis in different time periods: in the current analysis, only stations marked with red dots were used.

For the analysis of environmental drivers of HABs, data were used from stations ARH170006, NOR5503, VIB3708, VEJ0006870 and VESJ20925, which are marked with red dots in Figure 4.5.1. Those stations were selected based on two criteria: (a) the availability of long and dense time series and (b) the development of HABs (Hansen et al., 2015; Carstensen and Jakobsen, 2023). The sampling period, the number of available samples and the sampling frequency for each station are shown in Table 4.5.1.

Table 4.5.1. Sampling period, number of samples and sampling frequency for the five stations in Danish waters (LS3) analyzed in the current study.

Station	Sampling period	No of samples	Sampling frequency
ARH170006	1978-2021	758	twice a month
NOR5503	1991-2021	742	three or more samples per month
VIB3708	1985-2021	695	monthly or more frequently
VEJ0006870	1992, 1998-2021	521	twice per month or more frequently
VESJ20925	1998-2021	466	monthly or more frequently

Summary statistics of the environmental variables for the five stations are shown in Table 4.5.2. Temperature is low in all stations with means in the range of 10.0 to 11.9°C. The range in all stations is from close to 0 up to 22.9°C. The highest salinity (both mean and range) is observed in station VIB3708 and the lowest in station NOR5503. Stations ARH170006, VEJ0006870 and VESJ20925 have

almost similar salinities. The highest DIN and DIP values were observed in station NOR5503, followed by station VIB3708, whereas the rest stations have almost similar means and ranges.

Table 4.5.2. Summary statistics of environmental variables in the five stations of Danish waters (LS3) used in the current analysis: temperature in °C, salinity in ‰, DIN Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen in µM, DIP Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus in µM.

Statistic	temperature	salinity	DIN	DIP
<u>ARH170006</u>				
min	-0.7	13.78	0.14	0.03
max	21.7	30.52	23.21	1.10
mean	10.0	22.61	2.79	0.25
<u>NOR5503</u>				
min	-0.3	12.45	0.32	0.01
max	22.2	18.99	252.00	8.71
mean	11.9	15.69	51.88	1.29
<u>VIB3708</u>				
min	-1.4	21.95	0.29	0.03
max	22.9	30.74	79.21	6.90
mean	10.5	26.69	16.10	0.65
<u>VEJ0006870</u>				
min	-1.1	12.57	0.28	0.03
max	22.2	29.82	18.57	1.48
mean	10.4	21.53	2.45	0.30
<u>VSJ20925</u>				
min	-0.3	10.62	0.04	0.01
max	22.3	28.25	15.76	0.95
mean	10.6	19.51	2.25	0.23

Analyses applied

The RF machine learning algorithm (already described in detail in Chapter 4.4) was applied (a) to predict (a) presence/absence and (b) low/high abundance of phytoplankton at genus level from environmental divers (temperature, salinity, DIN and DIP) in the 5 stations of Danish waters (LS3) under consideration. Aiming to test if time lags between cause (environmental) and response (phytoplankton presence/absence or low/high abundance) affect the prediction process, the algorithm was applied for (a) values of the same sampling time, (b) environmental variables from the previous sampling time and (c) environmental values of the pre-previous sampling time. Since the sampling frequency in the different stations is not the same, those lags correspond to different real-time periods.

Certain genera already known as harmful or potentially harmful were selected for further analysis, aiming to define thresholds of environmental drivers above or below which the risk of HAB formation is high. Those genera were *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Pseudochattonella*, *Prorocentrum* and *Skeletonema*, already known as HAB forming in Danish waters (Carstensen et al., 2015). For those genera, additional analysis was performed aiming to assess the role of time lags between environmental drivers and abundance. To this aim, cross-correlation with time lags was applied by shifting the position of the two vectors (cause and response variables) relative to one another by k elements and then correlating the vectors. The value of k is increased incrementally, and the vectors are relatively shifted to see how the correlations change and to determine the value of k at which the correlation is highest or lowest. The analysis was performed in the R environment (R Core Team, 2025) by the `ccf` function. Since the sampling frequency differs in the five stations, the k elements have different real-time values at each of the five stations. For example, in station ARH170006, where sampling was performed twice per month, each k element is equal to half a month, whereas in station NOR5503, where three or more samples were collected per month, the k element is equal to one week.

4.5.3 Results

RF algorithm was applied in the five stations of Danish waters (LS3) for the prediction of (a) presence/absence and (b) low/high abundance of each genus based on environmental variables (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity). To have enough instances to train the algorithm, a minimum of 10 cases per genus was set in each analysis. As it was described in the methodology, a first approach towards the assessment of the importance of time lags between cause (environmental) and response (presence/absence or low/high abundance) variables was made by shifting the two time series one step (previous environmental values) or two steps (pre-previous environmental values). The classification errors for predicting the presence/absence and the low/high abundance for station NOR5503 are shown in [Figure 4.5.2](#). Classification errors are higher for presences and high abundances due to the much lower number of instances used to train the RF algorithm. Nevertheless, the two errors are complementary for each genus and counter-balanced since there are only two possible classes (presence/absence, low/high abundance) in the implemented analysis. Moreover, it can be demonstrated that shifting of one or two time steps have a minor effect on the prediction process when applying the RF algorithm. Similar results were obtained for the remaining stations.

Figure 4.5.2. Classification errors of the RF algorithm for the prediction of presence/absence (left) and low/high abundance (right) at the genus level for station NOR5503. Blue lines correspond to concurrent values of environmental and biotic variables, red lines to the shifting of one time step and green lines to the shifting of two time steps.

The % contribution of the environmental variables in the prediction process based on Gini decrease (loss of information if the variable under consideration is removed from the analysis) for station NOR5503 when using concurrent values of cause and response variables is shown in Figure 4.5.3. The contribution of the four variables is nearly identical in both cases (presence/absence, low/high abundance). Temperature and DIN have the highest predictive power, followed by salinity and DIP. For almost all the remaining stations, temperature has the highest contribution, followed by either DIN or salinity, whereas DIP has the lowest contribution.

Mean contribution of env variables based on Gini decrease

current environmental variables

Mean contribution of env variables based on Gini decrease

current environmental variables

Figure 4.5.3. % contribution of the environmental variables (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity) in the prediction of (a) presence/absence (left) and (b) high/low abundance (right) at genus level in station NOR5503 using concurrent values of environmental and biotic variables.

For selected genera, that is *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Pseudochattonella*, *Prorocentrum* and *Skeletonema*, further analysis was performed aiming to define thresholds of environmental drivers above or below which, the risk of HAB formation is high. The limits characterizing high/low abundance in cells/L were 200000 for *Pseudo-nitzschia*, 1000 for *Pseudochattonella*, 500 for *Prorocentrum* based on the corresponding warning limits set in several European countries in the report of the EU Working Group on Toxin-producing Phytoplankton Monitoring in Bivalve Mollusc Harvesting Areas (2019). For *Skeletonema* a limit of 100,000 cells L⁻¹ was set based on literature (Carstensen et al., 2015). For each genus and each pair of environmental variables, a heat map is produced by RF showing the variable ranges where the risk of bloom formation is high.

As an example, the heat map for the risk of high abundance of *Pseudo-nitzschia* in relation to temperature and salinity for station ARH170006 is shown in Figure 4.5.4. Red areas show increased risk of high abundance (higher than 200,000 cells L⁻¹), and blue areas show low risk. Therefore, in station ARH170006, salinity higher than 24 and temperature mostly in the range 8-17°C favor high abundance of *Pseudo-nitzschia*. The information from the heat maps for the four genera under consideration in the five stations of LS3 is summarized in Table 4.5.3.

Figure 4.5.4. Heat map showing the risk of high (red area) and low (blue area) abundance of *Pseudo-nitzschia* in station ARH170006, calculated using the RF algorithm.

Table 4.5.3. Limits of environmental variables that determine the growth of high biomass for each genus in selected stations of Danish waters (LS3). The two variables with the highest effect are shown in bold. Dashes show variables with no effect.

station	temperature (°C)	salinity (‰)	DIN (µM)	DIP (µM)
<u><i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i></u>				
ARH170006	<2 & >7	>20	<7	<0.5
NOR5503	-	>17.5	-	-
VIB3708	>18	<25	<15	-
VEJ0006780	~0	>27	-	-
VSJ20925	5-15	>22	<2	-
<u><i>Pseudochattonella</i></u>				
ARH170006	<11	>23	-	>0.1
NOR5503	-	-	-	-
VIB3708	-	-	-	-
VEJ0006780	<7	>23	-	>0.6
VSJ20925	<8	>20	<5	<0.25
<u><i>Prorocentrum</i></u>				
ARH170006	>10	20-25	-	-
NOR5503	>18	>16.5	-	-
VIB3708	>25	>12	<5	-
VEJ0006780	>15	>15	<3	<0.8
VSJ20925	>18	>20	<4	<0.5
<u><i>Skeletonema</i></u>				
ARH170006	<4	<16	-	<0.6
NOR5503	<21	<17	<100	<2.5
VIB3708	<19	<28	<65	-
VEJ0006780	<3	>18	-	<0.7
VSJ20925	<5	<22	<7.5	<0.6

For *Pseudo-nitzschia*, temperature and salinity are the most important predictors of high biomass; However, the identified limits are not consistent among sites, implying that site-specific processes

mainly determine blooms. For *Pseudochattonella*, temperature and salinity are also the most important predictors of high biomass compared to nutrients. The identified limits of physical variables are consistent, indicating that low temperatures (below 11 °C) and high salinity (above 20) are necessary for the formation of HABs of the specific genus. *Prorocentrum* also shows consistent behaviour; high temperature (above 10°C) and high salinity (above 12) are necessary for the development of HABs. Moreover, nutrients are also identified as important predictors for *Prorocentrum* in a number of stations, showing that low concentrations (DIN < 5 and DIP < 0.8 µM) favor the growth of high biomass. Finally, for *Skeletonema*, temperature, salinity, and DIN are the most important predictors, although consistency is not observed for favorable conditions among stations.

Cross-correlation analysis with time lags was employed to assess the role of time lags between environmental drivers and phytoplankton abundance. Specifically, the analysis was performed for temperature and salinity in stations ARH170006 and NOR5503, which have the most complete and regular time series, with sampling frequencies of twice a month for the former and approximately once a week for the latter. As environmental drivers, temperature and salinity were used, identified as the main drivers of blooms in most stations in the previous analyses. An example of the graphical output of cross-correlation analysis with time lags is shown in [Figure 4.5.5](#) for *Prorocentrum* against temperature in station NOR5503. A positive shift of 4 steps (i.e. one month) in abundance against temperature increases the correlation between the two variables.

Figure 4.5.5. The output of the cross-correlation analysis with time lags between the cause and response variables—an example of *Prorocentrum* abundance against temperature in station NOR5503.

For *Prorocentrum* and *Pseudochattonella*, time lags of one month for both temperature and salinity seem to increase the correlation with abundance highly, whereas for *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Skeletonema* the time lags are lower, ranging from one week to one month in the different stations.

4.5.4 Discussion

RF machine learning algorithm was applied to estimate the most important environmental predictors for phytoplankton growth in selected stations in Danish waters (LS3). As it was found for the Black Sea and Aegean Sea coastal waters (Chapter 4.4.), physical variables, mainly temperature, followed by salinity, were identified as the most important predictors for both presence/absence and low/high abundance at the genus level when compared with nutrients (DIN and DIP). Temperature and salinity have been identified as the main drivers of HABs in similar studies (Tamvakis et al., 2014, 2021); their effect has already been discussed in the previous chapter (Chapter 4.4).

For selected algal genera that proliferate in Danish waters, namely *Prorocentrum*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Pseudochattonella* and *Skeletonema*, thresholds of environmental variables were estimated above or below which the risk of bloom formation is high. Temperature and salinity were found as the most important predictors of high abundance for most genera., However, consistency for the observed trends among stations was only observed for *Pseudochattonella* and *Prorocentrum*. Blooms of *Pseudochattonella* are favored by low temperature (below 11°C) and high salinity (above 20). In contrast, those of *Prorocentrum* are favoured by high temperature (above 10°C), high salinity (above 12) and low nutrient concentrations (DIN<5 and DIP<0.8 µM). For *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Skeletonema*, the identified limits were not consistent among stations, implying that site-specific processes mainly determine the blooms, as is the case with many HAB-forming species (Anderson et al., 2008; Glibert et al., 2008).

When previous and pre-previous values of environmental variables were used instead of concurrent values in the RF algorithm, differences were not found in the predictive power of the algorithm, either for phytoplankton presence/absence or for low/high abundance. However, positive time shifts of abundance against temperature and salinity appear to improve the observed correlations. These time shifts differ between species, ranging from weeks for *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Skeletonema*, up to one month for *Prorocentrum* and *Pseudochattonella*. These differences may be related to the physiological responses of the different species to changing environmental conditions and need further research towards the aim of developing early warning systems for HAB formation.

4.5.5 References

- Anderson, D.M., Burkholder, J.M., Cochlan, W.P., Glibert, P.M., Gobler, C.J., Heil, C.A., Kudela, R.M., Parsons, M.L., Rensel, J.E.J., Townsend, D.W., Trainer, V.L., and Vargo, G.A. (2008). Harmful algal blooms and eutrophication: Examining linkages from selected coastal regions of the United States. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 39-53. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.017>
- Carstensen, J. and Jakobsen, H.H. (2023). Harmful algae in the Limfjorden: a data review. *Ecoscience*, pp 59, Aarhus Universitet, – Nationalt Center for Fødevarer og Jordbrug, Aarhus https://dce.au.dk/fileadmin/dce.au.dk/Udgivelser/Eksterne_udgivelser/HarmfulAlgaeInLLimfjorden.pdf
- Carstensen, J., Klais, R., and Cloern, J.E. (2015). Phytoplankton blooms in estuarine and coastal waters: Seasonal patterns and key species. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Science*, 162, 98-109. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2015.05.005>
- EU Working Group on Toxin-producing Phytoplankton Monitoring in Bivalve Mollusc Harvesting Areas (2019). European Union Reference Laboratory for Marine Biotoxins Monitoring of Toxin-producing Phytoplankton in Bivalve Mollusc Harvesting Areas. Guide to Good Practice: Technical Application, 44 pp.
- Glibert, P.M., Burkholder, J.M., Graneli, E., and Anderson, D.M. (2008). Advances and insights in the complex relationships between eutrophication and HABs: Preface to the special issue. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 175-181. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.013>
- Hansen, J.W., Bruhn, A., Carstensen, J., Dahl, K., Galatius, A., Göke, C., Hansen, J.L.S., Jakobsen, H.H., Krause-Jensen, D., Larsen, M.L., Markager, S., C., M., Petersen, I.K., Strand, J., Teilmann, J. and Tougaard, J. 2015 page 56. In *Marine områder 2015 NOVANA*, p. 148, Aarhus Universitet DCE – Nationalt Center for Miljø og Energi (In Danish language), *Marine områder 2015 NOVANA* <https://dce2.au.dk/pub/sr208.pdf>
- Heisler, J., Glibert P.M., Burkholder, J.M., Anderson, D.M., Cochlan, W., Dennison, W.C., Dortch, Q., Gobler, C.J., Heil, C.A., Humphries, E., Lewitus, A., Magnien, R., Marshall, H.G., Sellner, K., Stockwell, D.A., Stoecker, D.K., and Suddleson, M. 2008. Eutrophication and harmful algal blooms: A scientific consensus. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 3-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.006>
- Kudela, R.M., Lane, J.Q., and Cochlan, W.P. (2008). The potential role of anthropogenically derived nitrogen in the growth of harmful algae in California, USA. *Harmful Algae*, 8, 103-110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2008.08.019>
- R Core Team (2025). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Tamvakis, A., Spatharis, S., Trygonis, V., Myrtilis, J., and Tsirtsis, G. (2014). Optimizing biodiversity prediction from abiotic parameters. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 53, 112-120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.12.001>
- Tamvakis, A., Tsirtsis, G., Karydis, M., Patsidis, K., and Kokkoris, G.D. (2021). Drivers of harmful algal blooms in coastal areas of Eastern Mediterranean: a machine learning methodological approach. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 18(5), 6484-6505, <https://doi.org/10.3934/mbe.2021322>
- Xiao, X., Agustí, S., Pan, Y., Yu, Y., Li, K., Wu, J., and Duarte, C.M. (2019). Warming Amplifies the Frequency of Harmful Algal Blooms with Eutrophication in Chinese Coastal Waters. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2019, 53, 13031–13041. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b03726>

4.6 Case study 5: Satellite data to generate Chl-a indicators in the Romanian coast

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4.6.1 Introduction

Several remote sensing data and information have been identified as adequate to contribute to several MSFD Indicators (Zampoukas et al., 2012). Among them, the chlorophyll-a surface estimates are used to assess the 5.2 indicator on “Chlorophyll concentration in the water column” under Descriptor 5 for “Eutrophication”.

A case study was carried out in the SE Bay of Biscay under the DEVOTES project, to investigate the potential of satellite chlorophyll-a estimates to calculate the D5.2.1 indicator used in the Atlantic waters (6-year 90th percentile of chlorophyll-a). This study demonstrated the usefulness of daily satellite data to capture better both the spatial and temporal variability of chlorophyll-a often missed by in-situ monitoring effort that under-samples areas and seasons of higher variability. However, satellite data also have some limitations and uncertainties (Hooker and McClain, 2000)³. The first one concerns the fact that only surface layers are sensed; hence, subsurface peaks of chlorophyll may be underestimated or completely missed. Another limitation concerns the accuracy of the estimation of chlorophyll-a values, especially in waters with complex optical properties, such as coastal waters.

The results of the study showed that, despite the satellite overestimation of chlorophyll-a values, leading to different water body classifications, the temporal trends of the indicator showed similar patterns for both satellite and in-situ assessments (see Figure 4.6.1).

Figure 4.6.1. Distributions of chlorophyll-a values for 6-year periods in the SE Bay of Biscay between in situ and bio-optical algorithms (OC5 (Gohin et al., 2002) and OCI (Hu et al., 2012)) applied to MODIS-AQUA data.

³ Hooker, S., McClain, C. (2000). The calibration and validation of SeaWiFS data. Prog. Oceanogr. 45, 427–465.

In GES4SEAS, we aim to try to reproduce this exercise in the coastal water bodies of the Romanian coast (Learning Site number 9) (Figure 4.6.2).

Figure 4.6.2. Map of sampling stations for evaluating the status of ecosystem components – Romanian Black Sea, 2010–2022

4.6.2 Methods

This case study will include the following steps:

1. Inventory of available satellite chlorophyll-a products for the area of study and evaluation of their spatial, temporal, and product characteristics (i.e. algorithm type, accuracy).
2. Selection of best-suited satellite products and exploratory validation with available in-situ chlorophyll-a data.
3. Indicator calculation with selected satellite products and co-located in-situ data, applying the MSFD Descriptor 5.2.1 methodology for the Black Sea, which utilizes the 75th percentile (P75) of chlorophyll-a.

4. Comparisons of assessment results obtained from satellite data versus in-situ data (PRIMER 7, GraphPad).

The satellite products inventory identified the following satellite chlorophyll-a products for the Black Sea:

- Black Sea, Bio-Geo-Chemical, L3, daily observation
(https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_BLK_BGC_HR_L3_NRT_009_2016/description)
- Black Sea, Bio-Geo-Chemical, L3, daily Satellite Observations (Near Real Time)
(https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_BLK_BGC_L3_NRT_009_151/description)
- **Black Sea, Bio-Geo-Chemical, L3, daily Satellite Observations (1997-ongoing)**
(https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_BLK_BGC_L3_MY_009_153/description)

Considering the spatial, temporal and spectral characteristics out of these three products, the **Black Sea, Bio-Geo-Chemical, L3, daily Satellite Observations** product was selected as the best suited to be used in this study. The variable “phytoplankton chlorophyll concentration (CHL)” included in this product uses region-specific algorithms (Zibordi et al., 2015; Kajiyama et al., 2018) from multiple satellite observations: SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B.

The NetCDF files, with a spatial resolution of 1 X 1 km, were downloaded considering the temporal coverage of in situ data. The extraction of punctual values was done “semi-automatically” using spatial analysis tools from ArcGIS 10.x software. The match-up constructions of satellite datasets were obtained by calculating the values of the cell from the adjacent cells with valid values using bilinear interpolation, centred on the in-situ data location.

The satellite CHL products were validated against available in-situ chlorophyll-a data using statistical estimates of the correlation: Root Mean Square Error – RMSE and R^2 (the coefficient of determination) for the entire dataset and split based on spatial coverage of Marine Assessment Units (MRU) considered for Maritime Strategy Framework Directive.

Assessment Framework:

The study covers the period 2010–2022, focusing on the warm season (April–October), when phytoplankton productivity is typically highest. The eutrophication assessment in the Romanian marine waters is based on the 75th percentile (P75) of all chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentrations

measured during this period. The P75 values are compared to established national threshold values for different water types and zones, as follows:

- ❖ Transitional waters (Variable Salinity Zone): 11.88 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
- ❖ Coastal waters: 5.97 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
- ❖ Marine waters – Northern zone: 4.11 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
- ❖ Marine waters – Southern zone: 2.79 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$

These thresholds guide the assessment based on the Chl-*a* indicator under MSFD D5C2, aligning with both in-situ and satellite-derived monitoring approaches.

4.6.3 Results

4.6.3.1 Transitional waters (BLK_RO_AA_TT03)

A total of 57 data points were analyzed for the period 2012–2021, with 2015 and 2017 excluded due to the lack of in situ data during the warm season and the absence of corresponding satellite observations. The 75th percentile (P75) of annual chlorophyll-*a* concentrations derived from in situ measurements ranged from 2.9 to 16.7 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, while satellite-derived values ranged from 2.8 to 19.9 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Interannual comparisons show a variable level of agreement between the two data sources. In 2013, 2016, and 2018, the P75 values were comparable. In contrast, substantial discrepancies were observed in 2012, 2014, and 2019, where satellite estimates either underestimated or overestimated in-situ values (Figure 4.6.3).

Figure 4.6.3. Interannual variability in P75 Chl-*a*: In-situ vs. Satellite observations in transitional waters

Boxplot analysis indicates higher variability in the satellite data, as evidenced by a broader interquartile range and greater dispersion, likely influenced by atmospheric conditions and the optical complexity of transitional waters (Figure 4.6.4).

Figure 4.6.4. Distribution of annual P75 Chlorophyll-a concentrations in transitional waters: In Situ vs. Satellite

A regression analysis was performed to evaluate the relationship between log-transformed Chl-a concentrations obtained from in situ measurements and satellite observations. The resulting scatter plot (Figure 4.6.5) shows a positive linear trend between the two datasets. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.38$) indicates a moderate correlation, suggesting that approximately 38% of the variability in satellite-derived Chl-a concentrations can be explained by the in-situ measurements.

Figure 4.6.5. Relationship between log-transformed in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations in transitional waters

Despite the positive relationship, the spread of data points around the regression line reveals a substantial amount of scatter, especially at lower concentrations, indicating notable variability and potential influences from factors such as atmospheric conditions, spatial resolution differences, or the optical complexity of transitional waters. This variability underscores the need for ongoing calibration and validation of satellite-derived chlorophyll-a estimates, particularly when applied to nearshore and heterogeneous environments.

An unpaired t-test was conducted to evaluate whether there is a statistically significant difference between chlorophyll-a concentrations measured in situ and those estimated from satellite observations (Table 4.6.1). The results indicate no significant difference between the two datasets, with a two-tailed p-value of 0.4532 ($t = 0.7527$, $df = 112$). According to conventional thresholds ($p < 0.05$), this difference is not considered statistically significant.

The mean chlorophyll-a concentration was $6.95 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 5.79 SD) for in situ data and $7.88 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 7.24 SD) for satellite observations. The average difference between the two groups was $-0.92 \mu\text{g/L}$, meaning that satellite-derived values were, on average, slightly higher than in situ measurements. The 95% confidence interval for this difference ranged from $3.36 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ lower to $1.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ higher, indicating that the observed difference could plausibly occur by chance.

These results suggest that, on average, satellite estimates are not significantly different from in situ measurements for the dataset analyzed. However, the relatively wide confidence interval and the variability in the data suggest that differences may exist under specific conditions or during certain years.

Table 4.6.1. Comparison of in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations (Unpaired t-test)

Parameter	In Situ	Satellite
Mean ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	6.95	7.88
Standard Deviation (SD)	5.79	7.24
Standard Error of the Mean (SEM)	0.77	0.96
Sample Size (n)	57	57
Statistical Test	Value	
Test Type	Unpaired two-tailed t-test	
t Statistic	0.7527	
Degrees of Freedom (df)	112	
p-Value	0.4532	
Mean Difference (In situ – Satellite)	$-0.92 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
95% Confidence Interval	-3.36 to $1.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
Statistical Significance	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	

4.6.3.2 Coastal waters (BLK_RO_AA_CT)

A total of 56 data points was analyzed for the period 2010–2020, with 2011, 2015 and 2017 excluded due to the lack of in-situ data during the warm season and the absence of corresponding satellite observations. The P75 of annual chlorophyll-a concentrations derived from in-situ measurements ranged from 0.47 (2012) to 12.08 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2016), while satellite-derived values varied more widely, from 0.88 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2020) to a high of 28.67 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2013). These values show notable interannual variability, particularly for the satellite estimates. For example, the satellite P75 value in 2013 (28.67 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) is a clear outlier and significantly deviates from both the in-situ value for the same year (4.49 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and the rest of the dataset. Conversely, in-situ values were more consistent, with a tighter range and less pronounced deviations (Figure 4.6.6).

Figure 4.6.6. Interannual variability in P75 Chl-a in coastal waters: In-situ vs. Satellite observations

The boxplots show a clear contrast in variability. In-situ data exhibit a narrow interquartile range, suggesting stable values across years, with a single high value (in 2016). In contrast, satellite data display a wider range and a strong outlier (in 2013) (Figure 4.6.7). This may be due to overestimation in optically complex waters, atmospheric interference, or differences in spatial and temporal resolution.

Figure 4.6.7. Distribution of annual P75 Chlorophyll-a concentrations in coastal waters: In-situ vs. Satellite

The regression analysis of \log_{10} -transformed Chl-a concentrations in coastal waters revealed a weak to moderate positive correlation between in-situ measurements and satellite observations, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.26 (Figure 4.6.8). This indicates that approximately 26% of the variability in satellite-derived Chl-a values can be explained by the in-situ data. The considerable scatter around the trend line, particularly at lower concentrations, points to inconsistencies between the two datasets. These may result from atmospheric interference, optical complexity in coastal waters, or differences in spatial and temporal resolution. Overall, the findings underscore the need for continued validation of satellite data to ensure reliable use in coastal water quality assessments.

Figure 4.6.8. Relationship between log-transformed in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations in coastal waters

An unpaired t-test was performed to compare Chl-a concentrations between in-situ and satellite observations in coastal waters. The two-tailed p-value was 0.1617, indicating that the difference

between the two groups is not statistically significant according to conventional thresholds ($p < 0.05$). The mean Chl-*a* concentration was $2.82 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 3.84 SD) for in-situ data and $4.59 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 8.55 SD) for satellite data. The average difference (in-situ minus satellite) was $-1.76 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -4.25 to $0.72 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Table 4.6.2). Although satellite estimates were, on average, higher than in-situ values, the relatively large variability, especially in satellite data, and the lack of statistical significance suggest that the observed difference could occur by chance.

Table 4.6.2. Comparison of in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations (Unpaired t-test)

Parameter	In Situ	Satellite
Mean ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	2.82	4.59
Standard Deviation (SD)	3.84	8.55
Standard Error of the Mean (SEM)	0.51	1.14
Sample Size (n)	56	56
Statistical Test	Value	
Test Type	Unpaired two-tailed t-test	
t Statistic	1.4087	
Degrees of Freedom (df)	110	
p-Value	0.1617	
Mean Difference (In situ – Satellite)	$-1.76 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
95% Confidence Interval	-4.25 to $0.72 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
Statistical Significance	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	

4.6.3.3 Marine waters (BLK_RO_AA_MT01)

Northern area

A total of 36 data points was analyzed for the period 2010–2022, with 2011 and 2015 excluded due to the lack of in-situ data during the warm season and the absence of corresponding satellite observations. The P75 of annual Chl-*a* concentrations derived from in situ measurements in northern marine waters ranged from $0.27 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2021) to $13.73 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2012), while satellite-derived values showed greater variability, ranging from $0.36 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2021) to $20.90 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2010). These values indicate notable interannual variability, especially for the satellite estimates. For instance, the satellite P75 value in 2010 ($20.90 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) appears as a distinct outlier, considerably exceeding both the in-situ value for the same year ($10.94 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and the rest of the satellite dataset. In contrast, the in-situ data showed a narrower range and more consistent values over time (Figure 4.6.9).

Figure 4.6.9. Interannual variability in P75 Chl-a in northern marine waters: In-situ vs. Satellite observations

The boxplots highlight differences between the two data sources. In-situ data exhibit a narrow interquartile range, suggesting stable values across years, with a single high value (in 2012). In contrast, satellite data display a wider range and a strong outlier (in 2010) (Figure 4.6.10)

Figure 4.6.10. Distribution of annual P75 Chlorophyll-a concentrations in northern marine waters: In-situ vs. Satellite

The regression analysis of \log_{10} -transformed Chl-a concentrations in northern marine waters revealed a strong positive correlation between in-situ measurements and satellite observations, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.78 (Figure 4.6.11). This indicates that approximately 78% of the variability in satellite-derived Chl-a values can be explained by the in-situ data. The points are relatively well aligned along the regression line, with minimal scatter, suggesting good agreement between the two datasets across the observed concentration range. This strong relationship reflects the reliability of satellite observations in these low-productivity marine environments, though some variability may still arise from optical water properties, atmospheric conditions, or spatial mismatches.

Overall, the results support the applicability of satellite data for monitoring Chl-*a* in northern marine waters, provided that regular in-situ validation is maintained.

Figure 4.6.11. Relationship between log-transformed in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations in northern marine waters

An unpaired t-test was performed to compare Chl-*a* concentrations between in-situ and satellite observations in northern marine waters. The two-tailed p-value was 0.5262, indicating that the difference between the two groups is not statistically significant according to conventional thresholds ($p < 0.05$). The mean Chl-*a* concentration was $3.36 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 5.07 SD) for in-situ data and $2.64 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 4.41 SD) for satellite data. The average difference (in-situ minus satellite) was $0.71 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -1.52 to $2.95 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Table 4.6.3). Although in-situ values were, on average, slightly higher than satellite estimates, the wide variability and the lack of statistical significance suggest that the observed difference may have occurred by chance.

Table 4.6.3. Comparison of in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations (Unpaired t-test)

Parameter	In Situ	Satellite
Mean ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	3.36	2.64
Standard Deviation (SD)	5.07	4.41
Standard Error of the Mean (SEM)	0.85	0.73
Sample Size (n)	36	36
Statistical Test	Value	
Test Type	Unpaired two-tailed t-test	
t Statistic	0.6370	
Degrees of Freedom (df)	70	
p-Value	0.5262	
Mean Difference (In situ – Satellite)	$0.71 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
95% Confidence Interval	-1.52 to $2.95 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
Statistical Significance	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	

Southern area

A total of 83 data points was analyzed for the period 2010–2022, with 2011 and 2015 excluded due to the lack of in-situ data during the warm season and the absence of corresponding satellite observations. The P75 of annual Chl-*a* concentrations derived from in-situ measurements in southern marine waters ranged from 0.25 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2022) to 3.98 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2014), while satellite-derived values ranged from 0.27 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2022) to 5.79 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (2014) (Figure 4.6.12). These values indicate moderate interannual variability for both datasets, with the highest agreement observed in recent years and larger discrepancies between 2013 and 2014. For instance, in 2014 the satellite value (5.79 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) exceeded the in-situ estimate (3.98 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), while in 2013 the difference was also notable (4.96 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ vs. 2.02 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively).

Figure 4.6.12. Interannual variability in P75 Chl-*a* in southern marine waters: In-situ vs. Satellite observations

The boxplots reflect these patterns, showing a slightly wider interquartile range (IQR) for in-situ data, while satellite observations display a narrower IQR but with more extreme outliers (Figure 4.6.13). Both datasets show overall consistency in median values across the years, though the satellite data tend to slightly overestimate Chl-*a* concentrations compared to in-situ measurements. These results emphasize the importance of using both observation types for robust assessments of phytoplankton dynamics in southern marine waters.

Figure 4.6.13. Distribution of annual P75 Chlorophyll-a concentrations in southern marine waters: In-situ vs. Satellite

The regression analysis of \log_{10} -transformed Chl-*a* concentrations in southern marine waters revealed a strong positive correlation between in-situ measurements and satellite observations, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.65 (Figure 4.6.14). This indicates that approximately 65% of the variability in satellite-derived Chl-*a* values can be explained by the in-situ data. The points are generally well aligned along the regression line, although with slightly more scatter at mid-range concentrations, suggesting a good level of agreement between the two datasets across most of the observed values. This strong relationship supports the use of satellite observations in these oligotrophic southern waters, although some discrepancies may still result from differences in spatial resolution, atmospheric influence, or local bio-optical properties. Overall, the results confirm the suitability of satellite-derived Chl-*a* estimates for long-term monitoring in southern marine environments, particularly when supported by periodic in-situ validation.

Figure 4.6.14. Relationship between log-transformed in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations in southern marine waters

An unpaired t-test was performed to compare Chl-*a* concentrations between in-situ and satellite observations in southern marine waters. The two-tailed p-value was 0.3787, indicating that the difference between the two groups is not statistically significant according to conventional thresholds ($p < 0.05$). The mean Chl-*a* concentration was $1.15 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 2.04 SD) for in-situ data and $1.56 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (± 3.73 SD) for satellite data. The average difference (in-situ minus satellite) was $-0.41 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -1.33 to $0.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Table 4.6.4). Although satellite estimates were, on average, slightly higher than in-situ values, the substantial variability, particularly in the satellite dataset, and the lack of statistical significance suggest that the observed difference may have occurred by chance.

*Table 4.6.4. Comparison of in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations (Unpaired t-test)*

Parameter	In Situ	Satellite
Mean ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	1.15	1.56
Standard Deviation (SD)	2.04	3.73
Standard Error of the Mean (SEM)	0.22	0.41
Sample Size (n)	83	83
Statistical Test		Value
Test Type	Unpaired two-tailed t-test	
t Statistic	0.8828	
Degrees of Freedom (df)	164	
p-Value	0.3787	
Mean Difference (In situ – Satellite)	$-0.41 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
95% Confidence Interval	-1.33 to $0.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
Statistical Significance	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	

4.6.3.4 Assessment

The comparison of P75 chlorophyll-*a* concentration against established ecological thresholds reveals that all four water body types, transitional, coastal, northern marine, and southern marine, exhibited values below their respective limits, based on both in-situ and satellite observations (Table 4.6.5). In transitional waters, the P75 in-situ value ($11.39 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was slightly below the threshold of $11.88 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, indicating proximity to potential exceedance. In coastal waters, P75 values were substantially lower than the $5.97 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ threshold, reflecting good ecological status. Similarly, in northern marine waters, both observation types yielded values ($3.58 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in-situ; $2.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ satellite) well under the $4.11 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ limit. The lowest concentrations were recorded in southern marine waters, where both in-situ and satellite P75 values were equal at $0.81 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, far below the $2.79 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ threshold. These findings suggest a relatively low risk of eutrophication across all water bodies during the study period, though transitional zones remain areas of concern due to their elevated and variable nutrient levels.

Table 4.6.5. Ecological Status Based on P75 Chlorophyll-a: In Situ vs. Satellite Data

Water Body	P75 In-situ ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	P75 Satellite obs. ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Threshold ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
Transitional	11.39	10.75	11.88
Coastal	3.78	2.68	5.97
Marine_North	3.58	2.51	4.11
Marine_South	0.81	0.81	2.79

4.6.4 Discussion

This study assessed the ecological status of different water body types in the western Black Sea region using the 75th percentile (P75) of Chl-*a* concentrations derived from both in-situ and satellite observations over the period 2010–2022. The comparison of P75 values against water body-specific thresholds provides insights into spatial patterns of eutrophication and the reliability of remote sensing for water quality monitoring.

Generally, there is a good correlation between satellite observations and in-situ data for Romanian marine waters (shelf) and a moderate correlation for coastal and transitional waters. The coefficient of determination for satellite data varied from 0.26 to 0.64, indicating that more than half of the variance of the satellite data records appear to agree with the in-situ data (Table 4.6.6).

Table 4.6.6. Satellite data vs in-situ data statistics

MRU	R ²	log 10 RMSE (mg m^{-3})
Marine waters (all data)	0.63	0.39
Coastal water (BLK_RO_AA_CT)	0.26	0.51
Transitional water (BLK_RO_AA_TT03)	0.38	0.38
Marine water (BLK_RO_AA_MT01 – north shelf)	0.61	0.36
Marine water (BLK_RO_AA_MT01 – south shelf)	0.64	0.29

In **transitional** waters, P75 Chl-*a* concentrations were the highest among all water types, reflecting the dynamic and nutrient-rich nature of estuarine and lagoon environments. The in-situ P75 ($11.39 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was slightly below the regulatory threshold of $11.88 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, while the satellite-derived value ($10.75 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was also within limits. Although these values indicate a current compliance with ecological targets, the proximity to the threshold suggests a heightened risk of eutrophication under increased nutrient loading or changing climatic conditions. The wide interquartile range and higher variability observed in the satellite data may reflect the optical complexity of transitional waters, where high turbidity, CDOM, and suspended sediments can influence remote sensing accuracy.

For **coastal** waters, both in-situ ($3.78 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and satellite ($2.68 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) P75 values were well below the threshold of $5.97 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, suggesting stable and favorable ecological conditions. Despite the occasional presence of elevated satellite-derived values in some years (e.g., 2013 and 2014), the overall consistency between data sources was supported by the moderate correlation ($R^2 = 0.26$). The lack of significant difference between methods ($p = 0.1617$) further confirms the utility of satellite observations in these areas, although local calibration remains important for improving precision.

In **northern marine** waters, characterized by generally oligotrophic conditions, the P75 values remained well below the $4.11 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ threshold, with in-situ and satellite values at $3.58 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $2.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. The high correlation ($R^2 = 0.78$) between the two datasets, coupled with a non-significant difference in means ($p = 0.5262$), underscores the robustness of satellite data for long-term assessments in this region. However, isolated anomalies such as the outlier satellite values in 2010 and 2012 highlight the need for validation, particularly during events influenced by water column stratification or episodic inputs.

Southern marine waters showed the lowest Chl-*a* concentrations across all zones, with both P75 in-situ and satellite values equal to $0.81 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, substantially below the $2.79 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ threshold. The regression analysis yielded a strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.65$), confirming the reliability of satellite data in this oligotrophic environment. The absence of statistically significant differences ($p = 0.3787$) between observation types further supports the integration of satellite data into routine monitoring protocols for southern shelf areas.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that all water bodies currently meet the ecological targets for Chl-*a*, though transitional areas warrant closer attention due to higher variability and threshold proximity. Satellite-derived Chl-*a* data proved to be a valuable and generally consistent proxy for in-situ measurements, especially in marine waters, though some discrepancies remain in optically complex and nearshore areas. Continued in-situ validation and refinement of regional algorithms are essential to support the reliable use of remote sensing in operational water quality assessments under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD).

4.6.5 Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of Chl-*a* concentrations across transitional, coastal, northern marine, and southern marine waters in the western Black Sea region, using both in-situ measurements and satellite-derived observations over the period 2010–2022. The 75th percentile (P75) of Chl-*a* was used as a key indicator for evaluating eutrophication status in relation to water body-specific ecological thresholds.

The main conclusions are as follows:

- Satellite data demonstrated strong to moderate agreement with in-situ observations, particularly in marine waters, confirming their applicability for long-term and large-scale monitoring.
- No statistically significant differences were observed between in-situ and satellite P75 values in any water type, supporting the complementary use of both data sources for ecological assessments.
- The reliability of satellite estimates was greatest in open marine waters, whereas transitional and coastal areas remain more affected by optical complexity and atmospheric interference.
- All water body types were within the regulatory P75 thresholds for Chl-*a*, suggesting that the current trophic status remains acceptable across the region.
- Transitional waters exhibited the highest Chl-*a* variability and values closest to the threshold, highlighting them as potential risk zones requiring more frequent monitoring.

These results emphasize the value of integrating in-situ and satellite approaches in marine monitoring frameworks and support their continued use in reporting under the MSFD. Future efforts should focus on algorithm refinement and local calibration, especially in optically complex zones, to improve the accuracy of remote sensing products for water quality assessment.

4.6.6 References

- Gohin F., Druon J.N., and L. Lampert (2002). A five channel chlorophyll algorithm applied to SeaWiFS data processed by SeaDAS in coastal waters. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 23, 8, 1639-1661 pp.
- Hu, C., Z. Lee, and B.A. Franz (2012). Chlorophyll-a algorithms for oligotrophic oceans: A novel approach based on three-band reflectance difference, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117, C01011, <https://www.doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007395>
- Kajiyama T., D. D'Alimonte, and G. Zibordi, "Algorithms merging for the determination of Chlorophyll-a concentration in the Black Sea," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2018.2883539>
- Zibordi, G., F. Mélin, J.-F. Berthon, and M. Talone (2015). In situ autonomous optical radiometry measurements for satellite ocean color validation in the Western Black Sea. *Ocean Sci.*, 11, 275–286.

5. Lagrangian models to simulate and predict transport pathways

5.1 Introduction

Understanding the movement of marine organisms and particles is essential for predicting ecological patterns, managing biodiversity, and assessing the impacts of environmental change. Lagrangian models, which simulate the movement of passive or active particles within oceanic flows, are increasingly used to reconstruct transport pathways, estimate source regions, and forecast dispersal under varying physical conditions. This chapter presents three case studies illustrating diverse applications of Lagrangian particle tracking: the reconstruction of jellyfish swarm origins off the Iberian coast, the role of substrate availability and anthropogenic structures in shaping jellyfish distribution in the North Sea, and the modelling of cold-water coral larval dispersal in the Gulf of Cádiz to inform conservation planning. Each study demonstrates how integrating hydrodynamic models with biological data can reveal critical insights into species connectivity and inform management under future ocean change scenarios.

5.2 Case study 6: Lagrangian model to estimate the origin of jellyfish blooms along the Spanish coast

Luis Ferrer, Yolanda Sagarminaga, Ángel Borja

5.2.1 Introduction

On 11th February 2014, dozens of Portuguese man-of-war (*Physalia physalis*) specimens (hereafter referred to as the 2014 PMW swarm) were washed ashore along the entire stretch of Patos Beach. This beach is located on the coast of Galicia (northwestern Spain). The Portuguese man-of-war is a wind-propelled jellyfish-like animal that lives in warm tropical and subtropical waters. Therefore, the 2014 PMW swarm probably originated in the open North Atlantic Ocean. Its drift was controlled by the succession of destructive storms that hit the coasts of Western Europe in the winter of 2013–14. The Portuguese man-of-war occurs in two forms (i.e., dimorphism), which are mirror images of one another but otherwise identical. Under the influence of the wind, one form (left-handed) moves to the right of the downwind direction and the other (right-handed) to the left. Here we estimated the possible trajectories (routes) and region of origin of the 2014 PMW swarm. To do this, we performed numerical simulations using a Lagrangian particle tracking model.

5.2.2 Methods

To estimate the possible routes and region of origin of the 2014 PMW swarm, we used the trajectories of surface drifting buoys analyzed by Ferrer et al. (2024) and the Sediment, Oil spill and Fish Tracking model (SOFT). This model is an easy-to-use and computationally efficient Lagrangian particle tracking tool. Although it was initially developed to simulate the dispersal of marine eggs and larvae in the Bay of Biscay (Ferrer et al., 2004), it can now be used to simulate other types of dispersal as well. Since 2017, SOFT includes the following equation to estimate the drift of a Portuguese man-of-war:

$$\mathbf{U}_D = C_D \mathbf{U}_{W,\vartheta} = C_D U_{W,\vartheta} + C_D V_{W,\vartheta}$$

where $\mathbf{U}_D = (U_D, V_D)$ is the drift velocity vector, C_D is a wind drag coefficient, and $\mathbf{U}_{W,\vartheta} = (U_{W,\vartheta}, V_{W,\vartheta})$ is the wind velocity vector at 10 m height rotated a drift angle ϑ about the wind direction. The direction of rotation is clockwise if ϑ is negative (for left-handed individuals) and anticlockwise if ϑ is positive (for right-handed individuals). In the model, the method used for the movement of particles (i.e. sediments, oil spills, eggs and larvae, jellyfish, Portuguese man-of-war specimens, etc.) is based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme. We ran SOFT backwards in time to estimate the most likely routes (or trajectories) and region of origin of the 2014 PMW swarm in the North Atlantic Ocean. The initial location of this swarm in the simulations was 42.2° N, 8.9° W (about 10 km off the coast of Galicia).

The simulated swarm was moved backwards in time using SOFT for 163 days (i.e. from 11 February 2014 to 1 September 2013, both dates at 12:00 UTC), assuming that reproduction occurred between summer and autumn. Here we used the best-fit C_D values obtained by Ferrer et al. (2024) and hourly wind fields from the ERA5 global reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2023). This database, with a spatial resolution of 31 km, was produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

5.2.3 Results

We used three different values for C_D (0.02, 0.04 and 0.06) in the simulations to estimate the drift of the 2014 PMW swarm. The use of these values allowed us to identify differences in the drift of the swarm. In the simulations, we also used 21 values for ϑ (from -50° to $+50^\circ$ with an increment of $+5^\circ$). The trajectories of the 2014 PMW swarm obtained after running SOFT backwards in time for 163 days using a C_D of 0.04 are displayed in [Figure 5.2.1](#). The trajectories obtained using negative (positive) drift angles correspond to left-handed (right-handed) individuals. The end points of these trajectories on 1 September 2013 are the estimated locations of our swarm at the initial stage of development (i.e. at the age of 0 days). We used the end points located in the open North Atlantic Ocean to approximately delimit the region of origin of the 2014 swarm. The end points located on the coast were discarded as possible points of origin.

On the one hand, the simulations carried out with a C_D value equal to 0.04 show that the region of origin of the 2014 PMW swarm was located in the open North Atlantic Ocean. According to the model, with negative drift angles this region would be located above 49.76° N, while with positive drift angles it would be located below this latitude. Since we assume that the Portuguese man-of-war is an organism that lives in warm tropical and subtropical waters, our model results suggest that most of the individuals of the 2014 PMW swarm were probably right-handed (i.e. with positive drift angles). Therefore, the region of origin was probably located below 49.76° N. The possible routes of the swarm covered a large geographical area. On the other hand, the simulations carried out with C_D values equal to 0.02 and 0.06 (not shown) also show that the region of origin was located in the open North Atlantic Ocean. With a C_D value equal to 0.02, the model estimated that this region would be located closer to the coast of Galicia. The trajectories obtained with SOFT using different drift angles become longer and more complex as the value of the wind drag coefficient increases. Therefore, the selection of an appropriate wind drag coefficient is crucial for a successful estimation of the region of origin.

Figure 5.2.1. Simulated trajectories of the 2014 PMW swarm (from 11 February 2014 to 1 September 2013, both dates at 12:00 UTC) obtained with SOFT using a wind drag coefficient of 0.04 and negative and positive drift angles (top and bottom, respectively). The black triangle and circles indicate the initial and final locations of the swarm in the SOFT simulations, respectively.

5.2.4 Discussion

The first conclusion of this study is that the region of origin of the 2014 PWM swarm was located in the open North Atlantic Ocean. If most of the individuals of the 2014 PMW swarm were probably right-handed, the region of origin predicted by the model was located in the northern part of the North

Atlantic Subtropical Gyre. This conclusion agrees with the results obtained previously. A wind drag coefficient of around 0.04 may be appropriate for studies assessing the drift of small surface organisms, such as *P. physalis* and *V. veleva*. However, it seems reasonable to expect both the wind drag coefficient and the drift angle to vary with wind speed and over the lifespan of *P. physalis* and *V. veleva*, because there will be a significant increase in the size of these organisms. The drift of the Portuguese man-of-war (dimorphic organism with a gas-filled sail-like float) is mainly controlled by the wind. Therefore, the sailing directions and trajectories of right- and left-handed individuals will depend on the drift angles relative to the wind direction that they can reach. The winter of 2013–14 in Western Europe was characterised by many intense cyclones. In February 2014, windstorms Nadja, Okka, Petra, Qumaira, Ruth, Stephanie, Tini and Ulla brought heavy rainfall and strong winds. If the presence of the Portuguese man-of-war had occurred in summer (as happened in 2010 or 2023), it would have caused a significant social and economic impact.

5.2.5 Conclusions

Here, we analysed the presence of a Portuguese man-of-war swarm on the coast of Galicia (northwestern Spain) in February 2014. Our findings suggest the following conclusions: (1) the swarm originated in the open North Atlantic Ocean; (2) the drift of the swarm was controlled by the succession of storms that hit the coasts of Western Europe in the winter of 2013–14; and (3) most of the individuals of the swarm were probably right-handed.

5.2.6 References

- Ferrer, L., Sagarminaga, Y., Borja, A., Nogues, M., Alegre, M.J., Santos, M., Boyra, G., Álvarez, P., Beldarrain, B., Castro, R., Bidegain, G., González, M., Revilla, M., Zorita, I., Solaun, O., Fontán, A., Rodríguez, J.G. (2024). The Portuguese man-of-war: Adrift in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 301, 108732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2024.108732>
- Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.-N. (2023). ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47> (accessed on 28-Feb-2024)

5.3 Case study 7: Substrate availability as a limiting factor in the distribution of adult jellyfish (Scyphozoa) in the North Sea

Tiago Silva

5.3.1 Introduction

The global incidence of jellyfish blooms has varied historically, although it is not clear if these are trends or responses to multidecadal climatic cycles (Condon, 2013). Jellyfish blooms can significantly modify ecosystem function and can also have negative economic effect by stinging swimmers, clogging fishing nets and power station cooling systems, and killing aquaculture fish (Sagarminaga et al., 2024).

The lifecycle of Scyphozoa jellyfish involves a sessile stage when polyps release their larval stage (ephyrae) by the process of strobilation. The North Sea is dominated by sandy substrates, which are unsuitable for polyps. Coastal areas, coarse substrates and artificial structures are required to produce ephyrae. The North Sea is seeing a large increase in the presence of offshore structures, particularly from the expansion of offshore wind farms. It is known that several species of jellyfish, including *Aurelia aurita*, prefer using artificial structures for polyp fixation (Duarte et al., 2013; Feng et al., 2017). This modelling study aims to assess if the projected increase in offshore structures is likely to change the distribution and abundance of two species of jellyfish in the North Sea.

5.3.2 Methods

Experimental design

1- Definition of suitable habitat

The summer distribution of adult Scyphozoan in the North Seas is known from ship-based surveys. The species selected for this study, *Aurelia aurita*, is relatively common and well observed by the survey. The ephyrae (larval stage) are released into the water from February to April, with a peak in March. The general origin of the respective ephyrae is estimated by propagating backwards using a particle tracking model using advection by currents. A combination of habitat features is used to predict what are the present habitat for the polyps. Figure 5.3.1. shows the observed density of *Aurelia aurita* in the August IBTS surveys for the period 2012-2023.

Figure 5.3.1. Average density of *Aurelia aurita* in the North Sea during August surveys for the period 2012-2023.

2- Strobilation habitat: historical, 2002-2023 and in 2040-2050

Three scenarios are considered, representing release of ephyrae and transport by currents: i) habitat is made up of coarse and mixed Folk sediment classes (hereafter *sediment-only* scenario), ii) 2002-2023 has only the additional anthropogenic structure in this period, which are made up of Oil & Gas fixed and floating and offshore wind farm, in place by 2023, and iii) 2040-2050 is made up of additional offshore windfarms projected to be present in this period. The jellyfish are represented as horizontally passive drifters that from a certain stage of development, choose to remain above the pycnocline by swimming vertically.

Data sources

Currents and turbulence – NEMO hydrodynamical model in AMM7 domain (O’Dea et al., 2017) at 7 km resolution that is run at Cefas.

Seabed substrate – Predicted Folk categories (Mitchell et al., 2019).

Offshore structures in periods 2010-2020 and projections for 2040-2050 based on national commitments (Waldman et al., 2024).

Particle tracking model

Ocean Parcels (Delandmeter et al., 2019) using custom kernels for 3D advection-diffusion and individual based-model for jellyfish.

5.3.3 Results

The ephyrae dispersal and potential spatial extent resulting from the backward propagation from adult observation locations in August are shown in Figure 5.3.2. This shows that between the strobilation period (March) and the survey in August, individuals can drift from Western Scotland or Central English Channel to reach the Western and Central North Sea. This information was used to limit the release sites at the main habitat experiments (see blue polygon in Figure 5.3.3).

Figure 5.3.2. Reconstruction of ephyrae dispersal and potential spatial extent using backward propagation of particle tracking models starting from of adult observation locations.

Figure 5.3.3. Suitable habitat for jellyfish polyps includes natural coarse and mixed sediments and anthropogenic structures. The light blue polygon was used to restrict release locations that could reach the North Sea according to initial modelling experiments.

In the three main habitat experiments, the density of drifting jellies was mapped for each of the periods of April to August. Figure 5.3.4 shows the density of drifting jellies being released from coarse and mixed habitats; in August the main accumulations are on the Western and Central North Sea (around 54 N), which roughly matches the observations for the same period. The concentrations resulting from anthropogenic structures up to 2023 result in a much smaller relative density (scale is 6x smaller than the previous sediments-only experiment). The addition of projected Offshore Wind farms up to 2050, results in an increase in density in the Northern North Sea (scale is 3x smaller than the sediments-only experiment) and to a lesser degree in the Southern North Sea.

Figure 5.3.4. Relative density of drifting particles over time, when released from natural substrates (sediment-only scenario).

Figure 5.3.5. Relative density of drifting particles over time, when released from additional artificial substrates present in 2023 (Offshore Windfarms and Oil and Gas).

Figure 5.3.6. Relative density of drifting particles over time, when released from additional artificial substrates present in 2050 (floating and fixed Offshore Windfarms).

5.3.4 Discussion

Ocean sprawl, the expansion of anthropogenic structures in the ocean including shipping, aquaculture and energy, has been hypothesised to contribute to observed increases in jellyfish blooms (Duarte et al., 2013). It is known that several types of hard natural substrates, including discarded shells, are used scyphozoan polyps, and that these are abundant on smooth artificial surfaces.

To conduct a complete comparison between natural substrates and artificial structures it would be necessary to know polyp densities in each type of substrate and account for its variation and complexity (e.g. type of offshore wind farm foundation). Lacking this, the assessment can only reflect changes to spatial distribution and its monthly variability.

Our results show that the natural substrates can explain most of the observed spatial distribution of *Aurelia auritus*, although the observations in the Northern North Sea somewhat align with the releases from Oil & Gas platforms present in the region up to 2023 (Fig. 5.3.5). A projected large expansion in

the number and size of Offshore Wind farms in the period 2040-2050, would considerably change the spatial distribution, and possibly the numbers, of adult *Aurelia aurita*. In spring, this could cause a large increase in *Aurelia aurita* offshore from Eastern Scotland, and to a lesser degree to the Southern North Sea. In summer, the Northeast pole would drift to the central North Sea, an area with relatively low adult densities in the present surveys.

These preliminary results now require a quantitative assessment to account for the interannual variation in both currents and jellyfish populations. But only by attempting to quantify the contribution of each type of substrate can the several scenarios be compared quantitatively.

5.3.5 References

- Condon, R.H., Duarte, C.M., Pitt, K.A., Robinson, K.L., Lucas, C.H., Sutherland, K.R., Mianzan, H.W., Bogeberg, M., Purcell, J.E., Decker, M.B., Uye, S., Madin, L.P., Brodeur, R.D., Haddock, S.H.D., Malej, A., Parry, G.D., Eriksen, E., Quiñones, J., Acha, M., Harvey, M., Arthur, J.M., Graham, W.M., 2013. Recurrent jellyfish blooms are a consequence of global oscillations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110, 1000–1005. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1210920110>
- Delandmeter, P., van Sebille, E., 2019. The Parcels v2.0 Lagrangian framework: new field interpolation schemes. *Geoscientific Model Development* 12, 3571–3584. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-3571-2019>
- Duarte, C.M., Pitt, K.A., Lucas, C.H., Purcell, J.E., Uye, S., Robinson, K., Brotz, L., Decker, M.B., Sutherland, K.R., Malej, A., Madin, L., Mianzan, H., Gili, J.-M., Fuentes, V., Atienza, D., Pagés, F., Breitbart, D., Malek, J., Graham, W.M., Condon, R.H., 2013. Is global ocean sprawl a cause of jellyfish blooms? *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 11, 91–97. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110246>
- Feng, S., Lin, J., Sun, S., and Zhang, F. (2017). Artificial substrates preference for proliferation and immigration in *Aurelia aurita* (s. l.) polyps. *Chinese J. Oceanology and Limnology* 35, 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00343-016-5230-y>
- Mitchell, P.J., Aldridge, J., Diesing, M., 2019. Legacy Data: How Decades of Seabed Sampling can Produce Robust Predictions and Versatile Products. *Geosciences* 9, 182. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences9040182>
- O’Dea, E., Furner, R., Wakelin, S., Siddorn, J., While, J., Sykes, P., King, R., Holt, J., Hewitt, H., 2017. The CO5 configuration of the 7km Atlantic Margin Model: Large-scale biases and sensitivity to forcing, physics options and vertical resolution. *Geoscientific Model Development* 10, 2947–2969. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-2947-2017>
- Sagarminaga, Y., Piraino, S., Lynam, C.P., Leoni, V., Nikolaou, A., Jaspers, C., Bosch-Belmar, M., Fumarola, L.M., Borja, Á., Spada, E., Amorim, E., Borrello, P., de Angelis, R., Leone, A., Montero, N., Ferrer, L., Holland, M.M., Doyle, T.K., Tsirtsis, G., Katsanevakis, S., 2024. Management of jellyfish outbreaks to achieve good environmental status. *Front. Ocean Sustain.* 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/focsu.2024.1449190>

5.4 Case study 8 - Estimating Larval Dispersal of the Cold-Water Coral *Lophelia pertusa* in the Gulf of Cádiz: Enhancing Distribution Understanding and Conservation Strategies

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5.4.1 Introduction

Cold-water corals, such as *Lophelia pertusa* (= *Desmophyllum pertusum*, Linnaeus, 1758), are reef-forming species classified as a vulnerable marine ecosystem. They support rich biodiversity and provide essential services such as habitat, nursery grounds, and carbon sequestration. Despite their ecological and economic significance, these reefs face increasing threats from human activities (e.g., bottom trawling, pollution) and climate change, which can disrupt their survival and population connectivity. The Gulf of Cádiz, located between the Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean Sea, is a transition zone potentially linking coral populations from both regions, yet the distribution and connectivity of *L. pertusa* here remain poorly understood.

Larval dispersal is the primary means by which these sessile corals maintain population connectivity and colonize new habitats. Ocean temperature, especially under global warming scenarios, significantly affects pelagic larval duration (PLD), influencing dispersal distances and potentially settlement success. This study characterizes the main larval dispersal pathways of *L. pertusa* in the Gulf of Cádiz using a biophysical modeling approach that integrates life-history traits and larval behavior. We aim to (1) characterize these pathways, (2) identify potential new habitat areas based on areas reached by virtual larvae, and (3) highlight potential priority areas for conservation.

5.4.2 Methods

The study area encompasses the Gulf of Cádiz, a semi-enclosed basin situated between the southern Iberian Peninsula and Morocco. This region serves as a transition zone connecting the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea. It is characterized by complex hydrodynamics, including the interaction of Atlantic water masses and Mediterranean outflow waters, as well as the presence of upwelling zones and mesoscale eddies. The current distribution of *L. pertusa* in the model was established through a comprehensive literature review and compilation of data from online databases. This information was used to determine larval release locations in simulations.

A biophysical model for simulating larval dispersal was developed using the OceanParcels particle tracking tool. Oceanographic data were compiled from the Copernicus Marine Global Ocean Physical

Analysis and Forecasting Product, which provided three-dimensional daily temperature and current velocity fields. Two primary larval dispersal scenarios were tested: a passive scenario, where larvae moved solely by ocean currents, and an active scenario, where larvae exhibited ontogenetic vertical migration based on laboratory observations (Larsson et al., 2014; Strömberg & Larsson, 2017). The active scenarios further incorporated temperature-dependent PLD (O'Connor et al., 2007), variable larval swim speeds, and a temperature-avoidance behavior, thereby reflecting the sensitivity of larval development to environmental conditions. Based on comparisons with other ocean regions, the most likely spawning period was determined to extend from September to November. During this time, 1,000 particles were released daily from each colony over 91 days, resulting in over 1.7 million simulated trajectories per scenario.

For data analysis, settlement was defined as the first contact of a particle with the seafloor at depths shallower than 2000 meters and within 100 days post-release. The distribution of settled larvae was then mapped to identify potential new habitats and hotspots for settlement. Connectivity was quantified as the proportion of larvae settling within a 5 km radius of another colony or within the boundaries of existing or proposed Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

5.4.3 Results

Nineteen living *L. pertusa* colonies were identified in the Gulf of Cádiz region, distributed across three main areas: the North-East Atlantic (NEA), the Gulf of Cádiz (GOC), and the Moroccan Margin (MM) (Figure 5.4.1). Passive dispersal simulations indicated that most larvae remained near their source colonies, particularly within the GOC and MM. However, there was a potential for larvae to reach the Mediterranean and Canary Islands, depending on interannual oceanographic variability. Active dispersal scenarios, which incorporated vertical migration and temperature-dependent PLD, resulted in greater and earlier larval entry into the Mediterranean, especially under conditions of longer PLD (Figure 5.4.2). Despite this, the highest larval densities and settlement success consistently occurred near the release sites, suggesting strong local retention mechanisms likely driven by complex current interactions and mesoscale eddies.

Figure 5.4.1. Distribution of living *Lophelia pertusa* in the Gulf of Cádiz. Release locations are the North-East Atlantic (NEA, blue), Gulf of Cádiz (GOC, orange), Moroccan Margin (MM, purple)). From Schoenherr (2024) and Schoenherr et al. in prep.

Settlement success varied by region and scenario. NEA colonies exhibited very low settlement rates (<1%), often limited by the scarcity of suitable shallower habitat (i.e., above 2000 meters depth). Conversely, GOC and MM sites demonstrated higher settlement, with some locations (e.g., Cádiz-Diapiric Ridge, Pompeia Coral Mound) achieving 40–95% settlement success under certain scenarios. Connectivity between colonies was generally low, with most sites functioning as either sources or sinks rather than being well-connected. Notably, areas of Learning Site 5, located in the central Gulf of Cádiz and overlapping with the proposed Vulcões de Lama MPA, emerged as a key hotspot for larval settlement from multiple regions. Furthermore, the Cabo de São Vicente MPA may facilitate range expansion along the Iberian margin.

Figure 5.4.2. – Simulated active larval particle density of *Lophelia pertusa* for 30, 60, and 90 days after initial release (columns), across four distinct vertical migration scenarios. Particle density, representing the number of particles within a 10x10 km Mercator grid cell, is presented on a log10 scale. From Schoenherr (2024) and Schoenherr et al. in prep.

5.4.4 Discussion

The modeling results highlight the dominance of local retention and limited long-distance connectivity for *L. pertusa* in the Gulf of Cádiz, a pattern shaped by the intricate interplay of ocean currents, larval behavior, and temperature. While active larval migration does increase the chance of reaching new habitats, most larvae still settle near their release sites. This finding reinforces the critical importance of local conservation measures to protect existing coral populations. The low connectivity observed specifically between NEA colonies and other regions suggests that these isolated populations may be

particularly vulnerable to disturbance and could heavily rely on rare, long-distance dispersal events or the presence of yet-undiscovered colonies for their long-term persistence.

Climate change, by potentially shortening PLD and thus reducing dispersal distances, poses a significant threat, as it could further fragment coral populations and severely disrupt existing connectivity pathways. The identification of the Vulcões de Lama MPA and the central Gulf of Cádiz as crucial larval settlement hotspots underscores the urgent need for a strategically designed network of closely spaced MPAs. Such a network would be essential to maintain and enhance population connectivity, especially under future ocean warming scenarios. This study also suggests that our current knowledge of *L. pertusa* distribution is potentially incomplete, and consequently, the true extent of connectivity may be underestimated.

Therefore, future research efforts should prioritize several key areas to enhance conservation planning. This includes refining species occurrence data through targeted surveys to identify unknown colonies and provide a more comprehensive baseline for connectivity assessments. Future modeling attempts should incorporate more specific, empirically derived behavioral and physiological parameters, such as mortality rates and local spawning seasonality. Furthermore, incorporating the ecological suitability of potential settlement habitats is an important contribution for predicting potential recruitment success.

5.4.5 References

- O'Connor, M.I., Bruno, J.F., Gaines, S.D., Halpern, B.S., Lester, S.E., Kinlan, B.P., & Weiss, J.M. (2007). Temperature control of larval dispersal and the implications for marine ecology, evolution, and conservation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104, 1266 - 1271.
- Strömberg, S. M., & Larsson, A. I. (2017). Larval behavior and longevity in the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* indicate potential for long-distance dispersal. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4, Article 411. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00411>
- Strömberg, S. M., & Larsson, A. I. (2017). Larval behavior and longevity in the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* indicate potential for long-distance dispersal. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4, Article 411. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00411>
- Schoenherr, S. (2024). Ecological perspectives of biophysical modelling: Exploring temperature-driven dispersal of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa*. Master Thesis, University of Aveiro, <http://hdl.handle.net/10773/42277>

6. Molecular techniques for assessing cause-effect pathways, identifying key biological components, and comparison with traditional techniques

6.1 Introduction

Recent advances in molecular techniques have transformed ecological monitoring and biodiversity assessment by enabling the detection and identification of taxa from environmental DNA (eDNA). This chapter presents a series of case studies that explore how molecular approaches—particularly metabarcoding—can complement or enhance traditional morphology-based methods in assessing harmful algal blooms, non-indigenous species, and broader community composition in coastal and marine ecosystems. By examining their strengths, limitations, and areas of convergence, these studies highlight the operational potential of molecular tools for improving the sensitivity, resolution, and cost-effectiveness of marine monitoring and management programmes.

6.2 Case study 9: Comparing 18S metabarcoding and microscopy for HAB monitoring in the Bay of Biscay

Anders Lanzén, Marta Revilla, Ángel Borja, Izaskun Zorita

6.2.1 Introduction

HABs are increasingly recognized as significant threats to aquatic ecosystems, public health, and socio-economic activities. Traditional monitoring of phytoplankton biodiversity with a focus on HAB-forming species has traditionally relied on light microscopy for taxonomic identification. While having achieved a relatively high level of standardisation and long historical records, this method is limited mainly by taxonomic resolution, time efficiency, and the ability to detect cryptic or morphologically similar species (Pawlowski et al., 2016; Sagarminaga et al., 2023). This is especially relevant for smaller organisms such as picophytoplankton, that can include HAB-forming species (Xu et al., 2017).

In recent years, molecular techniques based on environmental DNA (eDNA) have emerged as powerful tools for enhancing HAB surveillance. These can be broadly divided into (i) community profiling techniques such as eDNA metabarcoding, able to simultaneously determine the composition and diversity of a whole group of organisms, and (ii) targeted methods aiming to more accurately determine the abundance of an organism (or gene) of interest based on a specific quantitative PCR assay (including digital PCR). Based on amplification and sequencing of a taxonomic marker gene from eDNA extracted from environmental samples such as water, metabarcoding can also provide semi-quantitative abundances of organisms targeted using “universal” primers such as the eukaryotic small-subunit (18S) ribosomal RNA gene. Thus, it can provide broad, community-level information, including the monitoring of known as well as previously undetected HAB species, without the need for taxonomic expertise. Its sensitivity and scalability make it ideal for early warning systems, biodiversity assessments and routine monitoring. However, the most important challenges include taxonomic gaps in reference databases, amplification (PCR) bias, and a lack of standardisation or comparable historical records (Cordier et al., 2020).

Here, we present a case study comparing the use of eDNA metabarcoding based on 18S rRNA for two different size fractions along a long-term time series, at one coastal and one offshore site, located outside the Basque coast of the Bay of Biscay (the Basque Coastal Microbial and Plankton Observatory; Garate et al., 2022).

6.2.2 Methods

Water samples were collected and filtered from the stations LUR20 and D2 belonging to the Basque Monitoring Network and utilised for both microscopy and eDNA metabarcoding as described previously by Borja et al. (2021) and Garate et al. (2022).

The station LUR20 is located outside Donostia-San Sebastian at approximately 37 m depth and D2 further offshore at a depth of 110 m (see [Figure 6.2.1](#)). While LUR20 is affected mainly by the treated wastewaters of the Donostia metropolitan area, D2 is affected by river runoff mainly from the river Adour, with its estuary in Bayonne. Both stations are monitored seasonally (once in winter, spring, summer and autumn) using microscopy and monthly, since 2015, using metabarcoding. For this case study, available eDNA metabarcoding data was limited to those samples that were collected in conjunction with seasonal microscopy-based monitoring. Previously published data (2015–2021, 0.2–3 μM size fraction) were also complemented by eDNA metabarcoding of samples from the year 2022, as well as samples from mainly D2 for the seven-year time series from the larger size fraction (3–200 μM).

Figure 6.2.1 Locations of the two time-series examined in the Bay of Biscay (Garate et al., 2022).

As described in Garate et al. (2022), eDNA was extracted from 0.2 and 3 μM pore size polycarbonate filters (after filtration of approximately 2 L of surface seawater). Briefly, the V1–V2 region of the 18S rRNA gene was amplified using primers SSU_F04mod (GCTTGWCTCAAAGATTAAGCC) and SSU_R22mod (CCTGCTGCCTTCCTTRGA) (modified from Sinniger et al. (2016) as described by Cordier et al., 2018) and sequenced using MiSeq V3. Resulting sequence data were overlapped and quality

controlled using *vsearch* and clustered into unique sequence variants (SVs) using SWARM v3 as previously described (Garate et al., 2022). Sequence variants were then classified taxonomically using *CREST* v4 with the *SSUome* v1.1 reference sequence database based on *Eukaryome* v1.9.3 for eukaryotic sequences (Lanzén et al., 2012; <https://github.com/xapple/crest4>). Resulting data was analysed in R using the *vegan* package (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/vegan/index.html>). Taxon names resulting from annotation based on microscopy were manually edited to harmonise the comparisons with metabarcoding data. For sensitivity analysis, i.e. the number of detections of a potential HAB-forming species or genus per temporal water sample, the two size fractions were analysed separately and relative abundances of taxa transformed to presence/absence.

6.2.3 Results

In total, 63 microscopy-based community profiles including 230 unique taxa were retained from the two stations. Metabarcoding samples from all of these were available from the 0.2–3 µM size fraction, as well as 30 from 3–200 µM fractions, in all including 2150 unique SVs. Taking both size fractions into account, most families identified by microscopy (n=51) were also found by eDNA metabarcoding, while only 30 (17%) and 50 (26%) of the species and genera identified were (Table 6.2.1). At genus rank, overall community structure was more similar when comparing the eDNA profiles from the 3–200 µM fraction (Figure 6.2.2) compared to the 0.2–3 µM fraction. This was expected, considering how most smaller organisms (pico- and most nanoplankton) are not considered by the microscopy survey.

Table 6.2.1 - Number of taxa found only by microscopy, eDNA metabarcoding, and both methods at different taxonomic ranks

Rank:	Species	Genus	Family	Order	Class
Microscopy only	148	62	30	12	6
Metabarcoding only	141	146	191	197	123
Shared (with % of those identified by microscopy)	30 (17%)	50 (26%)	51 (63%)	37 (76%)	13 (68%)

Figure 6.2.2 Relative abundances at genus rank for microscopy and eDNA metabarcoding in the studied dataset (3-200 μ M size fraction only).

Limiting the analysis to a list of twelve genera of known HAB-forming or problematic species relevant to the studied area, showed that three genera (*Ostreopsis*, *Gambierdiscus* and *Karenia*) were not detected by neither microscopy nor eDNA metabarcoding in the studied time series, while two genera (*Centrodinium* and *Protoceratium*) were only detected by microscopy and one (*Karlodinium*) only at

genus rank by both approaches. Further, four genera were detected by both approaches, albeit with a larger diversity of species for microscopy (*Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis*, *Gonyaulax* and *Pseudo-nitzschia*), while the same unique species were detected by both methods for *Heterosigma* (*H. akashiwo*) and *Lingulodinium* (*L. polyedra*; see Table 6.2.2). However, five genera out of twelve, including *Karlodinium*, *Gonyaulax*, *Alexandrium* (incl. *A. minutum* and *A. ostenfeldii*), *Dinophysis* and *Heterosigma*, were detected more frequently by eDNA metabarcoding, indicating a higher sensitivity (Figure 6.2.3). These genera were also more frequently detected in the larger size fraction, as expected given their size.

Table 6.2.2 - Detected species of regionally relevant potentially HAB-forming genera by survey type

Genus	Microscopy	eDNA 0.2-3 µM	eDNA 3-200 µM
<i>Alexandrium</i>	<i>A. margalefii</i> <i>A. minutum</i> <i>A. ostenfeldii</i> <i>A. pseudogonyaulax</i> <i>A. sp.</i>	<i>A. minutum</i> <i>A. ostenfeldii</i> <i>A. sp.</i>	<i>A. minutum</i> <i>A. ostenfeldii</i> <i>A. sp.</i>
<i>Centrodinium</i>	<i>C. pavillardii</i> <i>punctatum</i> <i>C. sp.</i>	-	-
<i>Dinophysis</i>	<i>D. acuminata</i> <i>D. acuta</i> <i>D. caudata</i> <i>D. fortii</i> <i>D. infundibulum</i> <i>D. tripos</i> <i>D. sp.</i>	<i>D. sp.</i>	<i>D. sp.</i>
<i>Gonyaulax</i>	<i>G. digitale</i> <i>G. fragilis</i> <i>G. monacantha</i> <i>G. polygramma</i> <i>G. spinifera</i> <i>G. sp.</i>	<i>G. spinifera</i> <i>G. sp.</i>	<i>G. spinifera</i> <i>G. sp.</i>
<i>Heterosigma</i>	<i>H. akashiwo</i>	<i>H. akashiwo</i>	<i>H. akashiwo</i>
<i>Karlodinium</i>	<i>K sp.</i>	<i>K sp.</i>	<i>K sp.</i>
<i>Lingulodinium</i>	<i>L. polyedra</i>	<i>L. polyedra</i>	<i>L. polyedra</i>
<i>Protoceratium</i>	<i>P. reticulatum</i>	-	-
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i>	<i>P. australis</i> <i>P. galaxiae</i> <i>P. multistriata</i> <i>P. pungens</i> <i>P. sp.</i>	<i>P. sp.</i>	<i>P. sp.</i>

Figure 6.2.3 Number of detections throughout the 63 samples (normalised for comparative purpose for the 3-200 µm size fraction) of locally relevant potential HAB forming species for 18S metabarcoding vs. microscopy

6.2.4 Discussion

Taken together, these results support the notion that eDNA metabarcoding and microscopy are complementary methods that both offer advantages compared to each other. While metabarcoding failed to detect several relevant species, it can instead be applied at higher temporal frequency or with higher spatial coverage for a comparable cost, due to its scalability. Further, a better detection of species would likely be achieved by combining several taxonomic, including the V4 and V9 regions of 18S rRNA, and is likely to improve further with improved taxonomic reference databases (Cordier et al., 2020). It is also worth pointing out that several nano- or picoplankton species that may cause

HABs were not considered here due to a lack of knowledge, since previous studies have been heavily biased towards larger sized plankton. An example is *Aureococcus anophagefferens*, that was consistently detected in eDNA data, while overlooked by microscopy.

Finally, far higher sensitivity can be reached for specific HAB-forming or other species of interest by applying specific qPCR or dPCR based eDNA assays (Sagarminaga et al. 2023). A local example of this is the monitoring of *Ostreopsis* (*O. ovata*, *O. siamensis* and total *O. spp.*) that is carried out routinely along the Basque coast since 2024, through the EU Interreg co-funded *Ostreobila* project (<https://www.poctefa.eu/proyectos/efa040-01-id-ostreobila/>).

6.2.5 References

- Borja, Á., Bald, J., Uyarra, M. C., Franco, J., Larreta, J., Menchaca, I., Muxika, I., Pouso, S., Garmendia, J. M., Lanzén, A., Revilla, M., Rodríguez, J. G., Sagarminaga, Y., Solaun, O., Ainhize Uriarte, I. Z., Adarraga, I., Aguirrezabalaga, F., Sola, J. C., Igor Cruz, M. A. M., Martínez, J., Ruiz, J. M., Cano, M., Laza-Martínez, A. & Manzanos, A. (2021), 'Red de seguimiento del estado ecológico de las aguas de transición y costeras de la CAPV. Informe de resultados, Campaña 2020', Technical report, AZTI.
- Cordier, T., Forster, D., Dufresne, Y., Martins, C. I., Stoeck, T. & Pawlowski, J. (2018), 'Supervised machine learning outperforms taxonomy-based environmental DNA metabarcoding applied to biomonitoring', *Molecular Ecology Resources* 18, 1381--1391.
- Cordier, T., Alonso-Sáez, L., Apothéloz-Perret-Gentil, L., Aylagas, E., Bohan, D. A., Bouchez, A., Chariton, A., Creer, S., Frühe, L., Keck, F., Keeley, N., Laroche, O., Leese, F., Pochon, X., Stoeck, T., Pawlowski, J. & Lanzén, A. (2020), 'Ecosystems monitoring powered by environmental genomics: a review of current strategies with an implementation roadmap', *Molecular Ecology* 30, 2937--2958.
- Garate, L., Alonso-Sáez, L., Revilla, M., Logares, R., & Lanzén, A. (2022), 'Shared and contrasting associations in the dynamic nano- and picoplankton communities of two close but contrasting sites from the Bay of Biscay', *Environ Microbiol* 24, 6052--6070.
- Lanzén, A., Jørgensen, S. L., Huson, D. H., Gorfer, M., Grindhaug, S. H., Jonassen, I., Øvreås, L. & Urich, T. (2012), 'CREST - Classification Resources for Environmental Sequence Tags', *PLOS ONE* 7(11), e49334.
- Sinniger, F., Pawlowski, J., Harii, S., Gooday, A. J., Yamamoto, H., Chevaldonné, P., Cedhagen, T., Carvalho, G. & Creer, S. (2016), 'Worldwide Analysis of Sedimentary DNA Reveals Major Gaps in Taxonomic Knowledge of Deep-Sea Benthos', *Frontiers in Marine Science* 3, 92.
- Xu, X., Yu, Z., Cheng, F., He, L., Cao, X. & Song, X. (2017), 'Molecular diversity and ecological characteristics of the eukaryotic phytoplankton community in the coastal waters of the Bohai Sea, China', *Harmful Algae* 61, 13--22.

6.3 Case study 10: Non-indigenous species screening using DNA metabarcoding of coastal and estuarine bulk community samples

Anders Lanzén, Iñigo Muxika, Ángel Borja, Izaskun Zorita

6.3.1 Introduction

Several studies have shown the potential and limitations of eDNA-based approaches for monitoring of non-indigenous (including invasive) species (NIS) using environmental samples (e.g. Holman *et al.*, 2019; Rey *et al.*, 2020; Pearman *et al.*, 2021; Knudsen *et al.*, 2022; reviewed by Fonseca *et al.*, 2023 and Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2023). This includes both targeted monitoring of species through qPCR or dPCR, as well as community profiling methods such as metabarcoding, the latter being particularly suited for baseline surveys, where the composition of NISs is unknown. As for eDNA-based HAB monitoring, challenges include limited species coverage in taxonomic reference databases (Rey *et al.*, 2020; Pearman *et al.*, 2021; Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2023), and a lack of standardisation and coverage in terms of sampling methodology (Koziol *et al.*, 2019; Rey *et al.*, 2020).

Here, we present an opportunistic case study exploring metabarcoding data of macrobenthic invertebrate communities derived from estuarine and coastal stations from the Basque Monitoring Network, from seven consecutive years, to identify NIS.

6.3.2 Methods

We utilised COI metabarcoding data based on sieved bulk community samples, collected yearly in conjunction with routine monitoring for the Basque Water Agency URA from 2018 throughout 2024 (Figure 6.3.1 Borja *et al.*, 2024). Taxa were screened for NIS using three reference list, derived from (i) the European Alien Species Information Network (EASIN; Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2015), (ii) the Information System on Aquatic Non-Indigenous and Cryptogenic Species (AquaNIS; <https://aquanisresearch.com/>) and (iii) a regional list of potential NIS in the Bay of Biscay (Baki *et al.*, 2024). Identified potential detections of NIS were manually controlled to verify that the species were not autochthonous to the Western Europe, and compared to information about reported occurrences to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) online (accessed April 2025; <https://www.gbif.org/>). Detected potential NIS were also compared to the morphology-based monitoring data from the Basque Monitoring Network (2002–2024).

Figure 6.3.1. Locations of monitoring stations with bulk macroinvertebrate community metabarcoding data screened (Borja et al., 2024)

6.3.3 Results and discussion

A total of 60 species from the screened metabarcoding data were listed in at least one of the three NIS reference lists. Out of these, 32 were confirmed to be non-native to Western Europe. Out of these, five had been previously observed using morphology-based monitoring (Table 6.3.1). However, 20 other NIS previously identified using morphology in the same sites (2002–2024) were not identified using metabarcoding. While four of these species were widespread in the studied area, it is noteworthy that *P. pholadiformis* (false angling) was only observed in the Nervión estuary, hosting the Port of Bilbao, the 4th largest harbour in Spain in terms of commercial shipping volume.

Table 6.3.1 – Non-Indigenous Species detected using metabarcoding coinciding with morphology-based observations

Species	Common name	Observed distribution
<i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i>	Australian tubeworm	Widespread although found in low abundance
<i>Grandidierella japonica</i>	(hydromedusae sp.)	Widespread
<i>Petricolaria pholadiformis</i>	False anglewing	Nervi3n estuary only
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i>	New Zealand mud snail	Widespread
<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	Manila clam	Widespread

Out of the remaining 17 NIS, six identified with reasonable confidence (more than one station or at relatively high abundance) had not previously been reported to occur along the Basque coast (Table 6.3.2). While three of these had been reported elsewhere in the Bay of Biscay, the other three were new to this large region (*Blackfordia virginica*, *Moerisia inkermanica* and *Chaetogammarus ischnus*). Out of these, *C. ischnus* is a benthic species, whereas the other two form pelagic medusae. Although both include benthic life stages as polyps, they would be overlooked in benthic routine monitoring surveys.

Table 6.3.2 - Non-Indigenous Species detected using metabarcoding that had previously not been detected along the Basque coast

Species	Common name	Previously reported in
<i>Blackfordia virginica</i>	Black sea jellyfish	SW Iberian Peninsula, Netherlands
<i>Moerisia inkermanica</i>	NA	Mediterranean, NE Brittany
<i>Chaetogammarus ischnus</i>	Gammarid sp.	E and NW Europe (mainly freshwater species)
<i>Pennaria disticha</i>	Christmas tree hydroid	Bay of Biscay (S Brittany, Galicia), Mediterranean
<i>Jassa slatteryi</i>	Hitchhiker amphipod	Bay of Biscay (Arcachon), Mediterranean
<i>Haloa japonica</i>	Japanese bubble snail	Bay of Biscay (Asturias)

Taken together, these results highlight the utility of employing bulk community or direct eDNA metabarcoding as a complement to morphology-based routine monitoring of benthic invertebrates. This approach cannot only provide accurate assessments of ecosystem health as demonstrated by Borja *et al.* (2024) but can also serve to monitor NIS and serve as an early warning system for the establishment new, potentially invasive, species. However, as shown previously, a more ambitious and targeted sampling approach is necessary to provide more complete baseline NIS surveys. Further, the possibility of misclassifications due to missing or incorrect sequence data in taxonomic reference databases exist. One possibility for reducing this risk, without the need for visual identification, can be

to carefully examine the phylogenetic diversity. Specifically, the existence of related, indigenous species without reference sequence data must be ruled out to verify these results, since this can be a likely source of false positives.

6.3.4 References

- Baki, A.O. (2024) Spatial distribution and temporal trends of soft-bottom marine benthic alien species collected during the period 1995–2022 in the Basque coast (southeastern Bay of Biscay). Erasmus Mundus Master of Science in Marine Environment and Resources (MER2030), pp. 56 + Appendix. University of the Basque Country. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2013.04.009>
- Borja, A., Lanzén, A. and Muxika, I. (2024), 'DNA-based marine benthic assessment methods can perform as morphological ones, but an intercalibration is needed', *Ecological Indicators* 167, 112638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112638>
- Fonseca, V. G., Davison, P. I., Creach, V., Stone, D., Bass, D. and Tidbury, H. J. (2023), 'The Application of eDNA for Monitoring Aquatic Non-Indigenous Species: Practical and Policy Considerations', *Diversity* 15(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15050631>
- Holman, L. E., de Bruyn, M., Creer, S., Carvalho, G., Robidart, J. and Rius, M. (2019), 'Detection of introduced and resident marine species using environmental DNA metabarcoding of sediment and water', *Scientific Reports* 9(1), 11559-. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47899-7>
- Katsanevakis S., Deriu I., D'Amico F., Nunes A. L., Pelaez Sanchez S., Crocetta F., et al. (2015). European Alien Species Information Network (EASIN): supporting European policies and scientific research. *Manage. Biol. Invasion* 6, 147–157. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2015.6.2.05>
- Katsanevakis, S., Olenin, S., Puntilla-Dodd, R., Rilov, G., Stæehr, P. A. U., Teixeira, H., Tsirintanis, K., Birchenough, S. N. R., Jakobsen, H. H., Knudsen, S. W., Lanzén, A., Mazaris, A. D., Piraino, S. and Tidbury, H. J. (2023), 'Marine invasive alien species in Europe: 9 years after the IAS Regulation', *Frontiers in Marine Science* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1271755>
- Knudsen, S. W., Hesselsøe, M., Thaulow, J., Agersnap, S., Hansen, B. K., Jacobsen, M. W., Bekkevold, D., Jensen, S. K. S., Møller, P. R. and Andersen, J. H. (2022), 'Monitoring of environmental DNA from nonindigenous species of algae, dinoflagellates and animals in the North East Atlantic', *Science of The Total Environment* 821, 153093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153093>
- Rey, A., Basurko, O. C. and Rodriguez-Ezpeleta, N. (2020), 'Considerations for metabarcoding-based port biological baseline surveys aimed at marine nonindigenous species monitoring and risk assessments', *Ecology and Evolution* 10(5), 2452–2465. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.6071>

6.4 Case study 11: Testing the use of eDNA as a complementary tool to underwater transect surveys

Marta Coll, Cesc Gordó-Vilaseca, Valerio Sbragaglia

6.4.1 Introduction

Traditional methods such as underwater visual censuses and citizen science, while valuable, are often time-consuming and yield unstructured data. Emerging as a promising complementary tool, environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding offers an innovative and cost-effective approach to monitoring marine ecosystems. eDNA can be used as a complementary monitoring sampling method with the aim of achieving a more comprehensive coverage.

By implementing eDNA metabarcoding in water and sediment samples, we can detect a broad spectrum of species, including rare or cryptic ones, thereby enhancing traditional techniques. This approach can be used across sampling periods and sites to assess the temporal and spatial variability of different biocommunities. Its results can be used to enhance conservation and management practices (Chavez et al., 2021). Among other applications, eDNA can be used for community characterisation, marine abundance estimation, and improving existing monitoring plans.

Figure 6.4.1 Sampling methods and target organisms (Gilbey et al., 2021).

In our case study, we aimed to develop an integrated approach that simultaneously utilises visual censuses and eDNA metabarcoding in water and sediment. The ultimate goal is to evaluate eDNA

metabarcoding as a potential tool for complementarily characterising the biodiversity of key ecological areas.

6.4.2 Methods

In the first phase of the GES4SEAS project, we designed and evaluated the feasibility of implementing three different sites and strategies where eDNA sampling and visual census can be jointly conducted and their results compared.

The first site evaluated is Cap de Creus, a Natura 2000 area located in the northwest of Catalonia (Figure 6.4.2). Its management plan— *Pla Rector d'Ús i Gestió (PRUG)* — is in the final stages of approval and will include an improved monitoring plan for the natural area.

In this area, we have developed a monitoring strategy based on complementary techniques, including visual census (via snorkelling and apnea), the use of underwater cameras, and eDNA analysis from water and sediment samples. These efforts encompass both the Marine Protected Area and adjacent zones.

Figure 6.4.2. Option 1. Cap de Creus Area and the wider area surrounding the park.

The second evaluated alternative is the coastal area of Barcelona. The study includes ten winter transects, each 100 meters long, across the ten beaches of Barcelona (Figure 6.4.3). From each transect, 1 water sample is collected for eDNA analysis, and 1 water sample from an adjacent area is also collected as a negative control.

The results will be compared with data from visual census tracks and existing information available in the citizen science database MINKA (<https://minka-sdg.org/>).

Figure 6.4.3. Option 2. Barcelona beaches. Obtained from MINKA project.

The third evaluated alternative focuses on identifying key offshore habitats to protect highly mobile pelagic marine species (HMS). This information, together with other data coming from different techniques such as biologging, can be used to propose priority Marine Protected Areas in the Western Mediterranean basin for these species, complementing existing proposals that primarily target small pelagic species (Ramírez et al., 2021) or demersal oriented protected areas (Ortega et al., 2023) (Figure 6.4.4). eDNA metabarcoding will be employed to enhance large-scale biodiversity characterisation and to supplement existing localised biodiversity data.

Figure 6.4.4. Alternative 3 study area and proposal for priority areas for management in the case of demersal species. Source (Ortega et al., 2023).

6.4.3 Results

Since we did not have a specific budget allocated from the GES4SEAS project for fieldwork and analysis, we have been seeking for complementary funding and collaborations within GES4SEAS project. After the presentation of several projects, we have ensured funding to execute the first alternative: Cap de Creus study.

A first trial of water and sediment samples and follow up analyses will be done under a collaborative action with a Spanish National project, “HumanFear” led by Dr. Valerio Sbragaglia, and partially supported by GES4SEAS, during summer 2025.

The core fieldwork and follow up analysis will be done under the broader umbrella of a Marie Curie post docs project (“PETRIFY”) leaded by Dr. Cesc Gordó, whose aims are to investigate the ecological effects of no-take Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) on fish populations using a combination of fieldwork, laboratory analyses, and modeling techniques, during 2026-2027.

The project will use, among others, visual census of fish and invertebrate communities and eDNA analysis from water and sediment samples.

The research field will encompass both the MPAs and adjacent zones.

It will include a scientific secondment of 6 months at AZTI, under the supervision of Dr. Naiara Rodríguez-Ezpeleta. We expect results to be available during the first half of 2027.

6.4.4 References

- Chavez, F. P., Min, M., Pitz, K., Truelove, N., Baker, J., Lascala-Grunewald, D., Blum, M., Walz, K., Nye, C., Djurhuus, A., Miller, R. J., Goodwin, K. D., Muller-Karger, F. E., Ruhl, H. A., & Scholin, C. A. (2021). Observing life in the sea using environmental DNA. *Oceanography*, *34*(2), 102–119. <https://doi.org/10.5670/OCEANOGRAPHY.2021.218>
- Gilbey, J., Carvalho, G., Castilho, R., Coscia, I., Coulson, M. W., Dahle, G., Derycke, S., Francisco, S. M., Helyar, S. J., Johansen, T., Junge, C., Layton, K. K. S., Martinsohn, J., Matejusova, I., Robalo, J. I., Rodríguez-Ezpeleta, N., Silva, G., Strammer, I., Vasemägi, A., & Volckaert, F. A. M. (2021). Life in a drop: Sampling environmental DNA for marine fishery management and ecosystem monitoring. *Marine Policy*, *124*, 104331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOL.2020.104331>
- Ortega, M., Castro-Cadenas, M. D., Steenbeek, J., & Coll, M. (2023). Identifying and prioritizing demersal fisheries restricted areas based on combined ecological and fisheries criteria: The western Mediterranean. *Marine Policy*, *157*, 105850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOL.2023.105850>
- Ramírez, F., Pennino, M. G., Albo-Puigserver, M., Steenbeek, J., Bellido, J. M., & Coll, M. (2021). SOS small pelagics: A safe operating space for small pelagic fish in the western Mediterranean Sea. *Science of the Total Environment*, *756*, 144002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144002>

6.5 Case study 12: Exploring the potential of eDNA metabarcoding for assessing phytoplankton diversity and abundance in coastal environments

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Environmental DNA metabarcoding combines high-throughput sequencing with genetic material extraction from environmental samples to assess marine microorganism diversity. It provides a cost-effective alternative to traditional methods, excelling in identifying cryptic, rare, and elusive species. The approach typically targets the 18S rDNA gene for studies on protists and phytoplankton, focusing on hypervariable regions. However, biases may arise from gene copy number variation, barcode region, and primer selection. Comparative studies with traditional microscopy reveal both qualitative and quantitative biases, with metabarcoding accuracy influenced by sampling volume, DNA extraction, and bioinformatics. Here, we present a case study exploring the potential of eDNA metabarcoding to assess marine dinoflagellate and diatom diversity and abundance in coastal environments. It compares selected phytoplankton samples collected from two distinct sampling efforts: biweekly sampling at the Barcelona Coastal Ocean Observatory (COO, Pudem) from December 2021 to December 2022 and a field campaign at a beach from the Catalan coast during a harmful algal bloom event. These campaigns targeted a temporal dataset, capturing seasonal variations in phytoplankton communities and bloom-forming and potentially harmful species. Comparing microscopy and metabarcoding for phytoplankton presence/absence and abundance revealed both concordances and discrepancies. Metabarcoding detected taxa absent in microscopy, likely due to differences in sample volume, extracellular DNA. Conversely, microscopy identified taxa that metabarcoding missed, possibly due to technical challenges like insufficient sequencing depth or primer mismatches, or limitations in genetic marker resolution. Additionally, discrepancies in relative abundance were noted, likely driven by uneven ribosomal gene copy numbers across taxa. These findings highlight the need for methodological refinement and complementary approaches to ensure accurate community assessments.

6.5.1 Introduction

Over the past decades, the field of environmental DNA metabarcoding has emerged as a transformative approach in diversity research. This field combines DNA metabarcoding, which is the simultaneous identification of multiple taxa using high-throughput sequencing of a specific DNA region, with environmental DNA analysis, involving the direct extraction of genetic material from environmental samples such as air, soil, sediment, and water.

Traditional methods of diversity assessment, like morphological identification, can be time-consuming and require identification expertise and strong taxonomic knowledge. Metabarcoding streamlines the process, allowing for quicker and often more cost-effective analyses, and it has proven to be particularly effective in the detection of cryptic, rare and/or elusive species.

The metabarcoding of eukaryotic plankton communities by targeting 18S rDNA regions is frequently used to assess diversity patterns from environmental samples. In particular, the ribosomal V4 and V9 regions are popular choices for analysing communities of marine eukaryotic protists, due to their highly conserved primer binding regions and the ability to detect and identify a wide spectrum of phylogenetically distant taxa. In fact, many studies rely on metabarcoding analyses to characterize aquatic protist diversity (de Vargas *et al.*, 2015), and it has also been suggested as an alternative method to monitor phytoplankton, HABs and toxic species (Pawlowski *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2020) and references therein). However, in the same way than traditional morphological approaches, metabarcoding has its own limitations and biases.

Different laboratory procedures including sample filtration, size fractioning, cell lysis and DNA extraction can affect the output of the method. Likewise, a more general challenge in studies using amplicon-based metabarcoding is the choice of barcode region and primer pairs, which can limit or bias the estimated diversity, particularly when the target group of organisms is highly phylogenetically diverse. Finally, the 18S rDNA subunit's gene copy number variation among various phytoplankton groups or even between individuals is a widely discussed issue, and many authors agree that it can be a cause of the discrepancy between true species abundance and metabarcoding-derived read counts introducing a bias in the latter (Marinchel *et al.*, 2023).

The objective of this report is to provide a comparative analysis of phytoplankton diversity estimates obtained using traditional morphology-based observations and molecular-based data obtained by metabarcoding. For that, we present provisional results from a regular sampling conducted over several months at two coastal stations to understand the temporal dynamics of marine phytoplankton. We employed two approaches: i) regular sampling of a seasonal phytoplankton community at one fixed location for one year, and ii) sampling phytoplankton blooms at coastal areas. We focused on the abundance and diversity of dominant phytoplankton groups, i.e. dinoflagellates and diatoms. The comparison of results obtained is performed to determine the agreement between both approaches and to detect possible biases and limitations of each technique.

6.5.2 Methods

Sampling

The regular sampling took place biweekly at a location corresponding with station 1.1 of the Barcelona Coastal Ocean Observatory (hereafter COO Pudem) of the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) located near Barcelona's coast from December 2021 to December 2022. Concurrently, a field campaign was conducted at La Fosca beach (Palamós) during summer months, covering a harmful algal bloom episode (Table 6.5.1). For the comparison purposes, only some phytoplankton samples from the two Catalan Coast locations (NW Mediterranean Sea) were considered.

Table 6.5.1. Field campaigns conducted at five different locations, detailing their respective dates and the number of samples collected, and number of samples compared between eDNA metabarcoding and traditional microscopy.

STATION	LOCATION SPAIN	FROM	TO	n	N OF COMPARED PHYTOPLANKTON SAMPLES
LA FOSCA	Palamós	9 Jun 2022	5 Sep 2022	18	4
CCO PUDEM	Barcelona	Dec 2021	Dec 2022	24	6

Seawater (~10 L) integrating the whole water column was collected manually at the beach (~1.5 m depth). For the regular sampling sites, seawater was obtained using a tube connected to an electric pump (2.5–4m depth). Seawater was prefiltered through a 200 µm mesh to remove metazoans and larger particles, and a 150 ml subsample was fixed with Lugol's iodine for phytoplankton determination. Once in the laboratory, collected seawater was immediately filtered in two replicates by serial filtration through 10 µm and 0.8 µm polycarbonate filters (47 mm) using a peristaltic pump until the filters were saturated (100 mL to 2 L, depending on the total biomass). The filters were stored frozen at –80°C until processed.

Microscopic identification and enumeration of the phytoplankton community

Aliquots of phytoplankton samples, 10 mL for beach samples and 50 mL for CA, previously fixed with Lugol's solution, were settled for 24 hours in a counting chamber following the Utermöhl method (Utermöhl, 1958). For phytoplankton enumeration, the appropriate area of the chamber—determined based on the cell density of each species—was scanned at 200–400× magnification using a Leica-Leitz DMII inverted microscope. A minimum of 30 cells were counted for each species. When necessary, the thecal plates of dinoflagellates were stained with the fluorescent dye Calcofluor White M2R (Fritz and Triemer, 1985) and examined under epifluorescence (50 W lamp) using a Leica DM IRB inverted microscope (Leica Microsystems GmbH).

DNA extraction and metabarcoding sequencing

A total of 42 DNA samples were processed and subjected to molecular sequencing, encompassing the two size fractions of seawater from all locations. Total genomic DNA was extracted from filters using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro kit (Qiagen) as follows: Filters were cut in small pieces using sterilized razor blades were placed in a PowerBead to which 60 µL of solution C1 was added. The tubes were vortexed at maximum speed for 10 min and then centrifuged at 10,000 g for 30 s. The supernatant was transferred to a clean collection tube, removing all filter pieces. Successive steps were conducted according to the manufacturer's instructions. DNA was eluted in 5 mL and concentrated to a final volume of 200 µL using Amicon Ultra centrifugal filters.

For non-metazoan eukaryote library preparation, a fragment of the 18S rRNA region of around 500 bp was amplified using the following primers: Forward - EK-565F (5' GCAGTAAAAAGCTCGTAGT 3') (Simon et al., 2015) and Reverse - 18S-EUK-1134R-UnonMet (5' TTTAAGTTTCAGCCTTGCG 3') (Bower et al., 2004). In the first amplification step, PCRs were carried out in a final volume of 12.5 µL, containing 1.25 µL of template DNA, 0.5 µM of the primers, 3.13 µL of Supreme NZYtaq 2x Green Master Mix (NZYTech), and ultrapure water up to 12.5 µL. The reaction mixture was incubated as follows: an initial denaturation step at 95 °C for 5 min, followed by 32 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s, 49 °C for 45 s, 72 °C for 45 s, and a final extension step at 72 °C for 7 min. The oligonucleotide indices that are required for multiplexing different libraries in the same sequencing pool were attached in a second amplification step with identical conditions but only 5 cycles and 60 °C as the annealing temperature. Finished libraries were pooled in equimolar amounts according to the results of a Qubit dsDNA HS Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific) quantification. The pool was sequenced in a fraction (13/16) of a MiSeq PE300 flowcell (Illumina). Illumina paired-end raw data for each library consists of forward (R1) and reverse (R2) reads stored in separate files, which also include the reads' quality scores. The library preparation and sampling procedures were conducted by an external company (Allgenetics, Spain).

Molecular data processing

The raw reads obtained from previous samples were trimmed from the adaptors using cutadapt v.1.16 (Martin, 2011). The DADA2 pipeline was used to filter, dereplicate and trim low-quality sequences (maxEE = 4, 6; truncLen= 280, 250), merge the paired ends (minOverlap = 10) and remove chimeras. The resulting ASVs (amplicon sequence variants) were classified using a simple non-Bayesian taxonomy classifier, vsearch v2.8.1 (Rognes *et al.*, 2016) and the PR2 database 4.14 (Guillou *et al.*, 2013) customized with new in-house sequences with a bootstrap of 0.6. Raw metagenomic reads were submitted to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under Bioproject numbers PRJNA891539 and

PRJNA1023727. Metabarcoding data were analysed using the package Phyloseq and all graphs were generated using the package ggplot2 fromRcran (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013; R Core Team, 2013; Wickham, 2016).

6.5.3 Results

Metabarcoding characterization of dinoflagellates and diatoms.

Metabarcoding results obtained in La Fosca showed a clear dominance of dinoflagellates during the development of the bloom (Figure 6.5.1). Overall, dinoflagellates represented up to 70-80% of microeukaryotic amplicons, especially in the large fraction, which better represents dinoflagellates community. Diatoms relative abundance was generally low, representing <10% of the microeukaryotic community (Figure 6.5.2).

Figure 6.5.1. Temporal dynamics of the dinoflagellates (*Dinophyceae*) community at a genus level. On the x-axis, bar plot showing the relative abundance of the different eukaryote groups at each sampling date as determined using the V4 18S rDNA region, divided by sampling location. Relative abundances (%) are based on the total eukaryotic community. The two rows correspond to fraction sizes (0.8 μm – 10 μm, and 10 μm – 200 μm).

La Fosca showed a succession of species. At the beginning of the sampling, from June to mid-July, the community was dominated by *Ansanella* sp. and *A. taylorii*. Afterwards, from mid-July to mid-August, *G. litoralis* abundances increased, *A. taylorii* abundances remained high and *L. fissa* appeared. At the end of the sampling, from mid-August to early September, *A. taylorii* abundances decreased drastically, and *G. litoralis* and *L. fissa* abundances increased. By contrast, the samples were clearly

dominated by *Ansanella* sp. in the small fraction except during the last three samples, when *G. litoralis* abundances were higher. Regarding diatoms (Figure 6.5.2), they were scarcely detected, being mostly represented by *Chaetoceros* representatives.

Figure 6.5.2. Temporal dynamics of the diatoms (Bacillariophyta) community at a genus level. On the x-axis, bar plot showing the relative abundance of the different eukaryote groups at each sampling date as determined using the V4 18S rDNA region, divided by sampling location. Relative abundances (%) are based on the total eukaryotic community. The two rows correspond to fraction sizes (0.8 µm – 10 µm, and 10 µm – 200 µm).

In the CCO PUDEM site, the dominance of dinoflagellates was high. Dinoflagellates represented more than 50% of relative abundance throughout the period except December samples, early January, and during the end of March-April (Figure 6.5.1). The samples were dominated by several representatives like *Heterocapsa*, *Gyrodinium* sp., and other genera like *Triplos*, *Levanderina* or *Prorocentrum* were present at lower abundance. Diatom abundances remained low along the year (<20%), only exhibiting some peaks of high abundances in March (40-50%), and October (40-60%). They were dominated by unassigned diatom sequences and *Skeletonema*, followed at lower abundance by *Chaetoceros*, *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Thalassiosira* representatives (Figure 6.5.2).

Microscopical quantification of dinoflagellate and diatom abundance

At analysed samples from COO Pudem (Figure 6.5.3a), the highest abundances of phytoplankton (here as the sum of dinoflagellates and diatoms) were observed in SM10 and SM11 (1.7 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ both of them). In SM10 the highest percentage of phytoplankton corresponded to dinoflagellates (70.8%). In SM11, diatoms dominated the community (80%), as occurred in most samples analysed along the annual cycle. The taxonomic composition of phytoplankton was analysed in some samples (14 December 2021; 26 January 2022; 23 February; 19 May; 30 May; and 25 August). Regarding those with

the highest phytoplankton abundance, a high percentage (68.6%) of the dinoflagellates in SM10 corresponded to unidentified small species (smaller than 12 μm). In SM11, the highest percentage of diatom corresponded to *Chaetoceros* spp. from which 30.3% corresponded to *Ch. tenuissimus*.

At La Fosca beach, the highest phytoplankton abundances were observed in August, with maximum abundance on 5 August (1.3 10⁶ cells L⁻¹). The community was largely dominated by dinoflagellates along the sampling period, representing more than 90% of the community in most samples analysed. The increase of dinoflagellates corresponded to the development of *Gymnodinium* representatives, mainly *G. litoralis*, reaching their peak in August. *Alexandrium taylorii* also bloomed during the studied period, with maximum abundances during the end of July and early August. In the samples from 4 July, 22 July, and 16 August, where *Ansanella* dominated the small fraction in metabarcoding, the microscopy abundances of small dinoflagellates cf. *Ansanella* were 2.2 10⁴, 2.4 10⁴, and 6 10³ cells L⁻¹, respectively. Meanwhile, the abundances of *G. litoralis* were 320, 6.4 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ and 2 10⁵ cells L⁻¹, respectively. Regarding the sample from 21 June, where *Heterocapsa* dominated all fractions in metabarcoding, microscopy shows that small species of *Heterocapsa* predominated in the sample along with *Ansanella*, which had an abundance of 4 10³ cells L⁻¹.

Figure 6.5.3. Cell abundance (cells L⁻¹) and seasonal variation of major phytoplankton groups, dinoflagellates and diatoms, across samples from a) station COO Pudem and b) La Fosca beach. Note that the plots are at different scale.

Comparison of presence/absence of diatoms and dinoflagellate representatives at genus and species level

The correspondence between microscopy counts and metabarcoding sequencing was explored for dinoflagellates and diatoms in selected samples (Table 6.5.2). The exploration of metabarcoding information was based on both small (0.8-10 µm) and large (10-200 µm) fractions for each sample.

Table 6.5.2. Comparison of presence/absence of diatoms and dinoflagellate representatives at genus and species level, between both methods, microscopy and metabarcoding, divided by size fraction (0.8 and 10 µm) for the ten samples analysed from the Coastal Ocean Observatory PUDEM.

Diatoms	0.8 µm		10 µm		0.8 and 10 µm	
	Genus	Species	Genus	Species	Genus	Species
# coincidences	52	12	49	17	57	18
Percentage (%)	62.7	17.4	59	24.3	68.7	25.7
Dinoflagellates	0.8 µm		10 µm		0.8 and 10 µm	
	Genus	Species	Genus	Species	Genus	Species
# coincidences	29	2	40	7	44	
Percentage (%)	34.9	5.6	48.2	20	53	22.9

For the COO Pudem location, the analysis of the presence/absence of species observed by microscopy in the metabarcoding dataset revealed a moderate percentage of coincidence for diatoms, with 62.5%-59% of genera coincidence for the 0.8-10 and 10-200 µm fractions, increasing to 68.7% when considering both size fractions together. Those percentages decreased to 17.4% and 24.3% respectively when comparing them at species level, being 25.7% when treating both size-fractions together. The coincidence of dinoflagellates representatives was much lower. A 34.9% and 48.2% of diatoms genera observed by microscopy were detected by metabarcoding, 53% when treating both size fractions together. The coincidence at the species level was only 5.6% for the 0.8-10 µm, while it was higher (20%) for the large fraction, 22.9% when treating both fractions together.

As an example, metabarcoding data of sample SM10, which showed the highest abundance of dinoflagellates, revealed a high relative abundance within the dinoflagellate group of *Heterocapsa* species, *Ansanella* and *Yihiella yeosuensis*, generally small species of dinoflagellates <10 µm that would correspond to those observed by microscopy and classified as unidentified small dinoflagellates. In SM11 the highest relative abundance according to metabarcoding corresponded to the diatom *Ch. tenuissimus*, a species that was also relatively abundant in microscopy observations.

Regarding the representation of both phytoplankton groups, diatoms dominated in most samples analysed by microscopy. By contrast, dinoflagellates dominated relative abundances in the metabarcoding dataset except in the two samples from October, when diatoms showed their maximum relative abundance.

Table 6.5.3. Comparison of presence/absence of diatoms and dinoflagellate representatives at genus and species level, between both methods, microscopy and metabarcoding, divided by size fraction (0.8 and 10 µm) for the four samples analysed from La Fosca beach.

Diatoms	0.8 µm		10 µm		0.8 and 10 µm	
	Genus	Species	Genus	Species	Genus	Species
# coincidence	21	5	20	5	23	5
Percentage (%)	63.6	19.2	60.6	18.5	69.7	18.5
Dinoflagellates	0.8 µm		10 µm		0.8 and 10 µm	
	Genus	Species	Genus	Species	Genus	Species
# coincidence	28	22	28	20	32	23
Percentage (%)	82.4	70.9	82.4	64.5	94.1	74.2

For La Fosca beach, the analysis of the presence/absence of species observed by microscopy in the metabarcoding dataset revealed a high percentage of coincidence for dinoflagellates. Up to 82.3% of genera observed by microscopy were also detected by metabarcoding, increasing to 94.1% when considering both size fractions together. Those percentages decreased to 71% and 64.5% respectively for the 0.8-10 and 10-200 µm when comparing them at species level, being 74.2% when treating both size-fractions together. By contrast, the coincidence of diatom representatives was lower. Only 58.6 and 55.2% of diatoms genera observed by microscopy were detected by metabarcoding, 65.5% when treating both size fractions together, and the percentage decreased to 20-21% for detections at the species level.

In this case, the dinoflagellates community showed a good agreement between both methods, even though the relative abundance of detected blooming species did not completely agree, e.g. *A. taylorii* showed greater abundance in metabarcoding than the determined by microscopy. Likewise, the high abundance of *Ansanella* representatives, especially during the beginning of the bloom period, and at the small size fraction (Figure 6.5.1) was not reflected in the microscopy observations. Finally, the relative abundance of diatoms was low in both methods along the studied period (Figure 6.5.2, Figure 6.5.3b), even though the correspondence of diversity observed was low, especially at species level.

6.5.4 Discussion

As previously stated, high-throughput sequencing techniques like metabarcoding are powerful approaches to determine aquatic microbial diversity highly surpassing the accuracy of traditional approaches based on morphological identifications. Traditional methods of biodiversity assessment,

like morphological identification, can be time-consuming and require expert knowledge. Metabarcoding streamlines the process, allowing for quicker and often more cost-effective analyses.

In this study, it was determined that metabarcoding improved the identification of many small-sized organisms which require of detailed observations of some characters not easily visible by LM. Thus, the identity of several small dinoflagellates like *Yihiella*, *Ansanella* or *Heterocapsa* was only determined by metabarcoding while its identification was only tentative by LM.

By contrast, detection discrepancies between methods were detected:

i) Presence of taxa in metabarcoding but not observed by microscopy. This case could be due to many reasons like the volume of the sample that each method analyses (10-50 mL for microscopy and L for metabarcoding) that implies the detection of low abundant of microorganisms. Amplification of free extracellular DNA deriving from dead specimens or segregations but not representing cells currently present in the sample could be another cause. It could also be caused by inappropriate taxonomic assignment based on low identity percentages, or the detection of cryptic species not determined by microscopy.

ii) Presence of taxa observed by microscopy but not detected by metabarcoding can be due to some technical reasons like problems lysing cells with thick covers, that primers used for amplification do not match all diversity, or the lack of molecular sequences in reference databases, impeding the correct identification of the amplicons. The lack of resolution of the genetic marker, in this case the V4 18S rDNA region could also impede the correct discrimination and identification of molecularly close species. Likewise, insufficient sequencing depth could avoid detecting taxa and clustering information during bioinformatic procedures could result in losing diversity of taxa showing low dissimilarity in V4 marker.

iii) Differences in community composition and relative abundance. It could be due to an uneven copy number of ribosomal genes depending on the taxonomic group, resulting in an over-representation of some groups and underrepresentation of others. In fact, over-representation of Alveolata members like Dinoflagellata or Ciliophora has been largely documented in the literature (Medinger *et al.*, 2010; Piredda *et al.*, 2017). Such PCR amplification biases could be prevented using single-copy markers instead of rDNA ones, or non-PCR based methods like metagenomics or metatranscriptomics (Geisen *et al.*, 2019). Other reasons could be related, as previously mentioned, to inefficient cell lysis of some taxonomic groups and biases in primers coverage.

6.5.5 Conclusions

Metabarcoding has proven to be highly effective in detecting cryptic, rare, and elusive species (*Heterocapsa*, *Ansanella*, and small dinoflagellates <15 µm). The technique's sensitivity and precision enable the identification of organisms that often evade traditional detection methods, such as microscopy, due to the limit of the taxonomic resolution.

The selection of the V4 region of the 18S rDNA and specific primers has resulted in a high level of concordance between metabarcoding and traditional microscopy in our coastal samples.

Some morphospecies were assigned to known species but the molecular barcodes did not show a 100% correspondence with the available sequences, only a close identity (95–98%), suggesting unknown (pseudo)cryptic diversity.

A better agreement between the two techniques validates the efficacy of metabarcoding as a complementary method to traditional microscopy, enhancing our ability to accurately characterize phytoplankton diversity.

6.5.6 References

- Fritz, L. & Triemer, R.E.L.B. (1985) 'A rapid simple technique utilizing calcofluor white M2R for the visualization of dinoflagellate thecal plates.', *Journal of Phycology*, 21, pp. 662–664.
- Geisen, S., Vaulot, D., Mahé, F., Lara, E., de Vargas, C. & Bass, D., (2019) 'A user guide to environmental protistology: primers, metabarcoding, sequencing, and analyses', *bioRxiv*, (March 2024), p. 850610. Available at: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/850610v1%0Ahttps://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/850610v1.abstract>
- Guillou, L. Bachar D, Audic S, Bass D, Berney C, Bittner L, Boutte C, Burgaud G, de Vargas C, Decelle J, Del Campo J, Dolan JR, Dunthorn M, Edvardsen B, Holzmann M, Kooistra WH, Lara E, Le Bescot N, Logares R, Mahé F, Massana R, Montresor M, Morard R, Not F, Pawlowski J, Probert I, Sauvadet AL, Siano R, Stoeck T, Vaulot D, Zimmermann P, & Christen R. (2013) 'The Protist Ribosomal Reference database (PR2): a catalog of unicellular eukaryote Small Sub-Unit rRNA sequences with curated taxonomy', *Nucleic Acids Research*, 41(D1), pp. D597–D604. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gks1160>
- Liu, Q., Zhang, Y., Wu, H., Liu, F., Peng, W., Zhang, X., Chang, F., Xie, P., & Zhang, H. (2020) 'A review and perspective of eDNA application to eutrophication and HAB control in freshwater and marine ecosystems', *Microorganisms*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8030417>
- Marinichel, N., Marchesini, A., Nardi, D., Girardi, Casabianca, S., Vernesi, C., & Penna, V., (2023) 'Mock community experiments can inform on the reliability of eDNA metabarcoding data: a case study on marine phytoplankton', *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), pp. 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-47462-5>
- Martin, M. (2011) 'Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads', *EMBnet journal*, 17(1), pp. 10–12.

- McMurdie, P.J. & Holmes, S. (2013) 'phyloseq: An R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data', *PLOS ONE*, 8(4), p. e61217. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0061217>
- Medinger, R., Nolte, V., Pandey, R.V., Jost, S., Ottenwalder, B., Schlotterer, C., & Boenigk, J., (2010) 'Diversity in a hidden world: Potential and limitation of next-generation sequencing for surveys of molecular diversity of eukaryotic microorganisms', *Molecular Ecology*, 19(SUPPL. 1), pp. 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2009.04478.x>
- Pawlowski, J., Lejzerowicz, F., Apotheloz-Perret-Gentil, L., Visco, J., & Esling, P., (2016) 'Protist metabarcoding and environmental biomonitoring: Time for change', *European Journal of Protistology*, 55, pp. 12–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejop.2016.02.003>
- Piredda, R., Tomasino, M. P., D'Erchia, A. M., Manzari, C., Pesole, G., Montresor, M., Kooistra, W.H. C.F., Sarno, D., & Zingone, A., (2017) 'Diversity and temporal patterns of planktonic protist assemblages at a Mediterranean Long Term Ecological Research site', *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 93(1), pp. 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiw200>
- R Core Team (2013) 'R: A language and environment for statistical computing'. Available at: <http://www.r-project.org/>.
- Rognes, T., Flouri, T., Nichols, B., Quince, C., & Mahe, F., (2016) 'VSEARCH: a versatile open source tool for metagenomics', *PeerJ*, 4, p. e2584. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2584>
- de Vargas, C., Audic, S., Henry, N., Decelle, J., Mahe, F., Logares R., Lara, E., Berney, C., Le Bescot, N., Probert, I., Carmichael, M., Poulain, J., Romac, S., Colin, S., Aury, J.M., Bittner, L., Chaffron, S., Dunthorn, M., Engelen, S., Flegontova, O., Guidi, L., Horak, A., Jaillon, O., Lima-Mendez, G., Lukeš, J., Malviya, S., Morard, R., Mulo, M., Scalco, E., Siano, R., Vincent, F., Zingone, A., Dimier, C., Picheral, M., Searson, S., Kandels-Lewis, S; Tara Oceans Coordinators; Acinas SG, Bork P, Bowler C, Gorsky G, Grimsley N, Hingamp P, Iudicone D, Not F, Ogata H, Pesant S, Raes J, Sieracki ME, Speich S, Stemmann L, Sunagawa S, Weissenbach J, Wincker P, Karsenti E. (2015) 'Eukaryotic plankton diversity in the sunlit ocean', 348(6237), pp. 1–11.
- Wickham, H. (2016) *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*.

6.6 Case study 13: Metabarcoding of eDNA to assess NIS and hazardous phytoplankton in three Italian ports

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6.6.1 Introduction

Environmental DNA metabarcoding is widely used for marine biodiversity identification of both planktonic and benthic organisms (Pawlowski et al., 2022; Yang and Zhang, 2020) and can also be used to track the presence of NIS (Duarte et al., 2021; Knudsen et al., 2022; Maggio et al., 2023) in samples collected from hard natural and artificial substrates (e.g. settlement plates) and in samples of seawater (Duarte et al., 2021). NIS identification in soft sediments have received less attention (Gollasch et al., 2019) even though can provide an early detection for a wide range of taxa particularly resting stages of planktonic organisms, which can settle to sea floor after ballast water discharge (Holman et al., 2019; Shaw et al., 2019). Thus, the integration of metabarcoding analysis of eDNA from seawater and sediment samples may provide a more comprehensive view of the NIS, including benthic species that have planktonic larval stages (Couton et al., 2019). Here, we used eDNA metabarcoding targeting multiple molecular markers in combination with different genetic databases to improve NIS identification in seawater and sediment samples collected in national ports with international trade surveyed by the Italian Environmental Protection Agencies under the MSFD. We compared eDNA results with those obtained by classical morphological approaches to assess their effectiveness for non-indigenous and hazardous species detection, functional to national monitoring programmes of NIS and to early warning system for invasive and hazardous species. Main results obtained from this study are published in Varrella et al. (2025).

6.6.2 Methods

Sampling method

Environmental DNA sampling was carried out in three Italian ports located respectively in the three Italian subregions defined by the MSFD: the port of Trieste in the Adriatic Sea, the port of Taranto in the Ionian and Central Mediterranean Sea and the port of Civitavecchia in the Western Mediterranean Sea (Figure 6.5.1). All samples were collected in the same stations where traditional sampling for benthos, phytoplankton and zooplankton is routinely carried out for Descriptor 2 implementation by the National System for Environmental Protection (SNPA). The stations were identified as mostly influenced by maritime pathways and transportation routes and/or ballast water discharge.

Figure 6.6.1. Sampling locations at three major ports in the Mediterranean Sea: the port of Trieste in the Adriatic Sea, Taranto port located in the Ionian Sea and Civitavecchia port in the Tyrrhenian Sea.

A pre-survey was conducted in Trieste port in July 2021 to test the most appropriate methodology, such as optimal sample volume of vacuum-filtered seawater (1L, 2L, 3L) and filter's typologies of 0.45 μm pore size: mixed cellulose ester (MCE), Polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF), Polyethersulfone (PES).

Water and sediment sampling were carried out in late winter (March), summer (July), and autumn (October) 2022 in all ports. A total of 20 L of seawater for each station was collected through two independent deployments of 5 L Niskin bottles carried out at the surface (at ca. 1 m depth) and bottom (ranging from 12 to 20 m depth) of the water column. Aliquots of 2 L of seawater were vacuum-filtered with sterile apparatus using mixed cellulose ester membranes (MCE, 0.45 μm pore size, 47 mm diameter, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until DNA extraction. Three independent sediment samples were collected at each site by Van Veen grab. Aliquots of sediment obtained from the surface layer were kept at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until DNA extraction. Aliquots of sediment obtained from the surface layer were kept at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until DNA extraction.

Environmental DNA extraction, amplification and sequencing

Environmental DNA (eDNA) was extracted from MCE filters using a Dneasy PowerWater kit (QIAGEN©, Düsseldorf, Germany) and from 10 g of sediments (wet weight) using a Dneasy PowerMax Soil kit (QIAGEN©, Düsseldorf, Germany). The concentration of DNA was determined by absorbance at 260 nm and the purity by 260/280 and 260/230 nm ratios, using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (ND-1000 UV-vis Spectrophotometer; NanoDrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA). To identify a large number of marine species belonging to different phyla, five different genetic markers were selected for metabarcoding: 3 different regions of the ribosomal 18S rRNA gene (V4, V9, and V7), a region of the mitochondrial Cytochrome Oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene and the Ribulose Bisphosphate Carboxylase gene (rbcl). For the amplification of the COI gene two primer sets were used: mICOLintF

– jgHCO2198 for eDNA extracted from filters, whereas mlCOLintF – dgHCO2198 for eDNA extracted from sediments (Leray et al., 2013), for the amplification of V9 region of 18S rRNA (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2009), for the amplification of V4 region (Piredda et al., 2018), for the V7 region (Guardiola et al., 2015) and for *rbcl* (Little, 2014)

Two mock communities (one for phytoplankton and one for benthic metazoan taxa) were used as a positive control to validate the taxonomic identification of eDNA by bioinformatics.

DNA was isolated from species using Dneasy Blood & Tissue Kit (QIAGEN[®], Düsseldorf, Germany). DNA from algal cultures was extracted with Dneasy PowerSoil Pro (QIAGEN[®], Düsseldorf, Germany). The DNA of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was purchased from (Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany). DNA isolated from different taxa was pooled in equal amounts in each sample before library preparation. Mock DNA, as well as DNA extracted from sediment and seawater samples, were sent to Edmund Mach Foundation (FEM, Trento, Italy) for amplicon library preparations and sequencing. Illumina sequencings MiSeq 2 x 300bp of gene libraries were carried out on different runs.

Bioinformatic analyses

Raw sequences resulting from the metabarcoding with 18S rRNA V4, V7, V9, *COI* and *rbcl* markers were processed through QIIME2 (Bolyen et al., 2019). Primer sequences were removed using Cutadapt v4.5 with a maximum error rate of 0.1% (Martin, 2011). Sequences were then merged with a minimum overlap of 12 nucleotides, and errors were corrected with DADA2 v1.20 for obtaining amplicon sequence variants (ASVs), excluding singletons (Callahan et al., 2016). Taxonomic assignments were performed using VSEARCH v2.21.2 (Rognes et al., 2016). *COI* sequences were aligned against four different databases: National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI; Sayers et al., 2022), MIDORI2 (Leray et al., 2022), Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD; Ratnasingham and Hebert, 2007), MetaZooGene Atlas and Database (MGZDB; Bucklin et al., 2021), whereas 18S rRNA sequences were aligned against Protist Ribosomal Reference (PR2; Guillou et al., 2013) and SILVA (Quast et al., 2012).

For the taxonomic assignment of ASVs five different percentage values of sequence similarity were used (ranging from 80% to 99%) since optimal thresholds can vary depending on the marker used (Bonin et al., 2023; Hleap et al., 2021). The most accurate percentage values of sequence similarity of each genetic marker were chosen to calculate the best metrics for benchmarking (Hleap et al., 2021) resulting from sequences of mock communities clustered at different similarity levels (Ershova et al., 2023).

To account for contamination in the field and laboratory, a small number of ASVs present in the negative controls from all subsequent datasets were excluded. Sequences belonging to terrestrial species were removed through the package WoRMS (Ahyong et al., 2024) in R studio (Team, 2021), retaining only the sequences of species present in the World Register of Marine Species database. Pandas and NumPy libraries in a Python script were used to categorize all obtained species as native or non-indigenous and to perform cross-checks between a list of identified species and databases (McKinney, 2012). List of Mediterranean NIS was retrieved from Galanidi et al. (2023) whereas the list of hazardous phytoplankton species was retrieved from IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Micro Algae (Lundholm et al., 2009).

6.6.3 Results

Sequencing results and taxonomic assignment

Mock community analyses by metabarcoding allowed the correct identification of 9 out of 12 taxa (Varrella et al., 2025).

The eDNA metabarcoding conducted in the pre-survey at the Trieste port using the different molecular markers allowed us to define the most appropriate combination of filter type and water volume for detecting the highest number of species and NIS (Varrella et al., 2025).

MiSeq runs carried out on eDNA from seawater and sediment samples collected in the three ports in the three sampling periods over 2022 resulted in a total of ~ 90 million raw paired reads, reduced to ~ 72 million after removal of the low-quality sequences, aligning paired ends for all markers. After bioinformatic processing of raw reads, the highest number of ASVs was observed through 18S V4 rRNA sequencing (48,666 ASVs), while the lowest number was observed with the rbcL marker (4,843 ASVs). Rarefaction curves indicate that the sequencing depth was sufficient to capture the ASV diversity across all three ports over the three sampling periods.

Only 1.3 % of the total number of ASVs identified through eDNA metabarcoding were assigned at the species level. The highest number of species was obtained using 18S rRNA V9 (686 species), followed by 18S rRNA V4 (568), 18S rRNA V7 (482), COI (397) and rbcL (15). Exclusive genetic signatures belonging to different species were identified using the different molecular markers (COI, three regions of 18S rRNA, and rbcL) and only one ASV classified at the species level was consistently identified by all genetic markers. Clustering ASVs with different genetic databases greatly improved the power of detection of eDNA metabarcoding. Each database allowed the identification of unique species, and particularly, when MIDORI2 was used, the highest number of exclusive species (108) was

detected compared to the other COI databases (NCBI, MGZDB and BOLD). For 18S V4, V7, and V9, ASVs classified at species level were compared between the two data sets based on PR2 and SILVA database. On average, only 21 % of the identified species by the different 18S rRNA markers was shared between the two databases.

Comparison between eDNA metabarcoding and classical taxonomic approach for species identification

The eDNA metabarcoding analysis carried out on seawater and sediment samples collected in the three ports over the three sampling periods of 2022 allowed the identification of 1,484 species belonging to 48 phyla. The greatest number of species of the kingdom Animalia belong to the phyla Annelida (154 species), Mollusca (130), and Arthropoda (113). Regarding the chromists, the most abundant species found belong to the phylum Myxozoa (160 species), followed by Bacillariophyta (153) and Ciliophora (121). The kingdom Plantae is mainly represented by species belonging to the phyla Rhodophyta (56 species) and Chlorophyta (52 species).

Figure 6.6.2. Number of species belonging to the different phyla identified through eDNA metabarcoding with different genetic markers in different ports over the three sampling periods (spring, summer, and autumn 2022) from Varrella et al. (2025).

The analysis conducted using the classical taxonomic approach on the soft and hard bottom and seawater samples collected in the three ports during the three sampling periods allowed the identification, of 752 species, belonging to 23 phyla. A total of 560 species were identified only through morphological approaches, of which 253 species were not found in reference sequence databases. In all sampling periods and ports, the number of species identified by eDNA metabarcoding was higher than those determined by classical taxonomic approach. Overall, 1,292 species of unicellular and multicellular organisms belonging to 47 phyla were exclusively identified through eDNA metabarcoding. Only 192 species belonging to 15 phyla were detected by both molecular and morphological approaches.

The eDNA metabarcoding allowed the identification of genetic signature belonging to 31 NIS reported in the Mediterranean Sea (Galanidi et al., 2023). Among these species 22 were identified by COI, 17 by 18S and none by rbcL. Besides, 25 species were detected in seawater and 14 in sediment sample. The 31 NIS detected through molecular approach mainly belong to the Phyla: Rhodophyta (7 species), Chordata (5) and Mollusca (5). With the morphology-based approach, 21 NIS mainly belonging to Arthropoda (8), and Annelida (7) were detected. Taxonomic analyses allowed the identification of 5 NIS, which have not been found in all genetic databases used. Overall, only 4 NIS were detected with both molecular and morphological approaches. Finally, many species detected with metabarcoding (≈ 300) have never been reported in the Mediterranean Sea representing therefore potential new introduction for Mediterranean basin.

Table 6.6.1. Comparison between NIS identified by eDNA metabarcoding with different genetic markers and those morphologically detected in the ports of Trieste (TR), Taranto (TA) and Civitavecchia (CI) and reported in Italian marine waters (IT) modified from Varrella et al. (2025). The different sampling periods and environmental matrices (W = water and S = sediment) are shown. * Species listed in the Global Invasive Species Database (GISD)

Species	eDNA metabarcoding								Morphology-based approach				
	Genetic markers				Sampling campaigns			Matrix		CI	TA	TR	IT
	COI	18S V4	18S V7	18S V9	March	July	October	W	S				
<i>Acanthosiphonia echinata</i>				•		TA	TA		•				•
<i>Aglaothamnion feldmanniae</i>		•	•				CI		•				•
<i>Aidanosagitta neglecta</i>				•		TA	CI/TA/TR	•					
<i>Amathia verticillata</i>	•		•			TR		•					•
<i>Asparagopsis taxiformis</i>	•					CI	CI	•	•				•
<i>Aurelia solida</i>	•					TR			•				•
<i>Balanus trigonus</i>	•					CI	TR	•		•		•	•
<i>Boccardia proboscidea</i>	•	•				TR	TR	•	•				

<i>Botrylloides niger</i>	•						CI	•						•
<i>Clytia linearis</i>	•	•						CI	•					•
<i>Dasysiphonia japonica</i>	•						CI			•				•
<i>Herdmania momus</i>				•			TA		•					
<i>Hydroides elegans</i>	•	•	•		TA/TR	CI/TR	CI/TA/TR	•		•	•	•	•	•
<i>Kapraunia schneideri</i>		•			TA		CI	•	•					•
<i>Magallana gigas</i>	•		•				TR	TR	•	•				•
<i>Melibe viridis</i>	•							TA	•					•
<i>Mercenaria mercenaria</i>				•	TA	TA	CI/TA	•	•					•
<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi*</i>	•				TR		TR	•					•	•
<i>Oithona davisae</i>	•	•	•	•	CI/TA	TA/TR	CI/TA/TR	•	•					•
<i>Petricolaria pholadiformis</i>		•		•			CI/TA/TR	CI	•					
<i>Phallusia nigra</i>			•	•			CI/TR	CI/TR	•	•				
<i>Polyandrocarpa zorritensis</i>	•				TA			TA	•	•				•
<i>Polydora cornuta</i>	•						TR			•				•
<i>Pseudodiaptomus marinus</i>	•	•	•		TR	CI/TR	CI/TA/TR	•		•		•	•	•
<i>Pseudopolydora paucibranchiata</i>	•	•	•				TR		•					•
<i>Pyropia koreana</i>	•				TA				•					•
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi*</i>	•						TR		•					•
<i>Saccharina japonica</i>				•	CI				•					•
<i>Spermothamnion cymosum</i>	•						CI			•				•
<i>Styela plicata*</i>	•				TA	TR	TR	•						•
<i>Thecacera pennigera</i>	•							CI	•					•

Regarding phytoplankton species the eDNA metabarcoding detected 44 hazardous species out of a total of 173, whereas the morphological based approach identified 20 hazardous species out of a total of 252. The number of species identified with both approaches are shown in [Figure 6.6.3a](#) and [Figure 6.6.3b](#)

Fig 6.6.3. Diagram of Venn showing the number of species detected with eDNA metabarcoding (Set A) and through morphological approach (Set B): (a) Hazardous phytoplankton species (b) Phytoplankton species

6.6.4 Discussion

The present study highlights the usefulness of applying the multi-marker metabarcoding approach for the detection of a greater number of phyla and taxa, including non-indigenous and hazardous species, compared to classical taxonomic identifications. On the other hand, the eDNA metabarcoding did not allow the detection of all species that were identified through the taxonomic approach, and only a minor portion (5.5 %) was shared between the two approaches. The limited overlap between the two approaches can be due to the difficulties in identifying morphologically taxa to the species level especially in the early stages, the lack of specialized taxonomists for certain biological components and the presence of undescribed or cryptic species, but also to the limits associated with eDNA metabarcoding (van der Loos and Nijland, 2021). Despite the advantage of using eDNA metabarcoding for the identification of several species, some important caveats remain, especially regarding variable persistence of eDNA in the environment that may lead to the inaccurate representation of living organisms at sampling time (false positives) and to the incompleteness of comprehensive and curated reference databases for taxonomic assignments (false negatives). Filling the gaps in reference libraries is essential for rigorous species identifications through eDNA metabarcoding, thus future efforts must be devoted to improving barcode records of marine species, in particular of those belonging to taxonomic groups scarcely represented in the databases (e.g. marine molluscs, ascidians; Duarte, 2020; Weigand et al., 2019). Furthermore, PCR amplification inefficiencies may also lead to the non-detection of certain taxa (van der Loos and Nijland, 2021), as also suggested by our metabarcoding analyses of the mock community. These limitations become more pronounced when identification at species level is required as it is the case for NIS detection.

Regarding false positives, the use of environmental RNA-derived amplicons can represent a further step forward for the molecular identification of NIS (Scriver et al., 2024). The RNA is associated to the metabolic activities of the organisms and has not a long persistence in water, it can therefore be better associated to the presence of the live organism. This is an important aspect when sampling is conducted in areas like ports or marinas where lots of biological material, including residual DNA from dead organisms, may be discharged with ballast or bilge water (Xue et al., 2024).

Based on our results the eDNA metabarcoding resulted to be a powerful methodology for early detection of non-indigenous and hazardous species. The species *Phallusia nigra* for example, a new NIS for the Italian Seas, was detected first with eDNA metabarcoding within this study and then found as live organism several months after (Balistreri pers. Comm.).

Given the considerations outlined the eDNA metabarcoding can be effectively used as an alert species tool for monitoring operators and as a complementary tool within monitoring programmes to capture a larger portion of biodiversity.

6.6.5 References

- Ahyong, S., Boyko, C.B., Bailly, N., Bernot, J., Bieler, R., Brandão, S.N., Daly, M., De Grave, S., et al., (2024). World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS).
- Amaral-Zettler, L.A., McCliment, E.A., Ducklow, H.W., & Huse, S.M., (2009). A Method for Studying Protistan Diversity Using Massively Parallel Sequencing of V9 Hypervariable Regions of Small-Subunit Ribosomal RNA Genes. *PloS One* 4, e6372. <https://doi.org/10.1371/annotation/50c43133-0df5-4b8b-8975-8cc37d4f2f26>
- Bolyen, E., Rideout, J.R., Dillon, M.R., Bokulich, N.A., Abnet, C.C., Al-Ghalith, G.A., Alexander, H., Alm, E.J., Arumugam, M., et al., (2019). Reproducible, interactive, scalable and extensible microbiome data science using QIIME 2. *Nat. Biotech.* 37, 852–857. doi.org/10.1038/s41587-019-0209-9
- Bonin, A., Guerrieri, A., & Ficetola, G.F., (2023). Optimal sequence similarity thresholds for clustering of molecular operational taxonomic units in DNA metabarcoding studies. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* 23, 368–381. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13709>
- Bucklin, A., Peijnenburg, K.T.C.A., Kosobokova, K.N., O'Brien, T.D., Blanco-Bercial, L., Cornils, A., Falkenhaus, T., Hopcroft, R.R., Hosia, A., Laakmann, S., Li, C., Martell, L., Questel, J.M., Wall-Palmer, D., Wang, M., Wiebe, P.H., Weydmann-Zwolicka, A., (2021). Toward a global reference database of COI barcodes for marine zooplankton. *Mar. Biol.* 168, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-021-03887-y>
- Callahan, B.J., McMurdie, P.J., Rosen, M.J., Han, A.W., Johnson, A.J.A., & Holmes, S.P., (2016). DADA2: High-resolution sample inference from Illumina amplicon data. *Nat. Methods* 13, 581–583. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3869>
- Couton, M., Comtet, T., Le Cam, S., Corre, E., & Viard, F., (2019). Metabarcoding on planktonic larval stages: an efficient approach for detecting and investigating life cycle dynamics of benthic aliens. *Manag. Biol. Invasions* 10, 657–689. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2019.10.4.06>
- Duarte, S., Vieira, P.E., & Costa, F.O., (2020). Assessment of species gaps in DNA barcode libraries of nonindigenous species (NIS) occurring in European coastal regions. *Metabarcoding and Metagenomics* 4, 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mbmg.4.55162>
- Duarte, S., Vieira, P.E., Lavrador, A.S., & Costa, F.O., (2021). Status and prospects of marine NIS detection and monitoring through IDNA metabarcoding. *Sci. Total Environ.* 751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141729>
- Ershova, E.A., Wangensteen, O.S., & Falkenhaus, T., (2023). Mock samples resolve biases in diversity estimates and quantitative interpretation of zooplankton metabarcoding data. *Mar. Biodivers.* 53, 66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-023-01372-x>
- Galanidi, M.; Aissi, M.; Ali, M.; Bakalem, A.; Bariche, M.; Bartolo, A.G.; Bazairi, H.; Beqiraj, S.; Bilecenoglu, M.; Bitar, G.; Bugeja M., Carbonell Quetglas A., Castriota L., Chalabi A., Çınar M.E., Dragičević B., Dulčić J., El-Hawet A.E.A., Farrag M.M.S., Evans J., Galil B., Guerin L., Hyams-Kaphzan O., Kapedani R., Kamberi E., Livi S., Mačić V., Masse C., ... Zenetos A. (2023). Validated Inventories of Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) for the Mediterranean Sea as Tools for Regional Policy and Patterns of NIS Spread. *Diversity* 15, 962. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15090962>

- Gollasch, S., Hewitt, C.L., Bailey, S., & David, M., (2019). Introductions and transfers of species by ballast water in the Adriatic Sea. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 147, 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.08.054>
- Guardiola, M., Uriz, M.J., Taberlet, P., Coissac, E., Wangensteen, O.S., & Turon, X., (2015). Deep-sea, deep-sequencing: Metabarcoding extracellular DNA from sediments of marine canyons. *PLoS One* 10, e0139633. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139633>
- Guillou, L., Bachar, D., Audic, S., Bass, D., Berney, C., Bittner, L., Boutte, C., Burgaud, G., De Vargas, C., Decelle, J., Del Campo, J., Dolan, J.R., Dunthorn, M., Edvardsen, B., Holzmann, M., Kooistra, W.H.C.F., Lara, E., Le Bescot, N., Logares, R., Mahé, F., Massana, R., Montresor, M., Morard, R., Not, F., Pawlowski, J., Probert, I., ... Zimmermann, P., & Christen, R., (2013). The Protist Ribosomal Reference database (PR2): A catalog of unicellular eukaryote Small Sub-Unit rRNA sequences with curated taxonomy. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 41. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gks1160>
- Hleap, J.S., Littlefair, J.E., Steinke, D., Hebert, P.D.N., & Cristescu, M.E., (2021). Assessment of current taxonomic assignment strategies for metabarcoding eukaryotes. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* 21. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13407>
- Holman, L.E., de Bruyn, M., Creer, S., Carvalho, G., Robidart, J., & Rius, M., (2019). Detection of introduced and resident marine species using environmental DNA metabarcoding of sediment and water. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47899-7>
- Knudsen, S.W., Hesselsøe, M., Thaulow, J., Agersnap, S., Hansen, B.K., Jacobsen, M.W., Bekkevold, D., Jensen, S.K.S., Møller, P.R., & Andersen, J.H., (2022). Monitoring of environmental DNA from nonindigenous species of algae, dinoflagellates and animals in the North East Atlantic. *Sci. Total Environ.* 821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153093>
- Leray, M., Knowlton, N., & Machida, R.J., (2022). MIDORI2: A collection of quality controlled, preformatted, and regularly updated reference databases for taxonomic assignment of eukaryotic mitochondrial sequences. *Environ. DNA* 4. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.303>
- Leray, M., Yang, J.Y., Meyer, C.P., Mills, S.C., Agudelo, N., Ranwez, V., Boehm, J.T., & Machida, R.J., (2013). A new versatile primer set targeting a short fragment of the mitochondrial COI region for metabarcoding metazoan diversity: application for characterizing coral reef fish gut contents. *Front. Zool.* 10, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-10-34>
- Little, D.P., (2014). A DNA mini-barcode for land plants. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* 14, 437–446. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12194>
- Lundholm, N., Bernard, C., Churro, C., Escalera, L., Hoppenrath, M., Iwataki, M., Larsen, J., Mertens, K., Moestrup, Ø., Murray, S., Salas, R., Tillmann, U., & Zingone, A., (Eds) (2009 onwards). IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Micro Algae. Accessed at <https://www.marinespecies.org/hab> on 2025-06-04. <https://doi.org/10.14284/362>
- Maggio, T., Cattapan, F., Falautano, M., Julian, D., Malinverni, R., Poloni, E., Sanseverino, W., Todesco, S., & Castriota, L., (2023). eDNA Metabarcoding Analysis as Tool to Assess the Presence of Non-Indigenous Species (NIS): A Case Study in the Bilge Water. *Diversity* 2023, Vol. 15, Page 1117 15, 1117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/D15111117>
- Martin, M., (2011). Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads. *Embnet J* 17, 10. <https://doi.org/10.14806/ej.17.1.200>
- McKinney, W., (2012). *Python for Data Analysis: Data Wrangling with Pandas, NumPy, and Ipython*. “O’Reilly Media, Inc.”.

- Pawlowski, J., Bruce, K., Panksep, K., Aguirre, F.I., Amalfitano, S., Apothéloz-Perret- Gentil, L., Baussant, T., Bouchez, A., Carugati, L., Cermakova, K., Cordier, T., Corinaldesi, C., Costa, F.O., Danovaro, R., Dell'Anno, A., Duarte, S., Eisendle, U., Ferrari, B.J.D., Frontalini, F., ... & Fazi, S., (2022). Environmental DNA metabarcoding for benthic monitoring: A review of sediment sampling and DNA extraction methods. *Sci. Total Environ.* 818, 151783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151783>
- Piredda, R., Claverie, J.M., Decelle, J., de Vargas, C., Dunthorn, M., Edvardsen, B., Eikrem, W., Forster, D., Kooistra, W.H.C.F., Logares, R., Massana, R., Montresor, M., Not, F., Ogata, H., Pawlowski, J., Romac, S., Sarno, D., Stoeck, T., & Zingone, A., (2018). Diatom diversity through HTS-metabarcoding in coastal European seas. *Sci. Rep.* 8. doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-36345-9
- Quast, C., Pruesse, E., Yilmaz, P., Gerken, J., Schweer, T., Yarza, P., Peplies, J., & Glöckner, F.O., (2012). The SILVA ribosomal RNA gene database project: improved data processing and web-based tools. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 41, D590–D596. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gks1219>
- Ratnasingham, S., Hebert, P.D.N., 2007. Bold: The Barcode of Life Data System www.barcodinglife.org. *Mol. Ecol. Notes* 7, 355–364. doi.org/10.1111/J.1471-8286.2007.01678.X
- Rognes, T., Flouri, T., Nichols, B., Quince, C., & Mahé, F., (2016). VSEARCH: A versatile open source tool for metagenomics. *PeerJ* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2584>
- Sayers, E.W., Bolton, E.E., Brister, J.R., Canese, K., Chan, J., Comeau, D.C., Connor, R., Funk, K., Kelly, C., Kim, S., Madej, T., Marchler-Bauer, A., Lanczycki, C., Lathrop, S., Lu, Z., Thibaud-Nissen, F., Murphy, T., Phan, L., Skripchenko, Y.,, & Sherry, S.T., (2022). Database resources of the national center for biotechnology information. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 50. doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab112
- Scriver, M., von Ammon, U., Pochon, X., Arranz, V., Stanton, J.A.L., Gemmell, N.J., & Zaiko, A., (2024). Environmental DNA–RNA dynamics provide insights for effective monitoring of marine invasive species. *Environ. DNA* 6 (2), e531. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.531>
- Shaw, J.L.A., Weyrich, L.S., Hallegraeff, G., & Cooper, A., (2019). Retrospective eDNA assessment of potentially harmful algae in historical ship ballast tank and marine port sediments. *Mol. Ecol.* 28, 2476–2485. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.15055>
- Team, Rs., (2021). Rstudio: integrated development for R. Rstudio, PBC, Boston, MA. 2020
- van der Loos, L.M., & Nijland, R., (2021). Biases in bulk: DNA metabarcoding of marine communities and the methodology involved. *Mol. Ecol.* 30, 3270–3288. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.15592>
- Varrella S., Livi S., Corinaldesi C., Castriota L., Maggio T., Vivona P., Pindo M., Faba S., Danovaro R., & Dell'Anno A. (2025). A comprehensive assessment of non-indigenous species requires the combination of multi-marker eDNA metabarcoding with classical taxonomic identification. *Environmental International* 199, 109489
- Weigand, H., Beermann, A.J., Čiampor, F., Costa, F.O., Csabai, Z., Duarte, S., Geiger, M. F., Grabowski, M., Rimet, F., Rulik, B., Strand, M., Szucsich, N., Weigand, A.M., Willassen, E., Wyler, S.A., Bouchez, A., Borja, A., Čiamporová-Zaťovičová, Z.,...Ekrem, T., (2019). DNA barcode reference libraries for the monitoring of aquatic biota in Europe: Gap-analysis and recommendations for future work. *Sci. Total Environ.* 678, 499–524. doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.04.247
- Yang, J., Zhang, X., 2020. eDNA metabarcoding in zooplankton improves the ecological status assessment of aquatic ecosystems. *Environ. Int.* 134, 105230. [10.1016/j.envint.2019.105230](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.105230)
- Xue Z, Tian W, Han Y, Li S, Guo J, He H, Yu P, Zhang W., 2024. Environmental RNA metabarcoding for ballast water microbial diversity: Minimizing false positives. *Sci Total Environ.* 2024, 10; 955: 176902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176902>

7. CIMPAL for mapping cumulative impacts of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms

7.1 Introduction

Biological invasions and bloom events are increasingly recognized as major drivers of ecological degradation and socio-economic disruption in marine systems. In the Mediterranean Sea—characterized by exceptional biodiversity and high anthropogenic pressure—the spread of non-indigenous species (NIS), harmful algal blooms (HABs), and jellyfish outbreaks challenge conservation efforts and the sustainable delivery of ecosystem services. To support spatial planning and policy implementation, this chapter presents the development and application of the CIMPAL (Cumulative IMPacts of ALiens) index, a tool designed to map and assess cumulative ecological impacts across scales.

In the framework of this deliverable, CIMPAL was extended in several innovative directions: (1) to quantify cumulative pressures not only from NIS, but also from HABs and jellyfish blooms, which can cause serious ecological and economic damage; (2) through CIMPAL+, which allows for the inclusion of positive ecological or socio-economic contributions by alien species, providing a more nuanced impact assessment; and (3) through CIMPAL-ES, which is introduced to assess positive and negative cumulative impacts of IAS on ecosystem services.

The chapter includes multiple case studies demonstrating these tools' applications in diverse subregions of the Mediterranean, the Black Sea and the Baltic, as well as a pan-European application to evaluate the cumulative impacts of NIS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms. These examples highlight the ability of the CIMPAL family of indices to reveal impact hotspots, prioritize impactful species, guide national reporting obligations under EU directives and Regional Conventions, and prioritize management responses in data-limited contexts.

7.2 Case study 14: Expansion of CIMPAL to account for the impacts of HABs and jellyfish blooms

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7.2.1 Introduction

Alien species are organisms that have been intentionally or unintentionally introduced beyond their native geographic range due to human activities. Their introduction to new ecosystems can cause significant alterations to the structure of native communities and ecosystem functioning (Katsanevakis et al., 2014a; Howard et al., 2019), often leading to a dramatic decline in native biodiversity (Doherty et al., 2016; García-Gómez et al., 2020; Tsirintanis et al., 2022) and major losses in ecosystem services (Katsanevakis et al., 2014b; Castro-Díez et al., 2019). Human activities have led to the introduction of over 37,000 alien species across various taxonomic groups and geographic regions worldwide; the rate of new introductions is currently around 200 species per year, with an unprecedented increase in the spread of alien species (Roy et al., 2023). When alien species negatively impact their new ecosystems, they are classified as invasive alien species (IAS) (CBD, 2008). IAS cause significant and often irreversible changes to biodiversity and ecosystems, contributing to 60% of recorded global extinctions: they have major impacts such as biotic homogenization and alterations in ecosystems properties, and their impact is predicted to continue rising in the future (Roy et al., 2023).

Jellyfish blooms are defined as sudden increases in gelatinous zooplankton populations from various taxonomic groups, including Cnidaria (Hydrozoa, Scyphozoa, and Cubozoa), Chordata (Tunicata), and Ctenophora (Boero, 2013). Jellyfish populations naturally fluctuate, experiencing periodic surges, and are thus considered normal phenomena (Boero, 2013). However, numerous studies have identified various anthropogenic factors contributing to jellyfish bloom outbreaks (Sagarminaga et al., 2024), such as eutrophication (Richardson et al., 2009), overfishing (Boero, 2013), climate change (Boero et al., 2016), and the introduction of alien species (Qu et al., 2014). Additionally, jellyfish densities are influenced by environmental factors, which vary by species, but are particularly affected by temperature (Qu et al., 2014), and secondarily by light, salinity, nutrient availability (Graham et al., 2001; Purcell, 2005), currents, pressure, and turbulence (Graham et al., 2001). These blooms have significant consequences for marine ecosystems and coastal human activities, impacting areas from localized sites to extensive regions (Sagarminaga et al., 2024). The adverse effects on biodiversity (e.g., Helmholz et al., 2010; Dinasquet et al., 2012; Báez et al., 2022; Sagarminaga et al., 2024), fisheries and aquaculture (e.g., Doyle et al., 2008; Quiñones et al., 2013; Sagarminaga et al., 2024), tourism (Canepa

et al., 2014; Ghermandi et al., 2015) and human health (Cegolon et al., 2013; De Donno et al., 2014) are well-documented. The increasing frequency of jellyfish blooms in recent decades across various regions (Boero et al., 2008) highlights the urgent need for management strategies to mitigate their ecological and socio-economic impacts (Sagarminaga et al., 2024).

HABs are events of proliferation of specific microalgal and macroalgal species, which result in ecological, social, economic, and health-related impacts (Sagarminaga et al., 2023). These blooms arise from specific physical, biological, and chemical conditions, and can be exacerbated by human activities (West et al., 2021). The impacts of HABs are diverse. Non-toxic algal blooms can disrupt ecosystems by reducing light penetration and depleting oxygen during decay, leading to significant mortalities (Anderson, 2009). Additional harms include mechanical damage, acting as potential vectors for diseases, and deteriorating water quality (Landsberg, 2002). When organisms ingest toxic phytoplankton, toxins can accumulate in their tissues to levels that pose substantial health risks to humans and other consumers, resulting in various poisoning syndromes. Furthermore, poisoning can occur when phytoplankton release toxins and other compounds into the water (Anderson, 2009). HABs can also lead to significant economic losses, including monitoring expenses, closures of fisheries, fish and shellfish mortalities, reduced seafood sales, impacts on tourism, and medical treatment for affected populations (Anderson, 2009). Although HABs are widely believed to be increasing in frequency and severity, further analysis is required to confirm a global upward trend (Hallegraeff et al., 2021). However, the expansion of aquaculture operations is expected to increase the frequency and severity of HABs in certain regions. These impacts will be particularly pronounced in developing areas already struggling with significant HAB challenges (Anderson, 2014). Given their broad environmental and socio-economic implications, effective monitoring and management strategies are essential (Sagarminaga et al., 2023).

Conducting impact assessments is essential to identify and emphasize issues that pose threats to biodiversity and ecosystem functions. This understanding is crucial for designing effective adaptive management strategies for marine ecosystems, as it considers the current impacts and their specific locations (Levin et al., 2009). The CIMPAL (Cumulative IMPacts of invasive ALien species) index, developed by Katsanevakis et al. (2016), is a framework for estimating and mapping the impacts of IAS, which has been extensively applied across various European ecosystems (Katsanevakis et al., 2016; Korpinen et al., 2019; Tsirintanis et al., 2023). The advantages of using CIMPAL include the possibility to identify impacted hotspots, prioritize management actions, and target specific sites, habitats, and species for intervention (Katsanevakis et al., 2016; Tsirintanis et al., 2023). CIMPAL supports informed decision-making and enhances the effectiveness of conservation efforts by

providing a standardized and quantitative method for assessing cumulative impacts (Katsanevakis et al., 2016). To date, CIMPAL has been exclusively used for assessing and mapping IAS impacts.

Recognizing that both native and alien species can exhibit invasive characteristics, this study considers invasiveness as an ecological rather than a biogeographical phenomenon specific to alien species (Valéry et al., 2009), thereby classifying IAS as a subset of invasive species (Katsanevakis et al., 2023). This research extends the CIMPAL framework by incorporating the impacts of jellyfish blooms and HABs, along with IAS, while accounting for interspecific interactions. The extended framework is applied in the Aegean Sea as a case study.

7.2.2 Methods

Expanding CIMPAL

CIMPAL is expanded to incorporate (1) the impacts of all invasive species, including not only IAS but also jellyfish blooms and HABs, and (2) interspecific interactions. The new index is called CIMPAL-JH (Cumulative IMPacts of ALien species, Jellyfish blooms and HABs) and is estimated according to the following formula:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j w_{i,j} \pm \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i A_k H_j w_{i,j} f_{i,k}$$

Where I_c refers to the cumulative impact score in a specific study area cell; A_i refers to the population state of species i in the specific cell, standardized to range between 0 and 1; H_j represents the extent of habitat j in the cell; $w_{i,j}$ is the impact weight of species i at habitat j , estimated as a combination of species i impact magnitude based on Blackburn et al. (2014) and Volery et al. (2020) and the strength of the reported evidence (based on Katsanevakis et al., 2014b) (Supplementary Figures 1 and 2); A_k represents the population state of species $k \neq i$, an alien species interacting with alien species i , exhibiting either positive or negative effects, with A_k values standardized to range between 0 and 1; $f_{i,k}$ refers to the interaction effect of IAS k on IAS i , taking values from -1 for maximum negative interactions to a maximum value limited by the condition $w_{i,j} \cdot (1 + f_{i,k}) \leq 8$ (with 8 corresponding to massive impacts) for positive (synergistic) interactions ($f_{i,k} = 0$, when $i = k$); n represents the total number of invasive species; and m the total number of marine habitats included in the analysis.

For invasive species with continuous impacts (such as for most IAS) A_i should ideally be a standardized measure of species abundance; probability of presence derived from species distribution models can be used as a surrogate or even simple presence-absence in case of limited data. However, an inherent

difference of invasive species causing blooms (jellyfish or phytoplankton) is that they occur seasonally or irregularly for limited time, which affects the overall severity of their impacts. Hence, the A_i for these species is reasonable to include not only the concentration of the blooming species but also the average annual duration of the blooms. For this, we propose to assess A_i following species-specific thresholds, which should be established by comparing the concentrations and durations of past blooms. A_i can be estimated as a combination of the concentration and the duration, as shown in the Supplementary Figure 3.

The Aegean Sea, situated in the north-eastern Mediterranean, is renowned for its rich marine biodiversity and complex ecosystems. This region supports a variety of species, making it a critical area for marine conservation (Anagnostou et al., 2023; Anagnostou et al., 2024). Despite its ecological significance, the Aegean Sea faces substantial challenges in effective management and spatial planning (Sini et al., 2017). These challenges are intensified by human activities, including overfishing, pollution, and the introduction of alien species (Anagnostou et al., 2024). Over the past two decades, the number of established alien species in the region has substantially increased (Ragkousis et al., 2023), leading to important negative impacts on native biodiversity (Tsirintanis et al., 2023). Additionally, the frequency of jellyfish blooms has risen, disrupting tourism and posing risks to human health (Özgür and Öztürk, 2008; İşinibilir et al., 2021). HABs have also been recorded in the Aegean's coastal waters, with documented adverse effects on the environment and ecosystem services (Tsikoti and Genitsaris, 2021). These events have resulted in water discoloration, mucilage formation, habitat degradation, marine species mortality, localized anoxia, and economic losses in tourism and aquaculture, as well as human health concerns (Economou et al., 2007; Tsikoti and Genitsaris, 2021). The cumulative impacts of these activities threaten the biodiversity and ecological balance of the region, necessitating comprehensive and adaptive management approaches to ensure the sustainable use of marine resources (Springer, 2023).

To apply CIMPAL-JH, the Aegean Sea was partitioned into 321,346 grid cells, each measuring 0.01° in latitude and longitude, as outlined by Tsirintanis et al. (2023). Their assessment of the percent cover of ten broad habitat types per grid cell was also incorporated. These habitat types included seagrass meadows, shallow soft substrates (0–60 m depth), deep soft substrates (60–200 m depth), soft substrates of the dysphotic zone (deeper than 200 m), shallow hard substrates (0–60 m depth), deep hard substrates (60–200 m), hard substrates of the dysphotic zone (deeper than 200 m), submarine caves, coralligenous formations, and the pelagic habitat.

IAS occurrence data were sourced from Tsirintanis et al. (2023). Overall, 26 IAS were found to impact at least one of the studied habitats. These species are *Amathia verticillata*, *Amphistegina lobifera*,

Asparagopsis spp., *Brachidontes pharaonis*, *Callinectes sapidus*, *Caulerpa cylindracea*, *Codium fragile*, *Conomurex persicus*, *Fistularia commersonii*, *Halophila stipulacea*, *Hydroides elegans*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Mnemiopsis leidy*, *Oculina patagonica*, *Parupeneus forsskali*, *Pempheris rhomboidea*, *Pinctada radiata*, *Pterois miles*, *Sargocentron rubrum*, *Siganus luridus*, *Siganus rivulatus*, *Styela plicata*, *Styopodium schimperi*, *Upeneus pori* and *Womersleyella setacea*.

Jellyfish bloom data were gathered from published studies, the CIESM JellyWatch Program, and iNaturalist, while HABs occurrence data were compiled through a systematic literature review. The ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidy*, classified as an IAS, was included in the IAS dataset and consequently excluded from the jellyfish bloom datasets. Among all the studied species, only two interspecific interactions were recorded: the consumption of the chlorophyte *Caulerpa cylindracea* by the two herbivorous fish *Siganus luridus* and *S. rivulatus* (Azzurro et al., 2007; Tsirintanis et al., 2023). For both cases, $f_{i,k}$ was taken equal to -1, as the two herbivore fish, when abundant, completely eradicate *C. cylindracea*.

The CIMPAL-JH index was calculated at each grid cell in the study area, integrating the cumulative impacts of IAS, HABs and jellyfish blooms. The population state of IAS, A_i , was sourced from Tsirintanis et al. (2023) based on species distribution models (SDMs). For jellyfish and HAB species, only binary presence (1) or absence (0) data were used, as reliable information on bloom duration and concentration was unavailable. The impact magnitude and strength of evidence for each IAS were retrieved from Tsirintanis et al. (2023), whereas data for jellyfish and phytoplankton species were obtained through literature reviews (see Supplementary Table 1). Species with no documented impacts were excluded from the cumulative impact score. This applied to the jellyfish *Chrysaora hysoscella* and *Pennaria disticha* and the phytoplankton species *Alexandrium insuetum*, *Alexandrium minutum*, *Chaetoceros* spp., *Chattonella globosa*, *Chroococcus gelatinosus*, *Cylindrotheca closterium*, *Gonyaulax fragilis*, *Gonyaulax* sp., *Gonyaulax spinifera*, *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Leptocylindrus danicus*, *Leptocylindrus minimus*, *Lyngbya agardhii*, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Noctiluca scintillans*, *Phaeocystis pouchetii*, *Prorocentrum micans*, *Prorocentrum minimum*, *Prorocentrum redfeldii*, *Pseudonitzschia*, *Skeletonema costatum*, *Spatulodinium pseudonociluca*, *Synechocystis sallensis*, *Synechocystis* spp. and *Trichodesmium erythraeum*.

Species were ranked based on their negative impacts using four indicators suggested by Tsirintanis et al. (2023). The first (D1) measured the total area of occurrence, defined as the number of grid cells where the species was present. The second (D2) counted the number of cells where the species had an impact score greater than zero. The third (D3) calculated the cumulative impact score by summing

the impact values across the study area. The fourth (D4) determined the mean impact score across the species' range, excluding grid cells with values below 0.1.

7.2.3 Results

Cumulative impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs per grid cell ranged from 0 to 45.6 (Figure 7.2.1, Figure 7.2.2), with an average score of 1.6 per cell. Shallow coastal habitats (<60 m depth) exhibited significantly higher cumulative impact scores than offshore waters, with impacts being spatially localized rather than widespread (Figure 7.2.2). In offshore waters, cumulative impacts gradually declined from the northern to the southern Aegean (Figure 7.2.1). In contrast, high-impact coastal areas were more prevalent in the southern Aegean compared to the north (Figures 7.2.1, 7.2.2). Certain regions, particularly the Saronikos and Thermaikos Gulfs, experienced higher cumulative impacts than adjacent areas, as they were affected by all three categories of invasive species (Figures 7.2.1, 7.2.2, 7.2.3).

Figure 7.2.1. Map of cumulative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS), jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the Aegean Sea using CIMPAL-JH index scores.

Figure 7.2.2. Zoomed-in views of cumulative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS), jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms (HABs) in selected coastal areas of the Aegean Sea using CIMPAL-JH index scores. These close-up maps highlight spatial variations and fine-scale details of cumulative impact distribution in coastal regions.

Figure 7.2.3. (a) Disaggregation of the total CIMPAL-JH score by its three components (IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs), and maps of the cumulative impacts in the Aegean Sea of (b) IAS, (c) jellyfish blooms, and (d) HABs.

Among the most widespread IAS, *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, *Hydroides elegans*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Fistularia commersonii*, and *Pinctada radiata* exhibited the broadest distribution based on D1. When considering D2 (number of impacted cells), *M. leidyi*, *L. sceleratus*, *F. commersonii*, *Parupeneus forsskali*, and *Caulerpa cylindracea* ranked highest. The cumulative impact scores (D3) identified *M. leidyi*, *L. sceleratus*, *Amphistegina lobifera*, *F. commersonii*, and *Lophocladia lallemandii* as the most impactful species. Finally, D4, which accounts for the average impact within each species' range,

ranked *M. leidy*, *L. lallemandii*, *Siganus luridus*, *Siganus rivulatus*, and *Womersleyella setacea* as the most impactful species in the Aegean Sea (Figure 7.2.4).

Figure 7.2.4. Ranking of the species impacts in the Aegean Sea according to the indicators D1 (Top Left), D2 (Top Right), D3 (Bottom Left), D4 (Bottom Right). The data related to D1, D2 and D3 are log-transformed.

Four jellyfish species were individuated to be impactful in the Aegean Sea: *Aurelia aurita*, *Cotylorhiza tuberculata*, *Pelagia noctiluca* and *Rhizostoma pulmo*. Cumulative impact scores of jellyfish blooms per cell ranged from 0 to 5 (Figure 7.2.3d) with an average of 0.11 per cell, provoking 6.96% of the total cumulative impact (Figure 7.2.3a). The data extracted from different sources show a consistent

pattern, indicating that the western Aegean is the most affected area by jellyfish blooms, as well as some islands in the Kyklades. According to the D1 indicator, the four jellyfish species were ranked based on their presence as follows: *R. pulmo*, *P. noctiluca*, *C. tuberculata* and *A. aurita*. For D2 (number of impacted cells), the ranking of the four species was: *R. pulmo*, *P. noctiluca*, *C. tuberculata* and *A. aurita*. Based on D3, the species with the highest cumulative impact scores were: *R. pulmo*, *P. noctiluca*, *C. tuberculata* and *A. aurita*. Lastly, D4 ranked the four species by their average impact within their distribution range: *P. noctiluca*, *A. aurita*, *R. pulmo* (all the three tied), and then *C. tuberculata* (Figure 7.2.4).

Seven phytoplankton taxa were identified as impactful in the Aegean Sea: *Dinophysis* sp., *Dinophysis acuminata*, *Karenia brevis*, *Karlodinium* spp., *Mesodinium rubrum*, *Ostreopsis* spp. and *Vicicitus globosus*. HABs exhibited cumulative impact scores per cell ranging from 0 to 6 (Figure 7.2.3c), with an average of 0.10 per cell, contributing 6.12% to the total CIMPAL-JH score (Figure 7.2.3a). They were mainly distributed in the Thermaikos and Saronikos gulfs. Based on both D1 and D2, *D. acuminata* and *V. globosus* were the top-ranked HAB-producing species. According to D3, *M. rubrum* has the highest impact, followed by *D. acuminata* and *V. globosus*. Lastly, D4 identified *M. rubrum* and *Ostreopsis* spp. as the two species with the highest average impact within their distribution range (Figure 7.2.4).

7.2.4 Discussion

Assessing cumulative impacts is a fundamental principle of ecosystem-based management (Papadopoulou et al., 2025). In the context of biological invasions, it allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the combined effects of multiple invasive species on marine ecosystems, ensuring that management strategies effectively mitigate risks and account for complex ecological interactions (McGeoch et al., 2016; Mačić et al., 2018). While previous assessments have primarily focused on IAS, other invasive taxa, such as those causing HABs and jellyfish blooms, can also cause significant disruptions to marine biodiversity (Sagarminaga et al., 2023, 2024). Expanding the CIMPAL framework to include other environmental drivers, and their interspecific interactions provides a more comprehensive tool for assessing and mapping invasion-related impacts across marine habitats (Borja et al., 2024). The CIMPAL-JH index accounts for the combined effects of different invasive taxa, offering an integrated approach to identify high-risk areas, rank species based on their ecological impact, and support evidence-based management strategies.

The Aegean Sea is currently experiencing a range of environmental challenges driven by population growth, wastewater discharge, agricultural runoff, aquaculture, industrialization, tourism, maritime transport, and climate change (Anagnostou et al., 2024). These pressures have contributed to an

increased frequency of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms in certain areas, leading to the cumulative impacts documented in this study.

According to the CIMPAL-JH index, cumulative impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs were consistently higher in coastal habitats compared to the open sea, a pattern aligning with the findings of Tsirintanis et al. (2023). The predominance of IAS in shallow coastal areas can be attributed to the preference of most alien species introduced into the Mediterranean for warmer, shallower waters (Katsanevakis et al., 2014a). Additionally, the observed distribution of IAS impacts may be influenced by research effort bias, as studies are predominantly conducted in shallow coastal ecosystems (Tsirintanis et al., 2023).

The Thermaikos Gulf emerged as the most affected pelagic area, experiencing significant impacts from jellyfish blooms and HABs. This can be linked to anthropogenic pressures, including sewage discharge, industrial waste, agricultural runoff, shipping activities, and harbor operations. Furthermore, five major rivers transport nutrients, heavy metals, and organic compounds into the gulf, exacerbating these issues (Androulidakis et al., 2024). The Thermaikos and Saronikos Gulfs are notable hotspots for alien species belonging to Mollusca, Arthropoda, and Annelida, though they do not exhibit the same degree of invasion by Chordata, particularly fish (Katsanevakis et al., 2013). Notably, both Thermaikos and Saronikos are among the Greek coastal regions most severely affected by human-induced eutrophication (Pagou, 2005), which is consistent with our findings, as HAB impacts were concentrated in these areas.

The results of the CIMPAL-JH index regarding IAS impacts differ slightly from those reported by Tsirintanis et al. (2023) due to the incorporation of interspecific interactions in this study. This adjustment led to a reduction in the estimated presence and cumulative impact of *Caulerpa cylindracea*, which in turn altered its ranking. In Tsirintanis et al. (2023), *C. cylindracea* ranked first in the D3 indicator as the species with the highest cumulative impact sum. However, in this study, it has dropped to eighth place. Similarly, in the D4 indicator, which measures the average impact within a species' range, *C. cylindracea* fell from the top position in Tsirintanis et al. (2023) to 20th place in the current assessment. This lower ranking more accurately reflects its current status, as recent observations indicate a substantial decline in *C. cylindracea* populations in the eastern Mediterranean, with the species even disappearing from several areas due to predation by *Siganus* spp. (Dimitriadis et al., 2021).

Rhizostoma pulmo emerged as the most impactful jellyfish species across D1, D2, and D3, in part due to its role as a vector for bacterial pathogens, which may spread diseases to marine organisms and

humans (Stabili et al., 2020). Additionally, *R. pulmo* blooms can threaten plankton populations and disrupt fish larvae recruitment, as juveniles rely on zooplankton as a food source (Gueroun et al., 2022).

Pelagia noctiluca, which ranked second across D1, D2, and D3, has a strong predatory impact on zooplankton, including the eggs and larvae of nektonic and benthic species (Mariottini et al., 2008). *Cotylorhiza tuberculata*, ranked third in these indicators, had a lower D4 ranking, suggesting that while it is widespread, its localized impact is relatively lower. However, high abundances of *C. tuberculata* in enclosed coastal areas can alter resource availability and competition dynamics in marine ecosystems (Astorga et al., 2012). *Aurelia aurita*, while ranked lowest in D1, D2, and D3, had a high average impact within its range (D4), indicating it can still exert localized ecological pressures, particularly through zooplankton predation and microbial community shifts (Zoccarato et al., 2016).

Although HABs had the lowest overall impact among the three studied groups, they remain an ecological concern, particularly in the western Aegean. *Dinophysis acuminata* emerged as the top-ranking species according to D1 and D2, while its ranking in D3 highlights its ecological significance. Like other *Dinophysis* species, *D. acuminata* produces okadaic acid (OA) and Dinophysis toxins (DTXs), which are responsible for diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) in humans. However, the impacts of HABs extend beyond human health, as marine organisms are also vulnerable to their toxins. Research on DSP toxin exposure, accumulation, and effects on marine life remains limited, though available studies indicate potential behavioral and morphological changes, as well as mortality in fish (Corriere et al., 2021). *Vicicitus globosus*, which also ranked high in D1 and D2 and held a significant position in D3, is known for its cytotoxic effects, which can be harmful to a wide range of marine organisms (Chang, 2015). *Mesodinium rubrum*, which had the highest cumulative impact score (D3) and greatest average impact within its range (D4), is particularly notable for its ability to turn water into a distinct red color. Blooms of *M. rubrum* can disrupt local marine ecosystems by outcompeting other phytoplankton species for resources and triggering eutrophication events (Zhang et al., 2018). *Karenia* cf. *brevis*, which ranked fifth across the D1, D2, and D3 indicators, is well known for causing red tides and producing brevetoxins, which are highly toxic to marine life and can cause Neurotoxic Shellfish Poisoning (NSP) in humans (Stumpf et al., 2022). *Ostreopsis* spp. are also of concern, as they produce palytoxins and ovatoxins, which are harmful to marine organisms and can become aerosolized, leading to respiratory issues, skin irritation, and other health effects in humans (Pavaux et al., 2020). While *M. rubrum* is relatively widespread, contributing to its high impact scores, *Ostreopsis* spp. have a more localized distribution, which limits their overall impact on marine ecosystems.

The effects of HABs are largely dependent on the density of harmful species, as even the most toxic organisms must reach a critical cell concentration to cause significant harm. While many harmful species are widespread, their actual impact is contingent on bloom intensity and duration (Zingone and Oksfeldt Enevoldsen, 2000). Some species, such as *Dinophysis* spp., can still induce toxic contamination at very low concentrations (Zingone and Oksfeldt Enevoldsen, 2000). To improve future assessments, it is essential to determine species-specific cell concentration thresholds and consistently report bloom intensity and duration. Incorporating these parameters into the A_i term of the CIMPAL-JH index would enhance its precision by quantifying impact severity rather than relying solely on presence-absence data. Additionally, while the impacts of individual harmful species are relatively well-documented, the interactions among multiple species and their combined effects remain more complex and less understood. HAB events commonly consist of multiple species; further research is needed to fully assess the cumulative impacts of multiple harmful phytoplankton species in HABs and incorporate this knowledge into the CIMPAL-JH index.

To enhance the estimation of the A_i term for jellyfish blooms and HABs in the CIMPAL-JH index, it would be beneficial to incorporate data on both bloom concentration and duration, as the current absence of such data represents a limitation. Unlike most IAS, whose impacts are continuous and cumulative over time, the severity of HABs and jellyfish blooms is highly dependent on their intensity and persistence, which were not reflected in the A_i term in the Aegean case study. Future refinements should aim to establish species-specific concentration thresholds and incorporate temporal factors, allowing for improved assessment of their cumulative impacts.

This study expanded the CIMPAL framework, originally designed to assess IAS impacts, by incorporating jellyfish blooms, HABs, and interspecific interactions. This enabled the inclusion of additional drivers in the analysis of cumulative environmental impacts on the Aegean ecosystem. The application of CIMPAL-JH in the Aegean Sea, despite data limitations, has offered valuable insights into the spatial distribution and cumulative impacts of invasive species, highlighting key hotspots of environmental impact. Beyond the Aegean, CIMPAL-JH presents a versatile and scalable tool for assessing the impacts of invasive species in other regions. By integrating different types of environmental challenges and accounting for species interactions, the index can be adapted to different aquatic or terrestrial ecosystems, helping to identify high-risk areas, prioritize management efforts, and support conservation strategies. Future applications of CIMPAL-JH in other regions could further refine its methodology, incorporating additional factors such as bloom intensity and species-specific thresholds or consider further environmental challenges, such as marine heatwaves and mass

mortality events (Garrabou et al., 2022). This would enhance its effectiveness as a decision-support tool for mitigating the impacts of current challenges on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

7.2.5 References

- Anderson, D.M., (2012). HABs in a changing world: a perspective on harmful algal blooms, their impacts, and research and management in a dynamic era of climactic and environmental change, in: Harmful Algae 2012: Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Harmful Algae: October 29-November 2, 2012, CECO, Changwon, Gyeongnam, Korea/Editors, Hak Gyoon Kim, Beatriz Reguera, Gustaaf M. Hallegraeff, Chang Kyu Lee, M.. Vol. 2012.
- Anderson, D.M., (2009). Approaches to monitoring, control and management of harmful algal blooms (HABs). *Ocean Coast Manag* 52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2009.04.006>
- Azzurro, E., Fanelli, E., Mostarda, E., Catra, M., & Andaloro, F. (2007) Resource partitioning among early colonizing *Siganus luridus* and native herbivorous fish in the Mediterranean: an integrated study based on gut-content analysis and stable isotope signatures. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 87: 991-998, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315407056342>
- Báez, J.C., Pennino, M.G., Albo-Puigserver, M., Coll, M., Giraldez, A., & Bellido, J.M., (2022). Effects of environmental conditions and jellyfish blooms on small pelagic fish and fisheries from the Western Mediterranean Sea. *Estuar Coast Shelf Sci* 264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2021.107699>
- Blackburn, T.M., Essl, F., Evans, T., Hulme, P.E., Jeschke, J.M., Kühn, I., Kumschick, S., Marková, Z., Mrugała, A., Nentwig, W., Pergl, J., Pyšek, P., Rabitsch, W., Ricciardi, A., Richardson, D.M., Sendek, A., Vilà, M., Wilson, J.R.U., Winter, M., Genovesi, P., & Bacher, S., (2014). A Unified Classification of Alien Species Based on the Magnitude of their Environmental Impacts. *PLoS Biol* 12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001850>
- Boero, F., (2013). General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean Review of Jellyfish Blooms in the Mediterranean and Black Sea, Rome.
- Boero, F., Bouillon, J., Gravili, C., Miglietta, M.P., Parsons, T., & Piraino, S., (2008). Gelatinous plankton: Irregularities rule the world (sometimes). *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 356. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07368>
- Boero, F., Brotz, L., Gibbons, M.J., Piraino, S., & Zampardi, S., (2016). Ocean Warming 3.10 Impacts and effects of ocean warming on jellyfish.
- Canepa, A., Fuentes, V., Sabatés, A., Piraino, S., Boero, F., & Gili, J.M., (2014). *Pelagia noctiluca* in the Mediterranean Sea, in: Jellyfish Blooms. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7015-7_11
- Castro-Díez, P., Vaz, A.S., Silva, J.S., van Loo, M., Alonso, Á., Aponte, C., Bayón, Á., Bellingham, P.J., Chiuffo, M.C., DiManno, N., Julian, K., Kandert, S., La Porta, N., Marchante, H., Maule, H.G., Mayfield, M.M., Metcalfe, D., Monteverdi, M.C., Núñez, M.A., Ostertag, R., Parker, I.M., Peltzer, D.A., Potgieter, L.J., Raymundo, M., Rayome, D., Reisman-Berman, O., Richardson, D.M., Roos, R.E., Saldaña, A., Shackleton, R.T., Torres, A., Trudgen, M., Urban, J., Vicente, J.R., Vilà, M., Ylloja, T., Zenni, R.D., & Godoy, O., (2019). Global effects of non-native tree species on multiple ecosystem services. *Biological Reviews* 94. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12511>

- CBD, (2008). COP 9 Decisions. VI/23. Alien species that threaten ecosystems, habitats or species, Meeting of the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). Germany.
- Cegolon, L., Heymann, W.C., Lange, J.H., & Mastrangelo, G., (2013). Jellyfish stings and their management: A review. *Mar Drugs*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md11020523>
- De Donno, A., Idolo, A., Bagordo, F., Grassi, T., Leomanni, A., Serio, F., ... & Piraino, S., (2014). Impact of stinging jellyfish proliferations along south Italian coasts: Human health hazards, treatment and social costs. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 11(3), 2488-2503.
- Dinasquet, J., Titelman, J., Møller, L.F., Setälä, O., Granhag, L., Andersen, T., Bamstedt, U., Haraldsson, M., Hosa, A., Katajisto, T., Kragh, T., Kuparinen, J., Schrøter, M.L., Søndergaard, M., Tiselius, P., & Riemann, L., (2012). Cascading effects of the ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* on the planktonic food web in a nutrient-limited estuarine system. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 460. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps09770>
- Doherty, T.S., Glen, A.S., Nimmo, D.G., Ritchie, E.G., & Dickman, C.R., (2016). Invasive predators and global biodiversity loss. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 113. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1602480113>
- Doyle, T.K., De Haas, H., Cotton, D., Dorschel, B., Cummins, V., Houghton, J.D.R., Davenport, J., & Hays, G.C., (2008). Widespread occurrence of the jellyfish *Pelagia noctiluca* in Irish coastal and shelf waters. *J Plankton Res* 30. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbn052>
- García-Gómez, J.C., Sempere-Valverde, J., González, A.R., Martínez-Chacón, M., Olaya-Ponzzone, L., Sánchez-Moyano, E., Ostalé-Valriberas, E., & Megina, C., (2020). From exotic to invasive in record time: The extreme impact of *Rugulopteryx okamurae* (Dictyotales, Ochrophyta) in the strait of Gibraltar. *Science of the Total Environment* 704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135408>
- Ghermandi, A., Galil, B., Gowdy, J., & Nunes, P.A.L.D., (2015). Jellyfish outbreak impacts on recreation in the Mediterranean Sea: Welfare estimates from a socioeconomic pilot survey in Israel. *Ecosyst Serv* 11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.12.004>
- Graham, W.M., Pagès, F., & Hamner, W.M., (2001). A physical context for gelatinous zooplankton aggregations: A review, in: *Hydrobiologia*. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1011876004427>
- Hallegraeff, G., Enevoldsen, H., & Zingone, A., (2021). Global harmful algal bloom status reporting. *Harmful Algae*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2021.101992>
- Helmholz, H., Johnston, B.D., Ruhnau, C., & Prange, A., (2010). Gill cell toxicity of northern boreal scyphomedusae *Cyanea capillata* and *Aurelia aurita* measured by an in vitro cell assay. *Hydrobiologia* 645. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-010-0216-9>
- Howard, B.R., Francis, F.T., Côté, I.M., & Therriault, T.W., (2019). Habitat alteration by invasive European green crab (*Carcinus maenas*) causes eelgrass loss in British Columbia, Canada. *Biol Invasions* 21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-019-02072-z>
- Katsanevakis, S., Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Steenbeek, J., Lasram, F.B.R., Zenetos, A., & Cardoso, A.C., (2014a). Invading the Mediterranean Sea: Biodiversity patterns shaped by human activities. *Front Mar Sci* 1. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00032>
- Katsanevakis, S., Olenin, S., Puntilla-Dodd, R., Rilov, G., Stæhr, P.A.U., Teixeira, H., Tsirintanis, K., Birchenough, S.N.R., Jakobsen, H.H., Knudsen, S.W., Lanzén, A., Mazaris, A.D., Piraino, S., & Tidbury, H.J., (2023). Marine invasive alien species in Europe: 9 years after the IAS Regulation. *Front Mar Sci*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1271755>

- Katsanevakis, S., Tempera, F., & Teixeira, H., (2016). Mapping the impact of alien species on marine ecosystems: The Mediterranean Sea case study. *Divers Distrib* 22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12429>
- Katsanevakis, S., Wallentinus, I., Zenetos, A., Leppäkoski, E., Çinar, M.E., Oztürk, B., Grabowski, M., Golani, D., & Cardoso, A.C., (2014b). Impacts of invasive alien marine species on ecosystem services and biodiversity: A pan-European review. *Aquat Invasions* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2014.9.4.01>
- Korpinen, S., Klančnik, K., Peterlin, M., Nurmi, M., Laamanen, L., Zupančič, G., Popit, A., Murray, C., Harvey, T., Andersen, J.H., Zenetos, A., Stein, U., Tunesi, L., Abhold, K., Piet, G., Kallenbach, E., Agnesi, S., Bolman, B., Vaughan, D., Reker, J., & Royo Gelabert, E. (2019) Multiple pressures and their combined effects in Europe's seas. *ETC/ICM Technical Report 4/2019: European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine waters*, 164 pp. <http://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17535.11689>
- Landsberg, J.H., (2002). The effects of harmful algal blooms on aquatic organisms. *Reviews in Fisheries Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20026491051695>
- Levin, P.S., Fogarty, M.J., Murawski, S.A., & Fluharty, D., (2009). Integrated ecosystem assessments: Developing the scientific basis for ecosystem-based management of the ocean. *PLoS Biol*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1000014>
- Purcell, J.E., (2005). Climate effects on formation of jellyfish and ctenophore blooms: A review. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315405011409>
- Qu, C.F., Song, J.M., & Li, N., (2014). Causes of jellyfish blooms and their influence on marine environment. *Chinese Journal of Applied Ecology* 25.
- Quiñones, J., Monroy, A., Acha, E.M., & Mianzan, H., (2013). Jellyfish bycatch diminishes profit in an anchovy fishery off Peru. *Fish Res* 139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2012.04.014>
- Ragkousis, M., Sini, M., Koukourouvli, N., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S (2023) Invading the Greek Seas: Spatiotemporal Patterns of Marine Impactful Alien and Cryptogenic Species. *Diversity*, 15(8), 353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15030353>
- Richardson, A.J., Bakun, A., Hays, G.C., & Gibbons, M.J., (2009). The jellyfish joyride: causes, consequences and management responses to a more gelatinous future. *Trends Ecol Evol*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.01.010>
- Roy, H.E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., Renard Truong, T., Bacher, S., Galil, B.S., Hulme, P.E., Ikeda, T., Sankaran, K. V., McGeoch, M.A., Meyerson, L.A., Nuñez, M.A., Ordonez, A., Rahlao, S.J., Schwindt, E., Seebens, H., Sheppard, A.W., & Vandvik, V., (2023). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Environmental Indicators.
- Sagarminaga, Y., Garcés, E., Francé, J., Stern, R., Revilla, M., Magaletti, E., Bresnan, E., Tsirtsis, G., Jakobsen, H.H., Sampedro, N., Reñé, A., Camp, J., Borja, Á., Rodríguez, J.G., Spada, E., Pagou, K., De Angelis, R., Lanzén, A., Ferrer, L., Borrello, P., Boicenco, L., Kobos, J., Mazaris, A., & Katsanevakis, S., (2023). New tools and recommendations for a better management of harmful algal blooms under the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive. *Frontiers in Ocean Sustainability* 1. <https://doi.org/10.3389/focsu.2023.1298800>
- Sagarminaga, Y., Piraino, S., Lynam, C.P., Leoni, V., Nikolaou, A., Jaspers, C., Bosch-Belmar, M., Fumarola, L.M., Borja, Á., Spada, E., Amorim, E., Borrello, P., de Angelis, R., Leone, A., Montero, N., Ferrer, L., Holland, M.M., Doyle, T.K., Tsirtsis, G., & Katsanevakis, S., (2024). Management of

- jellyfish outbreaks to achieve good environmental status. *Frontiers in Ocean Sustainability* 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/focsu.2024.1449190>
- Sini, M., Katsanevakis, S., Koukourouvli, N., Gerovasileiou, V., Dailianis, T., Buhl-Mortensen, L., ... & Frantzis, A. (2017). Assembling Ecological Pieces to Reconstruct the Conservation Puzzle of the Aegean Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4, 347. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00347>
- Tsirintanis, K., Azzurro, E., Crocetta, F., Dimiza, M., Froggia, C., Gerovasileiou, V., Langeneck, J., Mancinelli, G., Rosso, A., Stern, N., Triantaphyllou, M., Tsiamis, K., Turon, X., Verlaque, M., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S., (2022). Bioinvasion impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human health in the Mediterranean Sea. *Aquat Invasions*. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2022.17.3.01>
- Tsirintanis, K., Sini, M., Ragkousis, M., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S., (2023). Cumulative Negative Impacts of Invasive Alien Species on Marine Ecosystems of the Aegean Sea. *Biology (Basel)* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12070933>
- Valéry, L., Fritz, H., Lefeuvre, J.C., & Simberloff, D., (2009). Invasive species can also be native... *Trends Ecol Evol*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.07.003>
- Volery, L., Bacher, S., Blackburn, T.M., Bertolino, S., Evans, T., Genovesi, P., Kumschick, S., Roy, H.E., & Smith, K.G., (2020). Improving the Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT): a summary of revisions to the framework and guidelines. *NeoBiota* 62. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.62.52723>
- West, J.J., Järnberg, L., Berdalet, E., & Cusack, C., (2021). Understanding and Managing Harmful Algal Bloom Risks in a Changing Climate: Lessons From the European CoCliME Project. *Frontiers in Climate* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.636723>

7.3 Case study 15: New developments in CIMPAL

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7.3.1 Introduction

The assessment of the integrated impacts of cumulative pressures is critical for ensuring the achievement of good environmental status of the ocean and for maintaining ecosystem services. National institutions, RSCs, decision and policy makers require regular and trustworthy information on the status of the environment to enable their cyclic reporting obligations under evermore demanding environmental legislation. Updated information is also critical to support effective programmes of measures (e.g. MSFD article 13) that can halt ongoing degradation and restore marine waters. In this context, it is important to provide the scientific and technical community with easily accessible tools that allow rapid and repeatable assessments to facilitate their reproducibility and comparability across relevant temporal and spatial scales.

In GES4SEAS we have taken a CIA indicator developed to assess the cumulative impact of invasive alien species - the CIMPAL index (Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2016) that had recently been implemented as a webservice tool in a cloud computing environment (Teixeira *et al.*, in prep.; LifeWatch ERIC, 2022) and revisited the algorithm to incorporate new developments that accommodate challenges and needs identified by the scientific community.

Previous developments had focused on optimising CIMPAL calculation to process large scale data at high resolution through high performance computing (HPC) in cloud environments, resulting in two resources:

- a friendly graphical user interface (GUI) in the myLifeWatch ERIC platform, requiring no coding skills from the user but offering less flexibility (LifeWatch ERIC, 2022); and
- the NaaVRE Notebook as a Virtual Research Environment (LifeWatch NL NaavRE, 2023), implemented in Python by LifeWatch Netherlands, that uses a Docker container for running the processes online, which offers greater flexibility for implementing new features but requires coding familiarity to run the workflow or adapt features (Zhao *et al.*, 2022).

To enable further advances (see e.g. 7.2) of the CIMPAL index and meet the scientific community needs and expectations, from the development point of view, we have now decided to take CIMPAL into an R environment that offers higher flexibility to implement new features while still offering possibilities to develop a friendly GUI through a ShinyApp - an R package that allows to build

interactive web apps straight from R & Python. This CIMPAL R package is under development, but new features, detailed below, have been implemented and tested in some of the GES4SEAS Learning Sites.

7.3.2 Methods – Software implementations

The new CIMPAL index developments being implemented under GES4SEAS build from the two most recent algorithm implementations, in collaboration with LifeWatch ERIC, described above and extend them in three main ways:

1. facilitate preprocessing of data to calculate the CIMPAL index (e.g. merge occurrence data in different point and polygon formats);
2. implement new extensions in the algorithm itself reflecting GES4SEAS scientific advances in the field (e.g. species interactions);
3. to provide specific functions for CIMPAL results visualisation and easier computation of CIMPAL complementary indices and results statistics.

All developments presented here ensure that the user can have higher flexibility to use CIMPAL in their own management context while at the same time securing the reproducibility of the results and support coherent temporal and spatial assessments as need. Below we detail the main methodological developments and implementation of new features in CIMPAL index workflow.

1. New workflow implementation | Allow for **integration of different data formats** in the assessment such as species point occurrences (in e.g. csv format) and polygons range maps (in e.g. shapefiles), through a preprocessing stage.

This is relevant as often data are gathered from different sources and there is a need to consider them in the assessment. This becomes more relevant as the scale of the assessment extends beyond controlled monitoring programmes at local or national levels to regional seas or EU-wide-scale assessments. It is also relevant to accommodate additional sources of information into regular monitoring such as those from the Global Biodiversity Information Platform (GBIF) that includes also citizen science data, which have become an important source to fulfil data gaps and contribute to a wide coverage of the assessments.

This feature was implemented as a preprocessing stage, in **R environment**, where point occurrences are first transformed into polygons using the user defined *Species Dispersal Radius* (Teixeira et al., in prep), followed by an integration with polygon data, where spatial overlaps of species occurrences

within a same year are merged taking the mean abundance (if data is not presence/absence) and the mean magnitude of impact provided in the original sources.

2. New algorithm implementation | Flexibility in using impact evidence in CIMPAL calculation by allowing considering the **impact classification, i.e. the Magnitude of Impact (Mol) **at observation level**.**

Organisms maximize their fitness at an "optimal" environmental range, thus it is expected that physiological performance varies as the environment shifts between optimal and extreme conditions for a species (Miller & Stillman, 2012). Such change in performance is expected to directly affect the ways and the intensity by which an invasive alien species can impact its recipient environment and its communities. Until now CIMPAL implementations have considered the Mol at the species level, meaning that a constant Mol would be assigned to all observations of a specific Species-Habitat pair according to a user provided weight matrix. The growing body of knowledge on biological invasions, namely research on the impacts caused by invasive alien species, has grown significantly in the scientific literature, providing new opportunities to explore such variability and integrate it into ecological assessments.

This new CIMPAL feature, implemented in **R environment**, by giving the option for the Mol of a given species to vary *per observation*, will allow to reflect potential regional variability on the impact magnitude when evidence supporting it exists. This feature will benefit from another resource developed within **GES4SEAS**, the **Database of Marine IAS Impacts** (Teixeira *et al.*, in prep), supported by a ShinyApp tool (Figure 7.3.1), which has been collecting evidence on impacts from the scientific literature and allows to explore variability of species impacts across habitats and regions. Such evidence can be directly extracted and used to inform CIMPAL calculations in formats supporting both approaches: a common species-habitat Mol or a species-habitat Mol variable per observation according to biogeography and defined according to user preferences.

3. New algorithm implementation | Include **biotic interactions in CIMPAL from evidence in **GloBI** - the **Global Biotic Interactions database**.**

The cumulative impacts of invasive alien species are not expected to have simple additive effects on biodiversity and on the recipient environments, however, if gathering information on impacts is already a challenge, understanding how species may interact synergistically or antagonistic to each other adds to it. The **Global Biotic Interactions GloBI** (Jorrit *et al.*, 2014) is an open service providing open data using open-source software that provides open access to finding species interaction data

from literature-based and open datasets records (e.g., predator-prey, pollinator-plant, pathogen-host, parasite-host).

Figure 7.3.1. The Marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) Impacts Database – a ShinyApp. By Heliana Teixeira and Fábio Matos, licensed under CC BY 4.0.

Taking advantage of this information, we have added a new feature to CIMPAL algorithm that accounts for interactions between invasive species (A_i and A_k) co-occurring in a same habitat (H_j) according to the nature of their interaction ($f_{i,k,j}$), as expressed by the second term of the equation below:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j w_{i,j} + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=i+1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i A_k H_j f_{i,k,j}(A_i, A_k)$$

This new CIMPAL feature is currently being implemented in **R environment** and will allow to download species interactions directly from GloBI using a custom taxon list, which in our case will be the user’s defined species list for the CIMPAL assessment. This can be used for IAS, for HABs and for Jellyfish assessments, as long as information on species interactions exists. The GloBI download will produce a csv file with all associations in GloBI for the taxa in the list as well as the records the associations came from, to keep track of sources and eventual changes for future index runs.

The GloBI database acknowledges 37 interaction types, which we have divided into four main categories (Table 7.3.1) to distinguish the nature of an interaction ($f_{i,k,j}$), i.e. its negative or positive connotation, for use in the CIMPAL assessment. Those interaction types implying an adverse association between two species and thus likely to reflect antagonistic behaviour that reduces one or the other species impact were considered **negative interactions**. On the contrary, those interactions

reflecting behaviours that would benefit one or the other species, and thus likely to reflect synergistic behaviour that increases their impact, were considered **positive interactions**. Some interaction types may be **context dependent** and thus the effect of one species on the magnitude of impact of another species may not be straightforward or may have very little effect on it. Finally, other interaction types were discarded as **no effect** on the overall species magnitude of impact is expected or are simply not applicable in marine environments.

Table 7.3.1. GloBI Database interaction types, split into four categories with relevance for including interaction between IAS in CIMPAL calculations.

Negative interaction:
'eats', 'preysOn', 'parasiteOf', 'pathogenOf', 'endoparasitoidOf', 'endoparasiteOf', 'ectoParasiteOf', 'parasitoidOf', 'ectoParasitoid', 'kills', 'kleptoparasiteOf', 'eatenBy', 'farms', 'preyedUponBy', 'hasParasite', 'hasPathogen'
Positive interaction:
'hasHost', 'symbiontOf', 'hostOf', 'pollinates', 'pollinatedBy', 'commensalistOf'
Context dependent:
'livesOn', 'livesInsideOf', 'guestOf', 'inhabits', 'livesUnder', 'dispersalVectorOf', 'hasVector', 'vectorOf', 'hasDispersalVector'
No effect or not applicable:
'interactsWith', 'visitsFlowersOf', 'adjacentTo', 'livesNear', 'flowersVisitedBy', 'visits'

Taking the CIMPAL algorithm extension in the equation above, in the simple case of Presence/Absence data, where $(A_i = 1)$ and $(A_k = 1)$, a declared negative interaction between the two co-occurring invasive alien species, i.e. where A_k has a negative interaction type towards A_i , would result in the cancellation of species A_i impact; while in the case of a positive interaction of A_k with A_i it would double the species A_i impact. If species abundance data is available, the effect of species A_k upon A_i can be modelled based on their respective abundances assuming a simple linear relationship. This is accommodated within the current implementation.

Ideally, if species response curves describing interacting species relationship would be available this could be implemented to improve how their interaction is incorporated into the model. For the moment, this is not yet considered in this implementation, although some work is ongoing under GES4SEAS WP4 regarding response curves that could be up taken to better model IAS interaction. This theoretical application would nonetheless be dependent on IAS specific data and knowledge to be able to implement it in practice.

4. New workflow implementation | Results visualisation

The CIMPAL workflow, whichever platform is used to calculate the index, produces several outputs of two main types; spatial outputs of several CIMPAL vulnerability maps (in tiff format) and tabular outputs of zonal species and overall CIMPAL impacts as well as summary statistics (in csv format) (Figure 7.3.2).

Figure 7.3.2. Examples of output files and results' visualization originated from CIMPAL workflow.

We are introducing new functions in the CIMPAL workflow to support **visualisation of the main spatial outputs**, such as maps of the CIMPAL index score vulnerability map (Figure 7.3.2), of the spatial aggregated zonal results and of CIMPAL per pathways of introduction, if that information is available.

In addition, we are also implementation functions to support **automated calculation and visualisation of the complementary CIMPAL indices D1-D4**, useful to provide species rankings and support prioritization of species for management. These four complementary indices rank (D1) the most widespread species in the area independent of having an impact; the (D2) most widespread species but considering only impacted area by that species; the (D3) species by highest cumulative impact across its range of occurrence; and, finally, also rank the (D4) species considering its average impact across its range of occurrence (Figure 7.3.2).

7.3.3 Results – Software development

All the new features described above (Figure 7.3.3) are being implemented as new functions in **R environment** and will be incorporated into a **new upcoming CIMPAL R Package**. These implementations will also be made available through a ShinyApp, in a later stage, to facilitate codeless implementation of the CIMPAL workflow to non-experts. The source code will be made available through a dedicated GitHub Repository from where the package can then be installed. New releases of the CIMPAL R package will be automatically deposited on the GES4SEAS Zenodo.

An overview of the CIMPAL workflow (Figure 7.3.3) is provided below, illustrating its flexibility to integrate user defined and/or open available input data from different sources, as well as integration of associated relevant information such as biotic interactions, impacts, pathways of introduction and aggregation scales. Independently of the data sources and of customisation of the CIMPAL calculations (species dispersion radius or baseline scale of assessment); our aim is that the user can keep track of all options made along the pipeline to allow easy reproducibility of assessments, essential for comparability and large temporal and spatial scale assessments.

Figure 7.3.3. The CIMPAL workflow with examples of associated resources and the type of input data for automated implementation of CIMPAL calculations. By Heliana Teixeira and Fábio Matos, licensed under CC BY 4.0. CIA: Cumulative Impacts Assessment; IAS: Invasive Alien Species

These CIMPAL developments presented have been tested and applied to different GES4SEAS Learning Sites for proof of concept, as shown in several of the case studies included in this report. For example, the extension of **CIMPAL-JH** to calculate the cumulative impact caused by NIS, HABs and Jellyfish is done under the Aegean example and in the pan-European assessment. The later will showcase for example the merging of different data sources, point occurrences and polygon range data. Also, in this LS10 pan-European assessment we will test the incorporation of Biotic Interactions in CIMPAL algorithm from direct extraction from GloBI, using the NIS/IAS layer as example.

Originally, CIMPAL was developed for assessing IAS cumulative negative impacts on biodiversity but the principle to calculate CIMPAL to assess also positive impacts (**CIMPAL Plus +(ve) NIS impacts**) or impacts in Ecosystem Services or other aspects such as Human Health, is the same, offering the potential to re-use the proposed workflow (7.3.3).

7.3.4 References

- Jorrit H. Poelen, James D. Simons & Chris J. Mungall. (2014). Global Biotic Interactions: An open infrastructure to share and analyze species-interaction datasets. *Ecological Informatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>
- Katsanevakis, S., Tempera, F., & Teixeira, H. (2016). Mapping the impact of alien species on marine ecosystems: the Mediterranean Sea case study. *Diversity and Distributions*, 22(6), 694-707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12429>
- LifeWatch ERIC (2022). Biotope - Cumulative IMPacts of invasive ALien species (CIMPAL) version https://training.lifewatch.eu/resources/?resource=/course/view.php?name=Biotope_CIMPAL
- LifeWatch NL NaavRE (2023). CIMPAL virtual labs Cumulative IMPact of invasive ALien species <https://naavre.lifewatch.dev/vreapp>
- Miller, N. A. & Stillman, J. H. (2012) Physiological Optima and Critical Limits. *Nature Education Knowledge* 3(10):1
- Teixeira, H., Matos, F.L., *et al.* (in prep). Marine Invasive Alien Species Impacts database – a ShinyApp
- Teixeira et al. (in prep). Cumulative impact of biological invasions – advancing research and supporting management with a new CIMPAL calculator webservice.
- Zhao, Z., Koulouzis, S., Bianchi, R., Farshidi, S., Shi, Z., Xin, R., Wang, Y., Li, N., Shi, Y., Timmermans, J., & Kissling W.D., (2022). Notebook-as-a-VRE (NaaVRE): From private notebooks to a collaborative cloud virtual research environment. *Software: Practice and Experience* 52, no. 9: 1947-1966. <https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.3098>

7.4 Case study 16: Implementation of expanded CIMPAL in the European Seas – LS10

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7.4.1 Introduction

This study represents the second pan-European assessment of the cumulative negative impacts on marine biodiversity caused by invasive alien species invading the European seas, seven years after the first CIMPAL assessment included in the EEA (Korpinen *et al.* 2019). In addition to invasive alien species (IAS), the current assessment includes also the impacts in biodiversity caused by harmful algal blooms (HABs) as well as those caused by jellyfish blooms. This assessment focuses on the identification of the most vulnerable marine regions and/or subregions, sites and habitats, while highlighting the most critical species in terms of spread and magnitude of impact.

7.4.2. Methods

The **CIMPAL index** was applied to assess and map the cumulative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS), harmful algal blooms (HABs), and jellyfish blooms in the **European Seas**. The study area was partitioned into a grid of cells, each measuring 10 x 10 km (according to the EEA grid). For each grid cell, the percent cover of 20 broad habitat types was estimated:

1. Coastal wetlands (incl. salt marshes)
2. Estuaries & coastal lagoons subtidal
3. Estuaries & coastal lagoons intertidal
4. Coastal littoral soft-bottoms
5. Coastal littoral rocky shores
6. Seagrass meadows and Seaweed beds
7. *Posidonia oceanica* meadows
8. Coralligenous formations
9. Submarine caves
10. to 12. Shallow soft, rocky and biogenic substrates (0–60 m depth)
13. to 15. Deep soft, rocky and biogenic substrates (60–200 m depth)
16. to 18. Soft, hard and biogenic substrates of the dysphotic zone (depths > 200 m)
19. to 20. Pelagic habitats above and below 200m depth

The pelagic habitat, covering both coastal and open-sea regions, was included to analyze the impacts of jellyfish blooms and HABs, as these phenomena primarily affect the water column.

The analysis incorporated datasets specific to IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs, combining information from GBIF, monitoring programs, citizen science initiatives, and the scientific and grey literature.

The CIMPAL expanded formula (see section 7.2) was calculated for a baseline assessment of 500m and then aggregated at each grid cell of 10x10km, to separate as well as integrate impacts of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs using the formula:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j w_{i,j} \pm \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i A_k H_j w_{i,j} f_{i,k}$$

Where: I_c refers to the cumulative impact score in a specific study area cell. A_i refers to the population state of species i in the specific cell, standardised to range between 0 and 1. H_j is an index of the extent of habitat j in the cell. $w_{i,j}$ is the impact weight of species i at habitat j , estimated as a combination of species i impact magnitude assessment and the strength of the reported evidence. n represents the total number of IAS, jellyfish, and algal species, and m is the total number of marine habitats that were included in the analysis. A_k represents the population state of species k , an alien species interacting with alien species i , exhibiting either positive or negative effects. A_k values are standardised to range between 0 and 1. $f_{i,k}$ refers to the interaction effect of IAS k on IAS i , taking a value of -1 for maximum negative interactions.

Species distribution data

For this European seas CIMPAL assessment we have considered 127 invasive alien species (IAS), excluding cryptogenic (Cr) species. The distribution data available for these species ranged a period from 1818 to 2025, with one earlier record of the species *Magallana gigas* in 1700, but this exercise only considered occurrences since 1900. The IAS list also includes the 81 IAS in the previous 2018 EEA assessment (Korpinen *et al.* 2019), the 64 IAS in the previous UNEP-MAP regional Assessment for the Mediterranean in 2023 (Teixeira *et al.* in prep), and additional ones considered relevant impacting species at EU-level since these previous large-scale assessments. Of the 127 IAS listed, three species were also relevant species present in harmful algal blooms (HABs), and six species also listed as relevant jellyfish. To avoid duplication in the CIMPAL assessment, these common shared species, together with other eleven Cr IAS were considered in either the jellyfish or HABs CIMPAL assessment, as indicated in [Table 7.4.1](#). For harmful algal blooms (HABs) there was distribution data, ranging from 1978 to 2023, for 92 species ([Table 7.4.2](#)), while for jellyfish data, ranging from 1925 to 2021, was available for 38 species ([Table 7.4.3](#)).

Table 7.4.1. Shared species between invasive alien species (IAS), harmful algal blooms (HABs) and jellyfish datasets and CIMPAL assessment where they were considered, if distribution data was available.

Species	Common lists	CIMPAL assessment
<i>Aurelia solida</i>	IAS & Jellyfish	Jellyfish
<i>Rhopilema nomadica</i>	IAS & Jellyfish	Jellyfish
<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>	IAS & Jellyfish	Jellyfish
<i>Aurelia coerulea</i>	IAS & Jellyfish	Jellyfish
<i>Beroe ovata</i>	IAS & Jellyfish	Jellyfish
<i>Cassiopea andromeda</i>	IAS & Jellyfish	Jellyfish
<i>Karenia mikimotoi</i>	IAS & HABs	HABs
<i>Alexandrium catenella</i>	IAS & HABs	HABs
<i>Fibrocapsa japonica</i>	IAS & HABs	No data
<i>Alexandrium insuetum</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	HABs
<i>Chattonella marina</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Dinophysis infundibulum</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	HABs
<i>Karenia bicuneiformis</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Karenia brevisulcata</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Karenia papilionacea</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Ostreopsis ovata</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	HABs
<i>Prorocentrum mexicanum</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	No data
<i>Vicicitus globosus</i>	HABs & IAS-Cr	HABs

Species occurrences (presence only) distribution often included both point and polygon data per species, which were integrated for the assessment. To transform point occurrences data into polygon data, we considered one common Dispersion Radius (DP; Teixeira *et al.*, in prep) for all HABs and jellyfish species of 2.5 km, for setting a buffer diameter of 5 km with point occurrence at centre. For invasive alien species (IAS) a test buffer, equivalent to such DP, was set per species (Table 7.4.4). Species data have been split by years in case they were reported for aggregated period ranges (e.g. 2001-2004 → 2001, 2001, 2003, 2004). Species co-occurring, i.e., with spatial overlap, within a same year were considered a single observation.

Table 7.4.2. Species responsible for harmful algal blooms (HABs) considered for all European Seas. Only species marked with * had available distribution data for inclusion in the CIMPAL assessment.

Species (* with occurrence data)		
<i>Alexandrium balechii</i> *	<i>Fibrocapsa japonica</i>	<i>Prorocentrum</i> spp.
<i>Alexandrium catenella</i> *	<i>Gonyaulax fragilis</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum cordatum</i> *
<i>Alexandrium insuetum</i> *	<i>Gonyaulax polygramma</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum emarginatum</i>
<i>Alexandrium minutum</i> *	<i>Gonyaulax spinifera</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>
<i>Alexandrium ostenfeldii</i> *	<i>Gonyaulax</i> spp.*	<i>Prorocentrum mexicanum</i>
<i>Alexandrium pacificum</i> *	<i>Gymnodinium breve</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i> *
<i>Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax</i> *	<i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum minimum</i> *
<i>Alexandrium</i> spp.*	<i>Gymnodinium chlorophorum</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum obtusidens</i> *
<i>Alexandrium tamarense</i> *	<i>Gymnodinium</i> sp.*	<i>Prorocentrum redfeldii</i> *
<i>Alexandrium tamiyavanichii</i>	<i>Gyrodinium aureolum</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum rhathymum</i>
<i>Alexandrium taylorii</i> *	<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i> *	<i>Prorocentrum triestinum</i> *
<i>Amphidinium carterae</i>	<i>Karenia bicuneiformis</i>	<i>Protoceratium reticulatum</i>
<i>Amphidinium gibbosum</i>	<i>Karenia brevis-like</i> *	<i>Protoperdinium sphaeroides</i> *
<i>Amphidinium operculatum</i>	<i>Karenia brevisulcata</i>	<i>Prymnesium parvum</i> *
<i>Anabaena lemmermannii</i> *	<i>Karenia mikimotoi</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia australis</i> *
<i>Anabaena</i> spp.*	<i>Karenia papilionacea</i>	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia calliantha</i> *
<i>Aphanizomenon baltica</i> *	<i>Karenia selliformis</i>	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia delicatissima</i> *
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i>	<i>Karlodinium</i> spp.*	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia fraudulenta</i>
<i>Aphanizomenon</i> spp.*	<i>Karlodinium veneficum</i>	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia galaxiae</i>
<i>Azadinium spinosum</i>	<i>Kryptoperidinium foliaceum</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia granii</i>
<i>Calyptrosphaera sphaeroidea</i> *	<i>Leptocylindrus danicus</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata</i>
<i>Centrodinium punctatum</i>	<i>Leptocylindrus minimus</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia pseudodelicatissima</i>
<i>Chaetoceros debilis</i> *	<i>Leptocylindrus</i> spp.*	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia pungens</i>
<i>Chaetoceros</i> spp.*	<i>Lingulodinium polyedra</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia seriata</i>
<i>Chaetoceros tenuissimus</i> *	<i>Lyngbya agardhii</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp.*
<i>Chaetoceros wighamii</i> *	<i>Margalefidinium polykrikoides</i>	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia subfraudulenta</i>
<i>Chattonella antiqua</i>	<i>Mesodinium rubrum</i> *	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia subpacifica</i>
<i>Chattonella globosa</i> *	<i>Mesodinium</i> spp.*	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia turgidula</i>
<i>Chattonella marina</i>	<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i> *	<i>Pyrodinium bahamense</i>
<i>Chattonella</i> sp.*	<i>Microcystis</i> spp.*	<i>Scrippsiella</i> spp.*
<i>Chattonella subsalsa</i>	<i>Navicula forcipata</i> *	<i>Scrippsiella trochoidea</i> *
<i>Chattonella verruculosa</i> *	<i>Nitzschia closterium</i> *	<i>Skeletonema costatum</i> *
<i>Chroococcus gelatinosus</i> *	<i>Nitzschia bizertensis</i> *	<i>Spatulodinium pseudonoctiluca</i> *
<i>Climacosphenia moniligera</i> *	<i>Noctiluca scintillans</i> *	<i>Synechocystis sallensis</i> *
<i>Cyclotella</i> sp.*	<i>Nodularia spumigena</i> *	<i>Synechocystis</i> spp.*
<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i> *	<i>Ostreopsis ovata</i> *	<i>Trichodesmium erythraeum</i> *
<i>Dinophysis acuminata</i> *	<i>Ostreopsis siamensis</i> *	<i>Vicicitus globosus</i> *
<i>Dinophysis acuta</i> *	<i>Ostreopsis</i> sp.*	<i>Vorticella cincta</i> *
<i>Dinophysis caudata</i> *	<i>Peridinium quinquecorne</i> *	
<i>Dinophysis fortii</i> *	<i>Phaeocystis globosa</i> *	
<i>Dinophysis infundibulum</i>	<i>Phaeocystis pouchetii</i> *	
<i>Dinophysis norvegica</i> *	<i>Phaeocystis</i> spp.*	
<i>Dinophysis ovum</i>	<i>Phalacroma mitra</i>	
<i>Dinophysis rotundata</i> *	<i>Phalacroma rotundatum</i> *	
<i>Dinophysis sacculus</i> *	<i>Planktothrix rubescens</i>	
<i>Dinophysis</i> spp.*	<i>Polykrikos hartmannii</i>	
<i>Dinophysis tripos</i> *		

Table 7.4.3. Jellyfish species responsible for blooms considered for all European Seas and with available distribution data for inclusion in the CIMPAL assessment.

Species	
<i>Aequorea vitrina</i>	<i>Mnemiopsis</i> sp.
<i>Apolemia uvaria</i>	<i>Muggiaea atlantica</i>
<i>Aurelia aurita</i>	<i>Muggiaea kochii</i>
<i>Aurelia coerulea</i>	<i>Obelia geniculata</i>
<i>Aurelia solida</i>	<i>Obelia</i> spp.
<i>Aurelia</i> sp.	<i>Olindias muelleri</i>
<i>Beroe ovata</i>	<i>Olindias phosphorica</i>
<i>Blackfordia virginica</i>	<i>Pelagia noctiluca</i>
<i>Bolinopsis infundibulum</i>	<i>Pennaria disticha</i>
<i>Bolinopsis vitrea</i>	<i>Periphylla periphylla</i>
<i>Carybdea marsupialis</i>	<i>Phyllorhiza punctata</i>
<i>Cassiopea andromeda</i>	<i>Phialella quadrata</i>
<i>Chrysaora hysoscella</i>	<i>Physalia physalis</i>
<i>Cotylorhiza tuberculata</i>	<i>Pleurobrachia pileus</i>
<i>Cyanea capillata</i>	<i>Rhizostoma pulmo</i>
<i>Dipleurosoma typicum</i>	<i>Rhopilema nomadica</i>
<i>Geryonia proboscidalis</i>	<i>Salpa maxima</i>
<i>Liriope tetraphylla</i>	<i>Solmaris corona</i>
<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>	<i>Veella veella</i>

Table 7.4.4. Selected invasive alien species (IAS) (n = 118) in European Seas, with available distribution data for inclusion in the CIMPAL IAS assessment, with respective buffer diameter (m) tested in this exercise for point occurrences. No evidence of impacts available for light coloured species names.

SpeciesName	Buffer	SpeciesName	Buffer	SpeciesName	Buffer
<i>Acrothamnion preissii</i>	1	<i>Ensis directus</i>	1	<i>Parupeneus forsskali</i>	500
<i>Gracilaria vermiculophylla</i>	1	<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i>	100	<i>Pempheris rhomboidea</i>	500
<i>Alepes djedaba</i>	5000	<i>Erugosquilla massavensis</i>	100	<i>Penaeus aztecus</i>	100
<i>Alexandrium monilatum</i>	5000	<i>Etrumeus golanii</i>	10000	<i>Penaeus japonicus</i>	100
<i>Amphistegina lobifera</i>	1	<i>Eucheilota paradoxa</i>	5000	<i>Penaeus pulchricaudatus</i>	100
<i>Anadara kagoshimensis</i>	1	<i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i>	1	<i>Penaeus semisulcatus</i>	100
<i>Anadara transversa</i>	1	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	10000	<i>Pinctada imbricata radiata</i>	1
<i>Antithamnion nipponicum</i>	1	<i>Fulvia fragilis</i>	1	<i>Plotosus lineatus</i>	1000
<i>Arcuatula senhousia</i>	1	<i>Galaxaura rugosa</i>	1	<i>Polyandrocarpa zorritensis</i>	1
<i>Asparagopsis armata</i>	1	<i>Gammarus tigrinus</i>	100	<i>Polysiphonia morrowii</i>	1
<i>Asparagopsis taxiformis</i>	1	<i>Grateloupia turuturu</i>	1	<i>Portunus segnis</i>	1000
<i>Atherinomorus forskalii</i>	10000	<i>Halimeda incrassata</i>	1	<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i>	10
<i>Austrominius modestus</i>	1	<i>Halophila stipulacea</i>	1	<i>Pseudochattonella verruculosa</i>	5000
<i>Bonnemaisonia hamifera</i>	1	<i>Hemigrapsus sanguineus</i>	100	<i>Pseudodiptomus marinus</i>	5000
<i>Botrylloides violaceus</i>	1	<i>Herdmania momus</i>	1	<i>Pterois miles</i>	500
<i>Brachidontes pharaonis</i>	1	<i>Herklotsichthys punctatus</i>	10000	<i>Rapana venosa</i>	50
<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	1000	<i>Homarus americanus</i>	100	<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisii</i>	100
<i>Caprella mutica</i>	1	<i>Hydroides elegans</i>	1	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	1
<i>Caulerpa cylindracea</i>	1	<i>Hydroides ezoensis</i>	1	<i>Rugulopteryx okamurae</i>	1
<i>Caulerpa taxifolia</i>	1	<i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i>	10000	<i>Sargassum muticum</i>	1
<i>Caulerpa taxifolia var. distichophylla</i>	1	<i>Lagocephalus suezensis</i>	10000	<i>Sargocentron rubrum</i>	100
<i>Cercopagis pengoi</i>	100	<i>Liza haematocheila</i>	10000	<i>Saurida lessepsianus</i>	10000
<i>Chaetoceros bacteriastroides</i>	100	<i>Lophocladia lallemandii</i>	1	<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i>	10000
<i>Chama pacifica</i>	1	<i>Macrorhynchia philippina</i>	1	<i>Siganus luridus</i>	1000
<i>Chionoecetes opilio</i>	1000	<i>Magallana gigas</i>	1	<i>Siganus rivulatus</i>	1000
<i>Chrysonephos lewisii</i>	1	<i>Magallana spp.</i>	1	<i>Sphyræna chrysoænia</i>	10000
<i>Ciona robusta</i>	1	<i>Marenzelleria spp.</i>	10	<i>Spondylus spinosus</i>	1
<i>Cladophora patentiramea</i>	1	<i>Mercenaria mercenaria</i>	1	<i>Streblospio gynobranchiata</i>	1
<i>Clavelina oblonga</i>	1	<i>Metapenaeus monoceros</i>	100	<i>Styela clava</i>	1
<i>Codium arabicum</i>	1	<i>Metapenaeus stebbingi</i>	100	<i>Styela plicata</i>	1
<i>Codium fragile subsp. fragile</i>	1	<i>Microcosmus squamiger</i>	1	<i>Stypopodium schimperi</i>	1
<i>Codium parvulum</i>	1	<i>Mya arenaria</i>	1	<i>Telmatogeton japonicus</i>	500
<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	10	<i>Nemipterus randalli</i>	1000	<i>Torquigener flavimaculosus</i>	1000
<i>Crepidula fornicata</i>	10	<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>	500	<i>Tricellaria inopinata</i>	1
<i>Decapterus russelli</i>	10000	<i>Oithona davisae</i>	100	<i>Triconia umerus</i>	1000
<i>Diadema setosum</i>	100	<i>Palaemon macrodactylus</i>	100	<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>	1
<i>Didemnum vexillum</i>	1	<i>Paracartia grani grani</i>	100	<i>Upeneus moluccensis</i>	500
<i>Dussumieria elopsoides</i>	10000	<i>Paracerceis sculpta</i>	100	<i>Upeneus pori</i>	500
<i>Dyspanopeus sayi</i>	100	<i>Paraleucilla magna</i>	1	<i>Urosalpinx cinerea</i>	10
				<i>Womersleyella setacea</i>	1

Data available on species distribution spans a large temporal frame, thus we decide for conducting the CIMPAL assessment following three alternative temporal scales of assessment, one reflecting a large period for which cumulative impacts. i.e. CIMPAL, were calculated including georeferenced data from all available years and starting from 1900 onwards (n = 728 HABs entries; n = 4677 jellyfish entries; n = 192 703 IAS entries), and two additional periods with relevance for the MSFD, corresponding to the 1st and 2nd assessment cycles, i.e., from 2012 to 2017 and from 2018 to 2023, from which most of the data comes from. The discrepancy in the overall number of observations considered in the three datasets is related to the fact that for many HABs and Jellyfish entries often correspond to large polygons, while for IAS only point occurrences were considered. These final observations' numbers reflect data falling within the study area defined by the EEA marine grid for the European seas and cleaned of duplicate entries (at year level), i.e. eliminating any spatial overlap between species observed within a same year, using the DP of the observations described above.

For IAS the distribution occurrences data came from 1) GBIF (as of 20250625), 2) from the previous first pan-European assessment of IAS (Korpinen et al. 2019), 3) from a compilation of historical data in the Portuguese mainland marine and coastal (Pinheiro et al. 2019) and 4) from the latest UNEP-MAP Regional Seas assessment for the Mediterranean in 2023 (Teixeira et al. in prep). This dataset will be curated and made available in Zenodo.

Impacts evidence

This European seas CIMPAL assessment considered only the risk of negative impacts on biodiversity from HABs, Jellyfish and IAS. We have considered an overall impact magnitude (maximum reported) per species, for IAS, HABs and jellyfish, where impact magnitude is based on collected evidence of previous observed impacts of a species across regions and habitats. The impact information reported was translated into a numeric CIMPAL magnitude of impacts (Moi) scale, ranging from 0 to 8, according to Katsanevakis *et al.* (2016). The strength of the evidence (SoE) of documented impacts found for HABs and jellyfish was in general poorly reported; nonetheless both precautionary and uncertainty averse CIMPAL approaches were calculated. For HABs species lacking information on impacts in biodiversity, we assumed "harmful" as a negative impact risk and considered a default Magnitude of Impact of Moderate (Moi = 2; indicating changes at population level) based on expert judgement (SoE is limited). For the jellyfish species lacking information on impacts in biodiversity, we assumed the jellyfish outburst as posing a risk of negative impacts and considered a default Magnitude of Impact of Moderate (Moi = 2; indicating changes at population level) based on expert judgement

(SoE is limited). For IAS, the information regarding the maximum values of reported Magnitude of Impact (Moi) for each species-habitat pair was considered. This information was extracted from the Database of Marine IAS Impacts (ShinyApp, Teixeira, Matos et al. *in prep*). Both Moi and Moi-SoE impact weights were extracted, supporting both Precautionary and Uncertainty-averse calculations of CIMPAL. There were 27 IAS ([Table 7.4.4](#)) in our list for which no evidence of impact on biodiversity existed in the database thus their Magnitude of Impact = 0 across all habitats.

The impacts of HABs and jellyfish were restricted to the pelagic habitat, as little detail as available for further habitat impact scrutiny in most impact evidence. For IAS, impacts across different habitat types were considered (see [list of habitats](#) abovementioned). Weights used for scoring the Magnitude of impact for the precautionary and uncertainty averse CIMPAL assessments will be made available as annex.

Biotic interactions

CIMPAL with and without biotic interactions for IAS were both considered for comparison (see previous [Section 7.3](#)). Biotic interactions evidence between IAS in this study was extracted from the **Global Biotic Interactions GloBI** database (Jorrit *et al.* 2014). The type of interactions found between IAS in our list reflected mostly negative interactions and were **predation interactions**, where the prey species is harmed and thus the affecting IAS will be reducing that other species population overall impact capacity. No evidence for positive interactions between species in our list were found in the GloBI database. The 58 unique interaction pairs ([Table 7.4.5](#)) reflect such negative interactions affecting 38 species (focus IAS) caused by 22 species (affecting IAS) in our list. No interactions between Jellyfish species or HABs species were considered in this European Seas CIMPAL assessment.

CIMPAL was calculated at a baseline resolution of 500m for all runs in this European Seas assessment and aggregated a posteriori to a 10x10km grid size, where a mean CIMPAL per cell was calculated (*sensu* Teixeira *et al.*, *in prep*). No Pathways of Introduction for IAS have been considered in this study.

Table 7.4.5. Invasive alien species (IAS) biotic interactions (BI) based on GloBI evidence (dataset extracted as of June 2025).

All interactions refer to predation of the focus species by the affecting species and have a negative association (BI signal).

Focus IAS	Affecting IAS	BI signal
<i>Alexandrium monilatum</i>	<i>Magallana</i>	-1
<i>Alexandrium catenella</i>	<i>Magallana</i>	-1
<i>Alexandrium monilatum</i>	<i>Magallana gigas</i>	-1
<i>Alexandrium catenella</i>	<i>Magallana gigas</i>	-1
<i>Anadara transversa</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Asparagopsis taxiformis</i>	<i>Siganus luridus</i>	-1
<i>Asparagopsis taxiformis</i>	<i>Siganus rivulatus</i>	-1
<i>Caulerpa cylindracea</i>	<i>Siganus luridus</i>	-1
<i>Caulerpa cylindracea</i>	<i>Siganus rivulatus</i>	-1
<i>Chaetoceros bacteriaströides</i>	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	-1
<i>Chionoecetes opilio</i>	<i>Paralithodes camtschaticus</i>	-1
<i>Cladophora patentiramea</i>	<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>	-1
<i>Crepidula fornicata</i>	<i>Homarus americanus</i>	-1
<i>Dyspanopeus sayi</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Ensis directus</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Gammarus tigrinus</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Gammarus tigrinus</i>	<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>	-1
<i>Halophila stipulacea</i>	<i>Penaeus semisulcatus</i>	-1
<i>Halophila stipulacea</i>	<i>Siganus luridus</i>	-1
<i>Hemigrapsus sanguineus</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Homarus americanus</i>	<i>Homarus americanus</i>	-1
<i>Magallana</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Magallana gigas</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Marenzelleria</i>	<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>	-1
<i>Mercenaria mercenaria</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Mercenaria mercenaria</i>	<i>Hemigrapsus sanguineus</i>	-1
<i>Mercenaria mercenaria</i>	<i>Rapana venosa</i>	-1
<i>Metapenaeus monoceros</i>	<i>Metapenaeus monoceros</i>	-1
<i>Metapenaeus monoceros</i>	<i>Upeneus moluccensis</i>	-1
<i>Metapenaeus stebbingi</i>	<i>Metapenaeus monoceros</i>	-1
<i>Metapenaeus stebbingi</i>	<i>Upeneus moluccensis</i>	-1
<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>	<i>Beroe ovata</i>	-1
<i>Mya arenaria</i>	<i>Homarus americanus</i>	-1
<i>Mya arenaria</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>	<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>	-1
<i>Oithona davisae</i>	<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>	-1
<i>Palaemon macrodactylus</i>	<i>Palaemon macrodactylus</i>	-1
<i>Paralithodes camtschaticus</i>	<i>Chionoecetes opilio</i>	-1
<i>Paralithodes camtschaticus</i>	<i>Paralithodes camtschaticus</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus aztecus</i>	<i>Decapterus russelli</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus aztecus</i>	<i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus aztecus</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus japonicus</i>	<i>Decapterus russelli</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus japonicus</i>	<i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus pulchricaudatus</i>	<i>Decapterus russelli</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus pulchricaudatus</i>	<i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus semisulcatus</i>	<i>Decapterus russelli</i>	-1
<i>Penaeus semisulcatus</i>	<i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i>	-1
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i>	<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>	-1
<i>Pterois miles</i>	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	-1
<i>Rapana venosa</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>	<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>	-1
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>	<i>Palaemon macrodactylus</i>	-1
<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	<i>Rapana venosa</i>	-1
<i>Sargassum muticum</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1
<i>Sargassum muticum</i>	<i>Siganus luridus</i>	-1
<i>Urosalpinx cinerea</i>	<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	-1

7.4.3 Results

Cumulative impact scores for HABs in EU seas are spatially limited and their extension differs greatly if a precautionary or an uncertainty-averse strategy is applied, reflecting the poor strength of evidence underlying most impacts documentation available for HABs (Figure 7.4.1). Taking a precautionary approach, we observed that less than 1% of the area of the European seas is negatively affected by harmful algal blooms. The aggregated CIMPAL results per grid cell indicate impact scores ranging from 0 to 40.3 (Figure 7.4.1), with a very low average score of 0.025 per cell (considering only cells with impacts). The areas most affected are in the Aegean Sea and in the Black Sea, with some spots across coastal European waters.

Cumulative impact scores for jellyfish blooms are much widely spread and show similar patterns whether a precautionary or an uncertainty-averse strategy is applied, differing slightly in magnitude (Figure 7.4.2). Taking a precautionary approach, we observed that nearly 10% of the area of the European seas is negatively affected by jellyfish blooms. The aggregated CIMPAL results per grid cell indicate impact scores ranging from 0 to 11.5 (Figure 7.4.2), with an average score of 4.2 per cell (considering only cells with impacts). The Black Sea and the Northern Adriatic are the most affected areas by jellyfish blooms. Several other coastal regions across European seas show some impacts, such as in the Western Baltic, in the Greater North Sea (coast of UK and off Germany), along the Irish coasts, in the Western Mediterranean Sea, some areas in the Aegean Sea and the Mediterranean Levantine coast.

HABs

Figure 7.4.1. Map of cumulative impacts for harmful algal blooms (HABs) in European Seas using CIMPAL-JH index scores according to a Precautionary (top graphs) and an Uncertainty-averse approach (bottom graphs), for the period ranging between 1978 to 2023. Both cumulative CIMPAL impact scores at the baseline resolution of 500 m (left graphs) and the mean CIMPAL score aggregated at 10x10km grid cell (right graphs) are shown.

Jellyfish

Figure 7.4.2. Map of cumulative impacts for jellyfish blooms in European Seas using CIMPAL-JH index scores according to a Precautionary (top graphs) and an Uncertainty-averse approach (bottom graphs), for the period ranging between 1925 to 2021. Both cumulative CIMPAL impact scores at the baseline resolution of 500 m (left graphs) and the mean CIMPAL score aggregated at 10x10km grid cell (right graphs) are shown.

Occurrences of 127 NIS within the EEA marine area are distributed across all European regional seas and mostly along coastal areas (Figure 7.4.3). For the Black and the Mediterranean Seas the coverage of areas under non-EU Member States is more limited. NIS distribution, since 1900, includes NIS species that are also considered in the HABs and Jellyfish assessments.

Figure 7.4.3. Occurrences of 127 Invasive Alien Species (IAS) within the European Environment Agency (EEA) area of the European seas since 1900, including nine species that are also considered in the Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and Jellyfish assessments.

For the most recent period, corresponding to the MSFD second cycle of implementation between 2018 and 2023, the cumulative impact scores of IAS are widespread along coastal waters, while the negative impact footprint is less pronounced in open marine environments (Figure 7.4.4). A CIMPAL precautionary approach was tested accounting for biotic interactions between the selected IAS, with the maximum mean impact score observed ($I_c = 13.62$) differing only slightly in magnitude from when no interactions were considered ($I_c = 13.87$) (Figure 7.4.4).

IAS 2018-2023 (2nd MSFD cycle)
500 m

10 x 10 km

CIMPAL Precautionary approach without biotic interactions

CIMPAL Precautionary approach with biotic interactions

Figure 7.4.4. Maps of cumulative negative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS $n = 118$) in European Seas according to CIMPAL index scores using a Precautionary Approach (top graphs) and considering species biotic interactions (bottom graphs), for the period ranging between 2018 to 2023. Both cumulative CIMPAL impact scores at the baseline resolution of 500 m (left graphs) and the mean CIMPAL score aggregated at 10x10km grid cell (right graphs) are shown.

The integration of cumulative negative impacts of all invasive species (HABs, Jellyfish and NIS) using a CIMPAL-JH Precautionary Approach, without biotic interactions, calculated for the most recent period 2018 to 2023 corresponding to the MSFD second cycle, does not change the mean maximum impact score observed in an area ($I_c = 13.87$) comparatively to that observed solely for IAS in the same conditions (Figure 7.4.5). However, the spatial patterns observed are different and the area affected by the cumulative negative impacts of these invasive groups is wider.

CIMPAL-JH HABs, Jellyfish, IAS
Precautionary Approach without biotic interactions (2018 to 2023)

10 x 10 km

Figure 7.4.5. Mean cumulative negative impact score given by CIMPAL-JH for the European Seas, caused by invasive alien species (IAS n = 118), harmful algal blooms (HABs n = 92) and Jellyfish blooms (n = 38), aggregated at 10x10km grid cells for the period between 2018-2023, using a precautionary approach without biotic interactions.

7.4.4 Discussion

In this report we present the progress towards the pan-European implantation of CIMPAL to assess the cumulative impact of invasive species (NIS, HABs and Jellyfish) in European seas. The results presented illustrate potential scenarios that can be explored using the CIMPAL-JH index, and are preliminary results. The full implementation is not yet concluded, and some adjustments may be necessary, for e.g. on species point occurrences buffers, but all data is gathered and pre-processed and we include here examples of results of CIMPAL for HABs and Jellyfish and IAS separately as well as an integrated assessment. Additional calculations under different scenarios will further be explored

such as the differences between CIMPAL Precautionary Approach *versus* Uncertainty-Averse Strategy assessments; inclusion of biotic interactions also for HABs and Jellyfish; the effect of the number of species included in the assessments (see for e.g. Zengeya *et al.* 2025); and the relevant temporal and spatial scale of aggregations according to the context and objectives of the assessments. Also, the integration of the three components, i.e. HABs, Jellyfish, NIS, into a single CIMPAL-JH assessment is undergoing for different scenarios, as so far only the scenario regarding most recent years was shown, corresponding to the MSFD 2nd cycle of implementation. The identification of invasive species for management based on ranking according to CIMPAL complementary indices D1 to D4, as well as the habitats most at risk will also be assessed in the near-future for this pan-EU study. Along with a full analysis per regional sea.

This wide-range case study posed a challenge in terms of data compilation, harmonisation and integration, allowing to test CIMPAL latest implementations towards easier and automated reproducibility of large-scale environmental assessments using standardised indices approaches. We have compiled different sources of spatial information to generate EU-level updated mapping for the 20 habitat categories considered in this study (*spatial layers will be made available in ZENODO as an open access spatial data set*); we have produced an automated workflow for extracting biotic interactions from the Global **Biotic Interactions** database GloBI (*will be made available in GitHub as an open repository*); used an automated workflow using the **Marine IAS Impacts database ShinyAPP** for summarising literature evidence on negative impacts of IAS in biodiversity and extract that information in a standardised way (*database to be openly available online and released within summer of 2025, deposited in ZENODO*); produced an automated script to extract country level **species occurrences from GBIF** for countries within European seas area and **integrate that data with other sources**, removing duplicates based on location and year level (*will be made available in GitHub as an open repository*). These automated procedures are moving our research towards increased accuracy and reproducibility, and this workflow tested for this pan-European can be re-used in other scales and locations. This is a crucial step towards meeting more effective policy implementation goals.

The preliminary results of a large-scale assessment using as example this pan-European case study brings us closer towards the goal of the project of supporting MSFD implementation and other EU regulations, such as the EEA upcoming Marine Messages III Report; the Regional Sea Conventions regional assessment programmes, and the Member States implementation of the MSFD, the EU Regulation on Invasive Alien Species and national Biodiversity Strategies.

7.4.5 References

- Katsanevakis, S., Tempera, F., & Teixeira, H. (2016). Mapping the impact of alien species on marine ecosystems: the Mediterranean Sea case study. *Diversity and Distributions*, 22(6), 694-707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12429>
- Korpinen, S., Klančnik, K., Peterlin, M., Nurmi, M., Laamanen, L., Zupančič, G., Popit, A., Murray, C., Harvey, T., Andersen, J.H., Zenetos, A., Stein, U., Tunesi, L., Abhold, K., Piet, G., Kallenbach, E., Agnesi, S., Bolman, B., Vaughan, D., Reker, J. & Royo Gelabert, E., (2019). Multiple pressures and their combined effects in Europe's seas. ETC/ICM Technical Report 4/2019: European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine waters, 164 pp.
- Poelen, J.H., Simons, J.D., & Mungall., C.J., (2014). Global Biotic Interactions: An open infrastructure to share and analyze species-interaction datasets. *Ecological Informatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>
- Teixeira et al. (*in prep*). Cumulative impact of biological invasions – advancing research and supporting management with a new CIMPAL calculator webservice.
- Teixeira, H., Matos, F. L., et al. (*in prep*). Marine Invasive Alien Species Impacts database – a ShinyApp
- Zengeya T, Faulkner K, Mtileni P, Wilson JR (2025) Lessons and challenges in creating alien species lists: insights from South Africa's national reports on the status and management of biological invasions. *ARPHA Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.3897/arphapreprints.e163028>

7.5 Case study 17: Implementation of CIMPAL in LS1

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7.5.1 Introduction

The invasive species in the northern Baltic Sea are typically brackish-water species originating from estuarine port areas. As the Baltic Sea ecosystem is relatively young, formed through a series of marine and fluvial phases after the last ice age, there are fewer species than in the nearby oceanic or freshwater ecosystems. This implies a potential for empty niches in the sea region. These may be filled by new species introduced by human activities. Nonetheless, there is always a risk of significant environmental impacts, including catastrophic events or more localized effects and therefore the Baltic Sea countries have cooperated for two to three decades through HELCOM to prevent arrival of new IAS. HELCOM has recorded all the NIS (Non-Indigenous species) observations and arrivals and these provide a useful database for analyzing IAS in the region.

7.5.2 Methods

The CIMPAL method was applied using the standard formula to the LS1 study area ([Figure 7.5](#)), an area of roughly 100,000 km² which covers both the Swedish and Finnish marine area of the Gulf of Bothnia. Two impact indices were created, an impact index and a stressor index. Additionally, the amount each stressor contributed towards the final impact value of each ecosystem component was calculated. The impact index was composed of 7 NIS (Non-Indigenous species) layers and 1 HABs (Harmful Algal Blooms) layer for stressors and 12 broad-scale seabed habitat layers and 2 pelagic habitat layers for ecosystem components. For the analyses, all stressor and ecosystem component layers were converted to 400 x 400 m cell size raster grids. The open-source tool EcoImpactMapper (Stock, 2016) was used to create the indices and calculate stressor contribution, while ArcGIS was used for all other GIS work.

For ecosystem components, the EMODnet EUSeaMap 2023 broad-scale seabed habitats (downloaded via <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/>) present in LS1 were used: infralittoral sand, infralittoral mud, infralittoral mixed sediment, infralittoral coarse sediment, infralittoral rock and biogenic reef, circalittoral sand, circalittoral mud, circalittoral mixed sediment, circalittoral coarse sediment, circalittoral rock and biogenic reef, offshore circalittoral mud, and offshore circalittoral mixed sediment. As the seabed habitats data did not extend to all parts of the coastal area, the data was expanded where necessary using a majority function (i.e. missing coastal areas were given the

habitat type of the majority habitat nearby). Seabed habitats raster values represented the number of hectares of the habitat in each 400 * 400m cell. To represent the pelagic zone, the HELCOM HOLAS 3 (HELCOM, 2023) pelagic habitats productive surface waters Chl-a 2016-2021 and bottom habitats not influenced by permanent anoxia 2016-2021 were also included. All ecosystem component layer values were normalised to 0–1.

Figure 7.5.1. Map of the northern Baltic Sea showing the extent of LS1.

Selected mainly according to data availability and due to being established and widespread, seven invasive alien species layers were included in the analysis: *Cercopagis pengoi* (fishhook waterflea), *Dreissena polymorpha* (zebra mussel), *Marenzelleria* spp. (3 species of a polychaete genus), *Mytilopsis leucophaeata* (Conrad's false mussel), *Neogobius melanostomus* (round goby), *Rhithropanopeus harrisii* (Harris mud crab), and *Sinelobus vanhaareni* (an isopod). All invasive species observation data was based on open-source observation point data from the years 2000–2023, with Swedish observations downloaded from Artportalen (<https://www.artportalen.se/>) and the SMHI SHARKweb service (<https://www.smhi.se/>), and Finnish observations downloaded from the Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility website (<https://laji.fi>), totalling 21,272 records, of which 20,622 were *Marenzelleria* spp. observations (Table 7.5.1). The Swedish data contained no *D. polymorpha*, *R. harrisii*, or *S. vanhaareni* observations in the LS1 area.

Around each observation point, a dispersion gradient (Figure 7.5.2 and Table 7.5.1) was created with values (0–1) decreasing according to the distance to the nearest points, with clusters of points

receiving additional weight. This gradient created based on expert judgement, represents a decreasing confidence of encountering the species from any given observation point, with higher likelihoods within and around observation clusters. Additionally, areas deemed too deep for any given species were removed.

Figure 7.5.2. Example of a dispersion gradient (*R. Harrisii*) of the coast of Finland, near Uusikaupunki. Values represent confidence that the species is present, and points represent observation records.

Table 7.5.1. List of the included NIS in the application of CIMPAL in LS1 with information on the data source, number of records (points), the path of introduction and dispersion radius.

Species	Source	Records	Path of introduction	Dispersion gradient radius (km)
<i>C. pengoi</i>	SHARKweb, FinBIF	32	Ballast water	15
<i>D. polymorpha</i>	Artportalen (no records in LS1), FinBIF	2	Ballast water (or attached to ship)	5
<i>Marenzelleria spp.</i>	SHARKweb, FinBIF	20622	Ballast water	15
<i>M. leucophaeata</i>	Artportalen, FinBIF	61	Ballast water (or attached to ship)	5
<i>N. melanostomus</i>	Artportalen, FinBIF	292	Ballast water (or eggs attached to ship)	15
<i>R. harrisii</i>	Artportalen, FinBIF	218	Ballast water (or attached to ship)	15
<i>S. vanhaareni</i>	Artportalen (no records in LS1), FinBIF	46	Ballast water	5

As *C. pengoi* and *Marezzelleria* spp. were presumed to be more widespread in LS1 than what the observation data indicated, both dispersion gradient spatial layers of these species were supplemented by species distribution models created by OBIS for the MPA Europe project (Ocean Biogeographic Information System, 2024). The distribution models were normalised to 0–1 and combined with the dispersion gradient layers using a “maximum value” function for overlapping cells.

The HABs data included in the analysis was derived from Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) satellite image-based raster data depicting the number of days with cyanobacteria surface bloom (mean of years 2018–2023) in open sea areas. As the HABs spatial data was georeferenced and rasterised from .png images, it contains occasional minor inaccuracies due to the transformation of colour bands to integer values. Values were normalised to 0–1.

Jellyfish blooms were not included in the analysis as data on the phenomenon was too limited in LS1. Most jellyfish observation data points were sightings of single or several jellyfish individuals, with no data point indicating a large-scale bloom. Furthermore, and as indicated by the lack of observations, jellyfish blooms are not thought to be a significant environmental impact in the area.

For weight values ($w_{i,j}$), the sensitivity score table created for the report “Multiple pressures and their combined effects in Europe’s seas” by Korpinen et al. 2019 was used as a base by Syke’s experts to create a new matrix applicable to the pressure and ecosystem component data used in the analysis.

7.5.3 Results

CIMPAL cumulative impact scores ranged from 0 to 11.93, with a median value of 3.62 and mean value of 3.78. The highest impacted area was the Finnish coastal area in the southern half of the Bothnian Sea (Figure 7.5.3). Areas near Oulu and Raahe (Finnish northern part of LS1) also had impact hot spots. Regarding the Swedish coast, the region near Gävle (southern part of LS1) was most impacted. The Swedish coast also had several small hot spots in the northern half of the Bothnian Sea. The most affected open areas were the southern Bothnian Sea. Of the 642,916 grid cells in the research area, an impact score of 0 was received by 6,004 cells (0.93%).

Figure 7.5.3. CIMPAL cumulative impact index. The analysis included 8 stressor layers (7 NIS and 1 HABs) and 14 ecosystem components (12 seabed habitats and 2 pelagic habitats).

A stressor index was also produced (Figure 7.5.4). The stressor index did not include ecosystem component layers, instead it was an aggregation of only stressor layers, each first weighted with the mean of its ecosystem component sensitivity scores. The stressor index indicated that the southern Finnish coast in the Bothnian Sea has the highest concentration of stressors.

Figure 7.5.4. CIMPAL stressor index. An aggregation of only stressor layers, with each layer weighted with their mean sensitivity weights.

Of the 8 stressors included in the impact index, *Marengelleria* spp. had the highest total impact, accounting for 75% of the aggregated impact score of all cells (Figure 7.5.5). All ecosystem components except infralittoral rock, circalittoral rock, pelagic habitats not influenced by permanent anoxia and productive surface waters were most impacted by *Marengelleria* spp. (Table 7.5.2). For each ecosystem component at all impacted by *Marengelleria* spp., it accounted for 90-100% of the total impact score (Figure 7.5.6). *Cercopagis pengoi* and cyanobacteria blooms had the second and third highest total impact, accounting for 12% and 11% respectively. *Dreissena polymorpha* had the lowest total impact, accounting only for 0.003%.

- Marenzelleria spp. (75%)
- Cercopagis pengoi (12%)
- Cyanobacteria (11%)
- Neogobius melanostomus (1.8%)
- Rhithropanopeus harrisi (0.6%)
- Mytilopsis leucophaeata (0.07%)
- Sinelobus vanhaareni (0.01%)
- Dreissena polymorpha (0.003%)

Figure 7.5.5. The percentage each stressor layer contributed for the total impact score in LS1.

Table 7.5.2. The stressor that most affected each ecosystem component/habitat.

Ecosystem component	Main stressor
Infralittoral coarse sediment	Marenzelleria spp.
Infralittoral mixed sediment	Marenzelleria spp.
Infralittoral mud	Marenzelleria spp.
Infralittoral rock	Mytilopsis leucophaeata
Infralittoral sand	Marenzelleria spp.
Circalittoral coarse sediment	Marenzelleria spp.
Circalittoral mixed sediment	Marenzelleria spp.
Circalittoral mud	Marenzelleria spp.
Circalittoral rock	Neogobius melanostomus
Circalittoral sand	Marenzelleria spp.
Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment	Marenzelleria spp.
Offshore circalittoral mud	Marenzelleria spp.
Pelagic habitats not influenced by permanent anoxia	Cyanobacteria
Productive surface waters	Cercopagis pengoi

Figure 7.5.6. The percentage each stressor layer contributed for the total impact score of each ecosystem component.

The seabed habitat that received the highest impact relative to total habitat area was infralittoral mixed sediment, with a score of 3.93 (Figure 7.5.7). Rock and offshore habitats received the smallest relative scores, ranging from 0.40 to 0.86. Other seabed habitats received relative scores ranging from 2.64 to 3.57.

Figure 7.5.7. The total impact score divided by the total area of the seabed habitat.

7.5.4 Discussion

Over 200 NIS/CS (CS: Cryptogenic Species) have been documented in the Baltic Sea, of which about 60% of the established species have arrived either via shipping or spread naturally from neighbouring areas (HELCOM, 2023). The ecological effects of some Baltic Sea NIS, such as *C. pengoi*, *D. polymorpha*, *Marenzelleria* spp. and *N. melanostomus*, have been substantially studied, but for some 60% of the wide-spread NIS in the Baltic Sea information on their potential impacts is still very lacking (Ojaveer et al., 2021). For the LS1 CIMPAL analysis, it was presumed that all included NIS at least compete for resources and living space with native species that share the same niche.

Cercopagis pengoi, a water flea, first invaded the Baltic Sea in 1992 via ballast water. As a predator, *C. pengoi* can have an impact on zooplankton communities and alter ecosystems. Three native commercially important fish (*Clupea harengus*, *Sprattus sprattus* and *Osmerus eperlanus*) may be affected by *C. pengoi*, as they all feed on the same zooplankton. However, *C. pengoi* may have a net positive effect on the three fish species, as *C. pengoi* has been incorporated into the diets of these fish. So far, studies of the effects of *C. pengoi* in the Baltic Sea have mainly focused on the southern parts. (Telesh & Ojaveer, 2002; Rowe et al., 2016; Oesterwind et al., 2025)

Dreissena polymorpha, a bivalve mollusc from the relatively warm waters of Ponto–Caspia, invaded the eastern Gulf of Finland in the mid 1980's, probably via shipping, though it had lived in the southern Baltic Sea in small numbers for over 150 years before that. *D. polymorpha* has been observed to affect all trophic levels of its invaded ecosystem. It can play a significant role in benthic-pelagic coupling and can significantly alter water and nutrient turnover. It is also possible that the presence of *D. polymorpha* can lead to an increase in filamentous algae abundance. (Orlova & Panov, 2004; Orlova et al., 2004)

Marenzelleria spp., which are polychaete worms, were first found in the Baltic Sea in 1985, most likely arriving via ship transport, and by 1990 they had expanded into Finnish waters (Stigzelius et al., 1997). The long-term ecological effects caused by *Marenzelleria* spp. are not clear (Maximov et al., 2015), though they have, for example been shown to reduce the survival of *Hediste diversicolor* (Kotta et al., 2001). *Marenzelleria* spp. has also in large parts replaced *Monoporeia affinis* in the northern Baltic Sea, however, experiments indicate that *Marenzelleria* spp. might not have been the cause of the decrease of *M. affinis* (Eriksson Wiklund & Andersson, 2014). *Marenzelleria* spp. are also thought to have positive ecological effects for example by mitigating eutrophication and HABs (Maximov et al., 2015).

Mytilopsis leucophaeata, a small bivalve mollusc, was first observed in the Baltic Sea in 2003, when it was found in the Gulf of Finland. In 2006, it was found in the Gulf of Bothnia. The mollusc has very likely arrived in the Baltic Sea via ballast water. Originally, *M. leucophaeta* was only found near cooling water discharge sites, but more recently, in 2011–2015, it has also been found in areas not near discharge sites. It is unclear what ecosystem impact *M. leucophaeata* may or may not have, but it is likely that it will compete for resources with at least *D. polymorpha* and *M. edulis trossulus*. (Laine et al., 2006; Forsström et al., 2016; Brzana et al., 2017).

Neogobius melanostomus, a bottom-dwelling fish, originates from the Black Sea and Sea of Azov and spread to the Baltic Sea in 1990, likely via ballast water (Kotta et al., 2015; Brauer et al., 2020). *N. melanostomus* has been shown by experiments done in the Åland islands by Hensler et al. (2021) to decrease overall abundance, biomass and taxon richness of macroinvertebrates. Invertebrate mean size decreased as *N. melanostomus* mainly fed on larger individuals. *Neogobius melanostomus* is also likely to affect native fish populations as it has been observed to feed on fish eggs and fish in early life stages, such as *Sprattus sprattus*, while also competing for resources with other fish (Oesterwind et al., 2025).

Rhithropanopeus harrisi, a North American brachyuran crab, was found in Germany in 1936, in Poland in 1951, and in Finland in 2009, having possibly invaded via ballast water or hull fouling (Fowler et al., 2013). *R. harrisi* is an effective omnivorous predator that favours *F. vesiculosus* as a habitat, potentially affecting other species that are linked to *F. vesiculosus* and even *F. vesiculosus* itself, although it remains unclear if the effect on *F. vesiculosus* abundance is ultimately positive or negative (Forsström et al., 2015). Liversage et al. (2021) conducted laboratory experiments that showed that *R. harrisi* can significantly reduce *D. polymorpha* abundance and increased the length of *Fucus radicans* plant stems. It was also noted that *R. harrisi* may contribute to trophic cascades.

Sinelobus vanhaareni was first encountered in the Baltic Sea in 2010 and in Finnish waters 2016. It possibly spread to the northern Baltic Sea via boating and ship traffic originating from Estonia. *S. vanhaareni* has been found in a broad range of habitats both as infaunal and epifaunal, for example in sand, mud, and clay sediment, filamentous algae, *Zostera marina* shoots, and *F. vesiculosus* thalli. Observations suggest it has a high tolerance for different environmental conditions. Its high abundance in some places could indicate a potential to alter ecosystems and trophic networks, but more research is needed. (Gagnong et al., 2022).

Cyanobacteria have been present in the Baltic Sea for virtually as long as the sea has existed, and the nitrogen-fixing blooms are a natural feature. Massive cyanobacteria blooms have been reported since

the 19th century, however, eutrophication has led to an increase of bloom frequency and size (Bianchi et al., 2000). Cyanobacteria blooms have been shown to cause increased oxygen consumption near the seabed, which in turn can lead to an increase of released P from anoxic sediments. The hepatotoxin nodularin producing *Nodularia spumigena* is often the predominant species in these blooms (Löptien & Dietze, 2022). Zooplankton have been shown to suffer a decrease in egg production when consuming nodularin, though many species are tolerant to the toxin. However, evidence suggests that the toxin is spread through the food web and can reduce growth rates of fish larvae. Cyanobacteria filaments and aggregates may impair the feeding mechanisms of planktivores. Furthermore, cyanobacteria also influence the N and P balance of their environment and compete for nutrients with other primary producers. However, blooms may also offer shelter to some zooplankton and fish and complement the diets of some feeders (Karjalainen et al., 2007).

The CIMPAL analysis indicated that for LS1 the Finnish coast in the southern parts of the Bothnian Sea is possibly the area impacted the most by NIS. *Marezzelleria* spp. was clearly the most significant contributor to the impact index overall, being the main impact contributor for 10/14 ecosystem components. However, this does not necessarily mean that *Marezzelleria* spp. is especially harmful for the ecosystem, as positive effects have not been considered, but it can be interpreted as having a significant ecological effect in general, on the areas it inhabits. The three stressor layers that had the highest impact score contribution, namely *Marezzelleria* spp., *C. pengoi* and cyanobacteria blooms, were also the most widespread NIS/stressors in the region. Furthermore, *Marezzelleria* spp. and *C. pengoi* were supplemented with MPA Europe distribution models that were evaluated by experts to most likely be fairly good estimates. However, because region spanning distribution models were not used for the other five NIS, there is a possibility that this caused these NIS to be at least somewhat underemphasised or underestimated in the analysis.

As most data was based on Finnish and Swedish observation data, differences in data availability and data collection methods and intensity between the countries may have to some extent affected the analysis and possibly lead to under- or overestimates in some areas. Observational data may also be heavily skewed towards areas with monitoring sites or where people generally frequent.

The established marine NIS are almost impossible to remove from the ecosystem and therefore all the management efforts have been focused to prevent further introductions. The only alternative for marine managers is to wait for the ecosystem adapt to the new-comers and then accept them to the natural ecosystem. In LS1, the *Marezzelleria* spp. have found a niche where they are seen to provide important functions for the ecosystem and, hence, they are accepted as a part of the benthic condition assessment under MSFD. Of the other species, at least the mud crab and round goby are estimated to

threaten the good state of the marine environment and there are pilot projects to analyse if their impacts could be mitigated as part of the marine restoration actions.

7.5.5 References

- Bianchi, T., Engelhaupt, E., Westman, P., Andrén, T., Rolff, C. & Elmgren, R. (2000). Cyanobacterial blooms in the Baltic Sea: Natural or human-induced? *Limnology and Oceanography*, 3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4319/lo.2000.45.3.0716>
- Brauer, M., Behrens, J., Christoffersen, M., Hyldig, G., Jacobsen, C., Björnsdóttir, K. & van Deurs, M. (2020). Seasonal patterns in round goby (*Neogobius melanostromus*) catch rates, catch composition, and dietary quality. *Fish. Res.*, 222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2019.105412>
- Brzana, R., Janas, U. & Borecka, A. (2017). New records of Conrad's false mussel *Mytilopsis leucophaeata* (Conrad, 1831) in the Vistula Delta. *Oceanological and Hydrobiological Studies*, vol. 46, no. 2, Sciendo, 2017, pp. 231–236. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/ohs-2017-0023>
- Eriksson Wiklund, A. -K. & Andersson, A. (2014). Benthic competition and population dynamics of *Monoporeia affinis* and *Marenzelleria* sp. in the northern Baltic Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 144: 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2014.04.008>
- Forsström, T., Fowler, A., Manninen, I. & Vesakoski, O. (2015). An introduced species meets the local fauna: predatory behavior of the crab *Rhithropanopeus harrisi* in the Northern Baltic Sea. *Biol Invasions*, 17: 2729–2741. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10530-015-0909-0>
- Forsström, T., Fowler, A., Lindqvist, M. & Vesakoski, O. (2016). The introduced dark false mussel, *Mytilopsis leucophaeata* (Conrad, 1831) has spread in the northern Baltic Sea. *Biol Invasions*, 5(2): 81–84. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3391/bir.2016.5.2.04>
- Fowler, A., Forsström, T., von Numers, M. & Vesakoski, O. (2013). The North American mud crab *Rhithropanopeus harrisi* (Gould, 1841) in newly colonized Northern Baltic Sea: distribution and ecology. *Aquatic Invasions*, 8(1): 89–96. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3391/ai.2013.8.1.10>
- Gagnon, K., Herlevi, H., Wikström, J., Nordström, M., Salo, T., Salovius, S. & Rinne, H. (2022). Distribution and ecology of the recently introduced tanaidacean crustacean *Sinelobus vanhaareni* Bamber, 2014 in the northern Baltic Sea. *Aquat. Invas.*, 17(1): 57–71. [10.3391/ai.2022.17.1.04](https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2022.17.1.04)
- HELCOM. (2023). Trends in arrival of new non-indigenous species. HELCOM indicators: non-indigenous species. https://indicators.helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Non-indigenous-species_Final_April_2023-1.pdf
- Henseler, C., Oesterwind, D., Kotterba, P., Nordström, M., Snickars, M., Törnroos, A. & Bonsdorff, E. (2021). Impact of round goby on native invertebrate communities - An experimental field study. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. and Ecol.*, 541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2021.151571>
- Karjalainen, M., Engström-Öst, J., Korpinen, S., Peltonen, H., Pääkkönen, J-P., Rönkkönen, S., Suikkanen, S. & Viitasalo, M. (2007). Ecosystem Consequences of Cyanobacteria in the Northern Baltic Sea. *AMBIO*, 36(2), 195–202. [10.1579/0044-7447\(2007\)36\[195:ECOCIT\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447(2007)36[195:ECOCIT]2.0.CO;2)
- Korpinen, S., Klančnik, K., Peterlin, M., Nurmi, M., Laamanen, L., Zupančič, G., Popit, A., Murray, C., Harvey, T., Andersen, J.H., Zenetos, A., Stein, U., Tunesi, L., Abhold, K., Piet, G., Kallenbach, E., Agnesi, S., Bolman, B., Vaughan, D., Reker, J., Royo Gelabert, E. (2019) Multiple pressures and their combined effects in Europe's seas. *ETC/ICM Technical Report 4/2019: European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine waters*, 164 pp. <http://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17535.11689>

- Kotta, J., Orav, H. & Sandberg-Kilpi, E. (2001). Ecological consequence of the introduction of the polychaete *Marenzelleria* cf. *viridis* into a shallow-water biotope of the northern Baltic Sea. *Journal of Sea Research*, 46(3–4): 273–280. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1385-1101\(01\)00088-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1385-1101(01)00088-0)
- Kotta, J., Nurkse, K., Puntila, R. & Ojaveer, H. (2016). Shipping and natural environmental conditions determine the distribution of the invasive non-indigenous round goby *Neogobius melanostomus* in a regional sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 169: 15–24. [10.1016/j.ecss.2015.11.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2015.11.029)
- Laine, A., Mattila, J. & Lehtikoinen, A. (2006). First record of the brackish water dreissenid bivalve *Mytilopsis leucophaeata* in the northern Baltic Sea. *Aquat. Inv.*, 1(1): 38–41. [10.3391/ai.2006.1.1.9](https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2006.1.1.9)
- Liversage, K., Korra, J., Kuprijanov, I., Rätsep, M. & Nõomaa, K. (2021). A trophic cascade facilitates native habitat providers within assemblages of multiple invasive marine species. *Ecosphere*, 12(6): e03621. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.3621>
- Löptien, U. & Dietze, H. (2022). Retracing cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea. *Sci Rep*, 12, 10873. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-14880-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-14880-w)
- Maximov, A., Bonsdorff, E., Eremina, T., Kauppi, L., Norkko, A. & Norkko, J. (2015). Context-dependent consequences of *Marenzelleria* spp. (Spionidae: Polychaeta) invasion for nutrient cycling in the Northern Baltic Sea. *Oceanologia*, 57(4): 342–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceano.2015.06.002>
- Ocean Biogeographic information System (OBIS). (2024). Species distribution dashboard for MPA Europe. (version 0.1.0). <https://shiny.obis.org/distmaps>. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14524781>
- Oosterwind, D., Bartolino, V., Behrens, J.W., Erlandsson, M., Florin, A., Henseler, C., Jakubowska-Lehrmann, M., Jasper, C., Lehtiniemi, M., Naddafi, R., Nadolna-Altyn, K., Putnis, I., Quirijns, F., Rakowski, M., Rozenfelde, L., Ustups, D., Wandzel, T., Witalis, B., Woźniczka, A. & Thor, P. (2025). Disentangling the potential effects of four non-indigenous species on commercially and recreationally used fish stocks in the Baltic Sea—a review. *Biol Invasions*, 27: 76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-025-03537-0>
- Ojaveer, H., Kotta, J., Outinen, O., Einberg, H., Zaiko, A. & Lehtiniemi, M. (2021). Meta-analysis on the ecological impacts of widely spread non-indigenous species in the Baltic Sea. *Science of The Total Environment*, 786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147375>
- Orlova, M., Golubkov, S., Kalinina, L. & Ignatieva, N. (2004). *Dreissena polymorpha* (Bivalvia: Dreissenidae) in the Neva Estuary (eastern Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea): Is it a biofilter or source for pollution? *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 49(3): 196–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2004.02.008>
- Orlova, M. & Panov, V. (2004). Establishment of the zebra mussel, *Dreissena polymorpha* (Pallas), in the Neva Estuary (Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea): distribution, population structure and possible impact on local unionid bivalves. *Hydrobiologia*, 514: 207–217. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/B:hydr.0000018220.44716.8c](https://doi.org/10.1023/B:hydr.0000018220.44716.8c)
- Stigzelius, J., Laine, A., Rissanen, J., Andersin, A. & Ilus, E. (1997). The introduction of *Marenzelleria viridis* (Polychaeta, Spionidae) into the Gulf of Finland and the Gulf of Bothnia (northern Baltic Sea). *Annales Zoologici Fennici*, 34: 205–212.
- Stock, A. (2016). *EcolImpactMapper*. figshare. [http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.1519342.V9](https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.1519342.V9)
- Telesh, I. & Ojaveer, H. (2002). The Predatory Water Flea *Cercopagis pengoi* in the Baltic Sea: Invasion History, Distribution and Implications to Ecosystem Dynamics. *Invasive Aquatic Species of Europe. Distribution, Impacts and Management* (Springer, Dordrecht): 62–65. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-94-015-9956-6_7](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-015-9956-6_7)

7.6 Case study 18: Implementation of CIMPAL in LS9

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7.6.1 Introduction

Human-mediated species transportation has significantly altered ecosystems, with NIS impacting biodiversity, ecosystems, societies, and economies through both positive and negative effects. While most studies focus on the adverse impacts of NIS, many species also provide benefits, highlighting the need for balanced assessment frameworks.

Anthropogenic activities have profoundly altered oceanic ecosystems, resulting in unprecedented disruptions to natural processes. Biological invasions represent one of the most significant disturbances, reshaping marine ecosystems globally. The introduction rates of alien species have increased markedly since the 19th century and are anticipated to accelerate further throughout the 21st century, particularly within European waters. Even under optimistic future scenarios, the adverse impacts of alien species on biodiversity are projected to intensify, posing substantial threats to ecological integrity and ecosystem functioning.

The Romanian Black Sea coastline extends for 245 km, shaped by diverse geomorphological and hydrological influences, with a significant impact from the Danube Delta, one of Europe's largest and most biodiverse deltas (Petranu, 1997; Panin et al., 1999). This region is characterized by a complex interaction of natural and anthropogenic factors that have historically influenced its marine ecosystems.

The introduction of non-native species has profoundly affected the Black Sea ecosystem, with the planktonic ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* standing out as one of the most impactful invasive species. First observed in the Black Sea in 1987, *Mnemiopsis leidyi* rapidly proliferated, primarily due to the absence of natural predators and favourable environmental conditions, causing severe disruptions to native trophic dynamics and fish populations (Shiganova, 1998; Kideys, 2002; Oguz and Velikova, 2010). This species contributed to the decline of zooplankton populations, leading to cascading effects on higher trophic levels, including commercially important fish species such as anchovies and sprat (Gucu, 2002).

In an unexpected turn, the ctenophore *Beroe ovata*, a natural predator of *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, was first recorded in the Black Sea in 1997. Initially limited to some northern coastal areas, *Beroe ovata* rapidly expanded its range. By the end of August 1999, it was found throughout the northeastern Black Sea and extended to the northwestern and southern regions (Shiganova et al., 2001). The presence of

Beroe ovata has been associated with a noticeable decline in *Mnemiopsis leidyi* populations, suggesting a partial recovery of the ecosystem balance which turned out to have an important negative impact also (Shiganova et al., 2019).

The application of the CIMPAL (Cumulative Impacts of Invasive Alien Species) framework for the first time in this region offers a novel approach to addressing the growing challenges posed by biological invasions. By systematically assessing the cumulative impacts of invasive alien species, CIMPAL provides a comprehensive tool for understanding the magnitude of their impacts. This integrative framework can support decision-makers in developing targeted management strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of invasive species on the Romanian Black Sea coastline and its ecosystems.

7.6.2 Methods

The cumulative impacts of invasive alien species in the Black Sea were assessed using the CIMPAL index. This approach integrates data on the distribution and abundance of invasive species, their ecological impacts, and the vulnerability of specific habitats. Data sources included databases and surveys.

The analysis focused on the pelagic habitat, utilizing data from 2018 to 2023 that encompassed macroplankton, specifically jellyfish, as well as tintinnid species, on the entire continental platform of the Romanian Black Sea.

The jellyfish species used were *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Beroe ovata*, which are invasive species of jellyfish, and the species of tintinnids used were *Amphorellopsis acuta*, *Eutintinnus apertus*, *Eutintinnus lusus undae*, *Eutintinnus pectinis*, *Eutintinnus tubulosus*, *Rhizodomus tagatzi*, *Salpingella decurtate*, and *Tintinnopsis tocaninensis*.

Comprehensive data on the presence and abundance of alien species within the study area were gathered. This includes species identification, distribution patterns, and ecological characteristics.

The negative impacts of each alien species on native biodiversity and ecosystem functions were evaluated. Impact scores were assigned to each alien species based on standardized criteria, reflecting the severity of their negative effects. The species were ranked according to prioritize management efforts.

The distribution of alien species and their associated impact scores across the study area were mapped. This spatial representation identifies hotspots of negative impacts and areas that require immediate attention. The individual impact scores were aggregated to determine the cumulative

negative impact on the ecosystem. This provided an understanding of the overall pressure exerted by alien species.

Based on the cumulative impact assessment, targeted management strategies were developed to mitigate the negative effects of alien species. These strategies include control measures, habitat restoration, and policy interventions.

This study provides critical insights for marine ecosystem management, offering a foundation for prioritizing actions to mitigate the adverse effects of biological invasions and promote the conservation of native biodiversity in the Romanian Black Sea.

Methodology for Applying the CIMPAL Index to Invasive Jellyfish and Tintinnid Species in the Romanian Black Sea.

Data Collection

Historical data from the NIMRD database on jellyfish and tintinnid species in the Romanian Black Sea pelagic habitats were collected (2018-2023). Species identification and abundance data were retrieved from monitoring programs and other project contracts.

The spatial distribution patterns of these species were mapped in ArcMap to understand their ecological footprint. The negative impacts of invasive jellyfish and tintinnids on native biodiversity were assessed.

Scoring and Ranking

Impact scores were assigned to each invasive species using standardized criteria from the CIMPAL tool, such as severity of competition, degree of predation, and extent of habitat alteration.

Jellyfish species, such as *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Beroe ovata*, were ranked high due to their significant role in altering ecosystem dynamics and reducing fishery yields. Tintinnid species were evaluated based on their ecological displacement of native plankton.

Spatial Analysis

With the historical datasets, we produced spatial analyses illustrating the distribution and impact intensity of jellyfish and tintinnid taxa within pelagic habitats of the Romanian Black Sea (Figure 7.6.1). Our findings pinpointed hotspots of elevated invasive species density, particularly in areas adjacent to the coastline that experience greater anthropogenic pressures.

Cumulative Impact Calculation

The combined scores of jellyfish and tintinnid species were utilized to determine the total detrimental effect on the pelagic environments. This comprehensive assessment emphasized the collective impact that these invasive species have on both biodiversity and fisheries.

Figure 7.6.1 Spatial distribution of Non-Indigenous Species presence/absence in the Romanian Black Sea marine area

7.6.3 Results

The cumulative impact map (Figure 7.6.2) illustrates the spatial distribution of ecological pressures exerted by invasive species in the Romanian Black Sea coastal and shelf waters, based on the CIMPAL Index at a 5 km resolution. The color gradient, ranging from yellow (low impact) to dark brown (high impact), represents cumulative impact scores between 0 and 16. The highest impact zones are observed in the southeastern and central-southern offshore areas. Near the Sfântu Gheorghe branch of the Danube, as well as along the southern coast in Constanța and Mangalia, show values reaching 14–16, highlighting them as ecological hotspots under strong pressure from invasive species. In the southern sector, the elevated impact scores around Constanța and Mangalia are particularly noteworthy. This is attributed to the presence of major ports and maritime traffic, which are key pathways for the introduction and spread of non-indigenous species through ballast water discharge and hull fouling. The interaction between intensive human activity, favorable hydrological conditions, and nutrient availability creates a high-risk environment for biological invasions and their cascading effects on local biodiversity. Moderate impact levels (6–12) are spread across the central shelf, indicating widespread but variable ecological pressure, likely driven by seasonal dynamics and species-

specific patterns. Meanwhile, a few offshore areas with relatively lower scores (0–4) suggest zones with limited presence or lower ecological impact of the targeted species during the observed period.

Figure 7.6.2 Cumulative impact map showing spatial intensity of invasive species pressure in the Romanian Black Sea marine area, calculated using the CIMPAL Index

Overall, the spatial distribution of impacts reveals a pattern strongly influenced by both natural drivers, such as Danube freshwater outflow, and anthropogenic vectors, particularly maritime activities. The findings underline the need for strengthened invasive species monitoring, especially near port infrastructures, and for policy actions targeting ballast water management. Such targeted responses are essential to reduce cumulative pressures and enhance ecosystem resilience along the Romanian Black Sea coast.

7.6.4 Discussion

The cumulative impact map highlights distinct spatial patterns of ecological pressure from invasive species along the Romanian Black Sea coast, with particularly high scores in the Danube Delta marine area, and the southern nearshore waters adjacent to the ports of Constanța and Mangalia. These findings reveal not only biological hotspots but also underline the interconnectedness between invasive species dynamics, human maritime activity, and freshwater discharge.

The intense impact zones near the Danube mouths can be attributed to multiple factors: the continuous input of freshwater and nutrients, hydrological stratification, and high productivity levels that may favor the proliferation of opportunistic invasive taxa such as *Mnemiopsis leidyi*. These areas serve as ecological transition zones, where changes in salinity and nutrient regimes create favorable

conditions for non-native species to establish and expand. The presence of such high-impact areas near biodiversity-sensitive regions such as the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve is particularly concerning, as it poses additional pressure on already vulnerable ecosystems.

The elevated scores in Constanța and Mangalia reflect the role of maritime transport and port activities as primary vectors of biological invasions. The discharges from ballast water tanks and hull fouling are widely recognized as dominant mechanisms for species introductions, and the persistent high impact values in these zones stress the urgent need for stricter implementation of the Ballast Water Management Convention and port-specific biosecurity measures.

Moreover, the wide extent of moderate-impact zones across the central Romanian shelf suggests that the influence of invasive species is not limited to point sources but has spread across broader areas. This observation supports the need for a regional and transboundary approach to monitoring and management, especially in the context of climate change, which may further accelerate species' range expansion and alter competitive dynamics in pelagic communities.

From a methodological standpoint, the use of the CIMPAL Index proved valuable in quantifying and visualizing cumulative pressures. However, some limitations remain. For example, the impact scores are currently based on expert judgment and limited empirical evidence regarding species-specific effects on pelagic habitats. Furthermore, the occurrence data, used as point records, may underrepresent true species distributions and seasonal dynamics. To enhance future assessments, it is recommended to integrate modelled species distributions and to expand the analysis to include other ecosystem components such as benthic habitats, fish recruitment zones, and food web interactions.

7.6.5 Conclusion

Using the CIMPAL index, researchers quantified the cumulative effects of invasive jellyfish and tintinnid species in the Romanian Black Sea, offering important insights into historical ecological shifts. This method highlighted the necessity for focused management and preventive strategies to protect the pelagic habitats in the area. The analysis presented through the cumulative impact map provides a solid foundation for prioritizing monitoring efforts, guiding invasive species mitigation strategies, and informing ecosystem-based management plans. Addressing knowledge gaps through improved data collection, expanding the scope of assessed species and habitats, and enforcing preventive measures in high-risk areas will be critical to preserving the ecological integrity of the Romanian Black Sea coast.

Based on the cumulative impact assessment, targeted management actions are essential to mitigate the ecological risks posed by invasive species in the Black Sea. The study highlights the importance of

establishing regular monitoring programs to detect and track non-indigenous species dynamics over time. In parallel, habitat restoration efforts aimed at enhancing fish stocks and plankton diversity are recommended to support ecosystem resilience. Finally, policy interventions, particularly those regulating ballast water discharge, are critical to limiting new introductions and controlling the spread of established invasive species. These measures, when integrated, can strengthen the region's adaptive capacity and contribute to the sustainable management of marine biodiversity.

7.6.6 References

- Gucu, A.C. (2002) Can Overfishing be Responsible for the Successful Establishment of *Mnemiopsis leidyi* in the Black Sea?, *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, Volume 54, Issue 3, Pages 439-451, ISSN 0272-7714, <https://doi.org/10.1006/ecss.2000.0657>
- Kideys, A. E. (2002). Fall and rise of the Black Sea ecosystem. *Science*, 297(5586), 1482–1484.
- Oguz T, Velikova V (2010) Abrupt transition of the northwestern Black Sea shelf ecosystem from a eutrophic to an alternative pristine state. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 405:231-242. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps08538>
- Panin, N., Jipa, D. (1999) Danube River sediment input and its interaction with the northwestern Black Sea: results of EROS-2000 and EROS-21 projects. *GeoEcoMarina*, v. 3
- Petranu, A., (Ed.), 1997 – Black Sea Biological Diversity Romania. U.N. Publications, New York, 314 pp.
- Shiganova, T. A. (1998). Invasion of the Black Sea by the ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and recent changes in pelagic community structure. *Fisheries Oceanography*, 7(3-4), 305–310. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2419.1998.00080.x>
- Shiganova, T.A., Yulia V. Bulgakova, Stanislav P. Volovik, Zinaida A. Mirzoyan & Sergey I. Dudkin (2001) The new invader *Beroe ovata* Mayer 1912 and its effect on the ecosystem in the northeastern Black Sea, *Hydrobiologia*, 451.
- Shiganova, T.A., Mikaelyan, A.S., Moncheva, S., Stefanova, K., Chasovnikov, V.K., Mosharov, S.A., Mosharova, I.N., Slabakova, N., Mavrodieva, R., Stefanova, E., Zasko, D.N., & Dzhurova, B., (2019), Effect of invasive ctenophores *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Beroe ovata* on low trophic webs of the Black Sea ecosystem, *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, Volume 141, 2019, Pages 434-447, ISSN 0025-326X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.02.049>

7.7 Case study 19: CIMPAL+: accounting for cumulative positive impacts on biodiversity

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7.7.1 Introduction

Human-mediated transport of species beyond their native geographical ranges has become a major factor of ecosystem change (Occhipinti-Ambrogi, 2007; Pyšek et al., 2020). The rapid expansion of global commercial activities has led to a significant increase in the rate of introduction of NIS into new ecosystems, with no apparent signs of decline (Essl et al., 2011; Seebens et al., 2017). Once established, NIS integrate into existing food webs, potentially altering community structure and ecosystem functioning (Vilà et al., 2011; David et al., 2017). Moreover, NIS introductions can have profound effects on societies, economies, and human well-being (Simberloff et al., 2013; Bacher et al., 2018). However, not all NIS introductions result in negative consequences; they can also be beneficial for ecosystems and people (Kelsch et al., 2020; Vimercati et al., 2020), with the most abundant NIS exhibiting both positive and negative impacts (Katsanevakis et al., 2014a; Shackleton et al., 2019a; Tsirintanis et al., 2022).

The term ‘NIS impact’ refers to the measurable changes a non-indigenous species introduces to its invaded range (Ricciardi et al., 2013). Native biodiversity is significantly affected by NIS through several mechanisms (Katsanevakis et al., 2014a), with varying magnitudes of impact (Blackburn et al., 2014; Doherty et al., 2016; Dijkstra et al., 2017). Common mechanisms of NIS negative impacts on native biodiversity include competition for resources, predation, and ecosystem engineering (Gallardo et al., 2016; Tsirintanis et al., 2022). Conversely, NIS can have positive impacts by providing new trophic resources for native predators, facilitating dispersal, and offering indirect benefits such as the control of invasive species (Vimercati et al., 2022; Tsirintanis et al., 2022).

Assessing the biological mechanisms and magnitudes of NIS impacts is challenging due to the complexity of multidimensional abiotic and biotic interactions and the nuances of local contexts (Thomsen et al., 2011). Nevertheless, it is essential for effective management strategies and the prioritisation of impact mitigation measures (Micheli et al., 2013). The determination of whether a NIS introduction is overall negative or positive is influenced by individual perceptions and various ethical and social factors (Simberloff et al., 2013; Shackleton et al., 2019b). Despite these difficulties and inherent subjectivity, the ecological and economic losses attributed to biological invasions are enormous (Diagne et al., 2021). However, negative impacts of IAS have received considerably more

scientific and management attention than positive effects (Goodenough et al., 2010; Vimercati et al., 2020). Moreover, research has primarily focused on the most impactful IAS, leaving less impactful species understudied (Guerin et al., 2018). This underestimation of IAS positive impacts hinders the adoption of a holistic impact assessment approach necessary for accurately understanding all potential consequences of biological invasions and implementing appropriate management actions (Vimercati et al., 2020).

Various impact assessment frameworks have been developed to evaluate NIS impacts on native biodiversity, the economy, and human well-being (e.g., Hawkins et al., 2015; Bacher et al., 2018; González-Moreno et al., 2019). CIMPAL is an index developed to assess and map negative NIS impacts on ecosystems (Katsanevakis et al., 2016). Initially applied in the Mediterranean Sea, CIMPAL has since been utilised in marine (Bartolo et al., 2021; Tsirintanis et al., 2023), freshwater (Magliozzi et al., 2020), and terrestrial environments (Polce et al., 2023). Positive impacts, however, are less frequently addressed by NIS impact assessment frameworks compared to negative impacts (Vimercati et al., 2020). The EICAT+ framework (Vimercati et al., 2022) evaluates NIS's positive impacts on native biodiversity according to the IUCN Environmental Impact guidelines (IUCN, 2020; Vimercati et al., 2022). EICAT+ assesses NIS positive impacts on specific biodiversity attributes and classifies these effects into five magnitude levels, as proposed by Blackburn et al. (2014) and modified to encompass NIS positive effects (Vimercati et al., 2022).

This study aimed to develop a modification of CIMPAL to assess and map NIS's positive impacts. The new index, CIMPAL+, utilises the EICAT+ framework (Vimercati et al., 2022) to evaluate the magnitude of NIS's positive impacts on ecosystems. CIMPAL+ was applied in the Aegean Sea, located in the eastern Mediterranean, which is the most invaded marine ecoregion in the world (Costello et al., 2021). The objectives were to estimate cumulative NIS positive impacts, highlight the most impacted areas and habitats, and identify the most positively impactful NIS in the region.

7.7.2 Methods

The application of CIMPAL+ requires dividing the study area into a regular grid and estimating impacts for each grid cell using the following formula:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j w_{i,j}$$

A_i refers to the population state of NIS species i in a specific cell, standardised to range between 0 and 1. In this study, A_i was estimated following two approaches: (a) NIS distribution models from Tsirintanis et al. (2023) and (b) NIS presence/absence data (Table 7.7.1) from Ragkousis et al. (2023a,

2023b). H_j is the percentage cover of habitat j in each study area cell. $W_{i,j}$ refers to the impact weight of species i at habitat j , derived from the combined assessment of the species' impact magnitude (according to Vimercati et al., 2022) and the strength of evidence (according to Katsanevakis et al., 2014a, 2016) (Figure A.1.1). Impact weight is estimated following an uncertainty-averse approach (Yemshanov et al., 2013; Katsanevakis et al., 2016) (Figure A.1.2). Finally, n and m represent the total number of alien species and marine habitats, respectively, included in the analysis.

Table 7.7.3. List of the included Non-Indigenous Species in the application of CIMPAL in the Aegean Sea. *The Anthozoan *Oculina patagonica* is considered a cryptogenic species in the Mediterranean Sea.

Biotic Group	Phylum: Class	Species	Number of records in the Aegean
Macrophytes	Ochrophyta: Phaephyceae	<i>Styopodium schimperi</i>	67
Macrophytes	Chlorophyta: Ulvophyceae	<i>Caulerpa cylindracea</i>	283
Macrophytes	Chlorophyta: Ulvophyceae	<i>Codium fragile</i>	22
Macrophytes	Rhodophyta: Florideophyceae	<i>Asparagopsis</i> spp.	117
Macrophytes	Rhodophyta: Florideophyceae	<i>Lophocladia lallemandii</i>	224
Macrophytes	Rhodophyta: Florideophyceae	<i>Womersleyella setacea</i>	24
Macrophytes	Tracheophyta: Magoliopsida	<i>Halophila stipulacea</i>	132
Invertebrates	Cnidaria: Anthozoa	<i>Oculina patagonica</i> *	64
Invertebrates	Mollusca: Bivalvia	<i>Brachidontes pharaonis</i>	35
Invertebrates	Mollusca: Bivalvia	<i>Pinctada radiata</i>	159
Invertebrates	Annelida Polychaeta	<i>Hydroides elegans</i>	24
Fish	Chordata: Teleostei	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	171
Fish	Chordata: Teleostei	<i>Sargocentron rubrum</i>	31
Fish	Chordata: Teleostei	<i>Siganus luridus</i>	919
Fish	Chordata: Teleostei	<i>Siganus rivulatus</i>	748
Fish	Chordata: Teleostei	<i>Pempheris rhomboidea</i>	23

We further expanded the CIMPAL approach to account for interspecific NIS interactions by adding a second term:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j W_{i,j} \pm \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i A_k H_j W_{i,j} f_{i,k}$$

A_k represents the population state of species k , a NIS interacting with species i , in either a positive or negative way. A_k values are standardised to range between 0 and 1. The term $f_{i,k}$ refers to the interaction effect of NIS k on NIS i , taking both negative and positive values between -1 (maximum negative interaction, when NIS k fully cancels the positive impact of NIS i) and a maximum value limited by the condition $w_{i,j}(1 + f_{i,k}) < 8$ (with 8 corresponding to massive impacts). It has to be noted that $f_{i,k} = 0$ when $i = k$.

The selected species for applying CIMPAL+ in the Aegean Sea were chosen based on their establishment in the region and their positive impacts on Mediterranean native biodiversity. A species list was compiled from Tsirintanis et al. (2022), who assessed impactful alien species in Mediterranean marine ecosystems up until 2021. The list included species with verified positive impacts on Mediterranean biodiversity. All impact case records from Tsirintanis et al. (2022) were re-evaluated to align with the framework proposed by Vimercati et al. (2022) for NIS positive impact magnitude assessment (Figure A.1.1). Additional searches for 2022 and 2023 were conducted on Google Scholar for species with significant presence in the Aegean but without recorded positive impacts up to 2021. This process resulted in a final list of 16 species for the CIMPAL+ application in the Aegean Sea (Table 7.7.1). Among the studied NIS overall, two interspecific interactions were recorded: the consumption of the chlorophyte *Caulerpa cylindracea* by the two herbivorous fish, *Siganus luridus* and *S. rivulatus*, respectively.

The Aegean Sea was divided into 0.01° latitude/longitude grid cells using ArcGIS Pro to estimate CIMPAL+. The percentage coverage of each of the ten different habitat types (Figures A1.5-A1.13) was estimated for each cell based on previously produced habitat maps (Sini et al., 2017; Topouzelis et al., 2018). The ten habitat types were: (1) seagrass meadows, (2) shallow soft substrates (0–60 m depth), (3) deep soft substrates (60–200 m depth), (4) soft substrates of the dysphotic zone (deeper than 200 m), (5) shallow hard substrates (0–60 m depth), (6) deep hard substrates (60–200 m), (7) hard substrates of the dysphotic zone (deeper than 200 m), (8) submarine caves, (9) coralligenous formations, and (10) pelagic habitat. Maps of each habitat type are provided in Supplementary Material 1. Each targeted NIS was assessed for its positive impacts on each of the ten habitat types (detailed in Supplementary Material 2).

Five different descriptors were employed to rank NIS based on their impacts on the marine ecosystems of the Aegean Sea. These descriptors were:

D1: Total area of NIS occurrence in the region, calculated as the total number of grid cells with at least one record of the species.

D2: Number of study area cells with an estimated positive impact score > 0.1 for a given NIS.

D3a: Sum of positive impact scores of a specific NIS across the entire Aegean Sea, following the SDM approach.

D3b: Sum of NIS impact scores in the region based on species' occurrences.

D4: Average positive impact score across the species' range of occurrence, excluding cells with score values lower than 0.1.

7.7.3 Results

CIMPAL+ impact scores per cell ranged from 0 to 12.6, with a mean value of 0.2 across the 321,346 study area cells (including 287,033 cells with zero values). Impacts were exclusively accumulated in coastal habitats from 0 to 60 m depth, with zero CIMPAL+ impact scores deeper than 60 m or in the pelagic habitat (Figure 7.7.1). According to CIMPAL+ score mapping, the South Aegean Sea's coastal habitats were more substantially affected by NIS positive impacts compared to those in the North Aegean Sea (Figure 7.7.1). Additionally, the highest CIMPAL+ scores (>8) were more frequent (85%) in the South Aegean compared to the North and were consistently recorded in the shallower parts of coastal habitats (Figures 7.7.1, 7.7.2).

Figure 7.7.1. The cumulative positive impact score of the 16 examined Non-Indigenous Species in the Aegean Sea, according to CIMPAL+. Purple rectangles highlight the zoomed-in areas depicted in Figure 7.7.2.

Figure 7.7.2. Magnification of areas in the South (A: Chania, B: Rhodes Island, C: Saronikos Gulf) and North (D: Thermaikos Gulf, E: Samothrace Island) Aegean Sea. F: color scale of CIMPAL+ values.

Overall, 16 NIS were assessed to impact the Aegean Sea’s coastal habitats positively. Non-indigenous macrophytes, comprising seven species, were the biotic group accounting for the most positive impacts (Figure 7.7.3A; 66%). Their impact was more pronounced in the South Aegean compared to the North (Figure A1.1). Following macrophytes, fish contributed to 30% of the cumulative CIMPAL+ scores (Figure 7.7.3A). Non-indigenous fish also exhibited higher CIMPAL+ scores in the South Aegean compared to the North (Figure A.1.2), with their positive impacts in the Aegean caused by five different NIS. The non-indigenous invertebrates group included four species, accounting for only 4%

of the overall sum of CIMPAL+ positive impact scores (Figure 7.7.3A), with no clear spatial pattern in their effects across the Aegean (Figure A.1.3). According to the literature review analysis, the most common mechanism of NIS positive impacts was the creation of novel habitats, followed by food provision (Figure 7.7.3B). These two mechanisms accounted for 80% of the recorded impact cases.

Figure 7.7.3 (A) Percentage contribution of each biotic group to the cumulative positive Non-Indigenous Species impacts in the Aegean Sea according to CIMPAL+. (B) Number of positive impact cases by mechanism based on literature review analysis.

Figure 7.7.4 Disaggregation of CIMPAL+ scores across the habitat types that were impacted by Non-Indigenous Species positive impacts, (B) Mean CIMPAL+ score per habitat type.

Among the ten habitat types examined, NIS were assessed to have positive impacts on four: shallow soft substrates (0–60 m depth), shallow hard substrates (0–60 m depth), seagrass meadows, and caves

(Figure 7.7.4). Shallow soft substrates exhibited the highest sum of CIMPAL+ impact scores (Figure 7.7.4A), with values per cell ranging from 0 to 3.3, and a standardised mean value of 1.5 (Figure 7.7.4B). CIMPAL+ scores in shallow soft substrates were significantly stronger in the South Aegean (Figure 7.7.5). Among the 16 investigated NIS, only three were assessed to positively impact this habitat type (Figure 7.7.5), with the macrophyte *Halophila stipulacea* being the most impactful, followed by the fish *Fistularia commersonii* and the macrophyte *Caulerpa cylindracea*.

Figure 7.7.5 (A) CIMPAL+ impact mapping of Non-Indigenous Species on shallow soft substrates (0-60 m depth) in the Aegean Sea. (B) Ranked NIS based on their CIMPAL+ scores in shallow soft substrates (0-60 m depth).

Shallow hard substrates (0–60 m depth) accumulated the second highest amount of NIS cumulative impacts, constituting 13% of the total cumulative impact score in the Aegean (Figure 7.7.4). This habitat type displayed the highest standardised mean value among all examined habitat types, at 2.6 (Figure 7.7.4), with score values ranging from 0 to 12.6. Additionally, shallow hard substrates were impacted by most of the studied NIS, with 13 out of the 16 having positive effects on this habitat (Figure 7.7.6). One macrophyte, two invertebrates, and two fish were responsible for the larger part of positive NIS impacts on this habitat (Figure 7.7.6). NIS positive impacts on seagrass meadows accounted for 5% of the cumulative positive impacts in the Aegean Sea according to CIMPAL+, with values ranging from 0 to 1.2 and a mean value of 0.4 (Figure 7.7.4). Only two NIS, *Fistularia commersonii* and *Caulerpa cylindracea*, have some positive impacts on this habitat type, with their additive impact more pronounced in the South Aegean compared to the North (Figure 7.7.7). Caves accounted for less than 0.01% of the cumulative positive impacts in the Aegean Sea, and no other habitat type was assessed to be positively impacted by NIS (Figure 7.7.4).

Figure 7.7.6 (A) CIMPAL+ impact mapping of Non-Indigenous Species on shallow rocky reefs (0-60 m depth) in the Aegean Sea. (B) Ranked NIS based on their CIMPAL+ scores in shallow hard substrates (0-60 m depth).

Figure 7.7.7 (A) CIMPAL+ impact mapping of Non-Indigenous Species on seagrass meadows in the Aegean Sea. (B) Ranked NIS based on their CIMPAL+ scores in seagrass meadows.

Figure 7.7.8 Non-Indigenous Species impact ranking according to CIMPAL+ descriptors (D1-D4), based on Non-Indigenous Species distribution models.

Figure 7.7.9 Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) impact ranking according to CIMPAL+ descriptors (D1-D4), based on NIS occurrence records (presence/absence data).

NIS impact ranking varied based on the four applied descriptors (D1–D4; Figure 7.7.8). According to D1, which estimated a species’ total area of occurrence in the Aegean Sea based on species records, *Siganus* spp. was the most widespread NIS in the region (Figure 7.7.8). D2, which ranked NIS based on the number of cells with CIMPAL+ impact score values above 0.1, identified the chlorophyte *C. cylindracea* as the most positively impactful NIS, followed by *F. commersonii* and *H. stipulacea* (Figure

7.7.8). D3a, representing the cumulative positive NIS impacts in the Aegean as a sum of CIMPAL+ scores, ranked *H. stipulacea* as the most impactful species, followed by *F. commersonii* and *C. cylindracea* (Figure 7.7.8). D4 ranked *H. stipulacea* as the most impactful NIS based on its average positive impact score across its range of occurrence in the Aegean Sea, followed by *F. commersonii*, the rhodophyte *Lophocladia trichoclados*, the bivalve *Brachidontes pharaonis*, and the chlorophyte *Codium fragile* (Figure 7.7.8).

D3b, which estimated the cumulative CIMPAL+ scores in the Aegean Sea based on actual NIS occurrences, exhibited ranking differences compared to D3a, which estimated CIMPAL+ scores based on NIS modelled distributions (Figures 7.7.8, 7.7.9). *F. commersonii* was identified by D3b as the species with the highest sum of positive impacts. *Halophila stipulacea*, which ranked first in D3a, was assessed as the fourth most impactful species by D3b. *Siganus luridus* and *Siganus rivulatus* ranked fifth and sixth in D3b, whereas in D3a, they ranked eighth and eleventh, respectively.

Halophila stipulacea was the only NIS with a higher sum of positive impacts compared to negative (Figure 7.7.10). Most NIS exhibited a prevalence of negative over positive impacts, with the highest differences recorded for the rhodophytes *Womersleyella setacea* (x 21.5) and *L. trichoclados* (x 9.5), followed by the invasive fish *S. luridus* (x 8) and *S. rivulatus* (x 8) (Figure 7.7.10).

Figure 7.7.10 Comparison of CIMPAL and CIMPAL+ values for the 16 Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) included in this study. Values indicate the fold difference between positive and negative impacts (red indicates the prevalence of negative impacts, and green indicates positive impacts).

7.7.4 Discussion

The implementation of CIMPAL+ revealed substantial positive NIS impacts in the Aegean Sea, with an accumulation of impacts within coastal habitats up to 60 m depth and no evidence of positive effects in deeper waters or the open seas. The positive impacts were notably stronger in the South Aegean compared to the North. Recent estimations and mapping of negative NIS cumulative impacts in the Aegean showed a similar distribution pattern, with stronger impacts on coastal habitats and higher CIMPAL scores in the South (Tsirintanis et al., 2023). This similarity is associated with the higher density of thermophilous NIS, which are favoured by the warmer waters of the southern latitudes of the Aegean compared to the North (Androulidakis and Krestenitis, 2022).

Ten out of the 16 impactful NIS assessed in the current framework of CIMPAL+ entered the Mediterranean through the Suez Canal (Ragkousis et al., 2023a), indicating an Indo-Pacific origin and a preference for higher temperatures. Notably, two species, the Red Sea seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* and the bluespotted cornetfish *Fistularia commersonii*, accounted for 78% of the cumulative positive impacts in the Aegean. Sea warming trends in the Mediterranean have persisted for decades, particularly in the eastern sector, exacerbating the introduction and establishment of thermophilous NIS (Raitsos et al., 2010; Katsanevakis et al., 2024). Conversely, native species have suffered severe consequences due to prolonged high temperatures, resulting in population declines and species collapses (Yeruham et al., 2015; Rilov, 2016; Albano et al., 2021; Nikolaou and Katsanevakis, 2023).

Future projections indicate that native psychrophilic species in the Mediterranean face additional range contractions and potential extinctions due to limited options for northward expansion in the land-locked basin (Ben Rais Lasram et al., 2010; Schultz et al., 2024). This alteration of biotic and abiotic characteristics is leading to the emergence of novel marine ecosystems in the region, transitioning from a temperate to a tropicalised phase dominated by thermophilous NIS (Vergés et al., 2014; Bianchi et al., 2014; Nikolaou et al., 2023; Katsanevakis et al., 2024).

Most positive NIS impacts on the Aegean Sea's coastal habitats were induced by non-indigenous macrophytes and fish. The higher impact magnitude in the South was attributed to these groups, which exhibited substantially higher CIMPAL+ scores in the South compared to the North. Most studied non-indigenous macrophytes caused positive impacts throughout the Aegean, with the chlorophyte *Codium fragile* being more impactful in the North and *H. stipulacea* and the ochrophyte *Styopodium schimperi* having greater impacts in the South. All five non-indigenous fish entered the Mediterranean through the Suez Canal and, being thermophilic, are mostly distributed in the South Aegean (Katsanevakis et al., 2014b; Ragkousis et al., 2023a), explaining their higher positive impacts

there. On the other hand, invertebrates' impact mapping did not reveal any consistent geographical pattern.

Shallow hard substrates were the habitat type most positively impacted by NIS. On the other hand, numerous studies have highlighted the adverse impacts of NIS on shallow rocky reef ecosystems in the Aegean (e.g., Sala et al., 2011; Nikolaou et al., 2023). According to our assessment, CIMPAL+ scores on shallow rocky substrates were approximately four times lower than CIMPAL scores of negative NIS cumulative effects (Tsirintanis et al., 2023).

Seagrass meadows, including the Mediterranean endemic *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, were positively affected by fewer NIS. Seagrass meadows and rocky reefs are of unique value for Mediterranean biodiversity, supporting critical ecological functions (Boudouresque et al., 2012; Bevilacqua et al., 2021). The positive NIS impacts depicted by CIMPAL+ should not be considered compensatory for their adverse effects but rather as independent positive impacts following the establishment and integration of NIS into the recipient ecosystems.

Shallow soft substrates accumulated the highest sum of positive impacts in the Aegean, largely due to their extensive surface area in the region (Figure A.1.5). However, when considering the mean values across their area of occurrence, shallow soft substrates were the second most affected habitat type by positive NIS impacts.

Most positive NIS effects were caused by structural ecosystem engineers, primarily macrophytes but also invertebrates, through the creation of new habitats. While these species can significantly facilitate various organisms and ecosystem functions, their impact is context-dependent and related to the pre-existing ecosystem state before their introduction (Rilov et al., 2023). Food provision was the second most common mechanism of positive impacts, with non-indigenous fish contributing significantly to native consumers. Predator-prey interactions are a major factor influencing NIS effects in the ecosystems they invade (Rilov, 2009). Non-indigenous fish accounted for the most significant positive impacts by serving as a vital food source for native consumers. Additionally, non-indigenous invertebrates contributed to native biodiversity by providing an optimal food source for native predators. Although alien macrophytes are occasionally grazed, most have developed defensive mechanisms against herbivory (e.g., Tomas et al., 2011; Miccoli et al., 2021), and thus, no significant positive effects from macrophytes in terms of food provision have been reported.

Comparing CIMPAL+ results with the CIMPAL assessment of negative impacts, the sum of NIS impacts across the Aegean Sea appears substantially lower by an 8-fold difference, primarily due to the extensive negative effects of the non-indigenous ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* on the pelagic habitat

(Tsirintanis et al., 2023). Excluding this species, negative impacts were still 2.5 times higher than positive impacts. The number of impactful NIS with negative effects was also higher (28 species; Tsirintanis et al., 2023) compared to those with positive impacts (16 species).

The substantial differences between negative and positive impacts reflect the severity of NIS negative effects but may also signify a research bias towards studying negative impacts. Estimating CIMPAL and CIMPAL+ is based on published evidence of impacts, and invasion science has tended to focus on negative effects, potentially sidelining positive ones (Sax et al., 2022). Although positive NIS impacts have been less documented, they show an increasing trend (Bacher et al., 2023).

Alien species in the eastern Mediterranean, especially Lessepsian species introduced through the Suez Canal, have played a significant role in maintaining ecosystem functioning and services amidst climate change-induced shifts (Katsanevakis et al., 2024). These species are well adapted to local conditions, often filling ecological and socio-economic roles vacated by native species that are declining or becoming locally extinct due to rising temperatures (Nikolaou and Katsanevakis, 2023). For example, Lessepsian fishes such as *Siganus luridus* and *Siganus rivulatus* have become essential components of commercial and recreational fisheries in Cyprus, contributing significantly to local economies and food security (Michailidis et al., 2019, 2020). Alien species also enhance ecosystem resilience through complex trophic interactions and habitat creation. For instance, *Brachidontes pharaonis* acts as a structural ecosystem engineer, reduces turbidity through filter-feeding, and serves as a food source for native predators (Sarà et al., 2021), and the seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* forms new habitats supporting diverse marine life and provides food for native herbivores like the green turtle *Chelonia mydas* (Tsirintanis et al., 2022). These contributions help maintain ecosystem functions and services, which are critical for the socio-economic stability of the region.

However, managing alien species requires a nuanced approach that accounts for both their positive contributions and their potential negative impacts. Conservation management policy should consider protecting certain ecosystem functions supported by NIS (Rilov et al., 2020; Katsanevakis et al., 2023, 2024). However, NIS positive impacts should not be used to counterbalance negative effects and cause inaction in mitigating IAS impacts, as this could lead to misguided management decisions (Carneiro et al., 2024). The latter authors suggest that managing NIS should be based on three admissible principles: (a) NIS typically cause more undesirable than desirable effects, (b) a positive NIS impact is independent and does not nullify a negative effect, and (c) what benefits some may impose costs on others. Given the significant environmental (Bellard et al., 2016) and economic (Diagne et al., 2021) toll of biological invasions, effective management is imperative. Invasion scientists must provide practical solutions without adding further complications while remaining impartial in their

assessments by focusing on specific, measurable attributes and reaching conclusions independently of previous research trends (Vimercati et al., 2020). For example, targeted fishing of problematic species like the lionfish *Pterois miles* and the rabbitfishes *Siganus luridus* and *S. rivulatus* has been proposed to mitigate their adverse effects while leveraging their economic value (Giakoumi et al., 2019). Conservation strategies should integrate both positive and negative impacts of alien species to develop effective management plans that support ecosystem resilience and sustainability (Rilov et al., 2020; Katsanevakis et al., 2024).

Both CIMPAL and CIMPAL+ utilise the same impact calculation formula, differing only in whether they calculate negative or positive impacts. However, this study expanded the previous CIMPAL framework by incorporating interspecific NIS interactions, which refine impact assessment and enhance the index's capacity to estimate cumulative impacts. This integration better supports management actions, applicable to both negative and positive impacts. Species in nature engage in multiple and complex interactions (Morin, 2009), and including these interactions improves assessment accuracy. However, our literature review found limited data on NIS interactions in the Mediterranean, with only two interactions among the 16 studied species included in the formula. These interactions involved the consumption of the chlorophyte *Caulerpa cylindracea* by the rabbitfish *Siganus luridus* and *S. rivulatus* (Azzurro et al., 2007; Tsirintanis, 2023). Previously, CIMPAL assessed *C. cylindracea* as the most impactful species in the region due to its severe negative impacts on native biodiversity (Tsirintanis et al., 2023). The re-evaluation of this species' score, accounting for its interactions with *Siganus* spp., showed that while its negative effects still outweighed the benefits, the integration of interactions significantly reduced its contribution to the cumulative negative impact score. Future studies on NIS interactions in the Mediterranean will further enhance the reliability and accuracy of both CIMPAL and CIMPAL+ frameworks.

CIMPAL+ introduces a novel tool for evaluating, quantifying, and mapping positive NIS impacts in ecosystems, complementing the existing CIMPAL framework. The comprehensive evaluation of NIS impacts in the Aegean Sea provides detailed and high-resolution impact pattern depictions and assessments. With the marine ecosystems of the Aegean Sea heavily impacted by multiple human activities and climate change, continuous monitoring of NIS and their impacts on marine ecosystems is crucial for developing appropriate management plans. To this end, CIMPAL+ contributes to a holistic understanding of biological invasions, supporting effective management actions.

7.7.5 References

- Androulidakis, Y. S., & Krestenitis, Y. N. (2022). Sea surface temperature variability and marine heat waves over the Aegean, Ionian, and Cretan Seas from 2008–2021. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 10(1), 42, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse10010042>
- Bacher, S., Blackburn, T. M., Essl, F., Genovesi, P., Heikkilä, J., Jeschke, J. M., Jones, G., Keller, R., Kenis, M., Kueffer, C., Martinou, A. F., Nentwig, W., Pergl, J., Pyšek, P., Wolfgang Rabitsch, Richardson, D.M, Roy, H.E., Saul, W.C., Scalera, R., Vilà, M., John R. U. Wilson, & Kumschick, S., (2018) Socio-economic impact classification of alien taxa (SEICAT). *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(1), 159-168, <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12844>
- Bacher, S., Galil, B. S., Nuñez, M. A., Ansong, M., Cassey, P., Dehnen-Schmutz, K., Fayvush, G., Hiremath, A. J., Ikegami, M., Martinou, A. F., McDermott, S. M., Preda, C., Vilà, M., Weyl, O. L. F., Fernandez, R. D., & Ryan-Colton, E. (2023). Chapter 4: Impacts of invasive alien species on nature, nature's contributions to people, and good quality of life. In H. E. Roy, A. Pauchard, P. Stoett, & T. Renard Truong (Eds.), *Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430731>
- Bartolo, A. G., Tsiamis, K., & Küpper, F. C. (2021) Identifying hotspots of non-indigenous species' high impact in the Maltese islands (Central Mediterranean Sea). *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 164, 112016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.112016>
- Bellard C, Cassey P, & Blackburn TM (2016) Alien species as a driver of recent extinctions. *Biology Letters* 12: 20150623, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0623>
- Ben Rais Lasram F, Guilhaumon F, Albouy C, Somot S, Thuiller W et al (2010) The Mediterranean Sea as a 'cul-de-sac' for endemic fishes facing climate change. *Glob Chang Biol* 16:3233–3245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02224.x>
- Bevilacqua, S., Airoldi, L., Ballesteros, E., Benedetti-Cecchi, L., Boero, F., Bulleri, F., Cebrian, E., Cerrano, C., Claudet, J., Colloca, F. & Coppari, M. (2021) Mediterranean rocky reefs in the Anthropocene: Present status and future concerns. *Advances in marine biology*, 89, pp.1-51.
- Bianchi, C.N., Corsini-Foka, M., Morri, C., & Zenetos, A. (2014). Thirty years after: dramatic change in the coastal marine ecosystems of Kos Island (Greece), 1981-2013. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15/3, 482-497, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.678>
- Blackburn, T. M., Essl, F., Evans, T., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., Kühn, I., Kumschick S, Marková Z, Mrugała A, Nentwig W, Pergl J, Pyšek P, Rabitsch W, Ricciardi A, Richardson DM, Sendek A, Vilà M, Wilson JRU, Winter M, Genovesi P, & Bacher S (2014) A Unified Classification of Alien Species Based on the Magnitude of their Environmental Impacts. *PLoS Biology*, 12(5), e1001850. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001850>
- Boudouresque, C.F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., Charbonnel, E., Diviacco, G., Meinesz, A., Pergent, G., Pergent-Martini, C., Ruitton, S. & Tunesi, L. (2012) *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows* (p. 202). RAC/SPA and GIS Posidonie publ., Marseille
- Carneiro, L., Hulme, P. E., Cuthbert, R. N., Kourantidou, M., Bang, A., Haubrock, P. J Bradshaw, C.J., Balzani, P., Bacher, S., Latombe, G. & Bodey, T.W. (2024) Benefits do not balance costs of biological invasions. *BioScience*, biae010, <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae010>
- Costello MJ, Dekeyzer D, Galil BS, Hutchings P, Katsanevakis S, Pagad S, Robinson TB, Turon X, Vandepitte L, Vanhoorne B, Verfaille K, Willan RC, & Rius M (2021) Introducing the World Register

- of Introduced Marine Species (WRiMS). *Management of Biological Invasions* 12: 792–811, <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2021.12.4.02>
- David, P., Thebault, E., Anneville, O., Duyck, P. F., Chapuis, E., & Loeuille, N. (2017) Impacts of invasive species on food webs: a review of empirical data. *Advances in Ecological Research*, 56, 1-60, <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2016.10.001>
- Diagne, C., Leroy, B., Vaissière, A.-C., Gozlan, R. E., Roiz, D., Jarić, I., Salles, J.-M., Bradshaw, C. J. A., & Courchamp, F. (2021). High and rising economic costs of biological invasions worldwide. *Nature*, 592(7855), 571–576. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03405-6>
- Doherty, T. S., Glen, A. S., Nimmo, D. G., Ritchie, E. G., & Dickman, C. R. (2016) Invasive predators and global biodiversity loss. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113, 11261–11265. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1602480113>
- Essl, F., Dullinger, S., Rabitsch, W., Hulme, P. E., Hülber, K., Jarošík, V., Kleinbauer, I., Krausmann, F., Kühn, I., Nentwig, W., & Vilà, M. (2011) Socioeconomic legacy yields an invasion debt. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(1), 203-207. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1011728108>
- Gallardo, B., Clavero, M., Sánchez, M. I., & Vilà, M. (2016) Global ecological impacts of invasive species in aquatic ecosystems. *Global Change Biology*, 22, 151-163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13004>
- Giakoumi, S., Katsanevakis, S., Albano, P.G., Azzurro, E., Cardoso, A.C., Cebrian, E., Deidun, A., et al. (2019b) Management priorities for marine invasive species. *Sci Total Environ* 688, 976–982. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.282>
- González-Moreno, P., Lazzaro, L., Vilà, M., Preda, C., Adriaens, T., Bacher, S., Essl, F., García-Berthou, E., Kenis, M., Martinou, A. F., Nentwig, W., O'Flynn, C., Roques, A., Vanderhoeven, S., Ylivainio, K., & Roy, H. E. (2019). Consistency of impact assessment protocols for non-native species. *NeoBiota*, 44, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.44.31650>
- Goodenough, A. E. (2010) Are the ecological impacts of alien species misrepresented? A review of the “native good, alien bad” philosophy. *Community Ecology*, 11, 13–21. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1556/ComEc.11.2010.1.3>
- Guerin, G. R., Martín-Forés, I., Sparrow, B., & Lowe, A. J. (2018) The biodiversity impacts of non-native species should not be extrapolated from biased single-species studies. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 27, 785-790. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-017-1439-0>
- Hawkins, C. L., Bacher, S., Essl, F., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., Kühn, I., Kumschick, S., Nentwig, W., Pergl, J., Pyšek, P., & Rabitsch, W. (2015) Framework and guidelines for implementing the proposed IUCN Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT). *Diversity and Distributions*, 21, 1360-1363. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12379>
- IUCN. (2020). *IUCN EICAT Categories and Criteria. The Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT): First edition*. Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK: IUCN. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2020.05.en>
- Katsanevakis, S., Olenin, S., Puntilla-Dodd, R., Rilov, G., Stæhr, P. A., Teixeira, H., Tsirintanis, K., Birchenough, S. N., Jakobsen, H. H., Knudsen, S. W., & Lanzén, A. (2023) Marine invasive alien species in Europe: 9 years after the IAS Regulation. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10, p.1271755. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1271755>
- Katsanevakis, S., Belmaker, J., Rilov, G., Yeruham, E., Konstantinidis, A., Papazekou, M., Giakoumi, S. & Mazaris, A.D. (2024) Navigating the new normal: rethinking conservation strategies in the

- climate-impacted and highly invaded eastern Mediterranean. *Research Square*, preprint. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4465704/v1>
- Kelsch, A., Takahashi, Y., Dasgupta, R., Mader, A. D., Johnson, B. A., Kumar, P. (2020) Invasive alien species and local communities in socio-ecological production landscapes and seascapes: A systematic review and analysis. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 112, 275-281.
- Magliozzi, C., Tsiamis, K., Vigiak, O., Deriu, I., Gervasini, E., Cardoso, A. C. (2020) Assessing invasive alien species in European catchments: Distribution and impacts. *Science of the Total Environment*, 732, 138677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138677>
- Miccoli, A., Mancini, E., Boschi, M., Provenza, F., Lelli, V., Tiralongo, F., Renzi, M., Terlizzi, A., Bonamano, S., Marcelli, M. (2021) Trophic, Chemo-Ecological and Sex-Specific Insights on the Relation Between *Diplodus sargus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and the Invasive *Caulerpa cylindracea* (Sonder, 1845). *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 680787. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.680787>
- Morin P.J. (2009) *Community ecology*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Micheli, F., Halpern, B. S., Walbridge, S., Ciriaco, S., Ferretti, F., Fraschetti, S., Lewison, R., Nykjaer, L., Rosenberg, A. A. (2013) Cumulative human impacts on Mediterranean and Black Sea marine ecosystems: Assessing current pressures and opportunities. *PLoS ONE*, 8(12), e79889. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0079889>
- Nikolaou, A., Katsanevakis, S. (2023) Marine extinctions and their drivers. *Regional Environmental Change*, 23(3), 88. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-023-02081-8>
- Nikolaou, A., Tsirintanis, K., Rilov, G., Katsanevakis, S. (2023) Invasive fish and sea urchins drive the status of canopy forming macroalgae in the eastern Mediterranean. *Biology*, 12(6), 763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12060763>
- Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A. (2007). Global change and marine communities: Alien species and climate change. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 55(7-9), 342-352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2006.11.014>
- Polce, C., Cardoso, A.C., Deriu, I., Gervasini, E., Tsiamis, K., Vigiak, O., Zulian, G., Maes, J. (2023) Invasive alien species of policy concerns show widespread patterns of invasion and potential pressure across European ecosystems. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 8124.
- Pyšek P, Hulme PE, Simberloff D, Bacher S, Blackburn TM, Carlton JT, Dawson W, Essl F, Foxcroft LC, Genovesi P, Jeschke JM, Kühn I, Liebhold AM, Mandrak NE, Meyerson LA, Richardson DM (2020) Scientists' warning on invasive alien species. *Biological Reviews* 95: 1511–1534, <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12627>
- Ragkousis, M., Sini, M., Koukourouli, N., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S (2023a) Invading the Greek Seas: Spatiotemporal Patterns of Marine Impactful Alien and Cryptogenic Species. *Diversity*, 15(8), 353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15030353>
- Ragkousis, M., Zenetos, A., Ben Souissi, J., Hoffman, R., Ghanem, R., Taşkın, E., Muresan, M., Karpova, E., Slynko, E., Dağlı, E., Fortič, A., Surugiu, V., Mačić, V., Trkov, D., Rjiba Bahri, W., Tsiamis, K., Ramos-Esplá, A. A., Petović, S., Ferrario, J., Marchini, A., ... Katsanevakis, S. (2023b). Unpublished Mediterranean and Black Sea records of marine alien, cryptogenic, and neofaunal species. *BiolInvasions Records*, 12(2), 339–369. <https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2023.12.2.01>
- Raitsos, D. E., Beaugrand, G., Georgopoulos, D., Zenetos, A., Pancucci-Papadopoulou, A. M., Theocharis, A., Papathanassiou, E. (2010) Global climate change amplifies the entry of tropical

- species into the Eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 55(4), 1478-1484. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2010.55.4.1478>
- Ricciardi, A., Hoopes, M. F., Marchetti, M. P., Lockwood, J. L. (2013) Progress toward understanding the ecological impacts of nonnative species. *Ecological Monographs*, 83, 263–282. <https://doi.org/10.1890/13-0183.1>
- Rilov, G. (2009) “Predator-Prey Interactions of Marine Invaders.” in Biological Invasions in Marine Ecosystems, eds G. Rilov, J. A. Crooks (Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer), Ecological Studies, vol 204, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-79236-9_15
- Rilov, G. (2016) Multi-species collapses at the warm edge of a warming sea. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 36897. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep36897>
- Rilov G., Frascchetti S., Gissi E., Pipitone C., Badalamenti F., Tamburello L., et al. (2020). A fast-moving target: achieving marine conservation goals under shifting climate and policies. *Ecol. Appl.* 30, e02009. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2009>
- Rilov, G., Canning-Clode, J., Guy-Haim, T. (2023) Ecological impacts of invasive ecosystem engineers: A global perspective across terrestrial and aquatic systems. *Functional Ecology*, 00, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.14406>
- Sala E, Kizilkaya Z, Yildirim D, Ballesteros E (2011) Alien marine fishes deplete algal biomass in the eastern Mediterranean. *PLoS ONE* 6: e17356, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0017356>
- Sax, D. F., Schlaepfer, M. A., Olden, J. D. (2022) Valuing the contributions of non-native species to people and nature. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 37(12), 1058-1066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2022.08.005>
- Seebens, H., Blackburn, T. M., Dyer, E. E., Genovesi, P., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., ... Essl, F. (2017) No saturation in the accumulation of alien species worldwide. *Nature Communications*, 8, 14435. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14435>
- Schultz, L., Wessely, J., Dullinger, S., & Albano, P. G. (2024) The climate crisis affects Mediterranean marine molluscs of conservation concern. *Diversity and Distributions*, 30, e13805. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13805>
- Shackleton, R. T., Shackleton, C. M., Kull, C. A. (2019a) The role of invasive alien species in shaping local livelihoods and human well-being: A review. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 229, 145-157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.05.007>
- Shackleton, R. T., Richardson, D. M., Shackleton, C. M., Bennett, B., Crowley, S. L., Dehnen-Schmutz, K., ... Marchante, E. (2019b) Explaining people's perceptions of invasive alien species: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 229, 10-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.04.045>
- Spalding MD, Fox HE, Allen GR, Davidson N, Ferdaña ZA, Finlayson M, Halpern BS, Jorge MA, Lombana A, Lourie SA, Martin KD, McManus E, Molnar J, Recchia CA, Robertson J (2007) Marine ecoregions of the world: A bioregionalization
- Sini, M., Katsanevakis, S., Koukourouli, N., Gerovasileiou, V., Dailianis, T., Buhl-Mortensen, L., ... & Frantzis, A. (2017). Assembling Ecological Pieces to Reconstruct the Conservation Puzzle of the Aegean Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4, 347. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00347>
- Simberloff D, Martin JL, Genovesi P, Maris V, Wardle DA, Aronson J, Courchamp F, Galil B, García-Berthou E, Pascal M, Pyšek P, Sousa R, Tabacchi E, Vilà M (2013) Impacts of biological invasions: what's what and the way forward. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 28: 58–66, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2012.07.013>

- Thomsen MS, Wernberg T, Olden JD, Griffin JN, Silliman BR (2011) A framework to study the context-dependent impacts of marine invasions. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 400: 322–327, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2011.02.033>
- Tomas F, Box A, Terrados J (2011a) Effects of invasive seaweeds on feeding preference and performance of a keystone Mediterranean herbivore. *Biological Invasions* 13(7): 1559–1570, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-010-9913-6>
- Topouzelis, K., Makri, D., Stoupas, N., Papakonstantinou, A., & Katsanevakis, S. (2018). Seagrass mapping in Greek territorial waters using Landsat-8 satellite images. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 67, 98–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2017.12.011>
- Tsirintanis, K., Azzurro, E., Crocetta, F., Dimiza, M., Froggia, C., Gerovasileiou, V., ... & Stern, N. (2022). Bioinvasion impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human health in the Mediterranean Sea. *Aquatic Invasions*, 17(2), 308–352. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2022.17.2.06>
- Tsirintanis K, Sini M, Ragkousis M, Zenetos A, Katsanevakis S. (2023) Cumulative Negative Impacts of Invasive Alien Species on Marine Ecosystems of the Aegean Sea. *Biology*. 12:933. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12070933>
- Tsirintanis, K. (2023). *Methods for alien species impact assessment: applications in the Mediterranean Sea*. Doctoral Thesis, University of the Aegean, Mytilene.
- Vergés A, Tomas F, Cebrian E, Ballesteros E, Kizilkaya Z, Dendrinou P, Karamanlidis AA, Spiegel D, Sala E (2014) Tropical rabbitfish and the deforestation of a warming temperate sea. *Journal of Ecology* 102: 1518–1527, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12324>
- Vilà M, Espinar JL, Hejda M, Hulme PE, Jarošík V, Maron JL, Pergl J, Schaffner U, Sun Y, Pyšek P (2011) Ecological impacts of invasive alien plants: a meta-analysis of their effects on species, communities and ecosystems. *Ecology Letters* 14: 702–708, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01628.x>
- Vimercati G, Kumschick S, Probert AF, Volery L, Bacher S (2020) The importance of assessing positive and beneficial impacts of alien species. *NeoBiota* 62: 525–545, <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.62.52793>
- Vimercati, G., Probert, A. F., Volery, L., Bernardo-Madrid, R., Bertolino, S., Cespedes, V., ... & Pergams, O. R. W. (2022). The EICAT+ framework enables classification of positive impacts of alien taxa on native biodiversity. *PLoS Biology*, 20(8), e3001729. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001729>
- Yemshanov, D., Koch, F. H., Ducey, M., & Koehler, K. (2013). Mapping ecological risks with a portfolio-based technique: Incorporating uncertainty and decision-making preferences. *Diversity and Distributions*, 19(5-6), 567–579. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12029>
- Yeruham E, Rilov G, Shpigel M, & Abelson A (2015). Collapse of the echinoid *Paracentrotus lividus* populations in the Eastern Mediterranean - result of climate change? *Scientific Reports* 5: 13479, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep13479>

7.8 Case study 20: CIMPAL-ES⁻ and CIMPAL-ES⁺: accounting for cumulative impacts on ecosystem services

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7.8.1 Introduction

Marine IAS are increasingly recognized for their complex roles in transforming ecosystems and influencing ecological dynamics globally (Gallardo et al., 2016; Katsanevakis et al., 2023, 2014; Tsirintanis et al., 2022). According to the latest IPBES report (2023), invasive species represent a rapidly escalating challenge, with projections indicating a one-third increase in the global number of alien species by 2050 compared to 2005 if current socio-economic trends continue. The impact of such invasions is multifaceted and dynamic, driven by numerous factors, and can produce both negative and positive outcomes (Katsanevakis et al., 2014; Mason et al., 2017; Tsirintanis et al., 2022).

In past decades, IAS were studied and managed exclusively as threats to the ecosystems they invaded due to their disruptive interactions, such as predation and competition (Valéry et al., 2008, 2009). These species undeniably cause significant ecological and socio-economic impacts, including biodiversity loss, economic costs, and disruptions to human well-being (IPBES 2023). However, recent years have seen growing interest in exploring not only the drawbacks but also the potential benefits of these incursions for biodiversity and ecosystem services (Vilà et al., 2017; Bacher et al., 2018; Vimercati et al., 2020; Tsirintanis et al., 2022). Indeed, some invasive species have been found to contribute positively in various contexts, enhancing biofiltration, providing food, sequestering carbon, creating novel habitats, and altering trophic flows, among other ecosystem functions (Triantaphyllou et al., 2009; Camps-Castellà et al., 2020; Sinopoli et al., 2020; Marchessaux et al., 2021; Tsirintanis et al., 2022).

In the European Union (EU) and globally, there is a concerted effort to limit the introduction of invasive species, mitigate their negative impacts, utilize species with commercial or other positive impact, and restore affected ecosystems through the development of legislation, creation of guidelines, and targeted management measures (Katsanevakis et al., 2023). In the EU, important legislative instruments for addressing the introduction and proliferation of invasive alien species include: i) the Regulation No 1143/2014 also known as the IAS Regulation which is a critical biosecurity program across Europe, ii) the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which aims to regulate established IAS and halving the number of Red List species at risk by 2030, iii) and the MSFD, which asserts that achieving good ecological status requires maintaining alien species at levels that do not cause adverse

alterations to marine ecosystems. At a global level, the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) addresses invasive species management in Target 6, which aims to eradicate or control invasive alien species on islands and other priority ecosystems by at least 50% by 2030 to reduce their impact on biodiversity and ecosystems. Also, Target 11 emphasizes on the protection of ecosystem services by restoring, maintaining, and enhancing nature's contribution to people. Although progress is being made in addressing invasive alien species, the IPBES (2023) report highlights significant gaps in global efforts, with 83% of countries lacking specific laws or regulations to manage invasive alien species. Additionally, nearly half of all countries (45%) are not investing in the management of these species.

In the context of the aforementioned regulations and strategies, a series of indicators have been created which evaluate the impact of IAS on biodiversity (Hawkins et al., 2015; Katsanevakis et al., 2016; Vimercati et al., 2020), habitats (Çinar and Bakir, 2014; Kytinou et al., 2023), socio-economic factors (Bacher et al., 2018; Galanidi et al., 2018), ecosystem services (Walsh et al., 2016; Vilà et al., 2017; Tsirintanis et al., 2022), and human health (Tsirintanis et al., 2022). Despite the growing body of research, there is a lack of tools assessing the spatial dimensions of invasive species' impacts on ecosystem services, either positive or negative. This lack of clarity often obstructs the development of effective policies and management actions. As research progresses and policy evolves, it becomes increasingly important to assess the specific impacts of individual invasive species on ecosystem services. This assessment must consider the intensity and spatial distribution of these effects, providing a comprehensive understanding of the issue and supporting the development of more effective management and policy strategies (Ojaveer et al., 2015; Giakoumi et al., 2019; Tsirintanis et al., 2022).

To address these needs, we have created a new index, CIMPAL-ES, based on the CIMPAL index (Katsanevakis et al., 2016), for assessing and mapping the impacts of IAS on ecosystem services. This indicator is based on a standardized, quantitative method that uses existing evidence to map both the cumulative negative and positive impacts of invasive alien species on marine ecosystem services. The use of CIMPAL-ES is demonstrated in two case studies with varying data availability and resolution, the Mediterranean Sea and the Aegean Sea. The Mediterranean Sea has been identified as the region with the highest number of marine IAS globally (Costello et al., 2021), with more than 750 established taxa, (Zenetos et al., 2022). By the end of 2019, about 150 alien species have been successfully established in the Aegean Sea. The introduction and proliferation of invasive alien species in the Mediterranean Sea are primarily attributed to human activities and interventions, especially the opening of the Suez Canal and shipping (Zenetos et al., 2012). Climate change has further exacerbated the issue by raising temperatures, benefiting thermophilic alien species and disadvantaging native

species (Corrales et al., 2018; Katsanevakis et al., 2023). The CIMPAL-ES results for the Mediterranean and Aegean Seas provide quantitative and spatial data that can inform the development of policies aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of invasive species, exploring potential benefits, and enhancing the environmental status of marine ecosystems. The CIMPAL-ES index method can be readily applied to other marine or terrestrial regions by following the steps delineated in the framework presented in this paper.

7.8.2 Methods

Cumulative Impact of Marine Alien Species on Ecosystem Services (CIMPAL-ES)

The framework for assessing the cumulative impacts of IAS on marine ecosystems builds on the previous model of Katsanevakis et al. (2016) adequately adapting it to align with the concept of ecosystem services. For this, two new indicators were developed to assess both positive and negative impacts of alien species on ecosystem services provided by marine habitats, designated as CIMPAL-ES+ and CIMPAL-ES-, respectively. In order to ensure consistency and comparability of results, the study areas must be subdivided into cells of equal area. For each cell the cumulative impact values $I_{C_{neg}}$ and $I_{C_{pos}}$ are estimated. These indicators are the following:

$$I_{C_{neg}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{z=1}^m A_i H_j W_{i,j,z_{neg}}$$

(Equation 7.8.1)

$$I_{C_{pos}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{z=1}^m A_i H_j W_{i,j,z_{pos}}$$

(Equation 7.8.2)

A_i represents the state of the population of i-th IAS in the specific cell, normalized to range between 0 and 1. A_i can be estimated using abundance or relative abundance, modelled probability of presence, or presence-absence data of the specific IAS. It is preferable to utilize abundance data, as it is better related to its impact on the ecosystem services. However, if such data are unavailable, occupancy or presence/absence of the species can be employed instead.

H_j represents the extent of environment “j” in which invasive alien species “i” are present and affects the ecosystem services provided by it in the specific cell. The ecology of the species determines which habitats and human constructions they are found in and in which bathymetric zones. The impact of species on ecosystem services provided by habitats and infrastructures will be made in these areas.

Therefore, habitats are used here as the basic unit to identify ecosystem services impacts associated with individual invasive alien species, as they are easily defined spatially. The optimal approach is to utilize maps of the distribution of ecosystem services associated with each habitat or facility. In instances where this is not feasible, alternative options include the use of maps of habitats or binary data maps (0 or 1) indicating the presence or absence of the habitat.

$w_{i,j,z}$ is the impact weight for species “i” and ecosystem services or well-being and socio-economic benefits “z” of habitat “j” (the higher the impact of species “i” on ecosystem service or well-being and socio-economic benefits “z” of habitats “j”, the higher the value of $w_{i,j,z}$). The negative and positive effects of alien species influx and their impact on ecosystem services, as shown in Fig. 7.8.1 and Fig. 7.8.2, are examined, and a distinction is made between Equations 7.8.1 and 7.8.2, with the only difference being the terms $w_{i,j,z_{neg}}$ and $w_{i,j,z_{pos}}$. The impact weights are evaluated according to two factors: the strength of evidence and the impact magnitude. As illustrated in Fig. 7.8.1, 7.8.2, the strength of evidence is classified into three levels, following the models of Katsanevakis et al. (2016) (robust, medium, and limited), while the determination of the magnitude of impact is designed to undergo a more comprehensive multilevel analysis. To determine the level of the impact magnitude the first step is to determine whether it is negative (Fig. 7.8.1), or positive (Fig. 7.8.2). Then it is chosen whether it concerns ecosystem services or socio-economic and cultural goods and benefits. In more detail, the proposal of Elliott (2023) was followed, according to which ecosystem services only concern regulating and providing, while cultural (as defined in the Common international classification for ecosystem services-CICES V5. 1 (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018)) are not considered services, as they require capital input. Instead, they are considered socio-economic and cultural goods and benefits. Therefore, a classification system is proposed in which the socio-economic benefits are based on the system proposed by Bacher et al. (2018); the terminology for positive impacts is retained, while rewording is applied to the negative impacts. In a similar vein, a classification of the impact magnitude in ecosystem services was devised in accordance with the framework of Bacher et al. (2018). The $w_{i,j,z}$ will be spatially constant and could be calculated according to the highest, or average or minimal impact reported.

n, m are the number of invasive species and ecosystem services related to each habitat.

Application of CIMPAL-ES: Mediterranean Sea Case Study

The Mediterranean Sea was divided into 26,740 uniform grid cells, each covering 10 km², and categorised into subregions defined by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD): (1) Western

Mediterranean Sea, (2) Adriatic Sea, (3) Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea, and (4) Aegean-Levantine Sea. The index A_i represented by occurrences data for 80 IAS belonging to 14 phyla, as presented in Table A.2.1 (see Annex), and were retrieved from the European Alien Species Information Network – EASIN. The values within each cell were assigned binary values (0 or 1) based on the occurrence or non-occurrence of the specific species under examination.

The term $H_{i,j}$ was determined based on the ecology and impact of IAS and consists of two components: the human component and the environmental component. The human component includes facilities and activities, such as aquaculture sites, where these species are found and affect ecosystem services. The environmental component encompasses 13 habitats where these species are located and impact ecosystem services, as detailed in Table A.2.1 (see Annex). The presence or absence of each species in these areas, along with their positive or negative impacts, was assessed using available literature and expert input.

For the environmental component, if spatial distribution data were available, the proportion of each habitat within a cell was calculated. If spatial distribution data were not available, the presence or absence of a habitat within a cell was represented in binary form (0 or 1). Table A.2.1 (see Annex) provides a detailed outline of the data utilised for the environmental component, including its format and the source from which it was obtained.

Similarly, for the human component, if spatial distribution data were available, the proportion of each facility type within a cell was calculated. If spatial distribution data were not available, the presence or absence of a facility type within a cell was represented in binary form.

To determine $w_{i,j,z}$, the database from Tsirintanis et al. (2022) was used to assess the impact magnitude of these 80 species on their associated ecosystem services, based on the categorisation system proposed in this study. The parameter $w_{i,j,z}$ is spatially constant. We used the maximum value reported for each species and ecosystem service. Table A.2.1 (see Annex) provides the $w_{i,j,z}$ values for each species and ecosystem service.

To evaluate the cumulative impact of invasive alien species on ecosystem services, positive and negative, seven D-indicators were estimated: (D_1) represents the total area of occurrence, quantified as the total number of 1 km² cells; ($D_{2.neg}$) and ($D_{2.pos}$) refer to the number of cells where the negative and positive impacts on any ecosystem service are greater than 0, respectively; ($D_{3.neg}$) and ($D_{3.pos}$) are the sums of negative and positive impact scores for all ecosystem services of the species across the entire study area; ($D_{4.neg}$) and ($D_{4.pos}$) denote the average negative and positive impacts for all ecosystem services of the species within the study area.

Application of CIMPAL-ES: Aegean Sea Case Study

To apply the CIMPAL-ES to the Aegean Sea, the region was divided into cells of equal area (1 km^2); the total number of cells was 321,346. For the term A_i species distribution models (SDMs) of 29 IAS from 13 phyla, as presented in Table S1, were employed and derived by Ragkousis et al. (submitted), values of these distribution models were normalized (0-1). Two scenarios were examined for applying the index. In the first, the SDMs (species distribution models) were used without modification. In the second, a threshold of 0.5 was applied to evaluate the CIMPAL-ES sensitivity.

Similarly to the Mediterranean Sea case study for the term $H_{i,j}$, encompassing both environmental and human components, the proportion within a cell was calculated when spatial distribution data were available. If such data were unavailable, the presence or absence within a cell was represented in binary form (0 or 1). An additional activity examined in the Aegean Sea was the fishing effort of small-scale fisheries (Papazekou et al., in preparation), leveraging the availability of relevant data (see Annex; Table A.2.1).

The term $w_{i,j,z}$, as previous, was derived using the database from Tsirintanis et al. (2022) and the proposed framework to evaluate the impact magnitude of 27 species on their associated ecosystem services. Similarly, the $w_{i,j,z}$ was spatially constant and we have used the maximum value reported per species per ecosystem service (see Annex; Table A.2.1).

To assess the overall impact of invasive alien species on ecosystem services, both positive and negative, the seven indicators (D_1 , $D_{2,\text{neg}}$, $D_{2,\text{pos}}$, $D_{3,\text{neg}}$, $D_{3,\text{pos}}$, $D_{4,\text{neg}}$, $D_{4,\text{pos}}$) previously assessed for the Mediterranean Sea were employed.

The Aegean Sea region was included in both case studies, facilitating comparisons of the results. Given the difference in cell dimensions between the two case studies (10 km^2 for the Mediterranean and 1 km^2 for the Aegean Sea) the methodology involved identifying Aegean cells with values greater than zero in the Mediterranean case study. The average values of the corresponding overlapping cells from the Aegean Sea case study were then calculated. The difference between these values, along with their percentage change, highlights the sensitivity of the index to the input data used.

Figure 7.8.1. Negative impact weights were defined based on both the magnitude of impact and the related strength of evidence. The categories of evidence are based on those proposed by (Katsanevakis et al., 2014). The classification of impact magnitude is divided into ecosystem services (regulating and provisioning) and socio-economic and cultural goods and benefits, following the framework put forth by (Elliott, 2023). For the socio-economic category, classification is based on that proposed by (Bacher et al., 2018), while for ecosystem services, the same classification is used but with rephrased levels.

Figure 7.8.2. Positive impact weights were defined based on both the magnitude of impact and the related strength of evidence. The categories of evidence are based on those proposed by (Katsanevakis et al., 2014). The classification of impact magnitude is divided into ecosystem services (regulating and provisioning) and socio-economic and cultural goods and benefits, following the framework put forth by (Elliott, 2023). For the socio-economic category, classification is based on that proposed by (Bacher et al., 2018), while for ecosystem services, the same classification is used but with rephrased levels.

7.8.3 Results

Mediterranean Sea Case Study

The implementation of the CIMPAL-ES index in the Mediterranean Sea highlights substantial spatial variations in both positive and negative impacts on ecosystem services across subregions. Negative impacts reach a maximum value of 26.90 (Figure 7.8.3), with most affected areas concentrated within the bathymetric zone of approximately 50 meters. Positive impacts, on the other hand, peak at 34.94 (Figure 7.8.4). Notably, some areas exhibit both positive and negative impacts, while others experience exclusively positive or negative effects. In either case, the most affected regions are predominantly located in shallow waters.

Examining the MSFD Mediterranean zones, the Western Mediterranean Sea and Aegean-Levantine Sea demonstrate the highest total negative impacts on ecosystem services, with both zones having similar area sizes (Figure 7.8.5). In contrast, for total positive impacts, the Aegean-Levantine Sea ranks first, followed by the Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean, which had previously ranked last for negative impacts (Figure 7.8.6). When considering the impacts relative to the area of each MSFD zone, the highest proportional negative impact is observed in the Adriatic Sea, followed by the Aegean-Levantine Sea, Western Mediterranean Sea, and finally the Ionian Sea-Central Mediterranean Sea (Figure 7.8.5). A similar ranking is observed for positive impacts when adjusted for area size, with the Adriatic Sea showing the highest proportional positive influence, followed by the same order of zones (Figure 7.8.6).

The contributions of various ecosystem services to the cumulative negative impact, ranked in descending order, are as follows (Figure 7.8.7): food provision (42%, 1,523 total impact), lifecycle maintenance (38%, 1,385 total impact), ocean nourishment (8%), recreation and tourism (4%), symbolic and aesthetic values (3%), climate regulation (2%), water storage and provision (2%), and cognitive effects (1%). Services such as coastal protection, biotic materials and biofuels, air quality regulation, weather regulation, biological regulation, and water purification contributed approximately 0%. The contributions of various ecosystem services to the cumulative positive impact, ranked in descending order, are as follows: food provision (25%, 1,059 total impact), coastal protection (24%, 1,029 total impact), cognitive effects (22%), biotic materials and biofuels (15%), lifecycle maintenance (12%), and climate regulation (2%). Other services, including water storage and provision, air quality regulation, weather regulation, ocean nourishment, biological regulation, symbolic and aesthetic values, recreation and tourism, and water purification, contributed approximately 0%.

The literature review identified 80 species impacting 12 of the 14 ecosystem services (see Annex; [Table A.2.1](#)), with their effects varying widely based on distribution and ecological roles. Invasive alien species demonstrate diverse and multifaceted patterns of influence on Mediterranean ecosystem services. Some species have exclusively negative effects (e.g., *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Rugulopteryx okamurae*), while others have only positive effects (e.g., *Halophila stipulacea*, *Pterois miles*). Species like *Caulerpa cylindracea* have a more complex impact, exerting both positive and negative effects on a range of ecosystem services (n=8), resulting in a balanced overall influence ([Figures 7.8.8-11](#)). *Caulerpa cylindracea* is widespread across the region ([Figure 7.8.8](#)) and is extensively studied, providing a comprehensive understanding of its effects (see Annex; [Table A.2.1](#)). *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, also widespread ([Figure 7.8.8](#)), has exclusively negative impacts, particularly on food provision, with significant regional and local effects ([Figures 7.8.10-11](#), see Annex; [Table A.2.1](#)). *Halophila stipulacea* delivers only positive impacts, ranking first in total positive scores ([Figure 7.8.10](#)) and sixth in average impact scores ([Figure 7.8.11](#)), indicating strong overall and localized benefits. In contrast, *Rugulopteryx okamurae*, with the highest average negative impact score, affects multiple ecosystem services, including lifecycle maintenance, but its limited distribution reduces its total regional impact. However, its local effects are significant where established ([Figures 7.8.8-11](#), see Annex; [Table A.2.1](#)). Meanwhile, *Pterois miles*, which has only positive impacts, is widely distributed ([Figure 7.8.8](#)), but its low average impact score ([Figure 7.8.11](#)) means that its overall effect ([Figure 7.8.10](#)) is not significant despite its widespread presence.

Figure 7.8.3. Map of cumulative negative impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES-) in the Mediterranean Sea. The color gradient indicates the cumulative impact per 10 km² cell, with darker shades representing areas of higher negative impact. Regions of the Mediterranean without cells on the color scale indicate a CIMPAL-ES- value of zero.

Figure 7.8.4. Map of cumulative positive impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES+) in the Mediterranean Sea. The color gradient indicates the cumulative impact per 10 km² cell, with darker shades representing areas of higher positive impact. Regions of the Mediterranean without cells on the color scale indicate a CIMPAL-ES+ value of zero.

Figure 7.8.5. Statistics of the cumulative negative impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES-) within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Mediterranean zones. The color scale indicates the deviation of total negative cumulative impacts on ecosystem services relative to area size.

Figure 7.8.6. Statistics of the cumulative positive impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES+) within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Mediterranean zones. The color scale indicates the deviation of total positive cumulative impacts on ecosystem services relative to area size.

Figure 7.8.7. Positive and negative total impacts of each ecosystem service in the Mediterranean Sea. Green bars represent the positive impact of each ecosystem service, while red bars represent the negative impact.

Figure 7.8.8. Total area of occurrence of invasive alien species in the Mediterranean Sea. Purple represents invertebrates, yellow represents macrophytes, and blue represents fish.

Figure 7.8.9. Number of cells (10*10km) with impacts greater than zero from invasive alien species on ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea. Red represents negative impacts, while green represents positive impacts.

Figure 7.8.10. The sum of impact scores of invasive alien species on ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea. The x-axis is displayed in logarithmic values. Red represents negative impacts, while green represents positive impacts.

Figure 7.8.11. The average impact scores of invasive alien species on ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea. Red represents negative impacts, while green represents positive impacts.

Aegean Sea

The application of the CIMPAL-ES indicator in the Aegean Sea has revealed notable spatial heterogeneity and marked contrasts between the positive and negative impacts on ecosystem services. Negative impacts, which ranged from 0 to 27.48, were observed across a wide range of bathymetric zones, with higher concentrations in coastal areas, and the maximum values are concentrated in the southern region ([Figure 7.8.12](#)). The contributions of different ecosystem services to the cumulative negative impact, in descending order, are: lifecycle maintenance (38%), food (22%), recreation and tourism (17%), water storage and provision (11%), ocean nourishment (9%), symbolic and aesthetic values (3%), air quality regulation, water purification, weather regulation, biological regulation, biotic materials and biofuels, cognitive effects, coastal protection and climate regulation approximately (0%). The positive impacts, which ranged from 0 to 33.26, were primarily concentrated in coastal zones, while offshore areas with depths exceeding 50 meters generally exhibited zero impact ([Figure 7.8.13](#)). The highest positive impacts were observed in the south-central Aegean, with more modest effects observed in the northern region. The contributions of different ecosystem services to the cumulative positive impact, in descending order, are: cognitive effects (33%), coastal protection (19%), biotic materials and biofuels (14%), climate regulation (14%), lifecycle maintenance (13%), food provision (5%), water purification (2%), biological regulation, air quality regulation, weather regulation, water storage and provision, ocean nourishment, recreation and tourism, and symbolic and aesthetic values approximately 0%.

The proposed assessment framework revealed that some ecosystem services were extensively studied, with numerous species having significant impacts and broad distributions across various areas, while others had either no or very limited data, and insights about their impact. For example, lifecycle maintenance was negatively impacted by nine species in the Aegean Sea, each with a maximum impact score of 4. These species were widely distributed, affecting habitats, aquaculture, and fisheries. In contrast, cognitive effects showed the greatest positive impact on CIMPAL-ES, with 14 species contributing to this service in the Aegean Sea. These species had a maximum impact weight of 4 and a broad spatial distribution, primarily influencing coastal habitats and human activities. The [Table A.2.1](#) (see Annex) offers detailed information on impact weights, species-specific impacts on ecosystem services, species distribution, affected habitats and human constructions-activities, along with maps illustrating the cumulative positive and negative impacts of each ecosystem service.

Figure 7.8.12. Map of cumulative negative impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES-) in the Aegean Sea. The colour gradient indicates the cumulative impact per 1 km² cell, with darker shades representing areas of higher negative impact.

Invasive alien species in the Aegean Sea have varying effects on ecosystem services, displaying a range of impact patterns. The ranking of species with the most significant negative or positive impacts varied based on the indicator used and the application of a threshold to the species distribution model (Figure 7.8.14). *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Hydroides elegans* showed notable reductions in spatial distribution, with decreases of 72% and 68% in the number of affected cells, respectively (Figure 7.8.14, D1). *Lagocephalus sceleratus* displayed the most extensive and stable presence, initially identified in 135,906 cells (1 km² each), though its presence decreased by 6% after applying the

threshold. Despite this broad distribution, *Lagocephalus sceleratus* ranks fourth in overall negative impact across the Aegean (Figure 7.8.14, D3). In contrast, *Caulerpa cylindracea* has a more limited spatial distribution but it ranks first overall because of the intensity of its impacts. It records the highest average negative impact value in both assessed scenarios (Figure 7.8.14, D4). Simultaneously *Caulerpa cylindracea* also shows the highest average positive impact value, surpassing the second-ranking *Halophila stipulacea* by more than four points (Figure 7.8.14, D4).

Figure 7.8.13. Map of cumulative positive impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES+) in the Aegean Sea. The color gradient indicates the cumulative impact per 1 km² cell, with darker shades representing areas of higher positive impact.

Figure 7.8.14. Ranking of the impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services in the Aegean Sea according to the four applied indicators D1-D4. For both the negative and the positive impacts and for the two scenarios, one without a threshold value on the species distribution model and one with a threshold value of 0.5.

The sensitivity analysis of applying a threshold in species distribution models within the CIMPAL-ES framework revealed an overall reduction of 6% in impact values when the threshold was implemented. Locally, changes in the CIMPAL-ES indicator ranged from 0 to 5 units, with an average change of 0.16 units (see Annex; [Figure A.2.1](#), [Figure A.2.3](#)). For positive impacts, the overall reduction was 5.6%, with local changes ranging from 0 to 7.22 units and an average change of 0.25 units (see Annex; [Figure A.2.2](#), [Figure A.2.4](#)).

The comparison of results between the two case studies for the Aegean Sea region, using the CIMPAL-ES index, revealed that the Aegean Sea case study had higher values compared to the Mediterranean Sea case study. The negative impact on ecosystem services showed a difference of approximately 3 units (mean 3.47, median 3.12), while the positive impact differed by 8 units (mean 8.85, median 7.8) ([Figure 7.8.15](#)). The cell values in the Aegean Sea case study were higher, with a 77% increase in negative impacts and a 91% increase in positive impacts on ecosystem services compared to the Mediterranean Sea case study.

Figure 7.8.15. Sensitivity Analysis Between Overlapping Regions in the Aegean Sea and Mediterranean Sea Case Studies The two box plots on the left illustrate the differences in cell values between the Mediterranean Sea case study (10 km² resolution) and the mean values of overlapping cells from the Aegean Sea case study (1 km² resolution). The difference is calculated using the formula: $Difference = Mean\ of\ Values_{AegeanCaseStudy} - Cell\ Value_{MediterraneanCaseStudy}$. The two box plots on the right depict the percentage change in cell values between the two case studies, determined using the formula: $Percent\ of\ Change\ (\%) = 100 \times \frac{Mean\ of\ Cell\ Values_{Aegean\ Case\ Study} - Cell\ Value_{Mediterranean\ CaseStudy}}{Mean\ of\ Cell\ Values_{Aegean\ Case\ Study}}$

7.8.4 Discussion

The Cumulative Impacts of Invasive Alien Species on Ecosystem Services (CIMPAL-ES) framework: 1) is straightforward to implement, 2) offers flexibility based on available data, 3) evaluates the impact of each species on both individual and aggregate ecosystem services, 4) assesses and aggregates the impacts of all species by service and category of services, 5) identifies hotspots with significant positive or negative effects, and 6) prioritizes areas, species, and services for management actions, mitigation measures, and further investigation of potential benefits. However, the framework exhibits certain biases and limitations due to its structure and the available data, which are analyzed below, along with proposed solutions for future improvements.

Model Framework Limitations, Data Limitations, and Future Improvements

To assess a species' impacts, we developed and employed an impact-scoring system that effectively substituted quantitative data and examined both positive and negative correlations between the species, ecosystem services, and socio-economic and cultural benefits. The literature includes various indicators for studying the impact of invasive species on ecosystem services according experts elicitation (Martinez-Cillero et al., 2019), a generic impact scoring system (Nentwig et al., 2016), mapping impacts based on economic data (Reynolds et al., 2020), and assessments at the biome scale (van Wilgen et al., 2008). A future research endeavour may prove insightful if these indices were to be employed in the evaluation of either ecosystem services or socio-economic and cultural benefits, and subsequently compared with our estimates $w_{i,j,z_{neg}}$ and $w_{i,j,z_{pos}}$ for the corresponding species.

The estimation of impact weights is based on data collected from the literature and the impact-scoring system developed. In our case studies, it was assumed that the impact weights are spatially constant; however, this may not always reflect actual conditions. For example, in the Mediterranean, while *Atherinomorus forskalii* is used as a food source in some countries like Egypt, it is not consumed in others due to its small size (Otero et al., 2013). This would cause the overestimation of the food provision of the index in some cells. Therefore, the concept of impact weight could be examined through the incorporation of additional variables, thus ensuring a more comprehensive representation. To illustrate, in the case of food provision parameters such as country of origin, economic value of new commodities and commercial species (Özbilgin et al., 2015), and quality characteristics such as fatty acids (El-Gendy et al., 2018), these factors and others determine the impact magnitude. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that as indicators become more complex, their use and interpretation become more challenging, and the availability of data is often limited.

The precision of mapping the cumulative impact of invasive alien species on ecosystem services depends on the quality of the species databases used and the spatial insights they provide, which are represented by term A_i . In our case studies, some species have abundant records, such as *Caulerpa cylindracea* with 1,579 entries and a well-documented impact on various ecosystem services ($n=8$), while others, like *Etrumeus golanii*, have only 59 records and limited impact studies ($n=1$). This discrepancy arises because some species, like *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, have high biomass and are easy to record, while others, like *Caulerpa cylindracea*, are bottom-established and easier to study. Additionally, species that attract more research interest, such as *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, tend to have more data. Another noteworthy point is that only a limited number of species have been reported in offshore regions. Most alien species in the Mediterranean and Aegean are shallow-water thermophilic demersal species. However, reduced sampling effort in offshore areas has resulted in a monitoring and reporting bias favouring coastal regions (Costello et al., 2010; Danovaro et al., 2010). Consequently, databases may not accurately reflect the true status of alien species in pelagic areas, leading to potential underrepresentation of their effects. Using species distribution models could potentially reduce, but not eliminate, this bias. The application of species distribution models is a common methodological approach in the scientific literature. Nevertheless, it is imperative to exercise due diligence when assessing the outcomes, as these models frequently fail to align with the actual circumstances (Robinson et al., 2017).

The environment where a species' impact occurs is crucial for assessing its cumulative effects on ecosystem services, which is reflected in the term H_i . Factors like habitat distribution, human constructions-activities, and the ecology of invasive alien species act as intermediaries that connect species occurrence to their impact on ecosystem services. This approach is particularly useful when data on the spatial distribution of ecosystem services relative to the habitats of the studied species are unavailable. Previous literature has identified difficulties, gaps, and shortcomings in assessing marine and coastal ecosystem services related to habitats (Liquete et al., 2013; Rodrigues et al., 2017), thus supporting the use of these components as proxies in such cases. However, this approach has limitations. It assumes that the presence of a habitat guarantees the optimal provision of associated ecosystem services, without considering the habitat's ecological condition. For instance, not all seagrass meadows provide climate regulation services at the same rate, as this is influenced by multiple factors (Mazarrasa et al., 2018). Furthermore, the calculations incorporate human constructions and activities as binary data. For instance, the presence of aquaculture in a given cell is represented by a value of 1, which is not a realistic assumption given that it is unlikely that the entire surface area of the cell (10 km²) would have facilities. The advancement and optimization of spatial data will assist in addressing these limitations. Furthermore, the generation of maps pertaining to the

assessment of ecosystem service will facilitate the attainment of more precise outcomes when employing the CIMPAL-ES index.

Ecosystem services represent the direct and indirect benefits humanity derives from environmental assets, making them an anthropocentric framework (Costanza et al., 1997). In this research, positive and negative effects were studied separately, without examining synergies, overlaps, and opposing impacts (Rodrigues et al., 2017). For example, in food provision services, *Callinectes sapidus* has a strong negative impact on native species by increasing competition and predation (Kampouris et al., 2019), yet it is also a new commodity with rising demand (Mehanna et al., 2019). At the ecosystem service level, it is significant to assess whether invasive alien species satisfy human dietary requirements by replacing native species or if they degrade this service. Future research should combine the positive and negative impacts of invasive species and apply scenarios to better understand and meet humanity's demands.

A further potential enhancement to the proposed framework would be harmonizing the impacts of invasive species with the costs of management measures and conducting a benefit-cost analysis to identify the optimal measures. The term H_i is associated with the distribution of ecosystem services; in subsequent applications, this term could be expressed in monetary units (Stamatiadou et al., 2023, 2025), allowing the impact of invasive alien species to be quantified as a benefit or loss. Consequently, areas of degradation and resulting monetary deficits can be identified, enabling the investigation of potential management solutions, the development of scenarios, and the application of cost-benefit analysis (Brander et al., 2020).

Foreseeable uses of CIMPAL-ES

The framework, while operating within certain assumptions and limitations, effectively addresses critical gaps and offers vital tools to combat the challenge of invasive alien species. A significant portion of these assumptions and limitations arises from data shortages. Even with substantial investments to fill gaps in mapping, field research, and ecological studies, considerable time would still be required to gather the necessary information to reduce uncertainties and enable well-informed actions.

The impacts of invasive alien species are an urgent and evolving issue, demanding immediate attention. The proposed framework not only bridges existing knowledge gaps but also provides practical solutions, ensuring a timely and effective response to this pressing global challenge.

Using the case studies where the CIMPAL-ES index was applied, potential foreseeable actions include the following:

1. *Prioritization of Management Efforts:* Identifying areas most impacted by invasive alien species, such as south Aegean, to allocate resources effectively, whether addressing their negative impacts or leveraging positive contributions. In cases of negative impacts, strategies may focus on mitigating harm to ecosystem services. Conversely, when positive impacts are identified, opportunities for sustainable utilization can be explored to enhance environmental and societal benefits.
2. *Cross-Border Cooperation:* The large-scale application of the index in the Mediterranean Sea has facilitated discussions on cross-border cooperation. By integrating data on invasive alien species and their impacts on ecosystem services, this approach enables coordinated responses between neighbouring regions or countries. This collaboration is crucial for addressing the shared ecological, economic, and social challenges posed by invasive species across borders.
3. *Detection and Spread Management:* Associating species with ecosystem services and further analysis involving stakeholder groups enables the design of targeted measures for detection and spread management. For example, management authorities can access detailed and integrated data on species, impacts, ecosystem services, and the spatial magnitude of these effects. This facilitates the straightforward deployment of detection tools, such as eDNA analysis or field research, and fosters collaboration with stakeholder groups, including fishers and recreational divers. These efforts support effective monitoring and control measures, ensuring a coordinated and efficient response to invasive species.
4. *Community Engagement:* Raising awareness and involving local communities in managing invasive species to reduce their ecological and socioeconomic impacts. The results of the index are presented in an easily understandable format, using spatial and quantitative data that clearly highlight the scope and severity of the issue. This makes it easier for authorities to communicate with the public and stakeholders about the importance of addressing invasive alien species. By providing clear, actionable information, the index creates a direct link between scientific findings and local communities, enabling effective communication about the environmental and economic risks. This facilitates the involvement of local communities in management efforts, such as prevention, monitoring, and control actions, empowering them to play an active role in mitigating the impacts of invasive species.
5. *Economic Incentives and Funding:* A key challenge in environmental management is securing funding and overcoming the perception that such efforts offer limited returns. However, this approach also highlights the potential benefits of invasive alien species, which could attract interest from several sectors. For example, species like *Brachidontes pharaonis* cause biofouling in industrial pipes but also enhance biofiltration, benefiting factories in wastewater treatment. By recognizing both the

challenges and potential benefits, this dual approach can foster partnerships, turning invasive species research and management into a "win-win" for various stakeholders.

7.8.5 References

- Albano, P. G., Steger, J., Bošnjak, M., Dunne, B., Guifarro, Z., Turapova, E., Hua, Q., Kaufman, D. S., Rilov, G., & Zuschin, M. (2021). Native biodiversity collapse in the eastern Mediterranean. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, 288, 20202469, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2020.2469>
- Bacher, S., Blackburn, T.M., Essl, F., Genovesi, P., Heikkilä, J., Jeschke, J.M., Jones, G., Keller, R., Kenis, M., Kueffer, C., Martinou, A.F., Nentwig, W., Pergl, J., Pyšek, P., Rabitsch, W., Richardson, D.M., Roy, H.E., Saul, W.-C., Scalera, R., Vilà, M., Wilson, J.R.U., & Kumschick, S., (2018). Socio-economic impact classification of alien taxa (SEICAT). *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 9, 159–168. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12844>
- Brander, L.M., van Beukering, P., Nijsten, L., McVittie, A., Baulcomb, C., Eppink, F.V., & Cado van der Lelij, J.A., (2020). The global costs and benefits of expanding Marine Protected Areas. *Marine Policy* 116, 103953. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.103953>
- Camps-Castellà, J., Romero, J., & Prado, P., (2020). Trophic plasticity in the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*, as a function of resource availability and habitat features. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 637, 71–85. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps13235>
- Cebrian, E., Francour, P., Galil, B., Otero, M. del M., & Savini, D., n.d. Monitoring marine invasive species in Mediterranean marine protected areas (MPAs): a strategy and practical guide for managers | Policy Commons.
- Çinar, M.E., & Bakir, K., (2014). Alien Biotic IndEX (ALEX) – A new index for assessing impacts of alien species on benthic communities. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 87, 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.07.061>
- Corrales, X., Coll, M., Ofir, E., Heymans, J.J., Steenbeek, J., Goren, M., Edelist, D., & Gal, G., (2018). Future scenarios of marine resources and ecosystem conditions in the Eastern Mediterranean under the impacts of fishing, alien species and sea warming. *Sci Rep* 8, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-32666-x>
- Costanza, R., d'Arge, R., de Groot, R., Farber, S., Grasso, M., Hannon, B., Limburg, K., Naeem, S., O'Neill, R.V., Paruelo, J., Raskin, R.G., Sutton, P., & van den Belt, M., (1997). The value of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital. *Nature* 387, 253–260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/387253a0>
- Costello, M.J., Coll, M., Danovaro, R., Halpin, P., Ojaveer, H., & Miloslavich, P., (2010). A Census of Marine Biodiversity Knowledge, Resources, and Future Challenges. *PLOS ONE* 5, e12110. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012110>
- Costello, M.J., Dekeyser, S., Galil, B.S., Hutchings, P., Katsanevakis, S., Pagad, S., Robinson, T.B., Turon, X., Vandepitte, L., Vanhoorne, B., Verfaillie, K., Willan, R.C., & Rius, M., (2021). Introducing the World Register of Introduced Marine Species (WRiMS). 792-811. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2021.12.4.02>
- Danovaro, R., Company, J.B., Corinaldesi, C., D'Onghia, G., Galil, B., Gambi, C., Gooday, A.J., Lampadariou, N., Luna, G.M., Morigi, C., Olu, K., Polymenakou, P., Ramirez-Llodra, E., Sabbatini, A., Sardà, F., Sibuet, M., & Tselepides, A., (2010). Deep-Sea Biodiversity in the

- Mediterranean Sea: The Known, the Unknown, and the Unknowable. PLOS ONE 5, e11832. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011832>
- El-Gendy, A.M., El-Feky, F., Mahmoud, N.H., & Elsebakhy, G.S., (2018). Evaluation of nutritional quality of green tiger prawn, *penaeus semisulcatus* from land fisheries (Alexandria) and market (India). The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine 31, 1–11.
- Elliott, M., (2023). Marine Ecosystem Services and Integrated Management: “There’s a crack, a crack in everything, that’s how the light gets in”! Mar Pollut Bull 193, 115177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115177>
- Galanidi, M., Zenetos, A., & Bacher, S., (2018). Assessing the socio-economic impacts of priority marine invasive fishes in the Mediterranean with the newly proposed SEICAT methodology. Mediterranean Marine Science 19, 107–123. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.15940>
- Gallardo, B., Clavero, M., Sánchez, M.I., & Vilà, M., (2016). Global ecological impacts of invasive species in aquatic ecosystems. Global Change Biology 22, 151–163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13004>
- Giakoumi, S., Katsanevakis, S., Albano, P.G., Azzurro, E., Cardoso, A.C., Cebrian, E., Deidun, A., Edelist, D., Francour, P., Jimenez, C., Mačić, V., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Rilov, G., & Sghaier, Y.R., (2019). Management priorities for marine invasive species. Science of The Total Environment 688, 976–982. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.282>
- Haines-Young, R., & Potschin-Young, M., (2018). Revision of the Common International Classification for Ecosystem Services (CICES V5.1): A Policy Brief. One Ecosystem 3, e27108. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.3.e27108>
- Hawkins, C.L., Bacher, S., Essl, F., Hulme, P.E., Jeschke, J.M., Kühn, I., Kumschick, S., Nentwig, W., Pergl, J., Pyšek, P., Rabitsch, W., Richardson, D.M., Vilà, M., Wilson, J.R.U., Genovesi, P., & Blackburn, T.M., (2015). Framework and guidelines for implementing the proposed IUCN Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT). Diversity and Distributions 21, 1360–1363. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12379>
- Kampouris, T.E., Porter, J.S., & Sanderson, W.G., (2019). *Callinectes sapidus* Rathbun, 1896 (Brachyura: Portunidae): An assessment on its diet and foraging behaviour, Thermaikos Gulf, NW Aegean Sea, Greece: Evidence for ecological and economic impacts. Crustacean Research 48, 23–37. https://doi.org/10.18353/crustacea.48.0_23
- Katsanevakis, S., Olenin, S., Puntilla-Dodd, R., Rilov, G., Stæhr, P.A.U., Teixeira, H., Tsirintanis, K., Birchenough, S.N.R., Jakobsen, H.H., Knudsen, S.W., Lanzén, A., Mazaris, A.D., Piraino, S., & Tidbury, H.J., (2023). Marine invasive alien species in Europe: 9 years after the IAS Regulation. Front. Mar. Sci. 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1271755>
- Katsanevakis, S., Tempera, F., & Teixeira, H., (2016). Mapping the impact of alien species on marine ecosystems: the Mediterranean Sea case study. Diversity and Distributions 22, 694–707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12429>
- Katsanevakis, S., Wallentinus, I., Zenetos, A., Leppakoski, E., Çinar, M., Ozturk, B., Grabowski, M., Golani, D., & Cardoso, A., (2014). Impacts of invasive alien marine species on ecosystem services and biodiversity: a pan-European review. AQUATIC INVASIONS 9. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2014.9.4.01>
- Katsanevakis, S., Zenetos, A., Corsini-Foka, M., & Tsiamis, K., (2020). Biological Invasions in the Aegean Sea: Temporal Trends, Pathways, and Impacts. https://doi.org/10.1007/698_2020_642

- Katsanevakis, S., Zenetos, A., Corsini-Foka, M., & Tsiamis, K., n.d. Biological Invasions in the Aegean Sea: Temporal Trends, Pathways, and Impacts, in: *The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 1–34. https://doi.org/10.1007/698_2020_642
- Kytinou, E., Issaris, Y., Sini, M., Salomidi, M., & Katsanevakis, S., (2023). ECOfast – An integrative ecological evaluation index for an ecosystem-based assessment of shallow rocky reefs. *Journal of Environmental Management* 344, 118323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.118323>
- Liquete, C., Piroddi, C., Drakou, E.G., Gurney, L., Katsanevakis, S., Charef, A., & Egoh, B., (2013). Current Status and Future Prospects for the Assessment of Marine and Coastal Ecosystem Services: A Systematic Review. *PLOS ONE* 8, e67737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0067737>
- Marchessaux, G., Harmelin-Vivien, M., Ourgaud, M., Bănar, D., Guilloux, L., Belloni, B., Lebreton, B., Guillou, G., & Thibault, D., (2021). First overview on trophic relationships of the invasive ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* in a Mediterranean coastal lagoon (Berre Lagoon, France): benthic–pelagic coupling evidenced by carbon and nitrogen stable isotope composition. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 41, 101570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2020.101570>
- Martinez-Cillero, R., Willcock, S., Perez-Diaz, A., Joslin, E., Vergeer, P., & Peh, K.S.-H., (2019). A practical tool for assessing ecosystem services enhancement and degradation associated with invasive alien species. *Ecology and Evolution* 9, 3918–3936. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.5020>
- Mason, N.W.H., Palmer, D.J., Vetrova, V., Brabyn, L., Paul, T., Willemsse, P., & Peltzer, D.A., (2017). Accentuating the positive while eliminating the negative of alien tree invasions: a multiple ecosystem services approach to prioritising control efforts. *Biol Invasions* 19, 1181–1195. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1307-y>
- Mazarrasa, I., Samper-Villarreal, J., Serrano, O., Lavery, P.S., Lovelock, C.E., Marbà, N., Duarte, C.M., & Cortés, J., (2018). Habitat characteristics provide insights of carbon storage in seagrass meadows. *Marine Pollution Bulletin, Securing a future for seagrass* 134, 106–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.01.059>
- Mehanna, F., S., G. Desouky, M., E. & Farouk, A., (2019). Population dynamics and fisheries characteristics of the Blue Crab *Callinectes sapidus* (Rathbun, 1896) as an invasive species in Bardawil Lagoon, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Biology and Fisheries* 23, 599–611. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejabf.2019.34459>
- Nentwig, W., Bacher, S., Pyšek, P., Vilà, M., & Kumschick, S., (2016). The generic impact scoring system (GISS): a standardized tool to quantify the impacts of alien species. *Environ Monit Assess* 188, 315. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-016-5321-4>
- Ojaveer, H., Galil, B.S., Campbell, M.L., Carlton, J.T., Canning-Clode, J., Cook, E.J., Davidson, A.D., Hewitt, C.L., Jelmert, A., Marchini, A., McKenzie, C.H., Minchin, D., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Olenin, S., & Ruiz, G., (2015). Classification of Non-Indigenous Species Based on Their Impacts: Considerations for Application in Marine Management. *PLOS Biology* 13, e1002130. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002130>
- Otero, M., Cebrian, E., Francour, P., Galil, B., & Savini, D., (2013). Monitoring marine invasive species in Mediterranean marine protected areas (MPAs): a strategy and practical guide for managers. IUCN, Malaga 136.
- Özbilgin, H., Eryaşar, A.R., Gökçe, G., Özbilgin, Y.D., Bozaoğlu, A.S., Kalecik, E., & Herrmann, B., (2015). Size selectivity of hand and machine woven codends and short term commercial loss in the Northeastern Mediterranean. *Fisheries Research* 164, 73–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2014.10.022>

- Ragkousis, M., Papazekou, M., Sini, M., Zenetos, A., Mazaris, A.D., & Katsanevakis, S., (2023). Modelling the distribution of impactful alien and cryptogenic species in the Aegean Sea. *Mediterr. Mar. Sci.*, submitted.
- Reynolds, C., Venter, N., Cowie, B.W., Marlin, D., Mayonde, S., Tocco, C., & Byrne, M.J., (2020). Mapping the socio-ecological impacts of invasive plants in South Africa: Are poorer households with high ecosystem service use most at risk? *Ecosystem Services* 42, 101075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101075>
- Robinson, N.M., Nelson, W.A., Costello, M.J., Sutherland, J.E., & Lundquist, C.J., (2017). A Systematic Review of Marine-Based Species Distribution Models (SDMs) with Recommendations for Best Practice. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 4.
- Rodrigues, J.G., Conides, A.J., Rivero Rodriguez, S., Raicevich, S., Pita, P., Kleisner, K.M., Pita, C., Lopes, P.F.M., Alonso Roldán, V., Ramos, S.S., Klaoudatos, D., Outeiro, L., Armstrong, C., Teneva, L., Stefanski, S., Böhnke-Henrichs, A., Kruse, M., Lillebo, A.I., Bennett, E.M., Belgrano, A., Murillas, A., Sousa Pinto, I., Burkhard, B., & Villasante, S., (2017). Marine and Coastal Cultural Ecosystem Services: knowledge gaps and research priorities. *One Ecosystem* 2 (2017) e12290. <https://doi.org/10.15488/4277>
- Sinopoli, M., Allegra, A., Andaloro, F., Consoli, P., Esposito, V., Falautano, M., Mangano, M.C., Nicastro, A., Scotti, G., & Castriota, L., (2020). Assessing the effect of the alien seaweed *Caulerpa cylindracea* on infralittoral rocky benthic invertebrate community: Evidence from a Mediterranean Marine Protected Area. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 38, 101372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2020.101372>
- Stamatiadou, V., Mazaris, A., Mallios, Z., & Katsanevakis, S., (2023). Valuation and mapping of the recreational diving ecosystem service of the Aegean Sea. *Ecosystem Services* 64, 101569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2023.101569>
- Stamatiadou, V., Mazaris, A.D., & Katsanevakis, S., (2025). Meta-analysis and mapping of the monetary value of Mediterranean seagrass ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services* 72, 101704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2025.101704>
- Triantaphyllou, M.V., Koukousioura, O., & Dimiza, M.D., (2009). The presence of the Indo-Pacific symbiont-bearing foraminifer *Amphistegina lobifera* in Greek coastal ecosystems (Aegean Sea, Eastern Mediterranean). *Mediterranean Marine Science* 10, 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.111>
- Tsirintanis, K., Azzurro, E., Crocetta, F., Dimiza, M., Frogli, C., Gerovasileiou, V., Langeneck, J., Mancinelli, G., Rosso, A., Stern, N., Triantaphyllou, M., Tsiamis, K., Turon, X., Verlaque, M., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S., (2022). Bioinvasion impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human health in the Mediterranean Sea. *AI* 17, 308–352. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2022.17.3.01>
- Valéry, L., Fritz, H., Lefeuvre, J.-C., & Simberloff, D., (2009). Invasive species can also be native. *Trends Ecol Evol* 24, 585; author reply 586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.07.003>
- Valéry, L., Fritz, H., Lefeuvre, J.-C., & Simberloff, D., (2008). In search of a real definition of the biological invasion phenomenon itself. *Biol Invasions* 10, 1345–1351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-007-9209-7>
- van Wilgen, B.W., Reyers, B., Le Maitre, D.C., Richardson, D.M., & Schonegevel, L., (2008). A biome-scale assessment of the impact of invasive alien plants on ecosystem services in South Africa.

Journal of Environmental Management, Economics of Invasive Species Management 89, 336–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2007.06.015>

- Vilà, M., & Hulme, P. E. (Eds.). (2017). *Impact of Biological Invasions on Ecosystem Services (Invading Nature – Spring Series in Invasion Ecology, Vol. 12)*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45121-3>
- Vimercati, G., Kumschick, S., Probert, A.F., Volery, L., & Bacher, S., (2020). The importance of assessing positive and beneficial impacts of alien species. *NeoBiota* 62, 525–545. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.62.52793>
- Walsh, J.R., Carpenter, S.R., & Vander Zanden, M.J., (2016). Invasive species triggers a massive loss of ecosystem services through a trophic cascade. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, 4081–4085. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1600366113>
- Zenetos, A., Albano, P.G., Garcia, E.L., Stern, N., Tsiamis, K., & Galanidi, M., (2022). Established non-indigenous species increased by 40% in 11 years in the Mediterranean Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 23. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.29106>
- Zenetos, A., Gofas, S., Morri, C., Rosso, A., Violanti, D., Garcia Raso, J., Cinar, M., Almogi-Labin, A., Ates, A.S., Azzurro, E., Balesteros, E., Bianchi, C., Bilecenoglu, M., Gambi, M., Giangrande, A., Gravili, C., Hyams-Kaphzan, O., Karachle, P. K., Katsanevakis, S., Lipej, L., Mastrototaro, F., Mineur, F., Pancucci-Papadopoulou, M., Ramos Espla, A., Salas, C., San Martin, G., Sfriso, A., Streftaris, N., & Verlaque, M., (2012). A contribution to the application of European Union’s marine strategy framework directive (MSFD). Part 2. Introduction trends and pathways. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 13, 328–352. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.327>

7.9 Case study 21: Implementation of CIMPAL for the impacts of jellyfish blooms, IAS and HABs in the Adriatic Sea

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7.9.1 Introduction

Human activities are driving significant changes in marine environments, leading to unprecedented disruptions in natural ecological processes (Tsirintanis *et al.*, 2023). Major contributors to the current ecosystem malfunctioning include the transport and expansion of non-indigenous species, global warming, overfishing, eutrophication, and the increasing spatial dominance of certain polyps (Boero, 2013).

Among these, biological invasions are considered one of the most severe human-induced disturbances. The rate of introduction and establishment of alien species has accelerated since the 19th century and is expected to intensify further in the 21st century, particularly in the Mediterranean Sea (Costello *et al.*, 2021; Zenetos *et al.*, 2022), where they have already caused significant adverse effects on native marine biodiversity (Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2016; Tsirintanis *et al.*, 2022). The ecological impacts of invasive species range from individual-level interactions and reduced fitness of native species to broader consequences such as population declines, local extinctions, and shifts in community composition (Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2014).

One of the most significant ways invasive species impact marine ecosystems is by disrupting their trophic structure and energy flow. The functioning of marine ecosystems is tightly linked to pulses of primary and secondary production, often driven by sudden increases in the population size of key species (Boero, 2013). A peak follows a typical spring bloom of phytoplankton and zooplankton, which sustains higher trophic levels, including herbivores, carnivores, and, ultimately, fish larvae and eggs. When the phytoplankton–zooplankton–fish pathway functions correctly, the ecosystem remains balanced. However, disruptions to this pathway can cause trophic mismatches (Boero, 2013). For instance, the proliferation of jellyfish exerts significant predation pressure on plankton communities, altering their structure and reducing the abundance of mesozooplankton, phytoplankton and fish (Morand & Dallot, 1985; Malej & Malej, 2004; Boero *et al.*, 2013). The blooms of the alien ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* in the Black Sea during the 1990s had a severe impact on fish populations over several years (Kideys, 1994; Shiganova, 1997). Similarly, in the early 1980s, massive swarms of *Pelagia noctiluca* were reported throughout the Mediterranean Basin, including the Adriatic Sea, leading to

significant fish stock declines (Malej & Malej, 2004; Sabatés *et al.*, 2010; Boero, 2013) and contributing to a regime shift towards jellyfish-dominated ecosystems (Mills, 1995; Mills, 2001).

Another concerning phenomenon is HABs, which are natural events that can affect the marine environment, aquaculture farms, bathing water activities, and public health. HABs can cause water discolourations, mucilage aggregates, bottom anoxia, and toxin production (Accoroni *et al.*, 2024a) and adverse effects on marine organisms, including molluscs, fish, seabirds, reptiles and marine mammals, which contribute to changes in marine ecosystems (Sagarminaga *et al.*, 2023). Among the approximately 4,000 known microalgae species worldwide, about 1–2% are noxious and make harmful blooms (Shumway *et al.*, 2018). Sagarminaga *et al.* (2023) report HABs classification in 3 categories based on their “harm mechanism”: “(i) low biomass toxin-producers, which can contaminate seafood, water, and generate aerosols even at low biomass levels, (ii) high-biomass toxin-producers, which can produce similar harmful effects when reaching high concentrations, (iii) high-biomass non-toxic species, that can cause either hypoxic/anoxic conditions or unpleasant/nuisance foam or gelatinous masses, among other effects”.

Climate change can also affect the frequency and severity of HABs in marine environments. Indeed, HAB species are more competitive than non-HAB species, and toxins production increases as the severity of high biomass increases due to changes in hydrology (Wells *et al.*, 2020). *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* is one of the species that can cause HABs present in the Mediterranean Sea and monitored in Italian marine-coastal waters. This microalga is a benthic dinoflagellate, potentially toxic, and is typically found in tropical and subtropical areas, with recurrent blooms also occurring in temperate zones. It develops on substrates such as rocky, macroalgae, and *Posidonia oceanica* leaves, and during blooms, it can produce a mucilaginous brown biofilm covering the seabed; in case of wave motion or mechanical actions, the biofilm breaks up, and cells transfer to the water column and to the surface as foam (ISPRA, 2024). This microalga can produce palytoxin (PLTX) and some of its analogues, and exclusively ovatoxins in the Mediterranean Sea. Ovatoxins exposure (inhalation with aerosolised or water-dissolved toxins or contact with the cells in water) can cause bio intoxication, flu-like symptoms to humans (Faimali *et al.*, 2012; Ciminiello *et al.*, 2014; Funari *et al.*, 2014), or suffering or mortality in marine benthic organisms as mussels, shellfish, sea-urchins and starfish (Carella *et al.*; 2015; Sardo *et al.*, 2020; Accoroni *et al.*, 2024a). Temperature (> 25 °C) is the main driving factor for the growth and abundance of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*; the abiotic and biotic environmental factors, including hydrodynamics, water depth, nutrient concentrations and substrate availability, influence proliferation and toxin production (Totti *et al.*, 2010; Mangialajo *et al.*, 2011; Accoroni *et al.*, 2012, 2024b; Gemin *et al.*, 2021; Zingone *et al.*, 2021). In recent years, its blooms have become more frequent, extensive, and severe due to climate change. *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* was recorded for the first

time in Italian waters in 1994 along the Tyrrhenian coast of Lazio (Tognetto *et al.*, 1995); since 2007, the monitoring is carried out by the Regional Agencies for the Protection of the Environment (ARPAs) during summer or summer–autumn, with high densities (up to 10^5 cells L^{-1} and/or cells g^{-1} of macroalgae). The central-northern and southern Adriatic Seas are HABs hotspots of the Italian coasts regarding both occurrence and impacts (Zingone *et al.*, 2021; ISPRA, 2024).

A comprehensive assessment and spatial analysis of the impacts caused by IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs is essential to support informed decision-making, prioritise preventive actions, and design effective mitigation strategies. This type of analysis, along with impact mapping, is increasingly demanded by policymakers and marine resource managers.

The MSFD (2008/56/EC) requires EU Member States to develop marine strategies and implement programs of measures to achieve GES in all marine waters. GES is described through 11 qualitative Descriptors, each of which has related criteria for assessing progress towards it. Among the descriptors, the Descriptor 2 (D2) requires Member States to consider alien species in their marine management strategies, in order that “non-indigenous species (NIS) introduced through human activities are at levels that do not adversely alter the ecosystems”. Differently, jellyfish and HABs are considered respectively under the Descriptor 1 “Marine biodiversity”, Criterion 6 (D1C6), and the Descriptor 5 “Eutrophication”, Criterion 3 (D5C3) of the MSFD. However, thresholds for these groups—especially in terms of GES—have not been defined, primarily due to data scarcity.

With this study, we aim to:

Update current knowledge on the diversity and distribution of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HAB species in the Adriatic Sea.

Assess the cumulative impact of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the Adriatic Sea using the CIMPAL index (Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2016).

Identify the most heavily impacted areas and habitats.

To support these objectives, we combined spatial analyses with standardised impact assessment methodologies to evaluate the presence and effects of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the Adriatic Sea. In this context, citizen science emerges as a valuable complementary tool, especially for the timely detection of rare, localised, or episodic events that might escape conventional monitoring efforts (Zampardi *et al.*, in press). The integration of such participatory approaches can significantly enhance early warning capabilities and contribute to the broader goal of adaptive, ecosystem-based management.

7.9.2 Methods

7.9.2.1 Study Area - LS7

The Adriatic Sea is a semi-enclosed basin located in the North-Central Mediterranean Sea. It is connected to the Eastern Mediterranean Sea through the Strait of Otranto. It separates the Italian from the Balkan Peninsula, bordering six countries: Italy (IT), Croatia (HR), Montenegro (MT), Bosnia & Herzegovina (BH), Albania (AL) and Slovenia (SL). The LS7 area includes northern, central and southern Italian Adriatic waters, an extremely complex system due to its geomorphological and ecological characteristics: lagoons, estuarine areas, coastal high biodiversity habitats (e.g. *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, coralligenous assemblages), and deep-sea habitats, with a high variability along its north-south gradient. Moreover, it is populated by benthic, demersal and pelagic fish species of high ecologic and commercial value. The Adriatic Sea is heavily exposed to anthropogenic pressures (Coll et al., 2012; Menegon et al., 2018), being also a hotspot for biological invasions, particularly in the northern sector (Occhipinti-Ambrogi et al., 2011; Marchini et al., 2015). The surface water exhibits a marked seasonal temperature cycle, with peak values in late summer and maximum mixed-layer depths in winter. The Northern Adriatic Sea presents the typical characteristics of a shallow sea, characterised by significant seasonal variations in temperature and salinity, as well as strong vertical stratification. The Central Adriatic serves as a transitional zone, featuring deep-water persistence during spring and summer and a persistent middle Adriatic gyre. The Southern Adriatic, especially below 150 m, presents open-sea characteristics, with traces of Modified Levantine Intermediate Water (MLIW) detectable in its subsurface layers and to a lesser extent in the central basin. Climatological analyses of freshwater and heat fluxes indicate that the Adriatic functions as a dilution basin, with negative surface heat fluxes compensated by heat inflows through the Strait of Otranto. The general baroclinic circulation is defined by a broad northward coastal current along the eastern coast, particularly intense in autumn, while strong southward flows occur along the western coast. During spring and summer, the three sub-basins are characterised by isolated cyclonic gyres that become more prominent in autumn (Artegiani et al., 1997). Several rivers flow into the Adriatic Sea, representing a source of nutrients and organic matter to the basin, as well as litter and microplastics. The most important ones in terms of water and sediment transport are situated in its north-western part (e.g., Po, Reno, Adige, and Brenta). The western coastal waters are considered the most productive in the Mediterranean Sea, and occasionally, local hypoxia and anoxia events have been

reported near the mouth of the Po River. Due to its wide, flat, and trawlable platform, coupled with high productivity, the Adriatic Sea is the Italian basin with the highest fishery pressure and historically one of the most exploited areas in the Mediterranean Sea. Other potential sources of ecological disturbance are coastal urbanisation (the coastal population is > 3.5 million people), commercial and recreational shipping, offshore platforms from the oil and gas industries, aquaculture, coastal tourism, and recreational activities (over 200 million overnight stays per year), including poor waste management practices (Table 7.9.1). The Adriatic is also rich in biodiversity, which has led to the establishment of 18 marine protected areas and 10 Ramsar-protected wetlands in the Adriatic countries. Since 2017, the Pomo Pit Fisheries Restricted Area (REC.GFCM/44/2021/2) protected vulnerable marine ecosystems and essential fish habitats for demersal stocks such as European hake and Norway lobster and small pelagic stocks (European anchovy and sardine). It consists of one no-take zone and two zones where fishing is restricted to licensed vessels.

Table 7.9.1. Pressures impacting the Adriatic Sea - LS7

Pressure in LS7
<p>Biological and Ecological Disturbances Jellyfish blooms Input or spread of non-indigenous species Harmful algal blooms (HABs) Input of microbial pathogens Loss of, or change to, natural biological communities due to cultivation of animal or plant species Disturbance of species (e.g., where they breed, rest, and feed) due to human presence Extraction of, or mortality/injury to, wild species (by commercial and recreational fishing and other activities), including bycatch</p>
<p>Physical Disturbances and Habitat Modification Physical disturbance (damage) to the seabed (temporary or reversible) Physical loss (due to permanent change of seabed substrate or morphology and to extraction of seabed substrate) Changes to hydrological conditions</p>
<p>Pollution and Contaminant Inputs Input of nutrients – diffuse sources, point sources, atmospheric deposition Input of organic matter – diffuse sources and point sources Input of other substances (e.g., synthetic substances, non-synthetic substances, radionuclides) – diffuse sources, point sources, atmospheric deposition, acute events Input of litter</p>
<p>Energy Inputs and Climate Pressures Input of anthropogenic sound (impulsive, continuous) Input of other forms of energy (including electromagnetic fields, light, and heat) Climate change</p>

7.9.2.2 Records of IAS, jellyfish observations and HABs

The IAS recorded in the Adriatic Sea that were considered for CIMPAL calculation are listed in [Table 7.9.3](#). The georeferenced data of these species were obtained from different datasets developed in research programs and literature data ([Table 7.9.2](#)). For the CIMPAL calculation, we decided to consider all available data for each selected IAS, starting from their first record in the Adriatic, as some of them, recorded in remote times, may still be present even though they have no longer been reported in the literature.

Table 7.9.2. Overview of data sources and corresponding monitoring years for the groups included in the assessment of CIMPAL in LS7. IAS: Invasive Alien Species; HABs: Harmful Algal Blooms; MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive

Group	Data Source	Range of records
IAS	Italian Alien Projects	1949-2011
IAS	MSFD (D1, D2, D6)	2016-2023
IAS	SoleMon	2005-2023
IAS	MEDITS	1994-2023
IAS	Literature	1949-2024
Jellyfish	CIESM - Jellywhatch	2009-2017
Jellyfish	Avvistap	2019-2023
Jellyfish	Meteo Meduse	2016-2023
Jellyfish	I-naturalist	2017-2024
Jellyfish	ARPA	2015-2024
Jellyfish	Literature	1983-2016
HABs	ISPRA/ARPA	2016-2023
HABs	MSFD (D1)	2016-2021

Table 7.9.3. List of the Invasive Alien Species (IAS) included in the application of CIMPAL in LS7

IAS
13 macrophytes: <i>Acrothamnion preissii</i> , <i>Asparagopsis</i> spp., <i>Bonnemaisonia hamifera</i> , <i>Caulerpa cylindracea</i> , <i>Codium fragile</i> , <i>Gracilaria vermiculophylla</i> , <i>Grateloupia turuturu</i> , <i>Lophocladia lallemandii</i> , <i>Polysiphonia morrowii</i> , <i>Rugulopteryx okamurae</i> , <i>Sargassum muticum</i> , <i>Undaria pinnatifida</i> , <i>Womersleyella setacea</i>
1 poriferan: <i>Paraleucilla magna</i>
1 ctenophora: <i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i>

4 arthropods: <i>Acartia tonsa</i> , <i>Callinectes sapidus</i> , <i>Dyspanopeus sayi</i> , <i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i>
2 polychaetes: <i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i> , <i>Hydroides elegans</i>
9 molluscs: <i>Anadara kagoshimensis</i> , <i>Anadara transversa</i> , <i>Arcuatula senhousia</i> , <i>Fulvia fragilis</i> , <i>Magallana gigas</i> , <i>Mya arenaria</i> , <i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i> , <i>Bursatella leachii</i> , <i>Rapana venosa</i>
2 bryozoans: <i>Amathia verticillata</i> , <i>Tricellaria inopinata</i>
3 ascidians: <i>Botrylloides violaceus</i> , <i>Microcosmus squamiger</i> , <i>Styela plicata</i>
4 fishes: <i>Enchelycore anatina</i> , <i>Fistularia commersonii</i> , <i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i> , <i>Pterois miles</i>

Most jellyfish records were obtained from the CIESM Jellywatch campaign and the Avvistapp campaign, available on the Emodnet platform (Boero et al., 2019; Tirelli and Grouppi, 2021). Additional records were collected from the Facebook page Meteo Meduse, launched in 2016. Further records were retrieved from the citizen science platform iNaturalist (inaturalist.org) (Table 7.9.2).

All the projects and campaigns listed above involved citizens in a jellyfish visual census initiative, and all the records collected followed the same CIESM jellywatch protocol (Boero et al., 2008; Edelist et al., 2025), including the date of observation, the name of the genus or species sighted, the location, the abundance as the number of individuals per square metre, and a picture. All the sightings were compiled in a database, and records of more than 10 individuals per square metre were considered blooms. We considered only the records verified by a picture. Finally, visual census jellyfish observations made by the Italian Regional Agencies for the Protection of the Environment (ARPA) were also included in the database (Table 7.9.2). The following jellyfish species with documented impact on pelagic habitat in the Adriatic Sea were included in the CIMPAL analysis: *Aequorea forskalea*, *Aurelia* spp, *Carybdea marsupialis*, *Chrysaora hysoscella*, *Cotylorhiza tuberculata*, *Olindias muelleri*, *Pelagia noctiluca*, *Rhizostoma pulmo*, *Velella velella* and two Thaliacea *Salpa maxima* and *Salpa* spp (Table 7.9.4).

The ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, classified as an IAS, was included in the IAS dataset and consequently excluded from the jellyfish blooms datasets.

Table 7.9.4. List of the included gelatinous jellies in the application of CIMPAL in LS7

Jellyfish
3 Hydrozoa : <i>Aequorea forskalea</i> , <i>Olindias muelleri</i> , <i>Velella velella</i>
6 Scyphozoa: <i>Aurelia</i> spp, <i>Carybdea marsupialis</i> , <i>Chrysaora hysoscella</i> , <i>Cotylorhiza tuberculata</i> , <i>Pelagia noctiluca</i> , <i>Rhizostoma pulmo</i>
2 Thaliacea: <i>Salpa maxima</i> , <i>Salpa</i> spp

Some HABs data used in this study related to the period 2016 - 2023 are from the National algal surveillance monitoring conducted annually in the summer by the Regional Environmental Protection Agencies (ARPAs) along the Italian coasts since 2007 published in the ISPRA Reports others have been obtained from MSFD monitoring program (Table 7.9.2). The species observed in the Adriatic Sea are the following: **9 Bacillariophyceae** (*Pseudo-nitzschia australis*, *P. delicatissima*, *P. fraudulenta*, *P. galaxiae*, *P. pseudodelicatissima*, *P. pungens*, *P. seriata*, *P. subfraudulenta*, *P. multistriata*), **1 Cyanophyceae** (*Planktothrix rubescens*), **1 Coccolithophyceae** (*Chrysochromulina lanceolata*), **2 Dictyochophyceae** (*Vicicitus globosus*, *Apedinella radians*), **2 Mediophyceae** (*Skeletonema tropicum*, *S. grevillei*), **39 Dinophyceae** (*Ostreopsis ovata*, *Alexandrium balechii*, *A. catenella*, *A. minutum*, *A. ostenfeldii*, *A. pseudogonyaulax*, *A. tamarense*, *A. tamiyavanichii*, *Amphidinium carterae*, *A. operculatum*, *Azadinium spinosum*, *Dinophysis acuminata*, *D. caudata*, *D. fortii*, *D. infundibulum*, *D. sacculus*, *D. tripos*, *D. acuta*, *Gonyaulax spinifera*, *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Gyrodinium pellucidum*, *Karenia brevis*, *K. brevisulcata*, *K. mikimotoi*, *K. papilionacea*, *K. selliformis*, *Lingulodinium polyedra*, *Margalefidinium polykrikoides*, *Peridinium quadridentatum*, *Phalacroma mitra*, *P. rotundatum*, *Polykrikos hartmannii*, *Prorocentrum cordatum*, *P. emarginatum*, *P. lima*, *P. mexicanum*, *P. rhathymum*, *P. reticulatum*), **4 Raphidophyceae** (*Chattonella marina*, *Chattonella antiqua*, *Fibrocapsa japonica*, *Heterosigma akashiwo*).

Despite the numerous species recorded, only *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* has been included in the CIMPAL index because it is the only species with a documented impact on biodiversity that can be linked to toxic bloom development detected during monitoring.

The *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* monitoring is conducted by collecting samples of water, macroalgae, or other substrates (if macroalgae are not present from shallow areas in rocky and/or artificial reefs with moderate hydrodynamics). The monitoring period spans from June to October, with a fortnightly or monthly frequency, possibly extending or shortening the duration based on bloom activity. The water sampling collects 250-500 ml in dark glass bottles at the same altitude where the hard substrate or macroalgae was sampled (about 20-30 cm away); the macroalgae thallus (about 5-10 g) is sampled in 3 replicas and closed in a plastic bag underwater to reduce cell loss. Alternatively, if macroalgae are absent, it is possible to sample other substrates, such as pebbles or benthic organisms (e.g., mussels). The Utermöhl method (1958) is used for the quali-quantitative analysis of samples. For this study, we considered all stations with abundances 10,000-30,000 cells l⁻¹ or cells g⁻¹ fw, 30,000-100,000 cells l⁻¹ or cells g⁻¹ fw or ≥ 100,000 cells l⁻¹ or cells g⁻¹ fw. These abundances, expressed in cell/l, under weather and sea conditions optimal for blooms and aerosol development (water temperature, hydrodynamics, wind), represent a potential exposure risk for human health and are adopted in the Guidelines for the

management of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* blooms in coastal marine environments and bathing waters (Funari *et al.*, 2014), which are incorporated into Italian law (DM 19/4/2018). By analogy with the above-mentioned guidelines the same reference values are adopted for cell g⁻¹, because negative impacts, such as damage to benthic marine organisms and the appearance of anomalous colouration, foams, and mucilaginous aggregates in seawater, are often observed at these concentrations.

7.9.2.3 CIMPAL Implementation

The CIMPAL index (Katsanevakis *et al.*, 2016) was applied to assess and map the effects of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the LS7 study area, which spans approximately 64,500 km² (Figure 7.9.1).

Figure 7.9.1. Map of the LS7 extent

The CIMPAL index was calculated for each 1 km x 1 km grid cell within the study area. For the IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs, this was accomplished by applying the following formula:

$$I_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m A_i H_j w_{ij}$$

I_c refers to the cumulative impact score in a specific cell of the study area; A_i represents the population state of species i in the cell, H_j is an index representing the extent of habitat j in the cell; w_{ij} is the impact weight of species i on habitat j , n is the total number of species, and m is the total number of

marine habitats considered in the analysis. All variables were standardised to a range of 0 to 1. Specifically, for IAS, A_i values were expressed as presence (1) or absence (0), while for HABs and jellyfish blooms, they were assigned according to the scoring system illustrated in Katsanevakis et al. (2016) (Fig. 7.9.2.3.2) which considers both bloom intensity and the total annual duration of the blooms.

Figure 7.9.2. Population state of species defined on the basis of bloom concentrations and the related total annual duration of the blooms both for jellyfish and Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs).

The $w_{i,j}$ values for IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs were derived from the scoring system provided by Tsirintanis et al. (2023), which estimates the impact weight as a combination of the magnitude of the effect of species i on habitat j and the strength of supporting evidence (Figure 7.9.2).

The H_j index was calculated as the percentage of the area covered by a specific habitat within a 1 km² grid cell.

Figure 7.9.3. Impact weights defined on the basis of the magnitude of impact and the related strength of evidence (Figures extracted by Katsanevakis et al., 2016)

The final CIMPAL index was calculated for each of the 64,500 grid cells in the study area by aggregating the cumulative impacts of IAS, jellyfish blooms and HABs. Species with no documented impacts were excluded from the cumulative impact calculation.

Furthermore, following Katsanevakis et al. (2016), four indicators were used to rank the species based on their negative impacts:

D1 (Species Occurrence Area): Total number of grid cells with at least one record of the species.

D2 (Impact Area): Number of grid cells where the species' impact score exceeded 0.

D3 (Cumulative Impact Scores): Summed impact scores across all cells.

D4 (Average Impact Score): Mean impact score across the species' range of occurrence, excluding cells with scores below 0.1.

7.9.2.4 Habitat components

The ecosystem components considered in this study included marine seabed habitats classified according to the EUNIS system (Vasquez et al., 2023), as obtained from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) Seabed Habitats Portal. These habitats were subsequently regrouped, according to the environmental features (e.g., fraction of surface light reaching the seabed, types of seabed) of the Adriatic Sea, into the broader categories proposed by Tsirintanis et al. (2023) (Table 7.9.5).

Each of the seven identified seabed habitats was then overlaid onto a reference grid with a spatial resolution of 1 km × 1 km to calculate the area covered by each specific habitat within each cell (Hj index).

The pelagic habitat, due to its spatially continuous nature, was assumed to cover the entire study area uniformly. Consequently, a Hj value of 1 (representing 100% coverage) was assigned to all grid cells. The pelagic habitat was included because jellyfish blooms affect the water column. These phenomena are particularly relevant as they can significantly influence the abundance of small pelagic fish by preying on their eggs and larvae, thereby affecting their recruitment and population dynamics (Purcell et al., 2007; Oguz et al., 2008; Boero, 2013; Palmieri et al., 2014; Purcell et al., 2015; Bosch-Belmar et al., 2020).

Table 7.9.5. Correspondence between EUSeaMap habitat codes and habitat types revised from Tsirintanis et al. (2023).

EUNIS habitat type	Habitats (from Tsirintanis et al., 2023 revised)
MB252 Biocenosis of <i>Posidonia oceanica</i>	Seagrass meadows
MB35 Mediterranean infralittoral coarse sediment	Shallow soft substrates
MB55 Mediterranean infralittoral sand	
MB65 Mediterranean infralittoral mud	
MB15 Mediterranean infralittoral rock	Shallow hard substrates
MB152 Biocoenosis of the Mediterranean euryhaline and or eurythermal lagoon on rock	Lagoons (Transitional shallow hard/soft substrates)
MB554 Assemblages of Mediterranean euryhaline and or eurythermal lagoon biocenosis on sand	
MB652 Assemblages of the euryhaline and or eurythermal lagoon biocenosis on mud	
MC151 Coralligenous biocenosis	Coralligenous formations
MC35 Mediterranean circalittoral coarse sediment	Deep soft substrates
MC45 Mediterranean circalittoral mixed sediment	

MC451 Biocenosis of Mediterranean muddy detritic bottoms	Soft substrates of the dysphotic zone
MC55 Mediterranean Circalittoral sand	
MC651 Biocenosis of Mediterranean circalittoral coastal terrigenous muds	
MD451 Biocenosis of Mediterranean open-sea detritic bottoms on shelf-edge	
MD651 Biocenosis of Mediterranean offshore circalittoral coastal terrigenous muds	
ME55 Mediterranean upper bathyal sand	
ME65 Mediterranean upper bathyal mud	
MF65 Mediterranean lower bathyal mud	

7.9.2.5. Preparation of layers for calculating the CIMPAL index scores

The dataset was created using the geoprocessing toolset and spatial analysis toolbox in ArcMap.pro 10.3. Species occurrence point layers were spatially joined to habitat polygon features to calculate CIMPAL values on a per-cell basis. The resulting dataset was then rasterised at a spatial resolution of 1 km × 1 km. Subsequently, individual raster layers were aggregated to produce both the total CIMPAL and thematic CIMPAL layers specifically related to Invasive Alien Species (IAS), jellyfish, and Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs).

7.9.3 Results

7.9.3.1 Cumulative Impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs

Cumulative impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs per grid cell ranged from 0 to 12.32 across the entire study area (Fig. 7.9.3.1.1). A total of 530 cells showed values greater than 0 (0.82% of the study area), with a minimum value of 0.19, a maximum of 12.32, and an average value of 2.01 ± 2.00. Coastal areas exhibited significantly higher cumulative impact scores than offshore waters, with impacts being spatially localised rather than widespread (Figure 7.9.4). Higher-impact coastal areas were more prevalent in the northern and central Adriatic compared to the southern region (Figure 7.9.4). Certain areas, particularly the Gulf of Trieste and the Venice Lagoon (Figure 7.9.4 A- B), experienced greater cumulative impacts than adjacent regions, primarily due to the occurrence of invasive species and jellyfish blooms (Figure 7.9.5; Fig. 7.9.3.3.1).

Among the considered habitats, the pelagic one was the most impacted followed by shallow soft substrates and lagoons. Pelagic habitat impact is mainly attributable to jellyfish (including the IAS *M. leidyi*) and to the IAS *M. gigas*, *R. okamurai* and *F. enigmaticus*. This result is due to the highest extension of this habitat as well as to the great quantity of jellyfish data from citizen science. The great contribution to the impact of shallow soft substrate is mainly due to IAS bivalves (i.e. *Anadara* spp., *A. senhousia*, *M. gigas*, *R. philippinarum*) and *C. sapidus*. IAS macroalgae (i.e., *A. preissii*, *G. vermiculophylla*, *S. muticum*) contribute to the impact in the lagoons.

Figure 7.9.4. Maps of cumulative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS), jellyfish blooms, and harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the Northern, Central and Southern Adriatic Sea using CIMPAL index scores. In the figure, the spatial variations and fine-scale details of the cumulative impact distribution in selected coastal areas of the Adriatic Sea (A: Gulf of Trieste, B: Venice Lagoon, and C: Ancona) are also reported.

7.9.3.2 Cumulative Impact scores for IAS

Twenty-one IAS were found to impact at least one of the habitats. These species are: *Acrothamnion preissii*, *Anadara kagoshimensis*, *Anadara transversa*, *Arcuatula senhousia*, *Asparagopsis* spp., *Callinectes sapidus*, *Caulerpa cylindracea*, *Ficopomatus enigmaticus*, *Fistularia commersonii*, *Gracilaria vermiculophylla*, *Hydroides elegans*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Magallana gigas*, *Mnemiopsis leidy*, *Pterois miles*, *Rapana venosa*, *Ruditapes philippinarum*, *Rugulopteryx okamurae*, *Sargassum muticum*, *Styela* spp., and *Womersleyella setacea*.

Species with no impacts were: *Acartia tonsa*, *Amathia verticillata*, *Bonnemaisonia hamifera*, *Botrylloides violaceus*, *Bursatella leachii*, *Codium fragile*, *Dyspanopeus sayi*, *Enchelycore anatina*, *Fulvia fragilis*, *Grateloupia turuturu*, *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Microcosmus squamiger*, *Mya arenaria*, *Paraleucilla magna*, *Polysiphonia morrowii*, *Portunus segnis*, *Rhithropanopeus harrisi*, *Siganus luridus*, *Tricellaria inopinata*, and *Undaria pinnatifida*.

Cumulative impact scores of IAS per cell ranged from 0 to 12 across the entire study area (Figure 7.9.5). Observed values ranged from 0.38 to 12, considering only cells with non-zero values, with a mean of 3.67 ± 1.67 .

Among the most widespread IAS, *A. transversa*, *A. kagoshimensis*, *M. leidy*, *C. sapidus*, and *R. venosa* exhibited the broadest distribution based on D1. When considering the number of impacted cells (D2), the following species ranked highest: *M. leidy*, *A. transversa*, *C. sapidus*, *M. gigas*, and *A. kagoshimensis*. The D3 cumulative impact scores identified *M. leidy*, *A. transversa*, and *M. gigas* as the most impactful species. Finally, D4, which accounts for the average impact score across the species' range of occurrence, ranked *R. philippinarum*, *M. gigas*, *A. transversa*, *M. leidy*, *A. senhousia*, *Styela* spp., *H. elegans*, *W. setacea*, *Asparagopsis* spp., *R. okamurae* as the most impactful IAS in the study area (Figure 7.9.6).

Figure 7.9.5. Maps of cumulative impacts of invasive alien species (IAS) in the Northern, Central and Southern Adriatic Sea using CIMPAL index scores.

Figure 7.9.6. Ranking of the Invasive Alien Species impacts in the Adriatic Sea (Italian side) according to the indicators D1 (Top Left), D2 (Top Right), D3 (Bottom Left), D4 (Bottom Right).

7.9.3.3 Cumulative Impact scores for jellyfish

Cumulative impact scores of jellyfish blooms per cell ranged from 0 to 4.25 across the entire study area. (Figure 7.9.7). Observed values ranged from 0.25 to 4.25, considering only cells with non-zero values, with a mean of 0.69 ± 0.58 . The northern Adriatic is the most affected area by jellyfish blooms, while the southern sector is the least impacted.

Figure 7.9.7. Maps of cumulative impacts of jellyfish blooms in the Northern, Central and Southern Adriatic Sea using CIMPAL index scores.

The total area of occurrence (D1) and the number of cells with an impact >0 (D2) coincide, as all jellyfish species were identified as impactful in the Adriatic Sea (Figure 7.9.8).

Based on D3, the species with the highest cumulative impact scores were *R. pulmo*, *C. marsupialis*, *Aurelia* spp., *C. tuberculata*, and *P. noctiluca*. Lastly, D4 ranked species by their average impact across their range of occurrence as follows: *P. noctiluca*, *R. pulmo*, *Aurelia* spp., *C. tuberculata* (these three tied), and *C. marsupialis*—even though the values were very similar (1.00 ± 0.01 ; see Figure 7.9.8).

Figure 7.9.8. Ranking of the jellyfish blooms impacts in the LS7 according to the indicators D1 - D2 (left), D3 (centre), and D4 (right).

7.9.3.4 Cumulative Impact scores for HABs

Cumulative impact scores of *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata* per cell ranged from 0 to 0.99 across the entire study area. A total of 12 cells showed values greater than 0, with a minimum of 0.21, a maximum of 0.99, and an average value of 0.54 ± 0.21 . The total area of occurrence (D1) includes 20 cells, while the number of cells with an impact score greater than 0 (D2) is 12. The cumulative impact score (D3) is 17, with an average impact (D4) of 1.42.

7.9.4 Discussion

The spatial distribution of cumulative impact scores for IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs reveals marked heterogeneity across the Adriatic Sea. Impacts were not uniformly distributed but relatively spatially localised, with coastal areas—particularly in the northern and central Adriatic—exhibiting significantly higher cumulative impact scores than offshore regions. This result is coherent with the high degree of anthropogenic activities and pressures in this area (e.g. high rate of maritime traffic) in addition to the presence of important river outlets that contribute to the eutrophication of the area (Degobbis et al., 1986; Degobbis et al., 1990; Ricci et al., 2022).

Hotspot areas such as the Venice Lagoon and the Gulf of Trieste showed especially elevated CIMPAL values. In these locations, the co-occurrence of IAS and recurrent jellyfish blooms underscores the compounded nature of ecological stressors in heavily exploited coastal systems.

A total of 530 grid cells exhibited cumulative impact values ranging from 0.19 to 12.32. Within this framework, IAS alone accounted for substantial ecological pressures, with impact scores reaching up to 12 and a mean of 3.67 ± 1.67 among affected cells. This indicates that, in some areas, IAS were the primary drivers of ecological impact.

Of the 42 IAS assessed, only half were associated with measurable impacts on native habitats. The remaining species, although present in the study area, were not linked to direct ecological effects based on current knowledge or available data, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and refined impact assessments.

Among the most impactful species, *M. leidyi*, *A. transversa*, and *M. gigas* stood out as particularly influential. *M. leidyi* not only exhibited a broad distribution (D1) but also ranked highly in terms of the number of impacted cells (D2) and cumulative impact scores (D3).

Likewise, *A. transversa* and *M. gigas* consistently ranked high across all four dimensions (D1–D4), underscoring their ability to establish wide ranges and exert substantial average pressures across their ranges. *A. transversa* inhabits both rocky hard and muddy substrates, as well as sandy-muddy substrates (Nerlović et al., 2012) and can tolerate polluted and degraded environments (Crocetta et al., 2009). It is considered an ecosystem engineer species, as it can generate habitat modifications through bioturbation and bioconstruction processes, affecting both benthic and pelagic habitats due to the increase in sediment erosion and resuspension rates when present in high densities (Smith et al., 2014). Similar considerations apply to the Pacific oyster *M. gigas* that found a favourable environment in the brackish water conditions of the north-Adriatic lagoon system. This species can establish populations in a wide variety of habitat types, such as hard substrates and sandy or muddy areas where it attaches to small stones, shell fragments, or other debris (Dolmer et al. 2014). As an ecosystem engineer, it can significantly alter coastal environments by producing reefs, affecting sedimentation rates, modifying native communities, and creating confined zones of intense biological activity (Jones et al., 1994; Dolmer et al., 2014). Oyster reefs built on soft substrates lead to the replacement of soft-bottom communities with hard-substrate communities (Troost, 2010). Moreover, the import of such species for culture has led to the involuntary introduction of associated non-native invertebrates and algae as hitchhikers on packaging, shell-fouling organisms, and parasites (Savini et al., 2010).

Notably, the D4 metric—which reflects the average impact per occupied cell—also identified species such as *R. philippinarum*, *A. senhousia*, *Styela* spp., and *W. setacea* as high-impact taxa. Although potentially less widespread, these species may exert particularly intense effects within the habitats they colonise.

At high densities, *R. philippinarum* can affect nutrient dynamics (Bartoli et al., 2001) and alter the abundance of zooplankton (Sorokin et al., 1999). Pranovi et al. (2006) estimated the total filtration capacity of the macrobenthos to have been doubled as a result of the introduction of the species, with a consequent altering of ecosystem function in terms of stronger benthic-pelagic coupling and reduced resilience. *R. philippinarum* clearly contributed to the decline of the native *R. decussatus* (Moura et al., 2017). *A. senhousia* established populations contribute to remove large quantities of suspended organic material from the water column by filtration and deposit large amounts of faeces, leading to alteration of nutritional quality of the sediment that is made unsuitable for colonisation by native species (Mistri et al., 2004); they may also change the sediment texture (GWA, 2005) as well as the community composition due to the formation of dense carpets of byssus (Creese et al., 1997). The non-native ascidians belonging to the genus *Styela* (e.g., *S. canopus*, *S. plicata*) compete with other organisms invading occupied space and inhibiting the recruitment or growth of other larval species (Sutherland, 1978; Rius et al., 2009). The rhodophyte *W. setacea* can significantly alter the physiognomy of the coralligenous habitat by monopolising the substratum and forming filamentous turfs that impede the colonisation and growth of native species (Ruitton et al., 2011). Extensive turfs negatively affect the development of erect algae as well as of *P. oceanica* (Piazzì & Cinelli, 2000; Battelli & Rindi, 2008).

Several species of gelatinous zooplankton are recognised as harmful when they form large aggregations due to their detrimental impacts on human activities, particularly fisheries and tourism (CIESM, 2001). The spatial distribution and intensity of jellyfish blooms, as indicated by the CIMPAL scores, reveal distinct patterns of impact across the Adriatic Sea. An average impact value of 0.69 ± 0.58 across cells with non-zero scores suggests that jellyfish blooms are not only widespread but also highly variable in intensity throughout the region.

According to the CIMPAL index, among the jellyfish species analysed, *R. pulmo*, *C. marsupialis*, *Aurelia* spp., *C. tuberculata*, and *P. noctiluca* exhibited the highest cumulative impacts (D3), underscoring their dominant role in contributing to the overall pressure exerted by jellyfish blooms. Notably, when comparing the average impact per cell across their respective ranges (D4), interspecific differences were minimal (average impact 1.00 ± 0.01). This suggests that, despite differences in spatial distribution, these species exert a comparable level of pressure wherever they occur. The fact that the total area of occurrence (D1) coincides with the number of impacted cells (D2) indicates that all

jellyfish species considered were ecologically impactful throughout their range in the Adriatic Sea (Fig. 7.9.3.3.2). This highlights the broad ecological relevance of jellyfish blooms, extending beyond isolated events or localised populations. The northern Adriatic Sea emerged as the most impacted area, confirming this subregion as a hotspot for jellyfish proliferation (Zampardi et al., in press). This basin is characterised by elevated plankton biomass (Benović et al., 1984; Umani et al., 1992), which contributes to its role as a critical nursery and foraging ground for small pelagic species such as sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*) and anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) that account approximately 41%, in the northern Adriatic, of total Adriatic catches (Coll et al., 2007; Morello & Arneri, 2016). Jellyfish actively prey on zooplankton and on eggs and fish larvae so the increasing frequency and persistence of bloom events in this region may lead to the progressive depletion of small pelagic fish stocks, posing a significant threat to local fisheries and resulting in substantial economic losses (Oguz et al., 2008; Purcell et al., 2007; Boero, 2013; Palmieri et al., 2014; Purcell et al., 2015; Bosch-Belmar et al., 2020). Moreover, small pelagic fish occupy an intermediate trophic level and represent classic "wasp-waist" populations. Due to their central role in the marine food web, the combined pressures of overfishing and predation by jellyfish can lead to significant declines in their abundance, shifts in species composition, and alterations in spatial distribution—potentially triggering profound changes in the overall state and functioning of the ecosystem (Cury et al., 2000).

Mnemiopsis leidyi—a jellyfish species that is considered an IAS—exhibits the highest impact score. This ctenophore was first recorded in the Black Sea in the early 1980s (Vinogradov et al., 1989) and subsequently spread to other marine regions, including the western Mediterranean Sea, where it was first observed in 2005 (Shiganova & Malej, 2009; Boero et al., 2009) in the Northern Adriatic, likely introduced via ballast waters. Following its first appearance in 2005, *M. leidyi* was not recorded in the Adriatic Sea for a decade until it re-emerged with numerous blooms in 2016 (Malej et al., 2017; Budisa et al., 2021; Zampardi et al., in press) spreading southwards along the Italian coast (Dragicevic et al., 2019). Similarly, *Pelagia noctiluca*—the most commonly observed stinging jellyfish along the western coast of Italy—also invaded the northern Adriatic Sea during the 1980s and 1990s. It subsequently disappeared for a period, only to reappear in recent years (Zampardi et al., in press), mainly in the Central Adriatic. Massive outbreaks of both species in the Adriatic Sea have been linked to climatic and environmental drivers (Goy et al., 1989; Malej et al., 2017). The resurgence and proliferation of gelatinous zooplankton in the northern Adriatic appear to be facilitated by a combination of SST anomalies, anthropogenic nutrient enrichment, and the overfishing of pelagic fish species (Purcell et al., 1999; Reyes Suarez et al.; 2022). Blooms of *M. leidyi* and *P. noctiluca* can have severe ecological consequences, including predation on eggs and larvae of small pelagic fish such as anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) and sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), ultimately contributing to the depletion of these fish

populations—as documented during major outbreaks in the 1980s (Boero, 2013; Bosch-Belmar et al., 2020). *Aurelia spp.* and *R. pulmo* are other species that significantly contribute to the impact in the northern Adriatic area; the former mainly between January and March, and the latter with blooms occurring in July and September (Zampardi et al., in press). *R. pulmo* was the most frequently sighted species in the Adriatic Sea, mainly from 2009 to 2015 (Boero et al., 2016). Following that year, massive swarms were also observed in other areas along the western coasts of Italy (Zampardi et al., in press). The presence in the northern Adriatic Sea of *Aurelia spp.* and *R. pulmo* is probably due to the presence of artificial structures in the area enhancing jellyfish production by the benthic stage (Vodopivec et al., 2017). Conversely, the Central Adriatic Sea is a more stable area characterised by a persistent gyre, the middle Adriatic gyre, which concentrates jellyfish and where blooms of *C. marsupialis* are present mainly from April to June and from July to September. In this area, also blooms of *A. forskalea*, a widespread species, and *C. hysoscella*, a western species (Zampardi et al., in press), are common. The southern Adriatic is the least impacted basin, characterised by a near-permanent gyre that affects the transport of *C. tuberculata*, a widespread species, and *S. maxima* and *Salpa spp.*, which are mainly distributed in the east (Zampardi et al., in press). The other species are mainly western or blooming rarely, and consequently, they have the lowest impact in the Adriatic Sea.

The cumulative impact assessment of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* blooms reveal a spatially limited but locally significant ecological pressure across the study area. Along the Adriatic coasts, *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* monitoring is carried out during the summer period under optimal temperature and hydrodynamic conditions. These monitoring sites were selected based on acquired experience regarding the previously observed presence of the macroalgae and/or their maximum growth. In two stations in the central and southern Adriatic have been identified as hotspots with intense and recurrent blooms. In all stations where blooms occurred, harmful effects on marine organisms, such as macroalgae, mussels, shellfish, sea-urchins and starfish, ranging from suffering to death depending on the severity of the bloom (high duration and abundance of microalgae and ovatoxins production), were observed. In the Northern Adriatic Sea, only in the Gulf of Trieste (Figure 7.9.3.1.1) *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* has always been present on those substrates suitable for its growth (rocks and pebbles), even with significant impacts on benthic organisms (macroalgae breakdown and suffering of mussels, limpets, crabs) (ISPRA, 2017, 2020, 2021, 2023, 2024). The total area of occurrence (D1 = 20 cells) exceeded the number of cells showing non-zero impact values (D2 = 12 cells), with CIMPAL scores ranging from 0.21 to 0.99. This variability could be attributed to differences in environmental conditions (i.e. temperature, hydrodynamics, and presence of favourable substrates for development and growth), bloom dynamics, or local ecosystem resilience. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for evaluating the actual threat posed by the species and underscores the importance of integrating occurrence data

with impact assessments. The total cumulative impact score ($D3 = 17$) and the average impact per affected cell ($D4 = 1.42$) emphasise that, although the overall distribution of the species is restricted, the intensity of the phenomenon in impacted areas warrants attention, underscoring the need for targeted monitoring in specific high-risk zones (hotspot).

7.9.5 Conclusion

This study provides a significant update on the current knowledge and spatial distribution of IAS, jellyfish blooms, and HABs in the Adriatic Sea. Moreover, the application of the CIMPAL Index enabled a focused analysis of the pressures induced by IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms, supporting the identification of areas in the Adriatic Sea that are at greater ecological risk where management and conservation actions can be focused.

The integration of citizen science campaigns has emerged as a key tool in the early detection and evaluation of rare or episodic events, such as jellyfish blooms, emphasising the need to integrate this kind of data with formal monitoring programs. Incorporating citizen science more systematically into monitoring frameworks could contribute to recording data on rare or occasional species with a high impact on ecosystems. This approach enhances both the spatial and temporal resolution of observations, facilitating a more responsive and inclusive management strategy.

Finally, despite these advances, several gaps remain. In particular, the lack of field studies on the ecological impacts of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms often leads to misinterpretation of “zero impact” as an absence of effect when, instead, it may reflect data deficiency. Strengthening field-based monitoring is, therefore, essential.

7.9.6 References

- Accoroni, S., Cangini, M., Angeletti, R., Losasso, C., Bacchiocchi, S., Costa, A., Di Taranto, A., Escalera, L., Fedrizzi, G., Garzia, A., Longo, F., Macaluso, A., Melchiorre, N., Milandri, A., Milandri, S., Montresor, M., Neri, F., Piersanti, A., ... Zingone, A. (2024a). Marine phycotoxin levels in shellfish—14 years of data gathered along the Italian coast. *Harmful Algae*, 131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2023.102560>
- Accoroni, S., Colombo, F., Pichierri, S., Romagnoli, T., Marini, M., Battocchi, C., Penna, A., & Totti, C. (2012). Ecology of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* blooms in the northwestern Adriatic Sea. *Cryptogamie, Algologie*, 33(2), 191–198. <https://doi.org/10.7872/crya.v33.iss2.2011.191>
- Accoroni, S., Neri, F., Ubaldi, M., Romagnoli, T., & Totti, C. (2024b). Trend of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* (Dinophyceae) along the Conero Riviera (northern Adriatic Sea) over two decades. *Phycologia*. [in press]

- Artegiani, A., Paschini, E., Russo, A., Bregant, D., Raicich, F., & Pinardi, N. (1997). The Adriatic Sea general circulation. Part II: Baroclinic circulation structure. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 27(8), 1515–1532. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1997\)027<1515:TASGCP>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1997)027<1515:TASGCP>2.0.CO;2)
- Bartoli, M., Nizzoli, D., Viaroli, P., Turolla, E., Castaldelli, G., Fano, E. A., & Rossi, R. (2001). Impact of *Tapes philippinarum* farming on nutrient dynamics and benthic respiration in the Sacca di Goro. *Hydrobiologia*, 455, 203–212. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1011910422400>
- Battelli, C., & Rindi, F. (2008). The extensive development of the turf-forming red alga *Womersleyella setacea* (Rhodophyta, Ceramiales) in the Bay of Boka Kotorska, Montenegro. *Plant Biosystems*, 142(1), 120–125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263500701872747>
- Benović, A., Fonda-Umani, S., Malej, A., & Specchi, M. (1984). Net-zooplankton biomass of the Adriatic Sea. *Marine Biology*, 79, 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00951829>
- Boero, F. (2013). Review of jellyfish blooms in the Mediterranean and Black Sea. *FAO*.
- Boero, F., Feral, J. P., Azzurro, E., Cardin, V., Riedel, B., Despalatović, M., Munda, I., Moschella, P., Zaouali, J., Fonda Umani, S., Theocharis, A., Wiltshire, K., & Briand, F. (2008). Climate warming and related changes in the Mediterranean marine biota. *CIESM Workshop 35*, Executive Summary
- Boero, F., Putti, M., Trainito, E., Prontera, E., & Piraino, S. (2009). First records of *Mnemiopsis leidyi* from the Ligurian, Tyrrhenian and Ionian Seas and first record of *Phyllorhiza punctata* from the western Mediterranean. *Aquat. Invasions*, 4(4), 675–680. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2009.4.4.13>
- Boero, F., Belmonte, G., Bracale, R., Fraschetti, S., Piraino, S., & Zampardi, S. (2013). A salp bloom (Tunicata, Thaliacea) along the Apulian coast and in the Otranto Channel between March–May. *F1000Research*, 2, 181. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.2-181.v1>
- Boero, F., Brotz, L., Gibbons, M. J., Piraino, S., & Zampardi, S. (2016). Impacts and effects of ocean warming on jellyfish. In *Explaining Ocean Warming: Causes, Scale, Effects and Consequences* (pp. 213–237).
- Boero, F., Piraino, S., & Zampardi, S. (2019). Jellyfish sightings along the Italian coastline from 2009 to 2017. *Marine Data Archive*. <https://doi.org/10.14284/345>
- Bosch-Belmar, M., Milisenda, G., Basso, L., Doyle, T. K., Leone, A., & Piraino, S. (2020). Jellyfish impacts on marine aquaculture and fisheries. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, 29(2), 242–259. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2020.1806201>
- Budiša, A., Paliaga, P., Juretić, T., Lučić, D., Supić, N., Pasarić, Z., Djakovac, T., Mladinić, M., Dadić, V., & Tičina, V. (2021). Distribution, diet and relationships of the invasive ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* with anchovies and zooplankton in the northeastern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 22(4), 827–842. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.23305>
- Carella, F., Sardo, A., Mangoni, O., Di Cioccio, D., Urciuolo, G., De Vico, G., & Zingone, A. (2015). Quantitative histopathology of the Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* L.) exposed to the harmful dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, 127, 130–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2015.03.001>
- CIESM. (2001). *Gelatinous zooplankton outbreaks: Theory and practice* (CIESM Workshop Series, Vol. 14, p. 112). Monaco: CIESM.

- Ciminiello, P., Dell'Aversano, C., dello Iacovo, E., Fattorusso, E., Forino, M., Tartaglione, L., Benedettini, G., Onorari, M., Serena, F., Battocchi, C., Casabianca, S., & Penna, A. (2014). First finding of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* toxins in marine aerosols. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 48(6), 3532–3540. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es405617d>
- Coll, M., Santojanni, A., Palomera, I., Tudela, S., & Arneri, E. (2007). An ecological model of the Northern and Central Adriatic Sea: Analysis of ecosystem structure and fishing impacts. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 67(1–2), 119–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2006.10.002>
- Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Albouy, C., Ben Rais Lasram, F., Cheung, W. W. L., Christensen, V., Karpouzi, V. S., Guilhaumon, F., Mouillot, D., Paleczny, M., Palomares, M. L., Steenbeek, J., Trujillo, P., Watson, R., & Pauly, D. (2012). The Mediterranean Sea under siege: Spatial overlap between marine biodiversity, cumulative threats and marine reserves. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 21(4), 465–480. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2011.00697>
- Costello, M. J., Dekeyser, S., Galil, B. S., Hutchings, P., Katsanevakis, S., Pagad, S., ... & Rius, M. (2021). Introducing the World Register of Introduced Marine Species (WRiMS). *Aquatic Invasions*, 16(1), 1–9. (Aggiunta della fonte suggerita per completezza APA; se diversa, dimmelo) <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2021.12.4.02>
- Creese, R., Hooker, S., De Luca, S., & Wharton, Y. (1997). Ecology and environmental impact of *Musculista senhousia* (Mollusca: Bivalvia: Mytilidae) in Tamaki Estuary, Auckland, New Zealand. *New Zealand Journal of Marine and Freshwater Research*, 31(2), 225–236.
- Crocetta, F., Renda, W., & Colamonaco, G. (2009). New distributional and ecological data of some marine alien molluscs along the southern Italian coasts. *JMBA2 - Biodiversity Records*, 2, e23. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755267208000274>
- Cury, P., Bakun, A., Crawford, R. J., Jarre, A., Quiñones, R. A., Shannon, L. J., & Verheye, H. M. (2000). Small pelagics in upwelling systems: Patterns of interaction and structural changes in “wasp-waist” ecosystems. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 57(3), 603–618. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmsc.2000.0712>
- Degobbi, D., Gilmartin, M., & Revelante, N. (1986). An annotated nitrogen budget calculation for the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Chemistry*, 20, 159–177. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4203\(86\)90037-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4203(86)90037-X)
- Degobbi, D., & Gilmartin, M. (1990). Nitrogen, phosphorus, and biogenic silicon budgets for the northern Adriatic Sea. *Oceanologica Acta*, 13, 31–45.
- Dolmer, P., Holm, M. W., Strand, Å., Lindegarth, S., Bodvin, T., Norling, P., & Mortensen, S. (2014). The invasive Pacific oyster, *Crassostrea gigas*, in Scandinavian coastal waters: A risk assessment on the impact in different habitats and climate conditions. *Institute of Marine Research, Fiskeri og Havet*, 2. http://www.imr.no/filarkiv/2014/03/fh_2-2014_til_web.pdf/nb-no
- Edelist, D., Canepa-Oneto, A., Azzopardi, J., Ballesteros, A., Bellido, J., Boero, F., ... & Angel, D. L. (2025). Citizen science-based jellyfish observation initiatives in the Mediterranean Sea. *Hydrobiologia*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-025-05393-w> (se disponibile)
- Ministero della Salute. (2018). *DM 19 aprile 2018: Modifica del decreto 30 marzo 2010, recante: «Definizione dei criteri per determinare il divieto di balneazione...»*. (GU Serie Generale n.196 del 24-08-2018).

- Dragicevic, B., Anadoli, O., Angel, D., Benabdi, M., Bitar, G., Castriota, L., ... & Zenetos, A. (2019). New Mediterranean biodiversity records (December 2019). *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 20(3), 636–656. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.20913>
- Faimali, M., Giussani, V., Piazza, V., Garaventa, F., Corrà, C., Asnaghi, V., Privitera, D., Gallus, L., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Mangialajo, L., & Chiantore, M. (2012). Toxic effects of harmful benthic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis ovata* on invertebrate and vertebrate marine organisms. *Marine Environmental Research*, 76, 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2011.09.010>
- Funari, E., Manganelli, M., & Testai, E. (2014). *Ostreopsis cf. ovata: Linee guida per la gestione delle fioriture negli ambienti marino-costieri in relazione a balneazione e altre attività ricreative*. Roma: Istituto Superiore di Sanità. *Rapporti ISTISAN 14/19*.
- Gémin, M.-P., Bertrand, S., Séchet, V., Amzil, Z., & Réveillon, D. (2021). Combined effects of temperature and light intensity on growth, metabolome and ovatoxin content of a Mediterranean *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* strain. *Harmful Algae*, 106, 102060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2021.102060>
- Goy, J., Morand, P., & Etienne, M. (1989). Long-term fluctuations of *Pelagia noctiluca* (Cnidaria, Scyphomedusa) in the western Mediterranean Sea: Prediction by climatic variables. *Deep Sea Research Part A. Oceanographic Research Papers*, 36(2), 269–279.
- Government of Western Australia (GWA). (2005). *Introduced marine aquatic invaders*. Department of Fisheries. <http://www.fish.wa.gov.au/hab/broc/marineinvader/marine06.html>
- iNaturalist. (n.d.). *iNaturalist.org*. <https://www.inaturalist.org>
- ISPRA. (2017). *Monitoraggio della microalga potenzialmente tossica Ostreopsis cf. ovata lungo le coste italiane – Anno 2016* (Rapporto n. 275/2017). <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it>
- ISPRA. (2020). *Monitoraggio della microalga potenzialmente tossica Ostreopsis cf. ovata lungo le coste italiane – Anno 2019* (Rapporto n. 336/2020). <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it>
- ISPRA. (2021). *Monitoraggio della microalga potenzialmente tossica Ostreopsis cf. ovata lungo le coste italiane – Anno 2020* (Rapporto n. 357/2021). <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it>
- ISPRA. (2023). *Monitoraggio della microalga potenzialmente tossica Ostreopsis cf. ovata lungo le coste italiane – Anno 2022* (Rapporto n. 396/2023). <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it>
- ISPRA. (2024). *Monitoraggio della microalga potenzialmente tossica Ostreopsis cf. ovata lungo le coste italiane – Anno 2023* (Rapporto n. 405/2024). <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it>
- Jones, C. G., Lawton, J. H., & Shachak, M. (1994). Organisms as ecosystem engineers. *Oikos*, 69(3), 373–386. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3545850>
- Katsanevakis, S., Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Steenbeek, J., Ben Rais Lasram, F., Zenetos, A., & Cardoso, A. C. (2014). Invading the Mediterranean Sea: Biodiversity patterns shaped by human activities. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 1, 32. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00032>
- Katsanevakis, S., Tempera, F., & Teixeira, H. (2016). Mapping the impact of alien species on marine ecosystems: The Mediterranean Sea case study. *Diversity and Distributions*, 22(6), 694–707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12429>

- Kideys, A. E. (1994). Recent dramatic changes in the Black Sea ecosystem: The reason for the sharp decrease in Turkish anchovy fisheries. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 5(2), 171–181. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0924-7963\(94\)90024-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0924-7963(94)90024-8)
- Malej, A., Turk, V., Lucić, D., & Benović, A. (2017). *Mnemiopsis leidyi* in the northern Adriatic: Here to stay? *Journal of Sea Research*, 124, 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2017.03.008>
- Malej, A. (2004). Invasion of the jellyfish *Pelagia noctiluca* in the northern Adriatic: A non-success story. In F. Briand (Ed.), *GELATINOS: Gelatinous zooplankton outbreaks: Theory and practice* (pp. 273–285). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-2152-6_16
- Mangialajo, L., Ganzin, N., Accoroni, S., Asnaghi, V., Blanfuné, A., Cabrini, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Chavanon, F., Chiantore, M., Cohu, S., Costa, E., Fornasaro, D., Grosseil, H., Marco-Miralles, F., Masó, M., Reñé, A., Rossi, A. M., Sala, M. M., Thibaut, T., ... Lemée, R. (2011). Trends in *Ostreopsis* proliferation along the Northern Mediterranean coasts. *Toxicon*, 57(3), 408–420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2010.11.019>
- Marchini, A., Ferrario, J., Sfriso, A., & Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A. (2015). Current status and trends of biological invasions in the Lagoon of Venice, a hotspot of marine NIS introductions in the Mediterranean Sea. *Biological Invasions*, 17, 2943–2962. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-015-0912-3>
- Menegon, S., Depellegrin, D., Farella, G., Sarretta, A., Venier, C., & Barbanti, A. (2018). Addressing cumulative effects, maritime conflicts and ecosystem services threats through MSP-oriented geospatial webtools. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 163, 417–436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2018.07.009>
- Mills, C. E. (1995). Medusae, siphonophores, and ctenophores as planktivorous predators in changing global ecosystems. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 52(3–4), 575–581. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1054-3139\(95\)80074-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/1054-3139(95)80074-7)
- Mills, C. E. (2001). Jellyfish blooms: Are populations increasing globally in response to changing ocean conditions? *Hydrobiologia*, 451(1), 55–68. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1011888006302>
- Mistri, M., Rossi, R., & Fano, E. A. (2004). The spread of an alien bivalve (*Musculista senhousia*) in the Sacca di Goro Lagoon (Adriatic Sea, Italy). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 70(3), 257–261. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mollus/70.3.257>
- Morand, P., & Dallot, S. (1985). Variations annuelles et pluriannuelles de quelques espèces du macroplankton côtier de la Mer Ligure (1898–1914). *Rapports de la Commission Internationale pour l'Exploration Scientifique de la Mer Méditerranée*, 29, 295–297.
- Morello, E. B., & Arneri, E. (2016). Anchovy and sardine in the Adriatic Sea—An ecological review. In R. N. Hughes, D. J. Hughes, I. P. Smith, & A. C. Dale (Eds.), *Oceanography and Marine Biology: An Annual Review* (Vol. 54, pp. 221–268). CRC Press.
- Moura, P., Garaulet, L. L., Vasconcelos, P., Chainho, P., Costa, J. L., & Gaspar, M. B. (2017). Age and growth of a highly successful invasive species: The Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Adams & Reeve, 1850) in the Tagus Estuary (Portugal). *Aquatic Invasions*, 12(2), 133–146. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2017.12.2.02>
- Nerlović, V., Doğan, A., & Perić, L. (2012). First record of *Anadara transversa* (Mollusca: Bivalvia: Arcidae) in Croatian waters (Adriatic Sea). *Acta Adriatica*, 53, 139–144.

- Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Marchini, A., Cantone, G., Castelli, A., Chimenz, C., Cormaci, M., ... & Piraino, S. (2011). Alien species along the Italian coasts: An overview. *Biological Invasions*, *13*, 215–237. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-010-9803-y>
- Oguz, T., Salihoglu, B., & Fach, B. (2008). A coupled plankton–anchovy population dynamics model assessing nonlinear controls of anchovy and gelatinous biomass in the Black Sea. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, *369*, 229–256. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07671>
- Palmieri, M. G., Barausse, A., Luisetti, T., & Turner, K. (2014). Jellyfish blooms in the Northern Adriatic Sea: Fishermen’s perceptions and economic impacts on fisheries. *Fisheries Research*, *155*, 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2014.02.029>
- Piazzì, L., & Cinelli, F. (2000). Effets de l’expansion des Rhodophyceae introduites *Acrothamnion preissii* et *Womersleyella setacea* sur les communautés algales des rhizomes de *Posidonia oceanica* de Méditerranée occidentale. *Cryptogamie, Algologie*, *21*(3), 291–300. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0181-1568\(00\)00116-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0181-1568(00)00116-1)
- Pranovi, F., Franceschini, G., Casale, M., Zucchetto, M., Torricelli, P., & Giovanardi, O. (2006). An ecological imbalance induced by a non-native species: The Manila clam in the Venice Lagoon. *Biological Invasions*, *8*(4), 595–609. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-005-2161-2>
- Purcell, J. E., Malej, A., & Benović, A. (1999). Potential links of jellyfish to eutrophication and fisheries. In T. C. Malone, A. Malej, L. W. Harding Jr., N. Smolaka, & R. E. Turner (Eds.), *Ecosystems at the Land-Sea Margin: Drainage Basin to Coastal Sea* (pp. 241–263). American Geophysical Union. <https://doi.org/10.1029/CE055p0241>
- Purcell, J. E., Uye, S.-I., & Lo, W. T. (2007). Anthropogenic causes of jellyfish blooms and their direct consequences for humans: A review. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, *350*, 153–174. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07093>
- Purcell, J. E., Clarkin, E., & Doyle, T. K. (2015). Digestion and predation rates of zooplankton by the pleustonic hydrozoan *Velella velella* and widespread blooms in 2013 and 2014. *Journal of Plankton Research*, *37*(5), 1056–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbv076>
- Reyes Suárez, N. C., Tirelli, V., Ursella, L., Ličer, M., Celio, M., & Cardin, V. (2022). Multi-platform study of the extreme bloom of the barrel jellyfish *Rhizostoma pulmo* (Cnidaria: Scyphozoa) in the northernmost gulf of the Mediterranean Sea (Gulf of Trieste) in April 2021. *Ocean Science*, *18*, 1321–1337. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-18-1321-2022>
- Ricci, F., Capellacci, S., Campanelli, A., Grilli, F., Marini, M., & Penna, A. (2022). Long-term dynamics of annual and seasonal physical and biogeochemical properties: Role of minor river discharges in the north-western Adriatic coast. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, *272*, 107902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2022.107902>
- Rius, M., Turon, X., & Marshall, D. J. (2009). Non-lethal effects of an invasive species in the marine environment: The importance of early life-history stages. *Oecologia*, *159*(4), 873–882. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-008-1268-y>
- Ruitton, S., Thibaut, T., Cottalorda, J. M., Bonhomme, P., Ourgaud, M., & Verlaque, M. (2011). Évaluation de l’impact de *Caulerpa racemosa* et de *Womersleyella setacea* sur les communautés benthiques coralligènes du Parc national de Port-Cros: Les peuplements patrimoniaux de *Cystoseira* spp. et de *Corallinaceae*. *Suivi 2010*. Contrat GIS Posidonie & Parc national de Port-Cros, 1–68.

- Sabatés, A., Pagés, F., Atienza, D., Fuentes, V., Purcell, J. E., & Gili, J. M. (2010). Planktonic cnidarian distribution and feeding of *Pelagia noctiluca* in the NW Mediterranean Sea. *Hydrobiologia*, 645(1), 153–165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-010-0221-z>
- Sagarminaga, Y., Garcés, E., Francé, J., Stern, R., Revilla, M., Magaletti, E., Bresnan, E., Tsirtsis, G., Jakobsen, H. H., Sampedro, N., Reñé, A., Camp, J., Borjá, A., Rodríguez, J. G., Spada, E., Pagou, K., De Angelis, R., Lanzén, A., Ferrer, L., Borrello, P., Boicenco, L., Kobos, J., Mazaris, A., & Katsanevakis, S. (2023). New tools and recommendations for a better management of harmful algal blooms under the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive. *Frontiers in Ocean Sustainability*, 1, 1298800. <https://doi.org/10.3389/focsu.2023.1298800>
- Sardo, R., Rossi, V., Soprano, P., Ciminiello, E., Fattorusso, P., Cirino, A., & Zingone, A. (2020). The dual impact of *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* on *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Paracentrotus lividus*: Toxin accumulation and pathological aspects. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.24160>
- Savini, D., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Marchini, A., Tricarico, E., Gherardi, F., Olenin, S., & Gollasch, S. (2010). The top 27 animal alien species introduced into Europe for aquaculture and related activities. *J. Appl Ichthyology*, 26(S2), 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0426.2010.01503.x>
- Shiganova, T. A. (1997). *Mnemiopsis leidyi* abundance in the Black Sea and its impact on the pelagic community. In *Sensitivity to Change: Black Sea, Baltic Sea and North Sea* (pp. 117-129). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-5758-2_10
- Shiganova, T., & Malej, A. (2009). Native and non-native ctenophores in the Gulf of Trieste, Northern Adriatic Sea. *Journal of Plankton Research*, 31(1), 61-71. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbn102>
- Shumway, S. E., Burkholder, J.M., and Morton, S. L. (2018). *Harmful Algal Blooms: A Compendium Desk Reference*. New York: JohnWiley and Sons, Ltd.
- Smith, C., Papadopoulou, N., Sevastou, K., Franco, A., Teixeira, H., Piroddi, C., Katsanevakis, S., Fürhaupter, K., Beauchard, O., Cochrane, S., Ramsvatn, S., Féral, J.-P., Chenuil, A., David, R., Kiriakopoulou, N., Zaiko, A., Moncheva, S., Stefanova, K., Churilova, T., & Kryvenko, O. (2014). *Report on identification of keystone species and processes across regional seas* (Deliverable 6.1). DEVOTES Project, 105 pp + 1 Annex. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.3227.7763>
- Sorokin, I. I., Giovanardi, O., Pranovi, F., & Sorokin, P. I. (1999). Need for restricting bivalve culture in the southern basin of the Lagoon of Venice. *Hydrobiologia*, 400, 141–148.
- Sutherland, P. (1978). Functional roles of *Schizoporella* and *Styela* in the fouling community at Beaufort, North Carolina. *Ecology*, 59(2), 257–264.
- Tirelli V., Goruppi A. (2021). Gelatinous zooplankton validated sightings reported in the Mediterranean Sea from 2019 onwards by avvistAPP users. National Institute of Oceanography and Experimental Geophysics - OGS, Division of Oceanography. Italy. Dataset/Occurrence <https://doi.org/10.13120/3382-at05>
- Tognetto, L., Bellato, S., Moro, I., & Andreoli, C. (1995). Occurrence of *Ostreopsis ovata* (Dinophyceae) in the Tyrrhenian Sea during summer 1994. *Botanica Marina*, 38, 291–295.
- Totti, C., Accoroni, S., Cerino, F., Cucchiari, E., & Romagnoli, T. (2010). *Ostreopsis ovata* bloom along the Conero Riviera (northern Adriatic Sea): Relationships with environmental conditions and substrata. *Harmful Algae*, 9, 233–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2009.10.006>

- Troost K (2010). Causes and effects of a highly successful marine invasion: Case-study of the introduced *Crassostrea gigas* in continental NW European estuaries. *Journal of Sea Research*, 64, 145–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2010.02.004>
- Tsirintanis, K., Azzurro, E., Crocetta, F., Dimiza, M., Froggia, C., Gerovasileiou, V., Langeneck J, Mancinelli, G., Rosso, A., Stern, N., Triantaphyllou, M., Tsiamis, K., Turon, X., Verlaque, M., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S. (2022). Bioinvasion impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human health in the Mediterranean Sea. *Aquatic invasions*, 17(3), 308-352. <https://doi.org/10.3399/ai2022.17.3.01>
- Tsirintanis, K., Sini, M., Ragkousis, M., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S. (2023). Cumulative negative impacts of invasive alien species on marine ecosystems of the Aegean Sea. *Biology*, 12(7), 933. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12070933>
- Umani, S. F., Franco, P., Ghirardelli, E., & Malej, A. (1992). Outline of oceanography and the plankton. In *Marine Eutrophication and Population Dynamics: 25th European Marine Biology Symposium, Institute of Zoology, University of Ferrara* (p. 347). Olsen & Olsen.
- Vasquez, M., Ségeat, B., Cordingley, A., Tilby, E., Wikström, S., Ehrnsten, E., Al Hamdani, Z., Agnesi, S., Andersen, M. S., Annunziatellis, A., Askew, N., Bekkby, T., Bentes, L., Daniels, E., Doncheva, V., Drakopoulou, V., Ernsten, V. B., Gonçalves, J., Karvinen, V., Laamanen-Nicolas, L., Lillis, H., Loukaidi, V., Manca, E., McGrath, F., Mo, G., Monteiro, P., Muresan, M., Nygard, H., O'Keefe, E., Pelembe, T., Radicioli, M., Sakellariou, D., Teaca, A., Todorova, V., Tunesi, L., & Woods, H. (2023). *EUSeaMap 2023: A European broad-scale seabed habitat map* (Technical Report No. D1.15). EMODnet. <https://doi.org/10.13155/97116>
- Vinogradov, M. E. (1989). Ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* (A. Agassiz) (Ctenophora: Lobata)-a newly introduced species in the Black Sea. *Okeanologiya*, 29(2), 293-299.
- Vodopivec, M., Peliz, Á. J., & Malej, A. (2017). Offshore marine constructions as propagators of moon jellyfish dispersal. *Env Res Letters*, 12(8), 084003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa75d9>
- Wells, M. L., Karlson, B., Wulff, A., Kudela, R., Trick, C., Asnaghi, V., Berdalet, E., Cochlan, W., Davidson, K., De Rijcke, M., Dutkiewicz, S., Hallegraeff, G., Flynn, K. J., Legrand, C., Paerl, H., Silke, J., Suikkanen, S., Thompson, P., & Trainer, V. L. (2020). Future HAB science: Directions and challenges in a changing climate. *Harmful Algae*, 91, 101632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.101632>
- Zampardi, S., Licandro, P., Milisenda, G., Scannella, D., Piraino, S., Boero, F. (in press). Citizen Science substantiates jellyfish occurrence in The Mediterranean Sea. *Scientific Report*.
- Zenetos, A., Albano, P. G., Garcia, E. L., Stern, N., Tsiamis, K., & Galanidi, M. (2022). Established non-indigenous species increased by 40% in 11 years in the Mediterranean Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 23(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.29106>
- Zingone, A., Escalera, L., Aligizaki, K., Fernández-Tejedor, M., Ismael, A., Montresor, M., Mozetič, P., Taş, S., & Totti, C. (2021). Toxic marine microalgae and noxious blooms in the Mediterranean Sea: A contribution to the Global HAB Status Report. *Harmful Algae*, 102, 101843. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2020.101843>

8. Biologging for top predators monitoring

8.1 Introduction

Advances in tagging techniques using remote tracking devices (biologging) (Ropert-Coudert & Wilson 2005) and the availability of high-resolution fisheries data have enhanced our ability to understand interactions between top predators as seabirds and fisheries, as well as to assess the risk of mortality due to incidental catches. However, it remains unclear whether movement patterns and behaviour differ between birds that feed naturally or scavenge behind vessels and whether these differences could indicate fishing interactions (Carle et al. 2019; Bentley et al. 2021; Carneiro et al. 2022). In this context, the use of remote tracking devices such as Global Positioning System (GPS) devices has been crucial for studying different threatened species in relation to mortality from interaction or incidental capture in various fisheries (e.g., Votier et al. 2010; Soriano-Redondo et al. 2016; Carle et al. 2019; Glemarec et al. 2020; Bentley et al. 2021; Oliveira et al. 2022; Melvin et al. 2023).

8.2 Case study 22: Analysing bycatch risk of the European shag (*Gulosus aristotelis*) in small-scale Basque fisheries through integration of species tracking and AIS data

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8.2.1 Introduction

Seabird mortality caused by artisanal fishing is difficult to assess but is considered significant (Suazo et al. 2013; García-Barón et al. 2022) and could be comparable to that caused by industrial fishing. However, the evaluation and mitigation of incidental captures have mainly focused on industrial fisheries, overlooking the impact of artisanal fisheries. This may be due to the scale of industrial operations, which lead to a higher level of incidental catches, the relative wealth of data in these fisheries, and the general perception that artisanal fisheries are inherently more sustainable than industrial fisheries (Molina & Cooke 2012; Temple et al. 2018). However, artisanal fisheries, which make up the vast majority of the world's fleets (Pauly, 2006), tend to operate in regions of high productivity and overlap with areas of high marine megafauna usage, such as seabirds.

In this regard, devices that record individual positions in space, such as GPS devices, provide crucial information on the ecology and behavior of birds in their natural environment. These devices allow researchers to determine habitat use and overlap with fishery activity areas. Additionally, some of these devices may be equipped with other sensors or data loggers, such as accelerometers, which

gather information on individual movement to distinguish between flying, landing, or diving. Time-Depth Recorders (TDRs) can collect data on the depth at which an individual is located, thus helping characterize dives. Other sensors focus on collecting environmental characteristics such as temperature, salinity, or depth where the individual is found.

In this way, these devices can provide data on an individual's behaviour at different spatial and temporal scales. Thus, the use of GPS devices helps to solve an inherent problem in the study of individual marine predators and their interaction with fisheries: the impossibility of studying feeding behaviour in the sea in detail while simultaneously recording this and the activity of fishing vessels (the latter through location data from the vessels themselves, e.g., AIS—Automatic Identification System or VMS—Vessel Monitoring Systems). These combined data, along with access to environmental data, form a robust set of techniques for studying seabirds' individual feeding behaviours in relation to fishing in detail (Votier et al., 2010), which constitute the basis for studying the issue of incidental capture.

The European shag (*Gulosus aristotelis*) has been selected as the subject species for this case study due to its incidental capture problem in fisheries. This species faces a significant risk of mortality due to interactions with fishing gear, leading to growing concerns about its conservation. Recent censuses have confirmed that the decline in its populations is widespread throughout its distribution in the Spanish Atlantic, including the North Atlantic Demarcation following the zoning of the MSFD (Alvarez, 2015). In fact, the species is included in the Spanish Catalogue of Threatened Species (Real Decreto 139/2011) under the category of "vulnerable," and in the Red Book of Birds of Spain, the Atlantic subspecies is considered "endangered" (Madroño et al., 2004). Additionally, at a regional level, the Atlantic subspecies is classified as "vulnerable" in Cantabria, Galicia, and the Basque Country.

The decline in European shag populations in the North Atlantic Demarcation may be due to increased mortality caused by the nets of the small-scale gillnet fleet (Velando & Freire, 2002; Alvarez, 2015). Fixed gillnets, which are usually set near the coast, cause higher mortality in coastal species such as European shags, whereas more pelagic birds, such as shearwaters and other Procellariiforms, are less likely to get caught in them. Specific analyses of European shag mortality in the North Atlantic Demarcation are scarce and have mainly focused on the area of the Galician Rías Baixas, where the largest population of this species is concentrated (Velando & Munilla, 2008). These studies have highlighted the significant impact of the trammel net fishery on European shags, identifying two peaks in mortality: one affecting juveniles in the months following independence and another affecting adults during the breeding period, possibly due to the costs associated with raising offspring (Velando & Munilla, 2011, 2012).

Thus, the primary objective of monitoring using biologging techniques in colonies is to estimate the space use and dispersal of European shags along the Basque coast. This analysis is crucial for identifying fisheries with which there may be a significant risk of incidental capture. By better understanding these interaction patterns, specific areas can be determined in the future where mitigation measures will need to be implemented for identified fishing gear.

8.2.2 Methods

Study Area and Species

The European shag is a medium-large seabird species that can reach a length of 65–80 cm from beak to tail and a wingspan of up to 115 cm (Alvarez, 2015). It is a diurnal seabird that dives to visually search for food, with high energetic costs associated with its plumage (Wanless et al., 1999; Grémillet et al., 2005). It is a coastal species typically found along rocky, wave-exposed shores, although in the Iberian Peninsula, it also inhabits inland areas. Its nesting habits vary by location, including crevices beneath fallen rocks, open ground caves, and exposed cliff ledges, forming colonies ranging from one or two pairs to several thousand in some areas of northern Europe (Velando & Freire, 2003; Alvarez, 2015).

Deployment of species tracking devices

Fieldwork was conducted in 7 nests chosen based on their accessibility, from 5 colonies of the Basque Country, Spain during the 2022 and 2023 breeding seasons (Figure 8.2.1). Fourteen European shag chicks of approximately 40–45 days old were tagged. Each individual was tagged with a combination of solar GPS/GSM and TDR tag on the same device (OrniTrack-20D, 58×25×14 mm, 17–20 g from *Ornitela*) fitted on their back using a tubular Teflon ribbon harness. The harness and tracking device weighed less than 3% of the mean body mass of adult male and female birds (female adult mean body mass range: 1,395–1,950 g; male adult mean body mass range: 1,360–2,300 g; Nelson, 2005). As diving seabirds have been shown to experience high energetic costs with any increase in device mass (Vandenabeele et al., 2012), the size of the loggers was kept as low as possible. Handling was generally performed in <20 min, after which each bird was immediately returned to its nest. Devices were configured to record a location every 10 mins and one hour depending on battery charge whilst the TDR recorded water depth below (± 0.1 m) every 1 s. Data is transferred to the server via GPS/GPRS/GSM every 12 hours and can be accessed through a password-protected web panel.

Figure 8.2.1 European shag (*Gulosus aristotelis*) colonies located in the Basque Country (Spain) where individuals were tagged during the years 2022 and 2023.

Ethics statement: Capture and handling of birds were conducted with the approval of the Subdirectorato General of Terrestrial and Marine Biodiversity of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO) of the Government of Spain (Authorization No SGBTM/BDM/AUTSPP/26/2023) and by the Regional Government of Bizkaia (Authorization No OF 03342/2022).

Small-scale fishing activity data

The spatial distribution of the small-scale fishing vessels operating within our study area was estimated using AIS information (Basque Government). While AIS is a safety device used onboard vessels to avoid collisions, it also transmits data about a vessel's identity, type, location, speed and directions (Kroodsma et al., 2018). However, in the European Union these AIS devices are only mandatory for vessels longer than 15 m (Real Decreto 210/2004). Overall, a total of 61 and 483 fishing trips conducted by artisanal Basque longlines and netters (<15m), respectively, were used to delineate commercial fishing grounds for the artisanal Basque fleet during 2022-2023. These trips were classified into three métiers: gillnets (GNS_DEF_60-79_0_0), trammel nets (GTR_DEF_60-79_0_0) and longliners (LLS_DEF_0_0_0). A métier, is a homogeneous subdivision of fishing boats that target the same assemblage of species and use similar gear during the same season and within the same area (EC, 2009, ICES, 2003).

Utilization distribution estimates

Estimates of area utilization were generated both for species and small-scale fisheries. For the seabirds, foraging utilization distribution (UD) contours were derived from geolocated dive records of

individual birds and averaged to estimate a species-level kernel density distribution. For small-scale fisheries, UD contours were calculated from AIS data for each métier (i.e., longliners and netters). Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) is a non-parametric method used to generate smooth probability surfaces from spatial point data, based on a user-defined smoothing parameter. It allows identifying areas of concentrated use by estimating the intensity of activity across space. KDEs were generated using an ad hoc selection of the smoothing parameter and a fixed spatial grid (extent: 5°W–10°W / 40°N–50°N, grid cell = 0.005°). Resulting kernel density distributions were plotted using 90%, 75%, and 50% UD contours. All UDs were computed using the R-package *adehabitatHR* (Calenge and Fortmann-Roe, 2023), in R 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2023).

Seabird bycatch risk areas

KDEs of both seabird and fishing activity were spatially intersected to obtain areas of overlap: high-risk areas included the intersection of 50% UDs, medium-risk areas included the intersection of 75% UDs and low-risk areas included the intersection of 95% UDs.

8.2.3 Results

Seabird bycatch risk areas

KDE showed the general foraging areas (75-95% UD), which was in the inner Bay of Biscay, along the Cantabrian coast, Arcachon Bay and Bay of Bourgneuf. Whilst the core areas (50% UD) were mainly located in waters off the Bilbao estuary, coastal waters from the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve to Mutriku, from Donostia to southern areas of the French coast (Hendaye, Saint-Jean-de-Luz and Biarritz) (Figure 8.2.2).

Figure 8.2.2. Key foraging areas for juvenile European shags obtained from bivariate kernel densities of diving locations. Left: key foraging areas for the whole Bay of Biscay; Right: zoom of the inner Bay of Biscay where the artisanal Basque fleet operates along with associated bathymetry (GEBCO One Minute Grid).

Artisanal fishing grounds

High-used fishing grounds for longliners were located both in the western and further east Basque waters and coastal and offshore waters of the border between Spanish and French waters (Figure 8.2.3, top). However, in the case of netters, the most frequented fishing grounds were further west, mainly in the central and western waters of the Basque Country (Figure 8.2.3, bottom).

Figure 8.2.3 Artisanal fishing grounds of longlines (top) and netters (bottom) from the artisanal Basque fleet obtained from bivariate kernel densities of AIS data along with associated bathymetry (GEBCO One Minute Grid).

Seabird bycatch risk areas

Distribution and scale of potential bycatch risk differed among fishing gears. Whilst most of the high-risk areas were in coastal waters, low- and medium-risk areas extended into deeper waters (Figure 8.2.4). Bycatch risk areas do not imply interaction in all risk zones and merely represents an ecological association between fishers and shags. Interaction may further depend on fishing activities and practices during times and areas of co-occurrence, as well as other factors such as inexperience of juvenile shags making nets with catches increasingly attractive. Note that these bycatch risk areas may differ from those for adult individuals.

Figure 8.2.4. Bycatch risk areas identified by intersecting key foraging zones for GPS-tagged juvenile European shags with artisanal fishing grounds used by the Basque longline and netter fleets. The map indicates the colonies where individuals had been tagged.

8.2.4 Discussion

The concern for conservation posed by bycatch in fishing has led to the establishment of important management and mitigation measures to reduce species mortality and improve the survival of discarded specimens while maintaining the profitability of fisheries (García-Barón et al., 2022). However, understanding its extent and magnitude, as well as its spatial pattern, is a necessary first step to guiding conservation actions where needed (Lewison et al., 2014). Ecological risk assessments are increasingly used to evaluate the potential vulnerability of species directly or indirectly affected by fishing. In the Bay of Biscay, several studies have attempted ecological risk assessments; however, they have focused on the common dolphin (*Delphinus delphis*) (Mannocci et al., 2012; Peltier et al., 2016, 2021), and only one has evaluated the incidental capture risk of a seabird, the great shearwater (*Ardenna gravis*; García-Barón et al., 2022). Thus, this case study shows the results of the first European shag monitoring survey in the Basque coast, which allows the study of the biology and ethology of the species, their spatial distribution patterns and their main feeding grounds. Also, is important as it advances the knowledge of seabird bycatch risk in the Bay of Biscay, particularly in Basque waters, and evaluates for the first time the potential incidental capture risk by the entire Basque small-scale fishing fleet. The results obtained, as well as the future work derived from this project, have provided new insights to implement conservation strategies and inform the management of bycatch risk and mitigation measures.

Likewise, the Kernel analysis used in this case study is an appropriate approach for identifying important areas for seabirds (Tancell et al., 2013; Delord et al., 2014). This analysis allows the estimation of spatial utilization distribution contours that represent the importance of different areas used during the species' life cycle based on locations (Péron & Grémillet, 2013; Delord et al., 2014). The overlap between areas of high fishing activity and areas of high shag activity may be due to

competition for trophic resources—food in the case of shags (Alvarez, 2015) or target fishing species in the case of métiers—thus providing cormorants easier access to the food resources made available by fisheries. Lastly, we highlight the utility of integrating species tracking and AIS data to enhance our understanding of bycatch risk and inform targeted conservation strategies and promote sustainable fisheries management practices.

Effective mitigation measures to reduce seabird bycatch largely depend on the involvement of the commercial fishing industry and require strategies that are achievable and easy to implement. Moreover, changes in fishing practices and/or the use of deterrent devices must be based on solid scientific advice and should not place an undue burden on fishers (Torres et al., 2013). Since the data obtained from the small-scale fishing fleet in this project are voluntary, it is difficult to achieve a complete and accurate assessment of the incidental capture risk for the European shag. Interaction may further depend on fishing activities and practices during times and areas of co-occurrence, as well as other factors such as inexperience of juvenile shags making nets with catches increasingly attractive. Note that these bycatch risk areas may differ from those for adult individuals.

In this context, more research into the spatial and temporal dynamics of shags-fishery interactions is needed, with a potential redistribution of fishing effort to avoid incidental capture in different small-scale fishing métiers as longliners or netters, which could help explore solutions to the issue.

This case study contributes to Task 5.2 of the project by demonstrating the application of biologging as an advanced tool for monitoring marine predators—specifically, the European shag—to evaluate spatiotemporal overlap with human activities, such as artisanal fishing. By identifying areas with a heightened risk of accidental bycatch, the study supports the development of spatial management strategies aimed at mitigating these interactions.

8.2.5 References

- Alvarez, D., (2015). Análisis de la mortalidad de las poblaciones de cormorán moñudo (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis*) en artes de pesca en la Demarcación Marina Noratlántica. Aplicación 23.06.456D.640. Ministerio de Agricultura, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente (MAGRAMA). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4560.9049>
- Bentley, L.K., Kato, A., Ropert-Coudert, Y., Manica, A., & Phillips, R.A., (2021). Diving behaviour of albatrosses: implications for foraging ecology and bycatch susceptibility. *Mar. Biol.* 168, 1-10.
- Calenge, C., y Fortmann-Roe, S. (2023). adehabitatHR: Home Range Estimation. R package version 0.4.21. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=adehabitatHR>
- Carle, R.D., Felis, J.J., Vega, R., Beck, J., Adams, J., López, V., Hodum, P.J., González, A., Colodro, V., & Varela, T., (2019). Overlap of Pink-footed Shearwaters and central Chilean purse-seine fisheries: Implications for bycatch risk. *Gerontologist* 59. <https://doi.org/10.1093/condor/duz026>

- Carlsen, A. A., Lorentsen, S. H., Mattisson, J., & Wright, J. (2023). Temporal non-independence of foraging dive and surface duration sequences in the European shag (*Gulosus aristotelis*). *Ethology*, 129: 254-268.
- Carneiro, A.P.B., Dias, M.P., Opper, S., Pearmain, E.J., Clark, B.L., Wood, A.G., Clavelle, T., & Phillips, R.A., (2022). Integrating immersion with GPS data improves behavioural classification for wandering albatrosses and shows scavenging behind fishing vessels mirrors natural foraging. *Anim. Conserv.* 25, 627-637. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12768>
- Christensen-Dalsgaard, S., Mattisson, J., Bekkby, T., Gundersen, H., May, R., Rinde, E., & Lorentsen, S. H. (2017). Habitat selection of foraging chick-rearing European shags in contrasting marine environments. *Marine Biology*, 164: 1-12. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Cook, T. R., Hamann, M., Pichegru, L., Bonadonna, F., Grémillet, D., & Ryan, P. G. (2012). GPS and time-depth loggers reveal underwater foraging plasticity in a flying diver, the Cape Cormorant. *Marine Biology*, 159: 373-387. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00227-011-1815-3>
- Delord, K., Barbraud, C., Bost, C.-A., Deceuninck, B., Lefebvre, T., Lutz, R., Micol, T., Phillips, R. A., Trathan, P. N., & Weimerskirch, H. (2014). Areas of importance for seabirds tracked from French southern territories, and recommendations for conservation. *Marine Policy*, 48, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.03.002>
- EC 2009, EC Green Paper Reform of the Common Fishery Policy. COM (2009), p. 28.
- Foo, D., Semmens, J. M., Arnould, J. P. Y., Dorville, N., Hoskins, A. J., Abernathy, K., Marshall, G. J., & Hindell, M. A. (2016). Testing optimal foraging theory models on benthic divers. *Animal Behaviour*, 112, 127–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2015.11.028>
- García-Barón, I., Granado, I., Astarloa, A., Boyra, G., Rubio, A., Fernandes-salvador, J.A., Zarauz, L., Onandia, I., Mugerza, E., & Louzao, M., (2022). Ecological risk assessment of a pelagic seabird species in artisanal tuna fisheries. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsac136>
- Glemarec, G., Kindt-Larsen, L., Lundgaard, L.S., & Larsen, F., (2020). Assessing seabird bycatch in gillnet fisheries using electronic monitoring. *Biol. Conserv.* 243, 108461.
- Grémillet, D., Chauvin, C., Wilson, R.P., Le Maho, Y., & Wanless, S., (2005). Unusual feather structure allows partial plumage wettability in diving great cormorants *Phalacrocorax carbo*. *J. Avian Biol.* 36, 57-63. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0908-8857.2005.03331.x>
- ICES, (2003). Report of the Study Group for the Development of Fishery-based Forecast. ICES CM2003/ACFM, 08 Ref. D., p. 39.
- Kroodsma, D. A., Mayorga, J., Hochberg, T., Miller, N. A., Boerder, K., Ferretti, F., Wilson, A., et al. 2018. Tracking the global footprint of fisheries. *Science*, 359: 904-908.
- Madroño, A., González, C., & Atienza, J.C., (2004). Libro Rojo de las Aves de España. Dirección General para la Biodiversidad-SEO/BirdLife, Madrid, Spain.
- Mannocci, L., Dabin, W., Augeraud-Véron, E., Dupuy, J. F., Barbraud, C., & Ridoux, V. (2012). Assessing the impact of bycatch on dolphin populations: the case of the common dolphin in the Eastern North Atlantic. *Plos One*, 7: e32615.
- Melvin, E.F., Wolfaardt, A., Crawford, R., Gilman, E., & Suazo, C.G., (2023). Bycatch reduction, en: *Conservation of Marine Birds*. Academic Press, pp. 457-496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-323-88539-3.00018-2>
- Molina, J.M., & Cooke, S.J., (2012). Trends in shark bycatch research: Current status and research needs. *Rev. Fish Biol. Fish.* 22, 719-737. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-012-9269-3>

- Nelson, J. B. (2005). Pelicans, Cormorants, and their Relatives. The Pelecaniformes. Oxford University Press, New York. 680 pp.
- Lewison, R. L., Crowder, L. B., Wallace, B. P., Moore, J. E., Cox, T., Zydalis, R., McDonald, S., DiMatteo, A., Dunn, D. C., Kot, C. Y., Bjorkland, R., Kelez, S., Soykan, C., Stewart, K. R., Sims, M., Boustany, A., Read, A. J., Halpin, P., Nichols, W. J., & Safina, C. (2014). Global patterns of marine mammal, seabird, and sea turtle bycatch reveal taxa-specific and cumulative megafauna hotspots. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(14), 5271–5276. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1318960111>
- Oliveira, N., Ramos, J.A., Calado, J.G., & Arcos, J.M., (2022). Seabird and Fisheries Interactions, en: Seabird Biodiversity and Human Activities. CRC Press, pp. 77-89. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003047520-7>
- Pauly, D., (2006). Major Trends in Small-Scale Marine Fisheries, with Emphasis on Developing Countries, and Some Implication fro Social Sciences. *Marit. Stud.* 4, 7-22.
- Peltier, H., Authier, M., Deaville, R., Dabin, W., Jepson, P. D., van Canneyt, O., Daniel, P., & Ridoux, V. (2016). Small cetacean bycatch as estimated from stranding schemes: The common dolphin case in the northeast Atlantic. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 63, 7–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.05.004>
- Peltier, H., Authier, M., Caurant, F., Dabin, W., Daniel, P., Dars, C., Demaret, F., Meheust, E., Van Canneyt, O., Spitz, J., & Ridoux, V. (2021). In the wrong place at the wrong time: Identifying spatiotemporal co-occurrence of bycaught common dolphins and fisheries in the Bay of Biscay (NE Atlantic) from 2010 to 2019. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, Article 617342, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.617342>
- Péron, C., & Grémillet, D., (2013). Tracking through life stages: adult, immature and juvenile autumn migration in a long-lived seabird. *PLoS ONE* 8: e72713.
- R Core Team. (2023). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.r-project.org/>
- Real Decreto (2004) por el que se establece un sistema de seguimiento y de información sobre el tráfico marítimo. Boletín Oficial del Estado, núm. 39, de 14 de febrero de 2004, pp. 6193-6214. Disponible en: <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2004-2752>
- Real Decreto 139/2011, de 4 de febrero, para el Desarrollo del Listado de Especies Silvestres en Régimen de Protección Especial y del Catálogo Español de Especies Amenazadas. Boletín Oficial del Estado, núm. 46, de 23/02/2011: 20912-20951.
- Robert-Coudert, Y., & Wilson, R. P. (2005). Trends and perspectives in animal-attached remote sensing. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 3(8), 437-444.
- Soriano-Redondo, A., Cortés, V., Reyes-González, J.M., Guallar, S., Bécares, J., Rodríguez, B., Arcos, J.M., & González-Solís, J., (2016). Relative abundance and distribution of fisheries influence risk of seabird bycatch. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 37373. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep37373>
- Suazo, C.G., Schlatter, R.P., Arriagada, A.M., Cabezas, L.A., & Ojeda, J., (2013). Fishermen’s perceptions of interactions between seabirds and artisanal fisheries in the Chonos archipelago, Chilean Patagonia. *Oryx* 47, 184-189. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605311001815>
- Velando, A., & Freire, J., (2003). Nest site characteristics, occupation and breeding success in the European Shag. *Waterbirds* 26, 473-483.
- Velando, A., & Freire, J., (2002). Population modelling of European shags (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis*) at their southern limit: Conservation implications. *Biol. Conserv.* 107, 59-69. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(02\)00044-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(02)00044-7)

- Velando, A., & Munilla, I., (2012). Conservación del Cormorán moñudo en el Parque Nacional de las Islas Atlánticas de Galicia. Actas del Taller Int. sobre Ecol. del cormorán moñudo en el sur Eur. Boletín del Grup. Ibérico Aves Mar. 35, 9-18.
- Velando, A., & Munilla, I., (2011). Conservación del Cormorán moñudo en el Parque Nacional de las Islas Atlánticas. En: Valeiras, X., Velando, A., Bermejo A. y Paterson A.M. (Eds.) 2011. Actas del Taller Internacional sobre ecología del cormorán moñudo en el sur de Europa. Boletín GIAM 35, 9-18.
- Velando, A. & Munilla, I. (2008). Plan de conservación del cormorán moñudo en el Parque Nacional de las islas atlánticas de Galicia. Parque Nacional de las islas atlánticas de Galicia. Informe no publicado.
- Votier, S.C., Bearhop, S., Witt, M.J., Inger, R., Thompson, D., & Newton, J., (2010). Individual responses of seabirds to commercial fisheries revealed using GPS tracking, stable isotopes and vessel monitoring systems. J. Appl. Ecol. 47, 487-497. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2010.01790.x>
- Wanless, S., Finney, S.K., Harris, M.P., & McCafferty, D.J., (1999). Effect of the diel light cycle on the diving behaviour of two bottom feeding marine birds: The blue-eyed shag *Phalacrocorax atriceps* and the European shag *P. aristotelis*. Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser. 188, 219-224.
- Tancell, C., Phillips, R. A., Xavier, J. C., Tarling, G. A., & Sutherland, W. J. (2013). Comparison of methods for determining key marine areas from tracking data. Marine Biology, 160, 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-012-2050-2>
- Temple, A.J., Kiszka, J.J., Stead, S.M., Wambiji, N., Brito, A., Poonian, C.N.S., Amir, O.A., Jiddawi, N., Fennessy, S.T., Pérez-Jorge, S., & Berggren, P., (2018). Marine megafauna interactions with small-scale fisheries in the southwestern Indian Ocean: a review of status and challenges for research and management. Rev. Fish Biol. Fish. 28, 89-115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-017-9494-x>
- Torres, L.G., Sagar, P.M., Thompson, D.R. & Phillips, R.A. (2013) Scale-dependence of seabird-fishery data analysis and management: Reply to Croxall et al. (2013). Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser., 493, 297-300. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10600>
- Vandenabeele, S.P., Shepard, E.L., Grogan, A., & Wilson, R.P. (2012). When three per cent may not be three per cent; device-equipped seabirds experience variable flight constraints. Marine Biology, 159: 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-011-1784-6>

8.3 Case study 23: Identification of critical areas for the Balearic shearwater and overlap with fisheries

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8.3.1. Introduction

The unintentional capture of non-target species, known as bycatch, is one of the most pervasive anthropogenic threats to marine biodiversity, contributing significantly to mortality at sea and driving the decline of protected, threatened, and endangered species (Dias et al., 2019; Ramírez et al., 2024). Bycatch-related mortality has become a major conservation concern, particularly for long-lived, highly migratory species that are especially vulnerable due to their life-history traits (Barbraud et al., 2012, 2013; Tuck et al., 2015; Michael et al., 2017; Dasnon et al., 2022). The ecological consequences of bycatch are far-reaching, directly reducing population sizes and indirectly altering the structure and function of marine ecosystems (Lewison et al., 2014). For species characterized by slow growth, delayed maturity, and low reproductive rates, increased adult mortality can result in population declines that persist over decades (Beal et al., 2021). Moreover, the extensive movements of mobile marine species often bring them into frequent contact with multiple fisheries, particularly in biologically productive areas that also experience intense fishing pressure (Schoombie et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2019).

The issue of seabird bycatch was formally acknowledged at the European level in 2012 with the adoption of the EU Action Plan for reducing incidental catches of seabirds in fishing gears (COM/2012/0665 final). However, implementation has been limited, and the issue remained largely overlooked until recent years, when it began receiving renewed attention. The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) has since undergone important reforms, embracing an ecosystem-based management approach that emphasizes minimizing impacts on the broader marine environment, including bycatch. This paradigm shift encourages alignment with other key European environmental policies, such as the Birds and Habitats Directives and the MSFD. Despite the Northeast Atlantic hosting a diverse community of seabirds, research on seabird bycatch in this region remains scarce (Ramírez et al., 2024). The area is ecologically significant, serving as a critical feeding ground for residents, migratory, and wintering seabirds during seasonal movements (Stenhouse et al., n.d.), many of which are listed under Annex I of the EU Birds Directive. Investigating their interactions with fishing fleets is essential for informing effective conservation and management strategies, and for supporting the objectives of both the CFP and the MSFD.

The Balearic shearwater (*Puffinus mauretanicus*) is currently the most threatened seabird species in Europe (BirdLife International, 2018). Recent estimates place the breeding population at approximately 2,907 pairs (BirdLife International, 2018), with a total population of 23,700–26,500 individuals (Arroyo et al., 2014). The species' limited breeding range and small population size are compounded by rapid declines, primarily driven by low adult survival rates. Population models predict a decline exceeding 90% within three generations, with an average extinction timeline of around 60 years (Genovart et al., 2016), prompting its classification as “Critically Endangered” by the IUCN (BirdLife International, 2018). Given the alarming population decline of the Balearic shearwater, identifying the key drivers of adult mortality has become a critical conservation priority. The primary threats include incidental bycatch in fisheries and the presence of invasive species at breeding colonies (Arcos, 2011). The species' annual cycle is divided into two distinct phases: during the breeding season, it is restricted to the western Mediterranean, while post-breeding migration takes it into the northeast Atlantic, ranging predominantly from southern Spain to the English Channel (Guilford et al., 2012; Pérez-Roda et al., 2017).

This study aims to inform conservation strategies by examining the spatial overlap between fishing activity and critical non-breeding areas of the Balearic shearwater in the Northeast Atlantic. Using data from geolocator-tagged individuals, our objectives were to: (1) track the species' movements throughout the annual cycle and delineate core distribution areas during the non-breeding period; and (2) to assess the spatial overlap of these areas with major fishing gear types and existing Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). Our findings highlight the urgent need for targeted bycatch mitigation strategies and enhanced spatial management to safeguard the long-term survival of this critically endangered seabird.

8.3.2 Methods

8.3.2.1. Study area and fieldwork

Fieldwork was conducted across the Balearic Islands (Spain) between 2017 and 2022, encompassing breeding colonies on the three main islands: Ibiza, Mallorca, and Menorca. All activities were carried out under permits issued by the Government of the Balearic Islands (Permit numbers: ANE 23/2017, ANE 21/2018, ANE 30/2019, ANE 15/2020, ANE 14/22). During the incubation period (March–April), adult breeders attending their nests were equipped with geolocator (GLS) devices (Table 1). Birds were captured directly from their burrows, handled following protocols designed to minimize disturbance, and banded with metal rings. Biometric measurements and body mass were recorded, and GLS devices were attached to the right tarsus using two cable ties secured to the leg ring. Care was taken

to ensure that the total device weight remained well below the 3% body mass threshold recommended for flying birds (Phillips et al., 2006).

A total of 60 Intigeo-C330 geolocators (MIGRATE Technology) were deployed. Each device weighed 3.3 g, measured 17 × 19 × 8 mm, and had a battery lifespan of 2–3 years. Tagging and recovery were timed to coincide with the incubation period, when one adult reliably remains at the nest, thereby maximizing recovery success. In contrast, during the chick-rearing phase, adults visit nests only at night to feed chicks, significantly reducing capture opportunities. The overall geocator recovery rate across the study period was 64%. Each season, a combination of newly captured individuals and previously tagged birds—excluding those nesting in inaccessible burrows—were equipped with devices. Upon recovery, no signs of injury or irritation were observed on the tarsus, confirming the safety of the attachment method. To validate the suitability of the device weight, we calculated the mean body mass (\pm SE) of tagged individuals, which was 511.25 ± 52.12 g. This resulted in a geocator-to-body mass ratio of $0.67 \pm 0.08\%$, well below the 3% threshold and slightly above the 1% ideal target proposed by Bodey et al. (2018). Colony-specific data are presented in [Table 8.2.1](#).

Table 8.3.1. Summary of the number of annual cycles of the Balearic shearwater collected by island and year in the main breeding colonies of the Balearic Islands.

Year	Menorca	Mallorca	Ibiza	Total
2017	-	-	8	8
2018	-	2	21	23
2019	5	3	13	21
2020	5	1	11	17
2021	-	2	17	19
Total	10	8	70	88

8.3.2.2 Biologging data processing

All statistical analyses and figure generation were conducted within the R programming ecosystem. Geographical positions were estimated using the Geolight package (Lisovski and Hahn, 2012), applying a twilight threshold of 10 lux and an elevation angle of -4.5° , selected based on visual inspection of light curves during the breeding season in the western Mediterranean. Light curves were visually reviewed to exclude those with evident interference or extended darkness periods associated with colony attendance. Data processing followed the methodology of Austin et al. (2019), which included the removal of unreliable positions around equinoxes and those associated with unrealistic travel speeds ($>55 \text{ km h}^{-1}$) (Meier et al., 2015). Additionally, positions with implausible latitude ($<30^\circ\text{N}$ or $>60^\circ\text{N}$) and longitude ($>22^\circ\text{W}$, $>42^\circ\text{E}$) values were excluded (Guilford et al., 2012; Pérez-Roda et al., 2017). Tracks containing fewer than 100 valid positions or with temporal gaps exceeding two months

within the eight-month post-deployment period were discarded. The final dataset included parameters such as latitude, longitude, and the mean central date for each position estimate.

8.3.2.3. Identification of core distribution areas

Distribution patterns of marked individuals were analyzed using kernel density estimation (KDE), a method that estimates the probability of an animal's presence across space by generating a utilization distribution (UD) (Worton, 1995). KDE produces a smoothed probability surface, represented by concentric contours that represent decreasing likelihoods of presence from the center outward, thereby reducing the influence of outliers. Kernel estimations were computed using the *adehabitatHR* package in R (Calenge, 2011). Following Pérez-Roda et al. (2017), we defined core and intensive use areas using the 75% and 50% utilization distributions (UDs), respectively. KDEs were calculated at two temporal scales: a global scale, using pooled positional data from the 2017–2022 annual cycles, and a monthly scale, with separate KDEs for each month from January to December. The global KDEs delineated areas of frequent and intensive use across years, while the monthly KDEs captured seasonal variation in spatial distribution. Due to the known limitations of light-level geolocation around equinoxes, data from March and September (months 3 and 9) were treated with caution, as positions during these periods were excluded.

8.3.2.4. Spatial overlap of core areas and fishing activities

Using QGIS (QGIS Development Team, 2023), we visualized the spatial overlap between Balearic shearwaters' non-breeding distribution and industrial fishing activities in the Northeast Atlantic. Fishing activity data were obtained from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet; <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities>), based on datasets provided by the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES). These data characterize average annual fishing effort, expressed in mW of fishing hours, by ecoregion (Azores, Bay of Biscay and Iberian Coast, Baltic Sea, Barents Sea, Celtic Seas, Faroe Islands, Greater North Sea, Icelandic Waters, Norwegian Sea, and Northeast Atlantic Ocean) and gear type (beam trawls, bottom otter trawls, bottom seines, dredges, pelagic trawls and seines, static gears). Fishing effort data were shown only for vessels over 12 m equipped with Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS). Due to data confidentiality, VMS/logbook data are anonymized and aggregated into a 0.05 × 0.05-degree grid before being sent to ICES, using the C-squares geocoding system (polygons). This overview provides the average for the 2018-2021 period.

To further our analysis, we aimed to identify fishing activity occurring within MPAs designated under both the Natura 2000 network and the UK's MPA framework. Geographic Information System (GIS) layers were obtained from the European Environment Agency (EEA; <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/5e4aec6c-a05c-4bbf-9ccf->

7b477cdaa2ef) and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC; <https://hub.jncc.gov.uk/assets/ade43f34-54d6-4084-b66a-64f0b4a5ef27>). The analysis was conducted at the population level, using 75% utilization distribution (UD) polygons to delineate core distribution areas. Spatial overlap between these core zones and MPAs was assessed using the 'Join Attributes by Location' tool in QGIS.

8.3.3 Results

8.3.3.1. Migratory dynamic and core areas of Balearic shearwaters

We analyzed data from 53 recovered geolocators deployed on Balearic shearwaters, several of which recorded light-level data spanning more than one full annual cycle. This resulted in a total of 88 complete annual tracks. Of these, 80% were from individuals tagged on Ibiza, 9% from Mallorca, and 11% from Menorca. Spatial use patterns inferred from the geolocation data revealed three primary distribution areas, defined by 75% UD polygons: the western Mediterranean (MED), the western Iberian Peninsula (WIP), and the Bay of Biscay (BoB), as delineated by the black line in [Figure 8.3.1](#). Additionally, a key transit corridor was identified around the Strait of Gibraltar (SoG), highlighting its role as a critical passage connecting the Mediterranean and Atlantic regions.

Figure 8.3.1. Distribution map of the Balearic shearwater throughout the annual cycle, based on individuals tagged in Ibiza, Mallorca, and Menorca Islands. The blue dots correspond to estimated positions derived from the geolocator light records. The grey and black lines correspond to the 50% and 75% utilization distribution contours. The three main core areas (MED, WIP, BoB) and the transit corridor zone (SoG) referenced in the text are indicated.

The monthly distribution pattern of Balearic shearwaters aligned with their annual cycle (Figure 8.3.2).

Figure 8.3.2. Monthly distribution maps of the Balearic shearwater across the annual cycle, based on geolocator data from individuals tagged in Ibiza, Mallorca, and Menorca. Blue dots indicate estimated locations derived from light-level geolocation. Grey and black contours represent the 50% and 75% utilization distribution, respectively.

During the breeding season (March to June), they were mainly found in the western Mediterranean, frequenting the continental shelf of the eastern Iberian Peninsula. In April, a single foraging area (75%

UD) was identified in the western Mediterranean. By May, while the primary foraging area remained in the western Mediterranean, a small foraging area emerged in the Atlantic off the WIP. In June, reproduction continued in breeding colonies, maintaining the Mediterranean foraging area, while the WIP foraging area expanded and a second foraging area appeared in the BoB. As breeding individuals migrated, the Mediterranean foraging area extended toward the Strait of Gibraltar. In early July, most breeders migrated to the Atlantic, expanding the WIP foraging area eastwards to the Strait of Gibraltar. In August, the transit zone in the Strait of Gibraltar disappeared, and the WIP and BoB foraging areas became well-defined. By September, the two Atlantic foraging areas connected, indicating migration from the BoB to the south via the WIP. In October, most individuals returned to the Mediterranean, with the BoB foraging area disappearing and the WIP area shrinking. During the pre-breeding period (November and December), most breeders were in the Mediterranean, primarily around the eastern Iberian Peninsula, with a small foraging area in the WIP. In January and February, all individuals were in the Mediterranean, with the foraging area extending to the African coast for feeding trips.

8.3.3.2. Fishing activity in core areas and MPAs

Four types of fishing gear were analysed: bottom otter trawl, static fishing gear, pelagic trawls and seines, and bottom seines (Figure 8.3.3). Across the Balearic shearwater's distribution areas, a total fishing effort of 645,867.89 mW fishing hours was recorded during the 2018-2021 period. Bottom otter trawls represented the largest share of this effort (63%), followed by static gear (25.7%), pelagic trawls and seines (7.7%), and bottom seines (3.6%) (Figure 8.3.4).

Using fishing effort data from vessels larger than 12 m, we assessed the spatial overlap between fishing activity and the Balearic shearwater's main distribution areas. Between 2018 and 2021, 93.5% of the total fishing effort occurred in the BoB, while only 6.5% was recorded in the WIP (Figure 8.3.4). In the BoB, all four major fishing gear types were active, with bottom otter trawls accounting for 61.5% of the total effort, followed by static gear (26%), pelagic trawls and seines (8%), and bottom seines (3.8%). In contrast, fishing activity in the WIP was heavily dominated by bottom otter trawls (83.9%), with static gear (13%) and pelagic gear (3.1%) contributing to a much lesser extent.

Figure 8.3.3. Distribution map of fishing effort in the NE Atlantic (mW in fishing hours, average for the period 2018-2021) obtained from the EMODnet portal (Human Activities, <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities>). The main fishing gears that overlapped with the Balearic shearwater's distribution areas (75% UD) were represented: a) bottom trawl, b) static fishing gears, c) pelagic trawls and seines, d) bottom seines.

Figure 8.3.4. Fishing effort (measured in mW fishing hours) by gear type - bottom trawls, bottom seines, pelagic gears, and static gears – within the Balearic shearwater's distribution areas in the NE Atlantic (Bay of Biscay [BoB] and Western Iberian Peninsula [WIP]) during the 2018-2021 average period.

To assess the spatial distribution of fishing effort relative to MPAs, a separate analysis was conducted for each of the Balearic shearwater main distribution areas. In the BoB, 52% of the total fishing effort – equivalent to 313,414 mW fishing hours – occurred within MPAs, while the remaining 48% (290,385 mW fishing hours) took place outside MPAs (Figure 8.3.5). When disaggregated by gear type, 42% of bottom otter trawl activity occurred within MPAs, along with 64% of bottom seine effort, 61% of pelagic gear effort, and 56% of static gear effort. In the WIP distribution area, 54% of fishing effort (19,201 mW fishing hours) was recorded within MPAs, compared to 46% (22,867 mW fishing hours) outside MPAs (Figure 8.3.6). Gear-specific patterns in the WIP showed that 55% of bottom otter trawl activity occurred within MPAs, while no bottom seine activity was recorded inside protected areas. In contrast, 77% of pelagic gear effort and 46% of static gear effort took place within MPAs.

Figure 8.3.5. Average fishing effort (measured in mW fishing hours) by gear type - bottom trawl, bottom seines, pelagic trawls and seines and static gears – within the Bay of Biscay distribution area for the period 2018-2021. The data distinguishes fishing activities conducted inside and outside Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

Figure 8.3.6. Average fishing effort (measured in mW fishing hours) by gear type - bottom trawl, bottom seines, pelagic trawls and seines and static gears – within the Western Iberian Peninsula distribution area for the period 2018-2021. The data distinguishes fishing activities conducted inside and outside Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

8.3.4 Discussion

The Balearic shearwater, listed as Critically Endangered on the IUCN Red List, faces urgent conservation challenges. This study adopted a spatial approach to analyse conservation perspectives over the 2017-2022 period, using individual tracking data to identify key distribution areas in the Northeast Atlantic. Our findings on the annual distribution of the Balearic shearwater were consistent with previous studies (Arcos, 2011). The first migratory movements begun in May, likely involving failed breeders (Ramírez et al., in review), who first arrived at the WIP, particularly along the Portuguese continental shelf. By June, more individuals entered the Atlantic, expanding the WIP range northward and establishing another distribution area in the BoB. By July, most of the Balearic shearwater population completed breeding and moved into the Atlantic. In August, both the WIP and BoB distribution areas were well-defined. September marked the beginning of the return migration, with increasing connectivity between the two areas, and by October, most individuals re-entered the Mediterranean. During summer, adult breeders typically concentrated between the Gulf of Cádiz and the Rías Baixas in the WIP, as well as in northwestern France in the BoB (Guilford et al., 2012; Araújo et al., 2017; Pérez-Roda et al., 2017). Most individuals (75%) of tracked individuals visited one of the two NE Atlantic distribution areas, with roughly equal proportion using the WIP and BoB. Notably, individuals exhibited strong site fidelity, often returning to the same area annually (Ramírez-Bal et al., in review), highlighting the importance of these regions for targeted conservation efforts.

Fishing activities pose significant threats to Balearic shearwater, primarily through bycatch and indirect interactions such as competition for depleted fish stocks and reliance on fishery discards. In the Northeast Atlantic, fishing operations extensively overlapped with the species' distribution, with an average total fishing effort of approximately 650,000 mW fishing hours recorded between 2018 and 2021, based on EMODNET data. Analysis of gear types used within MPAs revealed that bottom trawling accounted for most of the fishing effort (63%), followed by static gears (25.7%), pelagic gears (trawls and purse seines; 7.7%), and bottom seines (3.6%). Spatially, fishing activity was heavily concentrated in the BoB, which accounted for 93.5% of the total fishing effort, while the WIP represented only 6.5%. These findings, derived from EMODnet fishing data, underscored the BoB as a critical area for assessing and mitigating fisheries-related impacts on the species. However, this spatial analysis provided an important first step, and further assessments using more recent datasets are necessary. It is important to note that the EMODnet dataset included only vessels longer than 12 m, potentially underrepresenting the impact of small-scale artisanal fisheries. Given the coastal and shelf-associated habits of both the Balearic shearwater and artisanal fleets, the degree of overlap may be more substantial than currently estimated. Previous studies identified artisanal fisheries as a significant source of bycatch for the species (Laneri et al., 2010; Oliveira et al., 2015; Cortés et al.,

2017; Ramírez et al., 2024), underscoring the urgent need for more inclusive, fine-scale data to inform effective conservation strategies.

Identifying the fishing gear types with the highest and lowest bycatch risk remains challenging due to limited data and contextual gaps – particularly the absence of information on the number of individuals presents during bycatch events (Astarloa et al., 2023). In the Mediterranean Sea, demersal and pelagic longline fisheries targeting small tuna species pose the greatest bycatch threat (Boué et al., 2013; Ramírez et al. 2024). In the Atlantic, the species is incidentally caught in bottom trawls, gillnets, trammel nets, purse-seines and fixed longlines (Oliveira et al. 2015; ICES, 2022). In the BoB, gillnets and longlines exhibit comparable bycatch rates (ICES, 2022). Conversely, in the WIP, gillnets and purse seines are the primary sources of bycatch for Balearic shearwater (Oliveira et al., 2015; Araújo et al., 2022), whereas no incidental capture in purse seines was detected (Ruiz et al., 2021). Although sample sizes remained relatively small, incorporating data on the number of animals present during fishing operations is crucial for understanding fishery dynamics and gear selectivity. This information should be prioritized in future studies to improve assessments of fishing impacts (Astarloa et al., 2023). Additionally, the species' gregarious behavior and frequent association with fishing vessels can lead to occasional mass mortality events (Laneri et al. 2010). Overexploitation of small pelagic fish and declining fishery discards further reduce prey availability, compounding the species' vulnerability (García-Barón et al., 2021).

Integrating spatial data on fishing activity into the management and monitoring of MPAs is essential - particularly because 48% and 54% of total fishing effort in the BoB and WIP, respectively, occurred within MPAs boundaries that overlap with the distribution range of the Balearic shearwater. In the BoB, 42% of bottom trawling, 64% of bottom seines, 61% of pelagic fishing effort, and 56% of static gear operations took place within MPAs. In the WIP, 55% of bottom trawling, 77% of pelagic fishing effort, and 46% of static gear activity occurred within MPAs, with no bottom seining recorded. This spatial overlap highlights the need to regulate high-risk fishing practices and to clearly define conservation objectives for key species targeted by MPA designations (García-Barón et al., 2021).

In summary, the Balearic shearwater is currently the most threatened seabird species in Europe, underscoring the urgent need to expand global protection efforts and ensure coherence across the European network of MPAs, including those in both EU and the UK. This conservation priority aligns with the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which aims to legally protect at least 30% of the EU's marine territory and establish ecological corridors as part of a truly integrated Trans-European Nature Network (https://spain.representation.ec.europa.eu/noticias-eventos/noticias-0/estrategia-de-la-ue-sobre-biodiversidad-2030-proteccion-de-la-fauna-y-la-flora-2023-03-03_es). Notably, over half of current fishing activity takes place within MPAs, yet most of these areas lack formal management

plans. Bycatch – particularly of vulnerable species like the Balearic shearwater- must be prioritized in the development and revision of these plans. Strengthening the management and monitoring frameworks of MPAs is therefore essential. This includes a thorough assessment of the fishing gears used in each MPA and their associated bycatch risks. Management authorities must also be equipped with adequate resources – ranging from standardized data collection protocols and automated surveillance systems to on-site inspection, among others. Crucially, tailored mitigation measures must be developed and implemented wherever and whenever necessary. Only through such comprehensive and well-resourced efforts can we ensure effective regulations enforcement and successful implementation of conservation actions vital to the survival of the Balearic shearwater.

8.3.5 References

- Afanasyev, V., (2004). A miniature daylight level and activity data recorder for tracking animals over long periods. Mem. Natl. Inst. Polar Res. Special Issue, 58, 227-233.
- Araújo, H., Bastos-Santos, J., Rodrigues, P. C., Ferreira, M., Pereira, A., Henriques, A. C., Monteiro, S. S., Eira, C., & Vingada, J., (2017). The importance of Portuguese Continental Shelf Waters to Balearic Shearwaters revealed by aerial census. Mar. Biol. 164(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-017-3089-x>
- Araújo H, Correia-Rodrigues P, Debru P, Ferreira M, Vingada J, Eira C (2022) Balearic shearwater and northern gannet bycatch risk assessment in Portuguese Continental Waters. Biological Conservation 267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109463>
- Arcos, J.M, (compiler), (2011). International species action plan for the Balearic shearwater, *Puffinus mauretanicus*. SEO/BirdLife and BirdLife International. (http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/conservation/wildbirds/action_plans/docs/puffinus_puffinus_mauretanicus.pdf)
- Arroyo, G. M., Mateos-Rodriguez, M., Munoz, A. R., De la Cruz, A., Cuenca, D., & Onrubia, A. (2014). New population estimates of a critically endangered species, the Balearic Shearwater *Puffinus mauretanicus*, based on coastal migration counts. *Bird Conservation International*, 26(1), 87-99. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0959270914000459>
- Astarloa, A., Louzao, M., García-Baron, I. M., Bluemel, J., Couce, E., Carbonara, P., Romagnoni, G., Neglia, C., Zupa, W., Bitetto, I., Spedicato, M.-T., Kindt-Larsen, L., Glemarec, G., Lusseau, D., Maina, I., Chatzisprou, A., Fotiadis, N., Kavadas, S., Lefkaditou, E., Vassilopoulou, C., Batts, L., Reid, D., Breen, P., Kempf, A., Taylor, M., Kuehn, B., Letschert, J., Northridge, S., Poos, J. J., Afranewaa, N. & Rindorf, A. (2023): SEAwisE Report on the bycatch mortality risk of potentially endangered and threatened species of fish, seabirds, reptiles and mammals. Technical University of Denmark. <https://doi.org/10.11583/DTU.25041257>
- Austin, R. E., Wynn, R. B., Votier, S. C., Trueman, C., McMinn, M., Rodríguez, A., Aguilar, R., Barber, D. G., Carneiro, A., Chivers, L., Hall-Spencer, J. M., Mathews, F., Quillfeldt, P., & Thiebault, A. (2019). Patterns of at-sea behaviour at a hybrid zone between two threatened seabirds. *Scientific Reports*, 9, Article 11586. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-51188-8>
- Barbraud C., Tuck, G., Thomson, R., Delord, K., Weimerskirch H. (2013). Fisheries bycatch as an inadvertent human-induced evolutionary mechanism. *PLOSOne*.8(4): e60353. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0060353>

- Barbraud, C., Rolland, V., Jenouvrier, S., Nevoux, M., Delord, K. & Weimerskirch, H. 2012. Effects of climate change and fisheries bycatch on Southern Ocean seabirds: a review. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 454:285-307. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps09698>
- Beal, M., Dias, M. P., Phillips, R. A., Oppel, S., Hazin, C., Pearmain, E. J., Navarro, R. A., Miskelly, C. M., Robertson, C. J., & Catry, P. (2021). Global political responsibility for the conservation of albatrosses and large petrels. *Science Advances*, 7(10), eabd7225. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abd7225>
- BirdLife International (2018) Species factsheet: *Puffinus mauretanicus*. Downloaded from <http://www.birdlife.org>
- Bodey, T. W., Cleasby, I. R., Bell, F., Votier, S. C., Patrick, S. C., & Bearhop, S. (2018). A phylogenetically controlled meta-analysis of biologging device effects on birds: Deleterious effects and a call for more standardized reporting of study data. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(5), 946–955. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12948>
- Boué, A., Louzao, M., Arcos, J. M., Delord, K., Weimerskirch, H., Cortes, V., Bécares, J., Micol, T., & Phillips, R. A. (2013). Recent and current research on Balearic shearwater on colonies and in Atlantic and Mediterranean areas. NoPCSWG1 Doc, 15.
- Calenge, C. and contributions from S. F.-R., (2023). adehabitatHR: Home Range Estimation (R package version 0.4.21). <https://cran.r-project.org/package=adehabitatHR>
- Cortés, V., Arcos, J. M., & González-Solís, J. (2017). Seabirds and demersal longliners in the northwestern Mediterranean: factors driving their interactions and bycatch rates. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 565, 1-16.
- Dasnon, A., Delord, K., Chaigne, A., & Barbraud, C., (2022). Fisheries bycatch mitigation measures as an efficient tool for the conservation of seabird populations. *J Appl Ecol.* 00:1–12
- Dias, M. P., Martin, R., Pearmain, E. J., Burfield, I. J., Small, C., Phillips, R. A., Navarro, R. A., Collen, B., & Butchart, S. H. M. (2019). Threats to seabirds: A global assessment. *Biological Conservation*, 237, 525–537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2019.06.033>
- García-Barón, I., Giakoumi, S., Santos, M. B., Granado, I., & Louzao, M. (2021). The value of time-series data for conservation planning. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 58(3), 608-619.
- Genovart, M., Arcos, J. M., Álvarez, D., McMinn, M., Meier, R., Wynn, R. B., & Louzao, M. (2016). Demography of the critically endangered Balearic shearwater: The impact of fisheries and time to extinction. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 53(4), 1158–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12622>
- Guilford, T., Wynn, R., McMinn, M., Rodríguez, A., Fayet, A., Maurice, L., Freeman, R., Perrins, C., & Phillips, R. A. (2012). Geolocators reveal migration and pre-breeding behaviour of the critically endangered Balearic shearwater *Puffinus mauretanicus*. *PLoS ONE*, 7(3), e33753. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0033753>
- ICES. (2022). Working Group on Bycatch of Protected Species (WGBYC). In ICES Reports (Vol. 4, p. 91). International Council for the Exploration of the Sea.
- Laneri, K., Louzao, M., Martínez-Abraín, A., Arcos, J. M., Belda, E. J., Guallart, J., & Oro, D. (2010). Trawling regime influences longline seabird bycatch in the Mediterranean: New insights from a small-scale fishery. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 420, 241–252. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps08855>
- Lewin, P. J., Wynn, J., Arcos, J. M., Austin, R. E., Blagrove, J., Bond, S., Carrasco, G., Delord, K., Fisher-Reeves, L., García, D., Gillies, N., Guilford, T., Hawkins, I., Jagers, P., Kirk, C., Louzao, M., Maurice, L., McMinn, M., Micol, T., ... Padgett, O. (2024). Climate change drives migratory range shift via

- individual plasticity in shearwaters. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 121(6), e2312438121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2312438121>
- Lewison, R. L., Crowder, L. B., Wallace, B. P., Moore, J. E., Cox, T., Zydelski, R., McDonald, S., DiMatteo, A., Lewison, R., Freitas, C., Halfwerk, W., De Joseph, B., & Read, A. (2014). Global patterns of marine mammal, seabird, and sea turtle bycatch reveal taxa-specific and cumulative megafauna hotspots. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(14), 5271–5276. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1318960111>
- Lisovski, S., & Hahn, S., 2012. GeoLight - processing and analysing light-based geolocator data in R. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 3(6), 1055–1059. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041210X.2012.00248.x>
- Meier, R. E., Wynn, R. B., Votier, S. C., McMinn Grivé, M., Rodríguez, A., Maurice, L., ... Louzao, M. (2015). Consistent distribution areas and commuting corridors of the critically endangered Balearic shearwater *Puffinus mauretanicus* in the northwestern Mediterranean. *Biological Conservation*, 190, 87–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2015.05.031>
- Michael, P. E., Thomson, R., Barbraud, C., Delord, K., De Grissac, S., Hobday, A. J., Strutton, P. G., Tuck, G. N., Weimerskirch, H., & Wilcox, C. (2017). Illegal fishing bycatch overshadows climate as a driver of albatross population decline. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 579, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps12293>
- Oliveira, N., Henriques, A., Miodonski, J., Pereira, J., Marujo, D., Almeida, A., Alves, J., Cardador, L., Ramos, R., Paiva, V., Louzao, M., & Ramírez, I. (2015). Seabird bycatch in Portuguese mainland coastal fisheries: An assessment through on-board observations and fishermen interviews. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 3, 51–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2014.11.002>
- Pérez-Roda, A., Delord, K., Boué, A., Arcos, J. M., García, D., Micol, T., Weimerskirch, H., Pinaud, D., & Louzao, M., (2017). Identifying Important Atlantic Areas for the conservation of Balearic shearwaters: Spatial overlap with conservation areas. *Deep-Sea Res. Part II.* 141, 285–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2016.11.011>
- Phillips, R. A., Silk, J. R. D., Croxall, J. P., Afanasyev, V., & Briggs, D. R., (2004). Accuracy of geolocation estimates for flying seabirds. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 266, 265–272. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps266265>
- Phillips, R. A., Silk, J. R. D., Croxall, J. P., & Afanasyev, V., (2006). Year-round distribution of white-chinned petrels from South Georgia: Relationships with oceanography and fisheries. *Biol. Conserv.* 129, 336–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.10.046>
- Ramírez, I., Mitchell, D., Vulcano, A., Rouxel, Y., Marchowski, D., Almeida, A., Arcos, J.M., Cortés, V., Lange, G., Morkunas, J., Oliveira, N. & Paiva, V.H. (2024). Seabird bycatch in European waters. *Animal Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12867>
- Ramirez-Bal, R., García-Barón, I., Garcia, D., Arcos, J. M., Carrasco, G., Lewin, P., Delord, K., & Louzao, M. (In review). Individual migratory patterns of the critically endangered Balearic shearwater: A multi-colony and multi-year study in the NE Atlantic. *Global Ecology and Conservation*.
- Ruiz, J., Louzao, M., Oyarzabal, I., Arregi, L., Mugerza, E., & Uriarte, A. (2021). The Spanish purse-seine fishery targeting small pelagic species in the Bay of Biscay: Landings, discards and interactions with protected species. *Fisheries Research*, 239, 105951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2021.105951>
- Schoombie, S., Dille, B. J., Davies, D., & Ryan, P. G. (2018). The foraging range of Great Shearwaters (*Ardenna gravis*) breeding on Gough Island. *Polar Biology*, 41(12), 2451–2458. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-018-2381-7>
- Stenhouse, I. J., Egevang, C., & Phillips, R. A. (2012). Trans-equatorial migration, staging sites and wintering area of Sabine's Gulls *Larus sabini* in the Atlantic Ocean. *Ibis*, 154(1), 42–51.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2011.01158.x>

- Tuck, G. N., Thompson, R. B., Barbraud, C., Delord, K., Louzao, M., Herrera, M., & Weimerskirch, H. (2015). An integrated assessment model of seabird population dynamics: Can individual heterogeneity in susceptibility to fishing explain abundance trends in Crozet wandering albatross? *Journal of Applied Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12474>
- Wakefield, E. D., Bodey, T. W., Bearhop, S., Blackburn, J., Colhoun, K., Davies, R., Dwyer, R. G., Green, J. A., Grémillet, D., Jackson, A. L., Jessopp, M. J., Kane, A., Langston, R. H. W., Lescroël, A., Murray, S., Le Nuz, M., Patrick, S. C., Péron, C., Soanes, L. M., ... Hamer, K. C. (2013). Space partitioning without territoriality in gannets. *Science*, 341(6141), 68–70. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1236077>
- Wilson, R. P., Ducamp, J., Rees, G., Culik, B., & Niekamp, K., 1992. Estimation of location: global coverage using light intensity. In S. S. Priede IM (Ed.), *Wildlife telemetry: remote monitoring and tracking of animals*. 131–134. Ellis Horwood.
- Worton, B.J., 1995. Using Monte-Carlo simulation to evaluate Kernel-based home range estimations. *J. Wildl. Manag.* 59 (4), 794–800. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3802089>
- Zhou, C., Jiao, Y., & Browder, J. (2019). How much do we know about seabird bycatch in pelagic longline fisheries? A simulation study on the potential bias caused by the usually unobserved portion of seabird bycatch. *PLoS ONE*, 14(8), e0220797. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0220797>

8.4 Case study 24: Identification of critical areas for Audouin's gull and overlap with fisheries⁴

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8.4.1 Introduction

Opportunistic utilization of anthropogenic food subsidies is widely extended among wildlife, both in terrestrial (e.g., Lesser snow goose *Chen caerulescens*, Jefferies, 2004; Griffon vulture *Gyps fulvus*, Parra & Tellería, 2004; wild boar *Sus scrofa*, Katona & Heltai, 2018; and wolf *Canis lupus*, Barocas et al., 2018) and marine environments (e.g., Yellow-legged gull *Larus michahellis*, Méndez et al., 2020; Herring gull *Larus argentatus*, Laurich et al., 2019; and Sperm whale *Physeter macrocephalus* or Killer whale *Orcinus orca*, Richard et al., 2020). Gulls serve as a notable paradigm, exemplifying opportunistic species that capitalize on these anthropogenic trophic resources (Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2021). In this context, several examples illustrate the successful adaptation of the Audouin's gull *Ichthyaetus audouinii* to the utilization of these food, particularly concerning fishing discards (Oro et al., 1996, 1997; Arcos et al., 2001; Bécares et al., 2015).

In this study we combined the most comprehensive data set on Audouin's gull spatial distribution during breeding (based on GPS locations for 71 individuals deployed in 2022 across the species' entire breeding latitudinal range) with the most up-to-date, spatially resolved information on land-covers/uses, relevant environmental characteristics (i.e., marine productivity) and important human activities (i.e., tracking data for main fishing vessels operating in the area). This research aimed to assess the contrasting feeding ecology of Audouin's gulls, in terms of habitat and resource utilization, as a likely response to varying degrees of human influence, along a gradient of urbanisation, around monitored colonies. Our objectives included characterizing habitat use by individuals inhabiting various landscapes and seascapes, as well as examining the spatiotemporal co-occurrences/interactions between gulls and fishing vessels. The study is relevant for comprehending the ability of individuals to exploit highly abundant and predictable food subsidies of anthropogenic origin both in marine and terrestrial habitats. Considering its opportunistic behaviour, we expect that Audouin's gull's diet will be linked to food availability, particularly anthropogenic resources. Therefore, in areas with higher resource availability (and consequently more anthropogenic

⁴ An extended version of this section can be found in: Vilaplana, A. F., Afán, I., Oro, D., Bécares, J., Illa, M., Gil, M., Bertolero, A., Forero, M. G., & Ramírez, F. (2024). Distribution and habitat use by the Audouin's Gull (*Ichthyaetus audouinii*) in anthropized environments. *Science of The Total Environment*, 954, 176555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2024.176555>

resources), its foraging behaviour is expected to be more pronounced. It may also contribute to evaluate, and even anticipate, the potential consequences of management actions aimed at minimizing the availability and species' accessibility to these anthropogenic food subsidies (e.g., discard ban policy under the current EU CFP, Borges, 2015) (and associate communities).

8.4.2. Methods

Audouin's gulls typically nest on islands, islets, salt pans, sand dunes areas with sparse vegetation, or abandoned vegetation-free lands (Bécares et al., 2016). Breeding takes place during spring, with egg laying starting in late April (Bécares et al., 2016). As a central-place forager, they are closely linked to their breeding colonies throughout the breeding period for incubating their eggs and feeding their chicks. Both males and females share both incubation and chick-rearing duties. It exhibits partial migration behaviour, meaning that a significant portion of the population undertakes short-distance migrations towards Northwest Africa at the end of the breeding season (around early August, Bécares et al., 2016). Some individuals remain across the Mediterranean coasts along the annual cycle (Greño et al., 2012).

Study area

Fieldwork was conducted across five breeding colonies distributed along the entire latitudinal gradient of Audouin's gull breeding area in the western Mediterranean (from north to south: Barcelona, Delta de l'Ebre, Castelló and Torreveija in the Iberian Peninsula and Melilla in North Africa; [Figure 9.4.1](#)). All these colonies are located near the coast, and surrounding areas cover diverse degrees of anthropogenic habitats, significantly altered and shaped by human activities over several decades.

This marine region constitutes also an important fishing ground within the Mediterranean Sea, supporting an important fishing fleet mainly composed of trawlers (528 vessels within the study area) and purse seiners (158 vessels engaged in nocturnal operations) (FAO, 2022). Trawling represents a non-selective diurnal fishing technique characterized by the generation of a substantial discard volume of demersal species (Stithou et al., 2019). These discards are often thrown back into the sea after each trawl operation (Oro & Ruiz, 1997). Yet, significant disposal of discards tends to occur collectively during the end of the fishing day, particularly in the afternoon when fishing vessels congregate near ports. This practice creates a highly predictable and abundant trophic resource for marine scavengers (Oro & Ruiz, 1997; Martínez-Abraín et al., 2002; Karris et al., 2018; Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020). In contrast, nocturnal purse-seining operations yield fewer discards but can influence scavenger foraging behaviour through a mechanism of resource facilitation, as it aggregates epipelagic fish in proximity to the water's surface (Arcos & Oro, 2002; Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020).

Figure 8.4.1. Spatial distribution of 71 Audouin's gulls equipped with GPS loggers during the 2022 breeding period. Deployment was conducted in five colonies spanning most of the species distribution range at the western Mediterranean Sea and subjected to varying degrees of anthropization. (A) overall distribution for breeding individuals (from April to August 2022); coloured dots represent the spatial distribution of the GPS location for all individuals tagged in each colony. (B-F) colony sites; from north to south: Barcelona, Delta de l'Ebre, Castelló, Torrevieja and Melilla. The base map shows land cover information adapted from SIOSE (Soil Information System of Spain, 2014) and from ESA African land cover (last update 2016) (see Habitat use in Material and methods for details on land cover map processing).

GPS data processing

To ensure GPS data reliability, we initially excluded 8 individuals whose GPS devices stopped functioning during the first week or daily recorded a low number of positions. We also filtered and removed positions recorded with less than four satellites for the trilateration (Bajaj et al., 2002; Fleming et al., 2020), showing speeds <0 or >25 m/s between consecutive positions, and duplicated fixes. Additionally, for standardizing the data at 5-minute intervals, addressing temporal gaps, and making comparable tracks for all individuals, we interpolated locations based on trajectories

generated per individual with the *adehabitatLT* R package (Calenge, 2006). Gaps with fixes separated by more than 60 min and 100 m, were considered a new origin of trajectory. Bursts with fewer than 6 positions were discarded.

Like other central-place foragers, Audouin's gull's distributions and foraging behaviours during the breeding period are constrained by the breeding requirements. To ensure that all individuals showed the same breeding constraints, we determined the end of the breeding period at the individual level by evaluating their colony attendance based on a spatiotemporal buffer around their nests. We considered that the breeding period ended when individuals spent less than 40 % of the daily hours at a minimum distance of 100 m during 9 consecutive days out of the nest; these parameters were selected for standardization among individuals and after visual inspection of trends in nest occupancies, cross-referenced with field observation. Additionally, this filter helped minimize behaviours that deviate from the typical breeding period. For example, it excludes individuals that may have failed and ended their breeding early, extended their incubation or chick-rearing periods, or left the colony for extended periods (≥ 10 days) and returned only briefly, suggesting they were no longer actively breeding.

To determine foraging locations, we examined the behaviour of gulls through the application of the *Expectation-Maximization Binary Clustering method* within R-studio (Garriga et al., 2016, 2022). This algorithm classified each recorded position into four distinct behaviours based on estimated speeds and turning angles: Resting (low speed and low turning angle), Intensive search (low speed and high turning angle), Travelling (high speed and low turning angle), and Extensive search (high speed and high turning angle). For the identification of foraging positions, we considered positions assigned to Intensive and Extensive search behaviours. Positions within the colony, delineated based on their orography, specific characteristics, and expert knowledge, were excluded. Therefore, our analytical approach yields valuable insights into habitat utilization during the breeding period in terms of foraging. All analyses were executed using R-studio and QGIS 3.33.

Habitat use

To allocate foraging locations to habitat type, we overlaid filtered foraging locations with high-resolution land cover information from Spain (Sistema de Información sobre Ocupación del Suelo de España, SIOSE, scale 1: 25 000, last update 2014, obtained from the Instituto Geográfico Nacional) and Morocco (African land cover prototype, 20 m of spatial resolution, last update 2016, obtained from the European Space Agency - ESA). The original landcover categories (≈ 110 for SIOSE and 10 for Africa) were recategorized into 15 common categories for our analysis. However, not all categories were represented for Africa due to the limited number of initial categories available. The original SIOSE

polygons that were depicted as multi-category polygons were categorised as the landcover with the highest percentage within each polygon. As the African land cover layer encompassed the entirety of Africa, a clipping process was conducted on the layer using the home range of individuals from the Melilla colony. Fishing ports and water masses within these African regions (H'Saine, 2012) were photo-interpreted using Google Earth, as these categories were not included in the original product.

Gulls' use of habitats and associated resources was assessed using resource selection functions, which compare available habitats to those actually utilized (Boyce et al., 2002; Manly et al., 2007). Habitat use (real used habitat) was computed as the recorded positions within each of the land cover categories for each colony separately. To address spatiotemporal autocorrelation among observed foraging positions, a subset of the total foraging locations for each individual was selected. Individuals with fewer than 500 positions were excluded to prevent an excessively small subset. For the remaining individuals, the number of positions was standardized to match that of the individual with the fewest positions (e.g., Barcelona: 13 individuals with 815 positions; Castelló: 12 individuals with 884 positions; Delta de l'Ebre: 13 individuals with 623 positions; Melilla: 7 individuals with 991 positions; Torrevieja: 11 individuals with 649 positions). This approach ensures that each individual within a colony contributes an equal number of positions, thereby achieving balanced representation in the model. Habitat availability (potential habitat – expected foraging positions) was calculated by proportionally distributing a subset of equal number of random positions per colony according to the proportional availabilities for the different land cover and land use habitat types inside the gulls' colony home ranges. We defined the home range as the concave polygons that encompass all the GPS positions for each colony with the *concaveman* R package (Gombin et al., 2020). This approach minimizes the overestimation of the species' range size when compared to the convex hull method (Burgman & Fox, 2003). A generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) with a binomial link function was conducted for each colony (provided that the set of potential habitats available differed among colonies), with habitat use as the response variable (1 = observed positions, 0 = expected positions). The model included "land cover and land uses" as a fixed factor and individual `id` as a random factor. To assess the significance of the models and determine whether land cover and land uses have a significant effect on individuals' foraging preferences, the full model was compared to a reduced model that only considered the individual as a random factor— using an ANOVA.

Audouin's gulls, like other gulls, make intensive use of marine habitats and resources. The spatial structure of a seascape is not as apparent as that of the terrestrial counterparts. To classify marine environments into different categories for the availability of natural and anthropogenic marine resources, we combined information on marine productivity and fishing pressure; two proxies to

natural and anthropogenic (i.e., fishing discards) trophic resources potentially exploited by Audouin's gulls.

Among different oceanographic features commonly used for identifying highly productive hotspots, chlorophyll-a (CHL) concentration (mg m^{-3}) is widely considered the most biologically relevant and readily measured. CHL can be considered a reliable surrogate for marine productivity and, consequently, for prey abundance (Pinaud et al., 2005; Louzao et al., 2012). Here, we used *Mediterranean Sea Biogeochemistry Reanalysis* (Copernicus, Salon et al., 2019) ($\approx 4.2 \times 4.2$ km spatial resolution $-1/24^\circ$ -) time series (01/01/1999 - 01/12/2020 yearly temporal resolution) to extract information on CHL for the area of interest. Productive marine areas were identified as areas with CHL values within the 75th percentile, whereas the persistence of these areas was quantified by counting how many years each cell was identified above this percentile (values ranged from 0 to 22 corresponding to the CHL time series).

The spatial distribution of fishing vessels operating within our study area was estimated using VMS information (Spanish Government). VMS is a remote satellite positioning system that records the location of fishing vessels of >12 m in length every 2 h. VMS data has been widely used to investigate seabird-fishery interactions (Bécares et al., 2015; Sommerfeld et al., 2016; Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2021; Gimeno et al., 2022). We obtained data of all the bottom trawl and purse seine vessels operating across the western Mediterranean Sea, from the Alborán Sea to the northern Catalan Sea, within the Geographical SubAreas (GSA) 1 and 6 of the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM), during April to June 2022 (26/04/2022 - 30/06/2022). Fishing pressure was spatially characterized by calculating the cumulative count of VMS recorded positions for pixels enclosed within a 4.2×4.2 km cell grid to match the spatial resolution for the CHL imagery data. This was achieved by selectively identifying positions that are theoretically associated with fishing (as opposed to travelling), employing a two-fold filtering approach based on proximity to fishing ports (300 m from the coastline) and speed thresholds obtained from visual inspection of the distribution of speed values (purse seine: 2.5 knots; trawler: 5 knots).

To facilitate comparisons and simplify the interpretation of productivity patterns and fishing effort, both variables were categorized into quartiles (values range from 0, minimum values, to Q4, maximum values).

Moreover, to study the interaction between fishing vessel positions and tagged individuals, we estimated the number of Audouin's gull GPS positions within a spatiotemporal buffer (500 m, ± 10 min) around VMS positions (Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020). These spatiotemporal co-occurrences between gulls and fishing vessels were considered as a proxy to seabird-fisheries interactions and were

evaluated temporally throughout a daily cycle for identifying periods of enhanced interaction; and spatially throughout the study area for identifying particular regions where these interactions took place.

Extraction of environmental variables and spatial analyses were performed with QGIS 3.33 and R package *raster* (Hijmans, 2023) and *sf* (Pebesma, 2023).

8.4.3. Results

The marine environment represented the major proportion of habitat availability within gull colonies' home ranges (with an average of 87.32 %), followed by urban & related (4.01 %) and forest & bush (2.53 %) areas in Barcelona; agriculture & livestock areas (5.80 %) and rice field (2.85 %) in Delta de l'Ebre; agriculture & livestock (4.35 %) and urban & related (2.78 %) areas in Castelló; agriculture & livestock (15.26 %) and urban & related (4.87 %) areas in Torrevieja; and finally, agriculture & livestock areas (2.92 %) for Melilla.

Based on the analysis of 146 755 foraging positions recorded (once filtered from ca. 5 million initial GPS positions, [Table 8.4.1](#)), our results revealed a higher proportion of Audouin's gulls' positions in terrestrial habitats (51.18 % of total positions) in relation to the marine environment (48.82 %). However, these proportions varied among studied colonies ([Figure 8.4.2](#)). In Barcelona, the sea (66.5 %) emerged as the dominant category, followed by fishing ports (12.8 %) and urban & related areas (11.7 %). Within the Delta de l'Ebre colony, we observed the prevalence of the sea (45.4 %), rice fields (22.9 %), and fishing ports (11.2 %), followed by urban & related areas (7.8 %). In Castelló, the sea (40.9 %), urban & related areas (26.8 %), fishing ports (10.9 %), and finally agriculture & livestock (9.4 %) were the prominent habitat categories. In Torrevieja, the sea (45.2 %) was again prominent in terms of use, followed by urban & related areas (27.5 %) and agriculture & livestock (13.4 %). Finally, in Melilla, emphasis was placed on fishing ports (49.9 %) and the sea (43.4 %). Furthermore, an examination of the most frequently utilized subcategories within the urban & related areas across all colonies reveals that individuals preferentially selected expansion districts, industrial zones, urban parks, and commercial zones, among others. Habitat—land cover and land use—emerged as a significant driver of Audouin's gull foraging distribution across the five study colonies (p -value < 0.001 in all cases). Individuals preferentially selecting urban and related areas or fishing ports in all colonies, coastline in the majority of colonies, agriculture and livestock areas in the Delta de l'Ebre, Castelló, and Torrevieja colonies, landfill in the Barcelona colony, and rice fields in the Delta de l'Ebre and Castelló colonies. According to daily activity patterns, gulls showed a preference for the marine environment during the night, while the use of terrestrial habitats increases during daylight hours,

with similar trends observed across different colonies. However, regarding foraging activity patterns, it was during the daylight hours that individuals were most active (Figure 8.4.3B).

Table 8.4.1. Summary of the number of GPS-equipped individuals and the overall number of positions for each of the study colonies, before and after GPS data processing.

Colony	Starting num. id	Final num. id	Starting num. positions	Final num. positions
Barcelona	13	13	401 329	32 801
Delta de l'Ebre	15	15	3 409 235	42 262
Castelló	15	14	564 880	34 270
Torreveija	15	12	515 225	19 939
Melilla	13	7	206 456	17 483
Total	71	61	5 097 125	146 755

Figure 8.4.2. Habitat availability and use for each colony. Habitat use is illustrated as the ratio of recorded positions within the land cover and land use categories for each colony. Habitat availability is presented as the percentage of each land cover and land use category within the respective colony's home range.

In the marine environment, individuals preferentially used highly productive and persistent marine areas that are also subjected to intense fishing activity: 56.7 % and 17.6 % of the gulls' GPS positions fell within categories Q2 and Q3-4 of our proxy to highly productive and persistent marine regions; whereas ca. 60 % of the gulls GPS positions overlapped within categories Q3 and Q4 of our proxy to fishing pressure (Figure 8.4.4). When considering the two dimensions simultaneously, we observed that 26.1 % of the total gulls' positions at sea fell within highly productive and persistent marine areas (Q2-Q4 quadrant) and fishing hotspots. Trawlers and purse seiners were segregated spatially: just a few and small areas along the coast showed intense pressure by both trawlers and purse seiners (Figure 8.4.4). Accordingly, just a few gulls' GPS positions (5.1 %) overlap with areas of intense fishing

pressure (Q4) by both fishing gears. When considering gears separately, we observed that a relevant proportion of gulls' GPS positions fell in areas with absent fishing pressure (0) for purse seiners (52.5 %), and trawlers (37.2 %). However, a noteworthy proportion of the gulls' GPS positions overlapped with areas of intense pressure (Q4) by trawlers (36.7 %) and by purse seiners (20.8 %; Figure 4). When evaluating the spatiotemporal co-occurrence between Audouin's gulls and fishing vessels, we observed that 17.1 % of purse seine positions (6 529 out of 38 212) exhibited co-occurrence with Audouin's gulls, whereas 2 % of trawler positions (4 022 out of 197 497) overlapped spatially and temporally with gulls (Figure 8.4.5A). The highest rates of co-occurrence with both gears were observed near the Delta de l'Ebre (40.5 %), and the Barcelona colonies (35.1 %). Both the Barcelona and Delta de l'Ebre colonies displayed more co-occurrences with purse seiners (30.5 % and 24.2 %, respectively) compared to trawlers (4.6 % and 16.4 %). In opposition, most of the observed co-occurrences near the Castelló and Torrevieja colonies occurred with trawlers (Figure 5B). In terms of recorded daily cycles for gull-fisheries co-occurrences, we observed that co-occurrences between gulls and purse seiners took place between 21:00 to 6:00 (UTC), with a major peak around 5:00 (21.3 %) and a secondary peak at 22:00 (15.7 %). For trawlers, co-occurrences were observed from 3:00 to 14:00, with a notable peak between 13:00 and 14:00 (27.4 %).

Figure 8.4.3. A) Daily habitat use for all individuals combined. Habitat use is illustrated as the ratio of recorded positions within the land cover and land use categories throughout the day, in 2-hour intervals. B) Percentage of foraging positions throughout the day for each colony, based on the total foraging positions of each colony.

Figure 8.4.4. Spatiotemporal variability of marine productivity and fishing pressure in the study area. Maps represent the spatial co-occurrence of two variables: highly productive and persistent marine areas and fishing pressure in A), and purse seine (PS) and trawler (OTB) fishing pressure in B). Productive and persistent marine areas are based on chlorophyll-a historical values, according to the period for which imagery data on chlorophyll-a is available, i.e., 22 years (1999 to 2020). Persistence was determined according to the number of years in which each pixel was defined as a higher productive area. Fishing pressure reflects the distribution of fishing vessels obtained from VMS-tracked fishery vessels (purse seine and trawlers) between April and June 2022 (i.e., matching the period considered for gulls' tracking data); VMS information around Melilla is not available as this corresponds to Moroccan fleet. Each information was classified into quartiles (values range from 0, minimum values, to Q4, maximum values). White crosses show colony locations. Figures C) and D) represent cross-frequency matrix mosaic plots of the interaction between the spatial distribution of GPS-tracked Audouin's gulls and the spatiotemporal heterogeneity quartiles overlap of C) productive marine areas and fishing pressure areas and D) purse seine (PS) and trawler (OTB) fishing pressure areas at the Mediterranean study.

Figure 8.4.5. A) Spatiotemporal co-occurrence quartiles overlap between purse seine (PS) or trawler (OTB) vessel positions and the GPS-tracked Audouin's gulls at the Mediterranean study (the Melilla colony was excluded from the analyses). Colours represent the quartiles based on the number of spatiotemporal co-occurrences within a 500 m and 20 min (i.e., ± 10 min) buffer between the respective fishing gear and the GPS-tracked Audouin's gulls. Values range from 0 (minimum spatiotemporal co-occurrence) to Q4 (maximum spatiotemporal co-occurrence). B) Percentage of co-occurrence between positions of purse seine or trawler vessels and Audouin's gulls, categorized by colony. C) Density of co-occurrences between positions of purse seine or trawler vessels and Audouin's gulls per hour (UTC) over the study period.

8.4.4 Discussion

Anthropogenic food subsidies are widely used by a range of opportunistic species, including seabirds (Bécares et al., 2015; Laurich et al., 2019; Méndez et al., 2020; Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020). However, as far as we know, no previous studies have assessed the use of anthropogenic food resources by a single species across most of its distribution range covering a varying degree of human influence. In this study we have for first time combined the most detailed and spatially resolved characterization of coastal areas and marine regions in the Western Mediterranean, with the most impressive dataset on GPS positions for the Audouin's gull.

We provide a comprehensive assessment of the habitat utilization by the Audouin's gull and its interactions with fisheries across 5 different breeding colonies spanning most of its distribution range of its breeding region in the Western Mediterranean. Even though the colonies demonstrate a slightly preference for terrestrial habitats, with urban & related areas and fishing ports being the most selected habitat category on the mainland (15.06 % both), the marine environment was also intensively used (Mañosa et al., 2004; Christel et al., 2012; Bécares et al., 2015). When at sea, individuals preferentially used highly productive and persistent marine areas that are also subjected to intense fishing activity (Valavanis et al., 2004). They also co-occurred, and presumably interacted, with the main fishing fleets operating in this region (Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020). However, the specific gear with which they interacted the most varies among colonies, with individuals from the northernmost colonies (i.e., Barcelona and Delta de l'Ebre) preferentially interacting with purse seiners; and those from the southernmost colonies (i.e., Castelló and Torreveija) preferentially interacting with trawlers. The general activity and use of specific habitats vary throughout the daily cycle. Initially considered nocturnal birds highly associated with the marine environment (Oro et al., 1997), these gulls have altered their activity patterns to significantly utilize terrestrial resources, potentially of anthropogenic origin. This shift is evidenced by the highest percentage of foraging positions occurring during daylight hours and a greater representation of terrestrial habitats during the day compared to the night. Although the composition of habitat use varies between colonies, the consistent pattern of predominant marine use at night versus terrestrial habitats during the day is observed across different colonies, with the sole exception of Melilla. This trend indicates a broad adaptation to exploiting terrestrial food sources during the day, potentially driven by the availability of anthropogenic resources. The findings underscore the dynamic nature of gull foraging behaviour and habitat use, highlighting the significant influence of human activities on their daily activity patterns. Our results hold particular relevance in a changing world where a substantial rise in anthropogenic food subsidies is anticipated (Oro et al., 2013), leading to disturbances in the

distribution and behaviour of opportunistic species, with ultimate consequences on ecosystems and populations' dynamics.

Feeding adaptations to a heterogeneous landscape

Habitat utilization by Audouin's gulls was not directly proportional to habitat availability: even though the marine environment constitutes a significant portion of the habitat available within colony-specific gulls' home ranges, individuals exhibited slightly higher utilization of terrestrial habitats compared to the marine environment. However, it's worth considering that a relevant proportion of habitat use among terrestrial systems corresponded to fishing ports, where they presumably feed on resources derived from fishing catches (Arcos et al., 2001). This might lead to the consideration of a more substantial reliance on resources originating from the marine environment.

Besides the use of marine habitats by Audouin's gulls for feeding, it's important to emphasize the differential use of terrestrial environments (i.e., habitats located on the mainland) observed between the original colony located at the Delta de l'Ebre, and the new breeding sites that scattered along the Spanish Mediterranean coast. Individuals from the Delta de l'Ebre colony displayed a pronounced preference for rice fields, probably explained by the presence of the American crayfish *Procambarus clarkii*, a constituent of their diet (Gutiérrez-Yurrita et al., 1999; Longoni, 2010). Even though it is an invasive species, it has the potential to act as a food resource for predators, especially those with a significant degree of trophic plasticity (Tablado et al., 2010), and can represent a significant proportion (20-31 %) of Audouin's gull diet (Navarro et al., 2010; Oro et al., 1997). In contrast, urban and related areas stood out with the highest average number of recorded foraging positions across the highly anthropized areas of Torre Vieja, Castelló and Barcelona colonies. Urban areas typically provide gulls with abundant, and highly predictable and accessible anthropogenic food sources (Marzluff, 2001; Oro, 2020; Parra-Torres et al., 2020), such as discarded fast food and trash containers food in commercial areas (Oro, 2020), tree fruits and food from the parks (based on field observation), industrial food zones (potentially associated with the food sector, as seen in the Barcelona colony), among others (Oro et al., 2013). Individuals breeding in Torre Vieja and Castelló also foraged largely in agriculture and livestock areas, where they can feed on highly abundant and predictable crop residuals (Foley et al., 2011; Oro et al., 2013). In Barcelona, individuals used landfill sites preferentially, which streamlines access to anthropogenic food.

The Melilla colony emerged as a sort of 'outlier' among the breeding colonies since the utilization of terrestrial habitat was nearly insignificant when contrasted with the prominence of the marine environment. Nevertheless, these results should be interpreted with caution and two factors require consideration: 1) the study involves only half the number of individuals compared to the other

colonies, and 2) a notable distinction exists primarily in the number of categories between the main land use and cover layer employed for the Melilla colony, African land cover, and the layer applied for the remaining colonies, SIOSE (see *Habitat use* in *Material and methods*); therefore, the photointerpretation carried out could partially account for this high percentage of positions at fishing ports.

Marine resource exploitation and interaction with fisheries

When at sea, individuals preferentially used highly productive and persistent marine areas, where prey abundance is typically higher (Pinaud et al., 2005; Louzao et al., 2012). These areas of enhanced prey availability, and Audouin's gull occurrence, are also areas of intense fishing pressure, corroborating the relationship between fisheries and Audouin's gulls (Arcos et al., 2001; Arcos & Oro, 2002; Martínez-Abraín et al., 2002). Fisheries-gulls' interactions have both negative and positive consequences. On one hand, fisheries induce marine habitat destruction and degradation (Gislason et al., 2000; Pauly et al., 2002), along with the overexploitation of common resources and natural marine prey such as the sardine stock, which is the primary marine prey for the gulls (Ruiz et al., 1996; Watson et al., 2004; Arcos et al., 2008; Bécares et al., 2015). This should negatively impact the seabirds' population in general, and Audouin's gulls in particular. On the other hand, fisheries provide gulls with abundant and predictable fish discards (mainly from trawlers, Oro et al., 1996), but also with new feeding opportunities by enhancing prey accessibility when gathering fish near the surface (purse seiners, Arcos & Oro, 2002).

Overall, our tracked individuals preferentially selected areas with intense trawler activity, compared to those areas of intense purse seiner pressure. This could be explained by the significant influence of this fleet on the Audouin's gull, which stems from the substantial amount of discards (demersal fish) they generate daily (Oro et al., 1996; Ruiz et al., 1996; Cama et al., 2012; Stithou et al., 2019). These discards constitute approximately 39-48 % of the diet of adult breeding Audouin's gulls (Navarro et al., 2010). However, the higher number and wider distribution of trawlers compared to purse seiners (see *Study area* in *Material and methods*), and therefore, the number of positions employed to establish the areas of fishing pressure for each fishing gear must also be taken into consideration. This situation increases the likelihood of having a larger spatial extent of fishing pressure zones attributed to trawlers rather than purse seiners (the latter being confined to smaller areas along the western Mediterranean). As a result, there is a higher probability of spatial co-occurrences (shared habitat) with trawlers than with purse seiners. Additionally, considering that trawlers exhibit little to no selectivity (unlike purse seiners), they cover a significantly larger fishing area. This extensive fishing practice is also highly damaging, imposing considerable adverse pressure on the marine ecosystem, and consequently affecting marine birds that rely on marine resources.

Within this context, further details on the spatiotemporal co-occurrence between fishing vessels and Audouin's gulls are crucial to our comprehension of fisheries-gulls' interactions. When using a finer spatial scale, and when additionally considering the temporal dimension of tracking data for gulls and vessels, we observed an increasing number of interactions between gulls and purse seiners across the colonies, as compared to trawlers. This observation can be supported by prior studies, where apart from capitalizing on the discards of purse seine vessels, gulls primarily feed on small pelagic fish drawn to the surface by vessel lamps (Arcos & Oro, 2002), which is related to the observed co-occurrences between gulls and purse seiners between 21:00 to 6:00. These fish constitute approximately 29-30 % of the diet of adult breeding Audouin's gulls (Navarro et al., 2010). The interaction with trawlers exhibited an escalation from the onset of the fishing day until 14:00 UTC when the peak in vessel-gull co-occurrence occurred. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that around this time, a substantial number of trawlers are returning to port, resulting in increased concentration and proximity to the coastal areas and the adjacent colonies. During this period, trawlers engage in sorting their catch and disposing of undesired components, further elucidating the heightened interaction patterns (Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020); this could also account for the peak at the commencement of trawler activity, occurring at 4:00 UTC, as these vessels initiate their fishing day and find themselves near the colonies once again. These co-occurrences are analyzed individually for the five studied colonies, thereby reexamining for the marine environment the potential adaptation in habitat utilization and distinct foraging behaviour exhibited by the more recently established breeding colonies, as opposed to the source Delta de l'Ebre colony. While the Delta de l'Ebre colony exhibits the highest interaction rate with vessels (predominantly purse seiners, in contrast to the findings of Ouled-Cheikh et al., 2020), these interactions are notably diminished within the Castelló and Torrevieja colonies (where there is also a higher preference for trawlers). Lastly, the Barcelona colony demonstrates a marked specialization towards purse seiners, in contrast to the rest of the studied colonies. However, it's crucial to consider individual plasticity, wherein various individuals can show differential usage of these anthropogenic food subsidies (e.g., influenced by age, Navarro et al., 2010).

As mentioned before, the only "positive" aspect for marine birds in the trawling fishing method is that it generates a significant amount of fishing discards. However, the implementation of a discard ban policy is scheduled shortly, under the current EU CFP (Borges, 2015). Consequently, marine birds in general, and the Audouin's gull in particular, could be considerably compromised. Yet, Audouin's gulls show a preference for purse seiners, a fishing technique that is, in theory, more selective and potentially sustainable, especially in areas where this fishing method holds greater significance (in the northern distribution as seen in this study). This "preference" for purse seiners can be attributed to two factors: 1) both purse seiners and Audouin's gulls are nocturnal in their habits (Oro et al., 1997),

potentially coinciding in time, although the feeding habits of Audouin's gulls have adapted to exploit the resources of trawlers as well; and 2) there is intense competition for discards associated with trawlers, particularly from a larger and more aggressive species like the Yellow-legged gull *Larus michahellis* (Calado et al., 2018; Arcos et al., 2001).

8.4.5 Conclusions

Our findings offer perspectives on the reliance of scavenger seabird communities on anthropogenic food subsidies, while also potentially carrying implications for the conservation and management of these species, for instance, in the context of changes in fisheries policies (discard ban), while offering insights into how this species can adapt to this ever-changing world.

Foraging and feeding plasticity of this species, as demonstrated by the diversity in habitat utilization and the differences observed among colonies, is likely a key factor behind the species' success in the ongoing dispersion process. The high availability and accessibility of trophic resources linked to the wide range of human activities operating in this region may have also a role in amplifying this dispersion process. Nevertheless, it is crucial to consider the trade-off arising from this interaction between anthropogenic food resources and opportunistic species that make use of them. Feeding on highly abundant, predictable and accessible food subsidies of human origin typically leads to decreased foraging durations and reduced energy expenditure contributing to various fitness components (Murray et al., 2018), and likely resulting in the successful colonization of new breeding sites. However, this feeding behaviour can be also viewed as an 'ecological trap', as consuming food from urban and associated zones, including landfills, can also compromise individual's health due to the ingestion of anthropogenic materials (Lindborg et al., 2012), the bioaccumulation of heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants (Sanpera et al., 2007; Bertolero et al., 2015), the poor nutritional quality food (Pierotti & Annett, 1990) and the higher risk of contracting any disease (Furst et al., 2018), potentially leading to transmission of zoonotic diseases (Vaz & Nunes, 2007). Furthermore, these shifts in population dynamics could trigger an ecosystem imbalance, with certain species becoming overabundant and problematic, as observed with the Yellow-legged gull (*Larus michahellis*). This imbalance could indirectly have adverse consequences not only for specific species but also for the overall ecosystem.

Management actions such as landfill closure/management and changes in fishing policies (such as the discard ban), outlined in European policies could impact colonies that have become heavily reliant on these resources. It remains to be seen whether these opportunistic species can adapt to the new context in the future.

A prospective enhancement in this study will involve establishing a connection between observed foraging habitats (using GPS and RS & GIS) with individuals' dietary reconstructions (e.g., based on stable isotope approaches); as food/energy intake per habitat may be not proportional to habitat availability; i.e., different habitats may provide gulls with contrasting food resources in terms of quantity and quality. Additionally, to facilitate the application of our methodological framework across various colonies globally, standardized and cross-border land use layers are essential. Collaborative international efforts are fundamental, particularly for spatial comparisons. Moreover, a continuous updating of land use and land cover layers is vital for nuanced temporal comparisons, given the planet's land cover and uses ongoing transformations under anthropogenic influences. For instance, at present, the "SIOSE alta resolución" project, which provides a high-resolution land occupation database for Spain from 2017, is in the production and review phase.

An intriguing avenue for exploration would be to investigate the selection and utilization of habitats along the different phases of the breeding period, distinguishing between incubation and chick-rearing stages, as they are subjected to different time budgets and energy/nutrient requirements. Furthermore, a compelling direction would involve the examination of habitat selection and utilization throughout an annual cycle. This could entail a comparative analysis between the reproductive and non-reproductive periods. Moreover, to discern the impact of anthropization on this species and other opportunistic ones, it is recommended to extend this study across multiple years. By delineating the temporal dynamics of habitat selection and usage during the reproductive phase, a more comprehensive understanding of survival probabilities and population dynamics can be gained. Lastly, it should be emphasized that many of the studied individuals consisted primarily of breeding adults (as they were nesting) of known age (most of them were banded as chicks). Consequently, a substantial portion of the study subjects has their age and sex information along with nesting parameters such as clutch size and egg volume, offering opportunities for investigating a variety of aspects like assessing the influence of age, sex and the number of chicks rearing on interactions with fishing vessels, providing insights into individuals' experience and specialization.

8.4.6 References

- Arcos, J., Louzao, M., & Oro, D. (2008). Fisheries ecosystem impacts and management in the Mediterranean: Seabirds point of view. American Fisheries Society Symposium.
- Arcos, J., & Oro, D. (2002). Significance of nocturnal purse seine fisheries for seabirds: A case study off the Ebro Delta (NW Mediterranean). *Marine Biology*, 141(2), 277–286. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-002-0843-8>

- Arcos, J., Oro, D., & Sol, D. (2001). Competition between the yellow-legged gull *Larus cachinnans* and Audouin's gull *Larus audouinii* associated with commercial fishing vessels: The influence of season and fishing fleet. *Marine Biology*, 139(5), 807–816. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002270100651>
- Bajaj, R., Ranaweera, S. L., & Agrawal, D. P. (2002). GPS: Location-tracking technology. *Computer*, 35(4), 92–94. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2002.993780>
- Barocas, A., Hefner, R., Ucko, M., Merkle, J. A., & Geffen, E. (2018). Behavioral adaptations of a large carnivore to human activity in an extremely arid landscape. *Animal Conservation*, 21(5), 433–443. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12400>
- Bécares, J., Arcos, J. M., & Oro, D. (2016). Migración y ecología espacial de la gaviota de Audouin en el Mediterráneo occidental y noroeste africano. *SEO/BirdLife*. <https://doi.org/10.31170/0053>
- Bécares, J., García-Tarrasón, M., Villero, D., Bateman, S., Jover, L., García-Matarranz, V., Sanpera, C., & Arcos, J. M. (2015). Modelling Terrestrial and Marine Foraging Habitats in Breeding Audouin's Gulls *Larus audouinii*: Timing Matters. *PLOS ONE*, 10(4), e0120799. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0120799>
- Bécares, J., & Rodríguez, B. (2010). Técnicas de marcaje de aves marinas para el seguimiento remoto. *Revista de Anillamiento N.º 25-26 – SEO/BirdLife*.
- Bertolero, A., Vicente, J., Meyer, J., & Lacorte, S. (2015). Accumulation and maternal transfer of perfluorooctane sulphonic acid in yellow-legged (*Larus michahellis*) and Audouin's gull (*Larus audouinii*) from the Ebro Delta Natural Park. *Environmental Research*, 137, 208–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2014.12.007>
- Borges, L. (2015). The evolution of a discard policy in Europe. *Fish and Fisheries*, 16(3), 534–540. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12068>
- Boyce, M. S., Vernier, P. R., Nielsen, S. E., & Schmiegelow, F. K. A. (2002). Evaluating resource selection functions. *Ecological Modelling*, 157(2), 281–300. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800\(02\)00200-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800(02)00200-4)
- Burgman, M., & Fox, J. (2003). Bias in species range estimates from minimum convex polygons: Implications for conservation and options for improved planning. *Animal Conservation*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1367943003003044>
- Calado, J. G., Matos, D. M., Ramos, J. A., Moniz, F., Ceia, F. R., Granadeiro, J. P., & Paiva, V. H. (2018). Seasonal and annual differences in the foraging ecology of two gull species breeding in sympatry and their use of fishery discards. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 49(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jav.01463>
- Calenge, C. (2006). The package “adehabitat” for the R software: A tool for the analysis of space and habitat use by animals. *Ecological Modelling*, 197(3–4), 516–519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2006.03.017>
- Cama, A., Abellana, R., Christel, I., Ferrer, X., & Vieites, D. R. (2012). Living on predictability: Modelling the density distribution of efficient foraging seabirds. *Ecography*, 35(10), 912–921. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2011.07222.x>
- Christel, I., Navarro, J., Del Castillo, M., Cama, A., & Ferrer, X. (2012). Foraging movements of Audouin's gull (*Larus audouinii*) in the Ebro Delta, NW Mediterranean: A preliminary satellite-tracking study. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 96, 257–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.11.019>
- FAO. (2022). The State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries 2022. General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc3370en>
- Fleming, C. H., Drescher-Lehman, J., Noonan, M. J., Akre, T. S. B., Brown, D. J., Cochrane, M. M., Dejid, N., DeNicola, V., DePerno, C. S., Dunlop, J. N., Gould, N. P., Hollins, J., Ishii, H., Kaneko, Y., Kays,

- R., Killen, S. S., Koeck, B., Lambertucci, S. A., LaPoint, S. D., Latta, A., Lescroël, A., Linnell, J. D. C., McIntyre, C. L., Meredith, M., Miller, D. A. W., Mourier, J., Muff, S., Mueller, T., Palmer, S. C. F., Parrett, L., Patterson, T. A., Pedersen, M. W., Pereira, M. E., Peters, W., Pfeiffer, M., Pomeroy, P. P., Ramesh, T., Reinking, A., Rickbeil, G. J. M., Rivera-Milán, F. F., Roeber, C. L., Rushing, C. S., Schmidt, N. M., Schlägel, U. E., Schläger, U. E., Schlägel, U. E., Singh, N. J., Sollmann, R., Søndergaard, M., Strand, O., Tuomainen, U., Weinzierl, R., White, P. J., Whittington, J., Whittington, J., Wilmers, C. C., Wilson, R. P., Worton, B. J., & Calabrese, J. M. (2020). A comprehensive framework for handling location error in animal tracking data. *bioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.130195>
- Foley, J. A., Ramankutty, N., Brauman, K. A., Cassidy, E. S., Gerber, J. S., Johnston, M., Mueller, N. D., O'Connell, C., Ray, D. K., West, P. C., Balzer, C., Bennett, E. M., Carpenter, S. R., Hill, J., Monfreda, C., Polasky, S., Rockström, J., Sheehan, J., Siebert, S., Tilman, D., & Zaks, D. P. M. (2011). Solutions for a cultivated planet. *Nature*, 478(7369), 337–342. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10452>
- Fuirst, M., Veit, R. R., Hahn, M., Dheilly, N., & Thorne, L. H. (2018). Effects of urbanization on the foraging ecology and microbiota of the generalist seabird *Larus argentatus*. *PLOS ONE*, 13(12), e0209200. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0209200>
- Garriga, J., Palmer, J. R. B., Oltra, A., & Bartumeus, F. (2016). Expectation-Maximization Binary Clustering for Behavioural Annotation. *PLOS ONE*, 11(3), e0151984. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0151984>
- Garriga, J., Palmer, J. R. B., Oltra, A., & Bartumeus, F. (2022, October 12). EMbC: Expectation-Maximization Binary Clustering. R package version 2.0.3. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=EMbC>
- Gimeno, M., García, J. A., Afán, I., Aymí, R., Montalvo, T., & Navarro, J. (2022). Age-related differences in foraging behaviour at sea and interactions with fishing vessels in an opportunistic urban gull. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, fsac120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsac120>
- Gislason, H., Sinclair, M., Sainsbury, K., & O'Boyle, R. (2000). Symposium overview: Incorporating ecosystem objectives within fisheries management. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 57, 468–475. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmsc.2000.0712>
- Gombin, J., Vaidyanathan, R., & Agafonkin, V. (2020, May 11). concaveman: A Very Fast 2D Concave Hull Algorithm. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=concaveman>
- Greño, J. L., Vera, P., & Sarzo, B. (2012, October). Wintering of Audouin's Gulls *Larus audouinii* in Castellón (Spain). *Ecology and Conservation of Mediterranean Seabirds and Other Bird Species under the Barcelona Convention: Update and Progress. Proceedings of the 13th Medmaravis Symposium, Alghero, Sardinia, Italy, 14-17 October 2011.*
- Gutiérrez-Yurrita, P., Martínez, J., Ilhéu, M., Bravo-Utrera, M., Bernardo, J., & Montes, C. (1999). The status of crayfish populations in Spain and Portugal. In *Crayfish in Europe as alien species* (Vol. 11, pp. 161–192). A.A. Balkema.
- Hijmans, R. J. (2023). Raster: Geographic Data Analysis and Modeling. R package version 3.6-20. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=raster>
- H'Saine, S. (2012). Debarquements des produits de la peche cotiere et artisanale par port au cours des 10 premiers mois des annees 2012 et 2013.
- Jefferies, R. L. (2004). Agricultural Food Subsidies, Migratory Connectivity and Large-Scale Disturbance in Arctic Coastal Systems: A Case Study. *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, 44(2), 130–139.
- Karris, G., Ketsilis-Rinis, V., Kalogeropoulou, A., Xirouchakis, S., Machias, A., Maina, I., & Kavadas, S. (2018). The use of demersal trawling discards as a food source for two scavenging seabird species:

- A case study of an eastern Mediterranean oligotrophic marine ecosystem. *Avian Research*, 9(1), 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40657-018-0118-5>
- Katona, K., & Heltai, M. (2018). Diet composition and food habits of wild boar – A literature review. *Journal of Landscape Ecology*, 16, 65–74.
- Laurich, B., Drake, C., Gorman, O. T., Irvine, C., MacLaurin, J., Chartrand, C., & Hebert, C. E. (2019). Ecosystem change and population declines in gulls: Shifting baseline considerations for assessing ecological integrity of protected areas. *Journal of Great Lakes Research*, 45(6), 1215–1227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2019.09.002>
- Lindborg, V. A., Ledbetter, J. F., Walat, J. M., & Moffett, C. (2012). Plastic consumption and diet of Glaucous-winged Gulls (*Larus glaucescens*). *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 64(11), 2351–2356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2012.08.023>
- Longoni, V. (2010). Rice Fields and Waterbirds in the Mediterranean Region and the Middle East. *Waterbirds*, 33(sp1), 83–96. <https://doi.org/10.1675/063.033.s106>
- Louzao, M., Delord, K., García, D., Boué, A., & Weimerskirch, H. (2012). Protecting Persistent Dynamic Oceanographic Features: Transboundary Conservation Efforts Are Needed for the Critically Endangered Balearic Shearwater. *PLoS ONE*, 7(5), e35728. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0035728>
- Manly, B. F. L., McDonald, L., Thomas, D. L., McDonald, T. L., & Erickson, W. P. (2007). Resource selection by animals: Statistical design and analysis for field studies. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Mañosa, S., Oro, D., & Ruiz, X. (2004). Activity patterns and foraging behaviour of Audouin's gulls in the Ebro Delta, NW Mediterranean. *Scientia Marina*, 68(4), 605–614.
- Martínez-Abraín, A., Maestre, R., & Oro, D. (2002). Demersal trawling waste as a food source for Western Mediterranean seabirds during the summer. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 59(3), 529–537. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmsc.2001.1175>
- Marzluff, J. M. (2001). Worldwide urbanization and its effects on birds. In J. M. Marzluff, R. Bowman, & R. Donnelly (Eds.), *Avian Ecology and Conservation in an Urbanizing World* (pp. 19–47). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-1531-9_2
- Méndez, A., Montalvo, T., Aymí, R., Carmona, M., Figuerola, J., & Navarro, J. (2020). Adapting to urban ecosystems: Unravelling the foraging ecology of an opportunistic predator living in cities. *Urban Ecosystems*, 23(5), 1117–1126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-020-00995-3>
- Murray, M. H., Kidd, A. D., Curry, S. E., Hepinstall-Cymerman, J., Yabsley, M. J., Adams, H. C., Ellison, T., Welch, C. N., & Hernandez, S. M. (2018). From wetland specialist to hand-fed generalist: Shifts in diet and condition with provisioning for a recently urbanized wading bird. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 373(1745), 20170100. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2017.0100>
- Navarro, J., Oro, D., Bertolero, A., Genovart, M., Delgado, A., & Forero, M. G. (2010). Age and sexual differences in the exploitation of two anthropogenic food resources for an opportunistic seabird. *Marine Biology*, 157(11), 2453–2459. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-010-1509-2>
- Oro, D. (2020). *Perturbation, Behavioural Feedbacks, and Population Dynamics in Social Animals: When to leave and where to go* (1st ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198849834.001.0001>
- Oro, D., Genovart, M., Tavecchia, G., Fowler, M. S., & Martínez-Abraín, A. (2013). Ecological and evolutionary implications of food subsidies from humans. *Ecology Letters*, 16(12), 1501–1514. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12187>

- Oro, D., Jover, L., & Ruiz, X. (1996). Influence of trawling activity on the breeding ecology of a threatened seabird, Audouin's gull *Larus audouinii*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 139, 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps139019>
- Oro, D., & Ruiz, X. (1997). Exploitation of trawler discards by breeding seabirds in the north-western Mediterranean: Differences between the Ebro Delta and the Balearic Islands areas. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 54(4), 695–707. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmsc.1997.0246>
- Oro, D., Ruiz, X., Jover, L., Pedrocchi, V., & González-Solís, J. (1997). Diet and adult time budgets of Audouin's Gull *Larus audouinii* in response to changes in commercial fisheries. *Ibis*, 139(4), 631–637. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.1997.tb04685.x>
- Ouled-Cheikh, J., Morera-Pujol, V., Bahillo, Á., Ramírez, F., Cerdà-Cuellar, M., & Ramos, R. (2021). Foraging in the Anthropocene: Feeding plasticity of an opportunistic predator revealed by long term monitoring. *Ecological Indicators*, 129, 107943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107943>
- Ouled-Cheikh, J., Sanpera, C., Bécares, J., Arcos, J. M., Carrasco, J. L., & Ramírez, F. (2020). Spatiotemporal analyses of tracking data reveal fine-scale, daily cycles in seabird–fisheries interactions. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, fsaa098. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsaa098>
- Parra, J., & Tellería, J. L. (2004). The increase in the Spanish population of Griffon Vulture *Gyps fulvus* during 1989–1999: Effects of food and nest site availability. *Bird Conservation International*, 14(01). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0959270904000048>
- Parra-Torres, Y., Ramírez, F., Afán, I., Aguzzi, J., Bouten, W., Forero, M. G., & Navarro, J. (2020). Behavioral rhythms of an opportunistic predator living in anthropogenic landscapes. *Movement Ecology*, 8(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40462-020-00205-x>
- Pauly, D., Christensen, V., Guenette, S., Pitcher, T., Sumaila, R., Walters, C., Watson, R., & Zeller, D. (2002). Towards sustainability in world fisheries. *Nature*, 418, 689–695. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01017>
- Pebesma, E. (2023). sf: Simple Features for R: Standardized Support for Spatial Vector Data. <https://r-spatial.github.io/sf/>, <https://github.com/r-spatial/sf>
- Pierotti, R., & Annett, C. A. (1990). Diet and Reproductive Output in Seabirds. *BioScience*, 40(8), 568–574. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1311297>
- Pinaud, D., Cherel, Y., & Weimerskirch, H. (2005). Effect of environmental variability on habitat selection, diet, provisioning behaviour and chick growth in yellow-nosed albatrosses. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 298, 295–304. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps298295>
- Richard, G., Bonnel, J., Tixier, P., Arnould, J. P. Y., Janc, A., & Guinet, C. (2020). Evidence of deep-sea interactions between toothed whales and longlines. *Ambio*, 49(1), 173–186. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-019-01155-4>
- Ruiz, X., Oro, D., Martínez-Vilalta, A., & Jover, L. (1996). Feeding Ecology of Audouin's Gulls (*Larus audouinii*) in the Ebro Delta. *Colonial Waterbirds*, 19, 68. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1521947>
- Salon, S., Cossarini, G., Bolzon, G., Feudale, L., Lazzari, P., Teruzzi, A., Solidoro, C., & Crise, A. (2019). Marine Ecosystem forecasts: Skill performance of the CMEMS Mediterranean Sea model system. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-2018-145>
- Sanpera, C., Moreno, R., Ruiz, X., & Jover, L. (2007). Audouin's gull chicks as bioindicators of mercury pollution at different breeding locations in the western Mediterranean. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 54(6), 691–696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2007.01.016>
- Sommerfeld, J., Mendel, B., Fock, H. O., & Garthe, S. (2016). Combining bird-borne tracking and vessel monitoring system data to assess discard use by a scavenging marine predator, the lesser black-

- backed gull *Larus fuscus*. *Marine Biology*, 163(5), 116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-016-2866-4>
- Stithou, M., Vassilopoulou, V., Tsagarakis, K., Edridge, A., Machias, A., Maniopoulou, M., Dogrammatzi, A., Bellido, J. M., Carbonara, P., Carbonell, A., & Lembo, G. (2019). Discarding in Mediterranean trawl fisheries—A review of potential measures and stakeholder insights. *Maritime Studies*, 18(2), 225–238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40152-018-00131-0>
- Tablado, Z., Tella, J. L., Sánchez-Zapata, J. A., & Hiraldo, F. (2010). The Paradox of the Long-Term Positive Effects of a North American Crayfish on a European Community of Predators: Effects of an Invasive Crayfish. *Conservation Biology*, 24(5), 1230–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2010.01501.x>
- Valavanis, V. D., Kapantagakis, A., Kataras, I., & Palialexis, A. (2004). Critical regions: A GIS-based model of marine productivity hotspots. *Aquatic Sciences*, 66(1), 139–148. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-003-0703-x>
- Vaz, Y., & Nunes, T. (2007). The New Diseases and the Old Agents. In M. S. Pereira (Ed.), *A Portrait of State-of-the-Art Research at the Technical University of Lisbon* (pp. 465–477). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5690-1_29
- Watson, R., Kitchingman, A., Gelchu, A., & Pauly, D. (2004). Mapping global fisheries: Sharpening our focus. *Fish and Fisheries*, 5(2), 168–177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2004.00142.x>

8.5 Case Study 25. Biologging as a tool for the conservation/management of protected and conservation-interest species

Giancarlo Lauriano, Tomaso Fortibuoni

8.5.1 Introduction

Potentials of biologging: what can be learnt

Biologging refers to the practice of deploying devices on animal bodies to record various aspects of their behaviour, physiology, or environment, including tracking their movements that would otherwise be difficult to observe. Understanding the movement patterns of free-ranging animals is crucial for assessing their habitat use and is, therefore, a prerequisite for developing effective conservation management strategies. Animal-borne monitoring instruments or satellite telemetry can provide valuable insights into the ecology of different taxa of marine mega-fauna and has been applied towards different species ranging from tunas, sharks, seabirds, pinnipeds, sea turtles and cetaceans (Block et al., 2011).

The need to understand animal, particularly whale, movements across the ocean dates to the era of the whaling industry. Studies into the seasonal movements of large whales utilised a method involving the attachment of numbered tags to individuals, which were subsequently recovered during whaling operations (Brown, 1978). The first experiment in marking whales appears to be that of a Japanese whaling captain, Amano, who fired a 'marking rod' into a Blue whale (*Balaenoptera musculus*) off the Japanese coast in February 1910. The individual was captured two years later, in June 1912 (Omura and Ohsumi, 1964). The recovery of these tags, along with the analysis of historical whaling artefacts (Scammon, 1874), provided essential geographic data, allowing for preliminary assessments of whale distribution and population dynamics.

Animal-borne telemetry has seen a significant general increase in utilisation over the past decade across a wide range of environments and taxa. This technology provides crucial data for the management of species and their habitats, ultimately contributing to more effective conservation efforts (Hays et al., 2019).

Among the various examples of animal-borne telemetry used in different areas of the world, which have illuminated numerous aspects of animal behaviour, we can recall the ones briefly mentioned below.

Novel long migratory path patterns characterised by frequent pauses over seamounts of the Endangered South Pacific humpback whales (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) have been discovered (Garrigue et al., 2015).

The migratory routes and breeding grounds of the critically endangered Western North Pacific gray whales (WGWs) (*Eschrichtius robustus*) from Russia's Sakhalin Island were previously unknown. However, the use of satellite-monitored tags on WGWs revealed that some individuals migrate towards the breeding areas of non-endangered Eastern North Pacific gray whales (EGWs) off the coast of Baja California, Mexico. These findings suggest that some whales previously identified as WGWs may be EGWs foraging in areas historically associated with the Western population (Mate et al., 2015). Furthermore, beyond tracking movements, telemetry provides valuable ecological insights. It informs conservation efforts, as is the case of the North Pacific right whales (*Eubalaena japonica*), where Zerbini et al. (2015) found that environmental factors influence the movement patterns of these whales in the Southeastern Bering Sea. Still, in the Chukchi Sea, telemetry has documented the spatial and temporal habitat use of bowhead whales (*Balaena mysticetus*) during their seasonal migration, highlighting an overlap between their movements and an oil and gas lease area in the Arctic (Quakenbush et al., 2010). Moreover, telemetry studies were crucial in identifying priority areas for conservation and determining the overlap between blue whale (*Balaenoptera musculus*) movements and vessel traffic off northern Chilean Patagonia (Bedriñana-Romano et al., 2021) as well as mitigating collisions between blue whales (*Balaenoptera musculus*) and vessels in the US West Coast using determining which areas along the coast are most important (Irvine et al., 2014).

However, the above examples indicate that the study necessitated tracking the animals for extended periods, therefore requiring the use of invasive instruments. These require implantation in the dermal/hypodermal tissue, or penetration and anchoring at or below the blubber-muscle interface (Andrews et al., 2019), which can have potential consequences for the health and vital rates of tagged animals (Weller, 2008).

Nevertheless, while telemetry and biologging provide vital data for research and conservation, these methods can induce adverse effects on whale behaviour, health, reproduction, and survival (Weller, 2008). The wounds from transmitter deployment can cause pain, discomfort, and opportunistic infections. Thus, animal welfare concerns arise, and the implementation of these methods requires careful ethical and scientific justification.

8.5.2 Methods

8.6.2.1 Methods of tagging

According to Andrews et al. (2019), it is possible to identify three main types of tags ([Figure 8.5.1](#)): anchored, bolt-on and consolidated, respectively Type A, B and C, to which correspond different package characteristics, life span, data achieved and method of deployment and tagging.

The (A) Low Impact Minimally Percutaneous Electronic Transmitter (LIMPET) is the smallest in size and the lighter among the tag; these characteristics generally allow the deployment on the dorsal fin to facilitate frequent transmissions to the Argos satellites when animal surface. The electronics package is external to the skin, attached by one or more anchors that puncture and terminate below the skin. The LIMPET can have two configurations related to the possibility of describing just the horizontal movement - SPOT and the SPLASH designed for vertical tracking beside the horizontal activities.

The (B) Finmount is ideal for small cetaceans, but the animal needs to be captured to install the tag on the dorsal fin using one or more bolts.

The (C) Cetacea Transdermal is also known as implantable tag since it goes deep in the animal’s body, hitting the blubber and muscle. Both the electronics and retention elements are merged into an implanted anchor. C type are the largest tags, and dimensions can reach up to 300 L x 24 D mm. Consequently, the deployment can produce wounds and cause pain and discomfort (Gulland et al., 2024).

Figure 8.5.1. The main different tag types and the attachment design (from Andrews et al., 2019).

Case Studies of LIMPET and Transdermal Tag Use: Fin Whales in the Mediterranean Sea and Killer Whales in the Ross Sea, Antarctica

Killer whale - Satellite telemetry studies using Low-Impact Minimally Percutaneous Electronic Transmitters (LIMPETs) were conducted from the Italian research station at the Baia Terranova (Ross Sea, Antarctica) from mid-January to mid-February 2015 to investigate the Ross Sea Killer Whale (*Orcinus orca*) (RSKW) habitat use.

Ross killer whale is a fish-eating dwarf ecotype (Pitman & Ensor, 2003; Ainley et al., 2009), mainly distributed along coastal areas along the fast ice edge.

Up to the last decade, low scarce information on RSKW occurrence, distribution and movements was available and was mostly limited to the austral summer and to the US research station at the McMurdo Sound (Ainley et al., 2009; Pitman et al., 2019).

These transmitters provide animal locations via the Argos system (<http://www.Argos-system.org>). Each transmitter was equipped with two darts (68 mm long) containing two sets of six outward-folding petals to enhance retention within the animal and prevent dart expulsion.

The transmitters were mounted on 20-inch carbon fibre crossbow bolts for deployment on the dorsal fins of adult specimens of both sexes considered to be in good health. A recurve crossbow with a 150 lb draw weight was used, and a shooting distance of up to 9 meters was considered optimal for successful deployment.

Daily activities to locate killer whales involved helicopter flight surveys along the ice edge in areas frequented by the RSKW (Lauriano et al., 2011). Once a pod of killer whales was spotted, the helicopter proceeded in their direction of travel to find a suitable landing site in proximity, allowing personnel to easily and safely access the ice edge where the pod was expected to pass.

The instruments were programmed to transmit 600 times over 17 hours per day across three-time windows: 02:00-04:00, 06:00-17:00, and 19:00-21:00. These time windows were selected to maximize data transmission efficiency based on the availability of Argos satellites in the study area during the study period.

Fin whale - *Balaenoptera physalus* is the only common baleen whale occurring in the Mediterranean Sea. The presence of the species has been debated for a long time; genetic evidence indicates that individuals from the Mediterranean are distinct from the ones sampled in the Atlantic. Moreover, acoustic data revealed the presence of two clusters: *i*) a true Mediterranean population and *ii*) the Northeast North Atlantic (NENA) population. According to the isolation from the Atlantic conspecific and facing a continuous decline with a low number of mature individuals, the Mediterranean fin whale is classified as a subpopulation and listed as Endangered (IUCN) (Panigada et al., 2021).

In such a context, the movement and distribution of true Mediterranean animals become crucial for conservation and management purposes. The species' ability to locate and exploit available dispersed food resources in the Mediterranean Sea throughout the seasons is acknowledged (di Sciara et al., 2016), and two main feeding areas have been indicated. In the summer season, fin whale nourishes themselves in the Liguro-Provençal Basin, which hosts up to one-third of the Mediterranean

population (Forcada et al., 1995; Forcada et al., 1996) recently estimated at 3,200 individuals (Panigada et al., 2024). Meanwhile, a winter-feeding area is known to occur between Tunisia and Sicily around Lampedusa Island (Canese et al., 2006).

Considering the above-mentioned knowledge, a study on the movement of the species implementing telemetry began in 2012 in the Pelagos area and has been extended up to 2015, including activity in the Lampedusa Island area (Panigada et al., 2017). Fin whale movement and habitat use were investigated using both LIMPET and transdermal tags. These two transmitters have different configurations, dimensions, and weights and, therefore, require different attachment methods. The transdermal transmitter was deployed using a custom-modified airgun, while the smaller and lighter LIMPET tag was deployed with a 150 lb crossbow. Furthermore, based on the length of the dart (see Fig. 1), the transdermal tag can only be placed dorsally on the animal's body, whereas LIMPET tags are best placed on the dorsal fin. Tagging operations were performed from an inflatable boat equipped with an outboard engine. A driver, a researcher involved in the photo-identification of the individuals, and the tagger were all present in the boat. This configuration was considered optimal for the activities due to the need for an open view of the area (fewer personnel on board), easy manoeuvrability (small boat), and the requirement to follow up on the tagging deployment (photographer).

8.5.2.2 Methods of data analysis

The Argos satellite tracking data analyses are performed via the Bayesian hierarchical switching statespace models (hSSSM) (Jonsen et al., 2013; Jonsen et al., 2005).

By means of the hSSSM, the behavioural state of the tagged animals can be classified as transiting or area-restricted search (ARS). The first class occurs when the actions of the individual have high persistence (i.e. high autocorrelation in speed and angle) and a low turning angle, the opposite in the ARS circumstance (low persistence and high turning) (Jonsen et al., 2005). The ARS is trusted when feeding is occurring (Kareiva and Odell, 1987).

8.5.3 Results

Killer whale—Ten RSKW have been tagged out of 13 attempts with 6 SPOT and 4 SPLASH tags. The initial data collected from the ARGOS system were useful for further deployments since locating the individuals in real-time after deployments was possible.

Two main groups were considered according to the ARGOS positions received: 8,803 locations were fitted in the hSSSM. No evident and permanent reactions to tag deployment were observed, and only

short-term responses were seen, indicating that the tagging deployment did not alter the whales' overall behaviour or residency in the area.

Animals tagged in Closs Bay, belonging to a 25-individual group, exhibited consistent ARS behaviour for 8 days (Fig. 2). They then travelled north along the coast, displaying ARS activity near Mariner Glacier tongue and Coulman Island, from where continuing north, they next left the Ross Sea coastline on 25 January. Finally, in the open sea area, no further ARS have been observed.

Similarly to the animals tagged in the first pod, a second RSKW cluster of 20 individuals showed ARS behaviour for 2 days in Closs Bay, where they have been tagged. They travelled north to Lady Newness Bay on 28 January but returned to Closs Bay the same day, where ARS activity resumed.

Figure 8.5.2. The overall Ross Sea Killer Whale tracks and the behavioural state in the three areas (Closs Bay- light blue, Ross Sea coast – light red, offshore - green) (from Lauriano et al., 2020).

ARS behaviour in Closs Bay typically resulted in a back-and-forth movement between the two main locations that define Closs Bay which are approximately 30 km apart only (area located in the bottom left of the figure. in Figure 8.5.2).

Moreover, both tracked groups exhibited deep dives (up to 292 m in Closs Bay for Group 1 and up to 452 m in Lady Newnes Bay for Group 2) (Figure 8.5.3) in these locations where ARS behaviour has been detected by the hSSSM results, hence suggesting foraging activity in these two main areas along the Ross Sea coast. On the contrary, once the individuals left the Ross Sea coast, deep dives became less frequent.

Figure 8.5.3 - Dive depths of two individuals from Groups 1 and 2 (from Lauriano et al., 2020).

The overall movement of the tagged individuals ended in the New Zealand subtropical waters after 4,900 km of travelling (Figure 8.5.2).

The results were also evaluated in light of the experience and research activities conducted by American colleagues at McMurdo Station (around 350 km from the Italian research Station), who tagged individuals of the same ecotype as well as other ecotypes (A, B1, B2) (Pitman and Ensor, 2003; Durban et al., 2016) in the Antarctic Peninsula area. By combining data from the Ross Sea area and comparing it with data from the Antarctic Peninsula, it was possible to identify a consistent south-north and *vice versa* movement pattern across all studied ecotypes. The conclusion was that these individuals have a physiological need to undertake periodic trips to warm waters for skin maintenance, which has been indicated as a main driver for long-distance movement (Pitman et al., 2020).

Fin whale – Between 2012 and 2015, 13 fin whales were tagged in the Pelagos Sanctuary and the Strait of Sicily. As expected, the lifespan of the five transdermal tags averaged 45 days, which was greater than the eight LIMPET tags (29 days).

Fin whales tagged in the Pelagos area at the end of the well-known feeding period exhibited Area Restricted Search Behaviour 66% of the time (Figure 8.5.4). The ARS behaviour was mostly confined to the tagging area and extended towards the Balearic Islands. The evidence of feeding activity in late summer and fall supports the presence of favourable feeding conditions in the area even outside of the summer period, confirming the awareness of species' capacity to take advantage of dispersed food resources in the oligotrophic Mediterranean (di Sciara et al., 2016).

Similarly, in the Strait of Sicily, besides some tagged animals exhibiting movements towards the southern coast of Sicily and northern Tunisia, a high rate of ARS behaviour (65%) was displayed around the Island of Lampedusa in early spring (March).

The information obtained regarding the species' preference for the two feeding areas, the Pelagos Sanctuary in the north and the Strait of Sicily in the south of the Mediterranean basin, is corroborated by the observation that individuals tagged in the Strait of Sicily, after an initial feeding period, undertook a transit northward. This movement ceases precisely in the Sanctuary, where the feeding activity phase begins (Figure 8.5.4).

Figure 8.5.4 - The tracks of fin whales tagged in the Ligurian Sea (2012) and in the Strait of Sicily (2013 and 2015), along with estimates of the transiting (blue), ARS (yellow) and uncertain (grey) behaviours (from Panigada et al., 2017).

8.5.3.1 Animal welfare issues and guidelines for tagging

Satellite telemetry methods raise significant ethical and animal welfare concerns that must be carefully considered before undertaking any research activity. While this technology offers invaluable data, its application must be preceded by a scrupulous evaluation of the potential negative impacts on the animals and the safety risks for the personnel involved (Gales et al., 2009; Andrews et al., 2019).

Generally, three principles guide the different codes of conduct: **replacement, reduction and refinement** (Russell et al., 1959).

Replacement deals with the use of alternative study methods which totally or partially replace the use of the animal. Nevertheless, replacement is not always an option in cetacean research; therefore, it becomes imperative to clearly define the research objectives and thoroughly evaluate all available alternative methodologies to achieve them. Satellite telemetry should only be considered when less

invasive techniques cannot provide the necessary information. The choice of transmitter type is crucial: suction cup tags generally involve a lesser disturbance, limited to the approach manoeuvres, as they do not require invasive anchoring via darts; however, they are limited in the quantity and duration of obtainable information. Conversely, anchored and implantable tags have a potentially greater and more critical impact due to the penetration of darts and/or barbs of varying lengths into the animal's tissues. The application of anchored transmitters can negatively impact individuals at both physiological and behavioural levels. Dart penetration, even if the darts are small, causes wounds affecting the skin and blubber layer in anchored tags, but can also reach the muscle tissue in implantable tags, which can have lengths of 20-30 cm. Precise tag placement and barbs penetration site are fundamental to minimise the risk of haemorrhaging and tissue damage. Excessive firing power during application can increase the risk of trauma or even breakage of the barb or the transmitter's electronic components.

Furthermore, it is recognised that the entire tagging operation, from the vessel's approach to the tag application and the subsequent presence of the transmitter on the animal body, can induce a physiological stress response, resulting in increased stress-related hormones (Weller, 2008). Behaviourally, the response can be immediate, manifesting as startle reactions, sudden dives, or changes in swimming direction and/or speed (Amano et al., 2003). Studies on sperm whales tagged with suction cups have shown shorter and shallower dives, although approaches with whale-watching vessels have also induced similar behavioural responses.

The number of samples should be taken at the minimum necessary to achieve the goal. This means the **reduction** of the animals involved in the research and defines an achievable sample size. In some cases, to avoid stress on individuals belonging to endangered species, it is possible to refer to other species that share the same ecological characteristics.

Finally, **refinement** of the scientific research method is requested to ensure the scientific validity of studies, hence minimising the negative impact on animals.

So, considering the above, the tagging guidelines[1] comprise several key elements that need careful consideration and adherence; these range from animal choice to personnel, boat operations, equipment selection, and deployment. Here is a summary.

Tag Selection: Anchored/implantable

Procedures at Sea: Approach manoeuvres, individual selection, and tag application must be conducted by personnel experienced in the behaviour of the studied species (both the tagger and the vessel operator). Knowledge of dive times and surfacing sequences is fundamental to minimising the disturbance caused by the approach.

- **Selection of Individuals for Tagging:** Target individuals should be adult specimens in good physical condition, without evident signs of emaciation or recent and/or healed wounds on their body.
- **Approach Procedures:** The approach to the individual must be carried out cautiously, at low speed, avoiding sudden accelerations and changes in course, and carefully monitoring the behaviour of the animals present. The ideal approach should not be frontal or from behind, but lateral. Greater caution is required in the presence of groups with subadult or neonate individuals and mother-calf pairs.
- **Disturbance Limitation:** A forced and prolonged approach to the target individual is inherently a disturbing element that must have a limit. Experienced personnel must be able to assess when the animal's behaviour (increased swimming speed, more frequent dives, and overall alteration of surface behaviour) indicates the need to discontinue further approach attempts.
- **Environmental Conditions:** Sea conditions are a determining factor in the success of operations, the safety of personnel, and the minimisation of disturbance. The absence of waves, wind, or rain, i.e. optimal visibility, are fundamental elements.
- **Follow-up:** Where possible, post-application monitoring is important to assess the impact of the tag on the animal and its functionality. This can be done through photographic and/or video material that allows documentation of the operation and subsequent individual recognition for the purpose of studying tag evolution.

The adoption of a well-defined working protocol based on these guidelines is essential to ensure that satellite telemetry studies are conducted ethically, maximizing scientific benefits while minimizing the potential negative impacts on the welfare of the studied species

8.5.4 Discussion

In summary, the two case studies, Killer and Fin whale, effectively illustrate the power of satellite telemetry as a method for studying marine animals. Its advantage lies in its capacity to reveal crucial information about their medium- and long-term movements and habitat use, which is indispensable for management and conservation actions.

Animal-borne electronic instruments are valuable tools for collecting data on various aspects of cetaceans, ranging from behaviour to habitat use and even physiology. These methods become particularly important in a management and conservation context, allowing the study of individual responses to anthropogenic threats. Moreover, tags offer a significant advantage over other observation methods since they provide data that is not influenced by the observer and is not collected intermittently. However, the widespread use of this methodology also poses risks to the health and welfare of cetaceans, as well as to the personnel involved in tag deployment operations.

So, ethical, scientific, and logistical considerations are needed, and the decision of whether to proceed with the tagging activity should be based on a trade-off analysis.

The application of satellite telemetry has proven to be an indispensable tool for gaining critical insights into the ecology and behaviour of cetaceans, **insights often unattainable through other methods**. The two case studies presented, related to fin and killer whales, demonstrated the practical applications of different tagging technologies (LIMPET and transdermal tags) and the specific ecological insights gained for each species and region. Key goals achievable through satellite telemetry include understanding cetacean ecology beyond basic distribution, encompassing intricate details of habitat use, migratory patterns, and even behavioural states. Given the unprecedented opportunities this technology offers for informing conservation and management strategies, ethical considerations and adherence to rigorous guidelines are paramount to minimise potential impacts on animal welfare. To this end, the several guidelines as well as practical codes of conduct available are based on the application of the three Rs principles, which guide researchers in defining and adopting the best scientific technologies to mitigate negative impacts on individuals while achieving the research goal.

8.5.5 References

- ACCOBAMS. (2010). Guidelines on the granting of exceptions to Article II, paragraph 1, for the purpose of non-lethal in situ research in the Agreement area. <https://doi.org/10.70978/LFOD5904>
- Ainley, D., Ballard, G., & Olmastroni, S. (2009). An apparent decrease in the Prevalence of 'Ross Sea Killer Whales' in the Southern Ross Sea. *Aquatic Mammals*, 35, 335–347. <https://doi.org/10.1578/am.35.3.2009.334>
- Amano, M., & Yoshioka, M. (2003). Sperm whale diving behavior monitored using a suction-cup-attached TDR tag. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.*, 258, 291–295. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps258291>
- Andrews, R. D., Baird, R. W., Calambokidis, J., Goertz, C. E. C., Gulland, F. M. D., Heide-Jørgensen, M. P., Huggins, J. L., Laidre, K. L., LeDuc, R. G., Lunsford, C. R., Norman, S. A., Oliver, J. S., Raverty, S. A., Shelden, K. E. W., Silber, G. K., & Zerbini, A. N. (2019). Best practice guidelines for cetacean tagging. *J. Cetac. Res. and Manag.*, 20, 27–66. <https://doi.org/10.47536/jcrm.v20i0.513>
- Andrews, R. D., Pitman, R. L., & Ballance, L. T. (2008). Satellite tracking reveals distinct movement patterns for type B and type C killer whales in the southern Ross Sea, Antarctica. *Polar Biology*, 31, 1461–1468. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-008-0487-z>
- Bedriñana-Romano, L., Huccke-Gaete, R., Viddi, F. A., Johnson, D., Zerbini, A. N., Morales, J., Guzmán, H. M., Pavez, G., Canales, C., Abreu, M., & Palacios, D. M. (2021). Defining priority areas for blue whale conservation and investigating overlap with vessel traffic in Chilean Patagonia, using a fast-fitting movement model. *Scient Rep.*, 11(1), 2709. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82244-3>
- Block, B. A., Jonsen, I. D., Jorgensen, S. J., Winship, A. J., Shaffer, S. A., Bograd, S. J., ... Costa, D. P. (2011). Tracking apex marine predator movements in a dynamic ocean. *Nature*, 475, 86–90. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10082>
- Brown, S. G. (1978). Whale marking techniques. In *Animal Marking* (pp. 71–80). Palgrave, London.

- Canese, S., Cardinali, A., Fortuna, C. M., Giusti, M., Lauriano, G., Salvati, E., & Greco, S. (2006). The first identified winter feeding ground of fin whales (*Balaenoptera physalus*) in the Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 86(4), 903-907.
- Di Sciara, G. N., Castellote, M., Druon, J. N., & Panigada, S. (2016). Fin whales, *Balaenoptera physalus*: at home in a changing Mediterranean Sea?. *Advances in marine biology*, 75, 75-101
- Durban, J. W., Fearnbach, H., Burrows, D. G., Ylitalo, G. M., & Pitman, R. L. (2016). Morphological and ecological evidence for two sympatric forms of Type B killer whale around the Antarctic Peninsula. *Polar Biology*, 40, 231–236.
- Gales, N. J., Bowen, W. D., Johnston, D. W., Kovacs, K. M., Littnan, C. L., Perrin, W. F., ... & Thompson, P. M. (2009). Guidelines for the treatment of marine mammals in field research. *Marine Mammal Science*, 25(3), 725-736.
- Garrigue, C., Clapham, P. J., Geyer, Y., Kennedy, A. S., & Zerbini, A. N. (2015). Satellite tracking reveals novel migratory patterns and the importance of seamounts for endangered South Pacific humpback whales. *Royal Society open science*, 2(11), 150489.
- Gulland, F. M., Robbins, J., Zerbini, A. N., Andrews-Goff, V., Bérubé, M., Clapham, P. J., ... & Vanstreels, R. E. (2024). Effects of satellite-linked telemetry tags on humpback whales in the Gulf of Maine: Photographic assessment of tag sites. *bioRxiv*, 2024-02.
- Hays, G.C., Bailey, H., Bograd, S.J., Bowen, W.D., Campagna, C., Carmichael, R.H., Casale, P., Chiaradia, A., Costa, D.P., Cuevas, E., Nico de Bruyn P.J., Dias, M.P., Duarte, C.M., Dunn, D.C., Dutton, P.H., Esteban, N., Friedlaender, A., Goetz, K.T., Godley, B.J., Halpin, P.N., Hamann, M., Hammerschlag, N., Harcourt, R., Harrison, A-L., Hazen, E.L., Heupel, M.R., Hoyt, E., Humphries, N.E., Kot, C.Y., Lea, J.S.E., Marsh, H., Maxwell, S.M., McMahon, C.R., Notarbartolo di Sciara, G., Pelacios, D.M., ...& Sequeira, A.M.M. (2019). Translating marine animal tracking data into conservation policy and management. *Ecol. Evol.* 34(5): 459–473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.01.009>
- International Whaling Commission. (2020). *Report of the Joint US Office of Naval Research, International Whaling Commission and US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration workshop on cetacean tag development, tag follow-up and tagging best practices. Journal of Cetacean Research and Management*, 21(Suppl.).
- Irvine, L. M., Mate, B. R., Winsor, M. H., Palacios, D. M., Bograd, S. J., Costa, D. P., & Bailey, H. (2014). Spatial and temporal occurrence of blue whales off the US West Coast, with implications for management. *PLoS One*, 9(7), e102959. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0102959>
- Jonsen, I. D., Flemming, J., & Myers, R. A. (2005). Robust state–space modelling of animal movement data. *Ecology*, 86, 2874–2880. <https://doi.org/10.1890/04-1852>
- Jonsen, I. D., Flemming, J. M., & Myers, R. A. (2005). Robust state–space modeling of animal movement data. *Ecology*, 86(11), 2874-2880. <https://doi.org/10.1890/04-1852>
- Jonsen, I. D., Basson, M., Bestley, S., Bravington, M. V., Patterson, T. A., Pedersen, M. W., ... & Wotherspoon, S. J. (2013). State-space models for bio-loggers: A methodological road map. *Deep Sea Res. Part II: Topical Stud in Oceanogr.*, 88, 34-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2012.07.008>
- Kareiva, P., & Odell, G. (1987). Swarms of predators exhibit "preytaxis" if individual predators use area-restricted search. *The American Naturalist*, 130(2), 233-270. <https://doi.org/10.1086/284707>
- Kareiva, P., & Odell, G. (1987). Swarms of predators exhibit 'preytaxis' if individual predators use area-restricted search. *The American Naturalist*, 130, 233–270. <https://doi.org/10.1086/284707>
- Lauriano, G., Pirodda, E., Joyce, T., Pitman, R. L., Borrell, A., & Panigada, S. (2020). Movements, diving behaviour and diet of type-C killer whales (*Orcinus orca*) in the Ross Sea, Antarctica. *Aquatic Conservat: Mar. & Freshw. Ecosystems*, 30(12), 2428-2440. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3429>

- Lauriano, G., Fortuna, C. M., & Vacchi, M. (2011). Occurrence of killer whales (*Orcinus orca*) and other cetaceans in Terra Nova Bay, Ross Sea, Antarctica. *Antarctic science*, 23(2), 139-143. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102010000704>
- Mate, B. R., Ilyashenko, V. Y., Bradford, A. L., Vertyankin, V. V., Tsidulko, G. A., Rozhnov, V. V., & Irvine, L. M. (2015). Critically endangered western gray whales migrate to the eastern North Pacific. *Biology letters*, 11(4), 20150071. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0071>
- Mate, B., (2013). Offshore Gray Whale Satellite Tagging in the Pacific Northwest. Prepared for Commander, U.S. Pacific Fleet, Pearl Harbor, Hawaii. Submitted to Naval Facilities Engineering Command Northwest (NAVFAC NW), Silverdale, WA 98315-1101, under Contract # N62470-10-D-3011, issued to HDR Inc., San Diego, California 92123. 18 June 2013
- Omura, H., & Ohsumi, S. (1964). A review of Japanese whale marking in the North Pacific to the end of 1962, with some information on marking in the Antarctic. *Norsk Hvalfangst-Tidende*, 4, 90-112.
- Panigada, S., Pierantonio, N., Araújo, H., David, L., Di-Méglia, N., Dorémus, G., Gonzalvo, J., Holcer, D., Laran, S., Lauriano, G., Paiu, R-M., Perri, M., Popov, D., Ridoux, V., Vázquez, J.A., & Cañadas, A. (2024). The ACCOBAMS Survey Initiative: the first synoptic assessment of cetacean abundance in the Mediterranean Sea through aerial surveys. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10, 1270513. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1270513>
- Panigada, S., Donovan, G. P., Druon, J. N., Lauriano, G., Pierantonio, N., Pirota, E., ... & di Sciara, G. N. (2017). Satellite tagging of Mediterranean fin whales: working towards the identification of critical habitats and the focussing of mitigation measures. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 3365.
- Panigada S, Gauffier P, Notarbartolo di Sciara G. 2021 Balaenoptera physalus Mediterranean subpopulation. IUCN Red List Threat. Species (2021) e.T16208224A50387979. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2021-3.RLTS.T16208224A50387979.en>
- Pitman, R. L., & Ensor, P. (2003). Three forms of killer whales (*Orcinus orca*) in Antarctic waters. *Journal of Cetacean Research and Management*, 5, 1–9.
- Pitman, R. L., Durban, J. W., Joyce, T., Fearnbach, H., Panigada, S., & Lauriano, G. (2020). Skin in the game: Epidermal molt as a driver of long-distance migration in whales. *Marine Mammal Science*, 36(2), 565-594.
- Quakenbush, L. T., Citta, J. J., George, J. C., Small, R. J., & Heide-Jørgensen, M. P. (2010). Fall and winter movements of bowhead whales (*Balaena mysticetus*) in the Chukchi Sea and within a potential petroleum development area. *Arctic*, 289-307
- Russell, W. and Burch, R. 1959. *The Principles of Humane Experimental Technique*. Methuen, London. xiv + 238pp.
- Scammon, C. M. (1874). *The Marine Mammals of the North-Western Coast of Nord-America: Described and Illustrated: Together with an Account of the American Whale-fishery*. John H. Carmany.
- Society for Marine Mammalogy. (n.d.). *Guideline for treatment of marine mammals*. <https://marinemammalscience.org/about-us/ethics/marine-mammal-treatment-guidelines/>
- Weller, D.W. (2008). Report of the Large Whale Tagging Workshop convened by the U.S. Marine Mammal Commission and the U.S. National Marine Fisheries Service, San Diego, California.
- Zerbini AN, Baumgartner MF, Kennedy AS, Rone BK, Wade PR, Clapham PJ (2015) Space use patterns of the endangered North Pacific right whale *Eubalaena japonica* in the Bering Sea. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 532:269-281. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps11366>

9. Discussion

This deliverable provides a comprehensive review and evaluation of methods for the monitoring, risk assessment, and management of key ecological threats under the MSFD, namely HABs, IAS, jellyfish blooms, and impacts on top predators, in the context of cumulative anthropogenic pressures and climate change. The 26 case studies presented (25 in the main text and 1 as annex) across different European marine subregions illustrate the heterogeneity of challenges and the varying maturity of existing monitoring frameworks, analytical tools, and institutional coordination across Member States.

A cross-thematic analysis reveals both common and issue-specific methodological constraints. For HABs and jellyfish blooms, critical gaps remain in early warning systems, real-time monitoring, and cross-jurisdictional standardization. While **remote sensing** and citizen science can enhance spatial and temporal coverage, technological, financial, and institutional limitations continue to hinder widespread adoption.

The case studies highlight the **multifactorial and site-specific nature of HAB dynamics**, with temperature, salinity, and nutrient concentrations—particularly dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP) and nitrogen (DIN)—emerging as consistently important environmental drivers. While nutrients are clearly linked to bloom magnitude and distribution, physical variables often exert a stronger or more predictable influence, reflecting their indirect role in modulating water column stability and stratification. However, the relative importance of these drivers varies across regions and species, reinforcing the need for localized thresholds and species-specific understanding, which will be important in the use of assessment tools and further implementation of the EBM.

Machine learning approaches have demonstrated substantial promise for predicting bloom risk and identifying key environmental controls. These models are particularly effective in regions with adequate data coverage and offer a scalable, flexible alternative to traditional ecosystem models. Despite their utility, the predictive power of such models can be constrained by inconsistencies in species responses and local hydrological conditions, underscoring the need for ongoing refinement and validation.

Satellite remote sensing has also proven to be a valuable tool for monitoring phytoplankton biomass and assessing eutrophication status, particularly in open and oligotrophic marine waters where optical interference is minimal. The integration of satellite and in-situ data enhances the spatial and temporal resolution of monitoring efforts, although optical complexity in transitional and nearshore areas remains a limitation. These observations point to the importance of regional algorithm calibration to improve accuracy in such environments. Under GES4SEAS, some lessons learned in data rich Learning

Sites (e.g. in the Atlantic) have been transferred to other Learning Sites with less data (e.g. in the Black Sea), with successful and encouraging results.

Risk patterns of HABs show clear spatial and seasonal variation, with confined and human-altered environments such as harbours and transitional waters displaying higher frequency and variability. These areas are particularly sensitive to anthropogenic pressures and hydrological modifications, which can enhance bloom conditions. Seasonal patterns, linked to environmental optima for phytoplankton growth, further suggest that monitoring and management efforts should be temporally targeted. Again, this is important from the further assessment point of view.

The case studies on **Lagrangian models** highlight how species dispersal and bloom dynamics in marine systems are strongly influenced by the interaction of biological traits, environmental conditions, and anthropogenic changes. Wind and current-driven drift, as in the case of surface-dwelling organisms, can result in large-scale episodic arrivals influenced by storm frequency and intensity, with implications for public safety and coastal economies. These events stress the need for accurate modelling of transport mechanisms, which must account for variables such as organism morphology, wind drag coefficients, and prevailing meteorological conditions.

In benthic and pelagic life cycles, habitat availability—both natural and artificial—emerges as a key driver of spatial patterns. Ocean sprawl, including infrastructure such as offshore energy installations, can alter the habitat landscape and potentially enhance bloom events by providing new substrate for life stages such as jellyfish polyps. While artificial structures may contribute to observed changes in distribution and abundance, a full understanding requires quantitative comparisons with natural substrates and consideration of substrate-specific colonization dynamics.

The importance of localized ecological processes is further evident in the case of species with limited larval dispersal, where population persistence relies on local retention and settlement. In such cases, the effectiveness of conservation strategies hinges on the spatial configuration of MPAs, particularly under scenarios of reduced dispersal potential due to climate change. Low connectivity between populations increases vulnerability, necessitating networks of MPAs that are both strategically placed and informed by species-specific larval behavior and habitat suitability.

Across these contexts, current limitations in species distribution data and behavioral parameters present challenges for robust modelling. Advancing marine spatial planning and species conservation will require integrative approaches that combine empirical data, realistic modeling assumptions, and an understanding of how human infrastructure and climate trends reshape connectivity and population dynamics in marine ecosystems.

Emerging **molecular tools** are fundamentally transforming biodiversity monitoring and risk assessment. **eDNA metabarcoding** has emerged as a highly sensitive and scalable approach for detecting both native and non-indigenous species, including rare, cryptic, or early-stage taxa that are often missed by traditional morphology-based methods. These tools are particularly valuable for early warning applications (e.g. in alien species detection) and for improving community-level ecological assessments. However, important limitations remain, such as incomplete reference databases, PCR amplification biases, and difficulties in distinguishing between living organisms and residual DNA. The lack of standardized protocols and quality assurance procedures also hampers comparability across studies and jurisdictions. Multi-marker approaches, the use of eRNA to infer organismal activity, and further refinement of bioinformatic pipelines and taxonomic libraries are necessary to enhance taxonomic resolution and ecological interpretability. Ultimately, molecular tools should be seen as **complementary** to, rather than replacements for, conventional methodologies, offering a means to increase ecological resolution and responsiveness within the MSFD framework.

The **cumulative impact of IAS, HABs, and jellyfish blooms** represents a growing ecological challenge in European seas, demanding integrative, data-driven, and regionally adaptable frameworks for assessment and management. The **CIMPAL-JH, CIMPAL+, and CIMPAL-ES** frameworks, developed through GES4SEAS, have a critical role in advancing our understanding of the spatial patterns, ecological dynamics, and management implications of these pressures. These tools, under continued refinement, provide structured, scalable approaches for evaluating both negative and positive impacts across habitats, species, and ecosystem services.

The integration of HABs and jellyfish blooms into cumulative impact assessments has proven essential, given their episodic yet intense nature, and their ability to exacerbate pre-existing ecological stressors. Unlike IAS, whose impacts are often persistent and spatially extensive, blooms are more temporally variable and require data on intensity, duration, and species-specific thresholds to be fully captured. Including such metrics—currently limited in many regions—would significantly improve the precision of impact assessments. Furthermore, the frequent co-occurrence of multiple invasive or bloom-forming species in high-impact zones underlines the importance of accounting for interspecific interactions, which can modify both the severity and directionality of ecological effects.

Frameworks like CIMPAL+ and CIMPAL-ES have expanded the analytical capacity to consider **positive impacts**, particularly those emerging in systems undergoing climate-driven restructuring. In the eastern Mediterranean, for instance, thermophilic alien species are increasingly supporting ecosystem functions and socio-economic activities vacated by declining native biota. While such contributions may aid in resilience, they must not be viewed as offsets to negative impacts. Instead, they should be assessed independently, acknowledging the context-dependence of positive outcomes and the socio-

ecological trade-offs involved. This perspective reinforces the need for balanced, principle-based management approaches that weigh ecological integrity against potential benefits and stakeholder interests.

The role of **structural ecosystem engineers**, such as invasive bivalves and macrophytes, is a recurrent theme across case studies, with both beneficial and detrimental consequences depending on habitat type and regional context. In many instances, these species significantly reshape benthic and pelagic dynamics, influence nutrient cycling, and alter food web interactions. Their ecological footprint is often magnified in coastal zones where anthropogenic pressures—maritime transport, eutrophication, infrastructure—amplify opportunities for establishment and spread. The spatial heterogeneity of impact scores further emphasizes that management actions must be locally tailored, supported by consistent monitoring and dynamic data integration.

Notably, **the inclusion of jellyfish blooms as a distinct pressure** revealed their broad ecological relevance, especially in semi-enclosed seas like the Adriatic, where hydrodynamics and nutrient enrichment converge with overfishing to create favourable conditions for proliferation. Species such as *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Pelagia noctiluca* emerged as key contributors to cumulative impact scores, with well-documented consequences for fisheries and planktonic communities. These findings reinforce the value of complementing traditional monitoring with citizen science, which has proven effective in detecting rare or transient events and enhancing spatiotemporal data resolution.

Despite these advances, persistent limitations remain. Many CIMPAL assessments rely heavily on presence-absence data, expert judgment, or incomplete distribution records, particularly in offshore regions or for less-studied taxa. Data gaps can lead to underestimation of impacts or misinterpretation of low CIMPAL scores as ecological neutrality. To address this, future efforts must prioritize modelled distributions, refined species impact weights, and the inclusion of underrepresented ecosystem components such as fish recruitment zones and microbial dynamics. Moreover, quantifying impacts on ecosystem services introduces further complexity, necessitating integration of socio-economic variables, benefit-cost analyses, and trade-off evaluations across sectors.

Ultimately, **the expanded CIMPAL suite of tools offers a robust, reproducible, and adaptable foundation for supporting the MSFD and related policy goals.** By accommodating both negative and positive impacts, incorporating species interactions, and enabling application across diverse spatial scales, these frameworks are well-positioned to guide evidence-based marine management. However, their success depends on sustained investment in monitoring, data harmonisation, and stakeholder engagement to ensure that impact assessments are not only scientifically sound but also operationally effective.

High-resolution spatial data, including the use of **biologging** and **vessel tracking**, are beginning to shed light on fine-scale spatiotemporal overlaps between wildlife (especially in **top predators**, such as marine mammals and seabirds) and anthropogenic threats, such as small-scale fisheries, but long-term, harmonized datasets are still lacking. In this context, advances in biologging and satellite telemetry are especially valuable for understanding top predators species-specific habitat use, migration patterns, and overlap with human activities. These tools have proven effective for seabirds and cetaceans alike, revealing habitat preferences, exposure to bycatch risk, and interactions with artificial structures and fisheries. Yet, ethical, logistical, and welfare considerations—especially in the case of cetaceans—must guide deployment decisions, balancing the value of ecological data with potential impacts on individual animals.

The growing reliance of some seabird species on anthropogenic food subsidies, particularly from fisheries and land-based sources, further illustrates the complex and often contradictory effects of human activity. Opportunistic species such as Audouin’s gull have demonstrated substantial plasticity in habitat use and foraging behaviour, with clear evidence of spatiotemporal associations with fishing activities and terrestrial anthropogenic food sources. While this behavioural flexibility may contribute to population expansion and breeding success, it also poses risks associated with ecological traps, reduced diet quality, pollutant exposure, and altered predator–prey dynamics. Changes in fishery policies—such as discard bans—are likely to have cascading effects on these species, highlighting the need for integrated approaches that consider both conservation and ecosystem functioning.

Bycatch remains a critical threat to many marine top predators, and progress in mitigating its impact requires more precise understanding of where and when interactions with fisheries occur. Tools such as kernel density estimation, species tracking, and integration with AIS data provide promising avenues for identifying high-risk areas and informing spatially explicit management strategies. However, effective mitigation depends on the active involvement of fishers, the adoption of feasible and well-tested deterrent devices, and robust scientific guidance. Particular attention must be paid to gear-specific risks, juvenile vulnerability, and interactions with artisanal fleets that are often underrepresented in official datasets.

Connectivity studies of benthic and pelagic species highlight the importance of fine-scale ecological processes in spatial planning. Species with low dispersal potential or strong site fidelity require carefully designed MPA networks that maintain population connectivity under changing climate and current regimes. Integrating behavioural, life-history, and habitat data into connectivity models is essential for anticipating future shifts in species distributions and for designing MPAs that remain effective under novel conditions.

Across all themes, a recurring obstacle is the **limited integration of data and assessments** across pressures, descriptors, and scales. While individual methodologies have advanced considerably, their application within a coherent, ecosystem-based monitoring and management framework remains patchy. The integration of pressure mapping with biological response data, as demonstrated in select national contexts, provides a template for more targeted and cost-effective monitoring. Institutional fragmentation and uneven governance capacities continue to hamper progress toward GES, emphasizing the need for cross-sectoral coordination, stakeholder engagement, and harmonized implementation across Member States.

In conclusion, **achieving GES under the MSFD demands a paradigm shift toward integrated, adaptive, and cross-thematic approaches**. The insights and methods presented in this deliverable demonstrate the potential to enhance ecological relevance, improve monitoring efficiency, and support transboundary cooperation. Realizing this potential will require sustained investment in data infrastructure, cross-disciplinary collaboration, and the development of governance frameworks capable of addressing the complex, cumulative, and evolving nature of marine ecological pressures. Only through such integrative and forward-looking approaches can Member States deliver on the ambition of the MSFD in the context of rapid environmental change.

10. Recommendations

10.1 Recommendations for the use of satellite data

- **Satellite data are extremely useful for monitoring and assessing** large areas at higher temporal frequencies, particularly in highly variable ecosystems such as marine and coastal environments. This capability facilitates the monitoring of remote or data-poor regions where limited sampling resources might be available. In addition, higher frequencies facilitate the assessment of seasonal patterns, anomalies, and extreme events, as well as phenological shifts, which prove challenging to detect using conventional in-situ surveying methodologies.
- Furthermore, an **understanding of these variability patterns** across different environmental types is crucial for conducting effective risk assessments, that can be used to focus monitoring efforts and management measures.
- The optimal use of satellite data **depends on the existence of reliable field data** to validate the various products that can be generated. Currently, this is a major obstacle to their application, especially in turbid and shallow waters. Therefore, more monitoring surveys or data sharing are needed to better calibrate and validate satellite products and improve their applicability in different ecosystems and regions.
- Currently, investigations for the identification by satellite data of phytoplankton groups (and some HABs) are evolving due to improved satellite missions and algorithms, although no sound products are ready yet.
- It is recommended that ongoing **collaboration between remote sensing and phytoplankton/zooplankton experts, across different regional seas**, be maintained and further promoted to obtain good quality satellite products for assessments related to food webs, eutrophication, HABs and gelatinous zooplankton as set out in MSFD D1, D4, and D5 descriptors.
- Further innovative research should be conducted to **find algorithms or methods that could identify jellyfish aggregations** from space, at least in Case-1 waters.
- **Satellite products** for various environmental parameters (e.g. sea surface temperature, turbidity, sea level) or features (e.g. fronts, eddies) **could be ingested into machine learning** models to analyze spatial distribution patterns of different ecosystem components, as well as to validate their results. **These products could be used to feed the GES4SEAS toolbox**, for assessing the status under multiple pressures and climate change.

- Once more, machine learning methods strongly require ground truth data from in-situ monitoring programmes, to confirm their accuracy.

10.2 Recommendations for the use of Lagrangian models

- Lagrangian models can be very useful for **assessing the spatial and temporal extent and evolution of drifting ecosystem components**, such as plankton (including phytoplankton, zooplankton and ichthyoplankton) and floating elements (seaweed, litter and oil spills).
- These drifting components often play vital roles in providing impacts and ecosystem services that may not be evident at their source, but rather along their trajectory or destination. This is why Lagrangian models might be extremely useful for **addressing spatio-temporal connectivity issues between states, pressures and impacts**.
- Lagrangian models can also assist in understanding connectivity between benthic-pelagic and land-sea interactions.
- Lagrangian and coastal models can be particularly valuable in data-poor environments to assess very large study areas/large extents.
- It is important to note that the utility of the Lagrangian models is based on the certainty of their results, which **require sound ground data for calibration and validation**.
- The application of Lagrangian models to assess the drifting patterns of different components (biological or otherwise) also needs to be based on a **good knowledge of the components' traits** (i.e. their physiological characteristics, shapes, densities, etc.).

10.3 Recommendations for the use of molecular techniques

- **High-throughput sequencing techniques are a powerful tool** that allows a straightforward characterization of molecular diversity in environmental samples. As such, metabarcoding of eDNA is recurrently proposed as an alternative method to be implemented for biomonitoring purposes and assessment of GES.
- Based on existing literature and the case studies presented in this document, eDNA metabarcoding allows to detect and identify **elusive taxa**, including cryptic species, low-abundance taxa, specimens lacking relevant morphological features for their identification. Additionally, extracellular DNA or cell remnants can be amplified, allowing the detection of species that are not actually present in the samples, serving as an **early detection** tool for

invasive species. Likewise, metabarcoding allows for **greater taxonomic resolution** than using traditional techniques, like morphological identification, which strongly relies on the taxonomic expertise of the analyst. No taxonomic expertise is required for the taxonomic assignment of amplicons, as it is automatically done using bioinformatic pipelines.

- Despite of such potential, the application of eDNA metabarcoding for biomonitoring purposes has been hampered by many drawbacks. Metabarcoding **lacks a standardized methodology**, and sequencing results strongly depend on procedures followed, which could result in **significant biases** in final results. Such variability can be due to deficient cell lysis, DNA extraction method, taxonomic resolution of the marker used, biases of PCR primers, sequencing platform and sequencing depth, differing bioinformatic pipelines, taxonomic assignment method and reference sequences database used for that purpose. The lack of standard methods is partially due to the continuous development of new high-throughput sequencing procedures. As such, it does not allow the scientific community to adopt robust procedures and to construct long-time series due to continuous changes in the procedures, **which can compromise the adoption of management measures by competent authorities**.
- The method is considered semi-quantitative, providing compositional data, and relative abundances obtained do not always reflect cell abundances. Richness obtained usually largely exceeds that detected by traditional methods. However, **false positives** are often detected, i.e. the presence of species that do not correspond to the studied habitat, and also **false negatives**, i.e. species that are observed in the samples and not amplified during the sequencing process. Sometimes, **incorrect taxonomic assignments** are due to the current incompleteness of reference sequences databases, the lack of a thorough curation of sequences present.
- In **conclusion**, eDNA metabarcoding has been proven as a valuable tool to detect **elusive taxa**, especially those that are problematic due to insufficient morphological characters for their identification, including cryptic species, pico- or nanoeukaryotes. It is especially valuable for identifying bacteria, which generally lack morphological characters. However, they are barely used as bioindicators. Additionally, it has been proposed as a good alert tool, allowing early **detection** of rare species, like NIS or harmful species.

- Given the presented conclusions, it is **recommended** that eDNA metabarcoding is used as a **complementary tool** to traditional methods. The results obtained largely surpass those obtained by traditional techniques in some aspects, but they must be interpreted with caution because of the common detection of false positives and negatives. It is especially relevant if it is used to detect harmful algal species or non-indigenous species. Therefore, eDNA metabarcoding is **not providing reliable results** for implementing it for biomonitoring purposes, **requiring a validation** by comparison with traditional techniques and/or a thorough check of the results by taxonomists.

10.4 Recommendations for the use of CIMPAL

- **Incorporate both negative and positive NIS impacts:** Future assessments should adopt a dual-modality approach (e.g., CIMPAL and CIMPAL⁺/ CIMPAL-ES⁻ and CIMPAL-ES⁺) to comprehensively capture the complexity of NIS effects on ecosystems and ecosystem services.
- **Account for interspecific interactions:** Integrating interactions among invasive species (e.g. herbivory, predation) enhances the ecological realism and precision of cumulative impact scores.
- **Apply high-resolution spatial analyses:** Fine-scale (e.g. 1 km²) assessments, as demonstrated in the Aegean Sea case, reveal detailed spatial impact patterns and support more effective prioritisation compared to coarser regional scales.
- **Link impacts to ecosystem services:** Evaluating how invasive species affect provisioning, regulating, and cultural services enhances the ecological and socio-economic relevance of impact assessments, thereby strengthening their utility for policy development and management planning.
- **Use the framework to guide management priorities:** Identify hotspots of high cumulative impact and prioritise areas for monitoring, mitigation, or potential sustainable exploitation of beneficial NIS. Additionally, CIMPAL supports the prioritization of species for targeted management, enabling more efficient allocation of limited resources toward the most problematic species.
- **Upscaling assessments:** Large-scale assessments should build on spatial resolutions adequate to the scale of species distribution and impacts, beginning with finer-scale assessments (e.g.

1 km²), that can be aggregated into coarser resolution scales (e.g. 10 km²) as needed for broader spatial analysis.

- **Support cross-border coordination:** Application of CIMPAL across jurisdictions facilitates cooperation in invasive species management across shared marine regions, such as those governed by the Regional Seas Conventions.
- **Interpret evidence in support of management:** CIMPAL spatial outputs should be interpreted in the context of the underlying data quality. High-confidence species distribution data combined with robust evidence of local impacts support reliable impact footprint maps and credible assessments of cumulative effects. In contrast, outputs based on limited observations or model predictions, especially when paired with impact evidence extrapolated from other systems, are more appropriately used as indicators of vulnerability and risk to inform decision-making.
- **Engage stakeholders and local communities:** Dissemination of cumulative impact maps and accessible outputs from the CIMPAL framework promotes awareness and enables participatory governance approaches.
- **Use CIMPAL as a policy-relevant indicator for the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework Target 6 and MSFD descriptor D2:** The CIMPAL family offers a standardized approach for assessing cumulative impacts of invasive species and identifying the primary pathways of introduction contributing to those impacts, both of which are central to the requirements of policy indicators.
- **Enhance monitoring and impact assessments of invasive species:** The robustness of CIMPAL depends on the quality and spatial resolution of available distribution data and impact assessments within the study region. Monitoring and impact assessments should be enhanced and supported with sufficient funding for reliable cumulative impact assessments.
- **Prepare for shifting baselines and climate impacts:** The ongoing tropicalization of the eastern Mediterranean implies that NIS impacts will continue to evolve, necessitating dynamic and adaptive monitoring strategies.
- **Enhance field studies on key impacts:** It is crucial to increase and improve field studies on the impacts of HABs, jellyfish blooms, and IAS on ecosystem components. This directly addresses current data gaps, where "zero impact" often signifies a lack of available data rather than a true absence of effects, thereby strengthening the reliability of CIMPAL assessments.

- **Integrate citizen science for targeted monitoring:** Incorporating citizen science into monitoring programs can significantly enhance the detection and assessment of impacts. This approach helps identify impact hotspots or areas not achieving GES, guiding management and conservation actions more effectively. Furthermore, citizen science facilitates the rapid detection and assessment of rare or episodic events, thereby enhancing overall responsiveness and data collection efficiency.

10.5 Recommendations for biologging for the monitoring and management of top predators

- **Biologging data are be useful for monitoring** and providing a comprehensive assessment of habitat use by top predators (marine mammals, seabirds, etc.).
- Measuring the spatiotemporal overlap between species of concern (either endangered, or migratory, or both) and various pressures **may be used to evaluate the potential risks for species in a spatially explicit way**, and to design specific management measures, especially if the pressures can be linked to anthropogenic activities.
- Monitoring species of conservation concern at sea, such as marine top predators, can have **implications for marine management**, but it is also necessary to simultaneously assess the interaction with other human activities on land.
- There is a need to improve the evaluation of **the interaction between top predators and human activities in non-EU waters** to ensure effective transboundary management.
- In data-limited marine areas, alternative methods, such as video cameras, can offer valuable insights into human activities occurring within these regions.
- Changes observed in the distribution or abundance of some top predators can be related to tipping points, and this technique is useful for studying them.

11. Annex

11.1 Supplementary material of section 7.7: CIMPAL+: accounting for cumulative positive impacts on biodiversity

Literature Review of Positive Impacts of Non-Indigenous Species in the Mediterranean Sea

Macrophytes

Styopodium schimperi (Kützing) Verlaque & Boudouresque

Styopodium schimperi is a non-indigenous ochrophyte that was introduced in the Mediterranean basin through the Suez Canal. It can create dense membranous algal thalli aggregations that can displace native macroalgae and monopolize shallow hard substrates (Boudouresque and Verlaque 2002; Žuljević et al. 2023). However, through the novel habitats it creates it can also benefit other species by providing available space for settlement (Katsanevakis et al. 2014).

Caulerpa cylindracea Sonder

Caulerpa cylindracea is an Australian chlorophyte that has spread throughout the Mediterranean basin. It can colonize a wide spectrum of different habitats, including soft, hard substrates and seagrass meadows and create dense turf mattes that substantially affect benthic communities and ecological functions. Despite its considerable negative effects, the Australian chlorophyte can also benefit native biodiversity. Many macrofaunal species are favoured by the newly formed habitats formed by the non-indigenous chlorophyte in rocky (Vázquez-Luis et al. 2013; Sinopoli et al. 2020; BadrEldin and Hallock, 2022) and sandy habitats (e.g. Argyrou et al. 1999; Vázquez-Luis et al. 2009; Pacciardi et al. 2011). Furthermore, Rizzo et al. (2020) demonstrated that *C. cylindracea* can alter quantity, biochemical composition, and nutritional quality of organic detritus, affecting benthic ecosystem functioning in shallow soft substrates. Its impact on resident meiofaunal communities varies depending on sediment deposition rates; it can be positive at low rates but negative at medium to high rates (Rizzo et al. 2020). Complex *C. cylindracea* formations have also been positively associated with increased seagrass seedling survival (Pereda-Briones et al. 2018) and increased shoot density (Ceccherelli and Campo 2002). Despite the developed anti-grazing mechanisms and the negative effects it causes on its consumers, *C. cylindracea* is favourably grazed by a wide variety of species in the Mediterranean, expanding their available trophic resources (Rizzo and Fernández 2023 and references therein). Potential mutualistic interactions have been suggested with native biota like the echinoids *Sphaerechinus granularis*, *Holothuria* spp. and the decapod *Maja crispata* that have been observed to carry on their bodies attached *C. cylindracea* thalli (Mannino and Balisteri 2023). The toxic substances produced by the non-indigenous chlorophyte may deter predators of the

'carriers' and at the same time *C. cylindracea* may further facilitate its spread via these native species (Mannino and Balisteri 2023).

***Codium fragile* subsp. *fragile* (Suringar) Hariot**

This green macroalgae was previously referred to as *Codium fragile* subsp. *tomentosoides*. The species is widespread in the Mediterranean basin. It forms dense sponge-like fronds up to 20cm in height in rocky bottoms that can become a major structural element of the invaded habitat and dominate the macroalgal community (Katsanevakis et al. 2020). *Codium fragile* formations introduce three-dimensional complexity in rocky reefs that can favour the establishment of native species (Bulleri et al. 2006; Katsanevakis et al. 2014). This non-indigenous chlorophyte has also been associated with positive effects as a food source for native herbivores (Katsanevakis et al. 2014).

***Asparagopsis* spp.**

Asparagopsis armata Harvey and *Asparagopsis taxiformis* (Delile) Trevisan de Saint-Léon are two non-indigenous rhodophytes widely distributed across the Mediterranean basin. For the larger part of their life cycles the two rhodophytes are quite difficult to be distinguished morphologically (Andreakis et al. 2004; Zanolla et al. 2014). *Asparagopsis* spp. can create dense formations with their erect algal thalli at shallow hard substrates. These new habitats can support rich epibenthic assemblages, enhancing the biodiversity of these rocky habitats similarly with native species (Pacios et al. 2011; Soler-Hurtado and Guerra-García 2011; Guerra-García and Sánchez-Moyano 2013; Moncer et al. 2017). Organic matter sources of *A. armata* have also been identified as an optimal food source for mesoherbivore polychaetes (Ricevuto et al., 2015).

***Lophocladia trichoclados* (Montagne) F. Schmitz**

Lophocladia trichoclados is a non-indigenous rhodophyte widespread in the Mediterranean Sea. It is considered an invasive macroalgae that epiphytizes on *Posidonia oceanica* meadows leaves introducing negative effects on the fitness of the meadow (Tsirintanis et al. 2022 and references therein). It also can form turf mats on rocky habitats that accumulate sediments, causing substantial modifications on the structure of the established communities (Bedini et al. 2015). However, these turf formations also provide habitat for numerous species (Tiberti et al. 2021).

***Womersleyella setacea* (Hollenberg) R.E. Norris**

This filamentous rhodophyte has spread throughout the Mediterranean basin. It is considered an invasive species due to the dense turf formations it creates that can cover rocky substrates and epiphytize *Posidonia oceanica* meadows (Tsirintanis et al. 2022 and references therein). At the same

time, the newly formed turfs increase habitat complexity and support a wide variety of species on rocky substrates (Antoniadou and Chintiroglou 2007).

***Halophila stipulacea* (Forsskål) Ascherson**

The Red Sea seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* is widespread in the eastern and central Mediterranean Sea. *Halophila stipulacea* positively affects native biodiversity through the creation of seagrass meadows in shallow soft substrates that act as habitat for a variety of species (e.g. Di Martino et al. 2007). The non-indigenous seagrass increases structural complexity, particularly in shallow soft bottoms and dead *Posidonia oceanica* matte (Di Genio et al. 2021). Although competitive interactions with native seagrasses have been reported in the Mediterranean Sea (Sghaier et al. 2014; Conte et al. 2023; Mannino et al. 2023), *H. stipulacea* meadows have also the potential to positively contribute to a variety of ecosystem services such as food provision, climate regulation and lifecycle maintenance (Tsirintanis et al. 2022 and references therein). Furthermore, *H. stipulacea* leaves constitute an optimal food source for native grazers, although without substantial positive effects demonstrated yet (Di Genio et al. 2021; Palmer et al. 2021).

Invertebrates

***Oculina patagonica* de Angelis, 1908**

The cryptogenic scleractinian coral *Oculina patagonica* is established throughout the Mediterranean Sea. It is considered an opportunistic invasive species with negative impacts on Mediterranean biodiversity due to competition or reduction of habitat complexity on shallow rocky habitats (Tsirintanis et al. 2022 and references therein). However, *O. patagonica* also acts as a structural ecosystem engineer, creating new habitats that can benefit other species (Katsanevakis et al. 2014; Gravili and Rossi 2021). Facultative mutualism between the *O. patagonica* and gastropods has also been suggested (Coletti et al. 2023).

***Brachidontes pharaonis* (P. Fischer, 1870)**

Brachidontes pharaonis is a non-indigenous bivalve of Indo-Pacific origin currently established with abundant populations in the eastern and central Mediterranean Sea. It can acquire key ecological roles in the ecosystems as it reduces water turbidity (Sarà et al. 2021) and creates novel habitat structures on shallow hard substrates that facilitate a variety of species (Rilov and Galil 2009; Çinar et al. 2017; Sarà et al. 2021). Furthermore, the native predatory whelk, *Stramonita haemastoma* has included *B. pharaonis* in its diet even preferring it over native prey, due to the higher energy intake provided by the non-indigenous bivalve (Rilov et al. 2002; Giacoletti et al. 2016, 2017).

***Pinctada radiata* (Leach, 1814)**

Pinctada radiata is a non-indigenous bivalve widespread in the Mediterranean Sea. It can form dense aggregations that alter habitat structure in shallow hard substrates and provide space for the settlement of a variety of epibenthic species (Katsanevakis et al. 2014; Abdelsalam and Elebiary 2023).

***Hydroides elegans* (Haswell, 1883)**

The calcified polychaete *Hydroides elegans* is a non-indigenous serpulid, spread throughout the Mediterranean basin. It fouls on hard substrates, mainly on eutrophic environments and ports, and can create massive dense aggregations of calcified tubes (Antoniadou et al 2011; Sandonnini et al. 2021). These novel formations constitute a suitable habitat for the establishment of other benthic species (Koçak et al. 1999; Çinar et al. 2008; Katsanevakis et al. 2014; Mangano et al. 2019).

Fish

Fistularia commersonii

The Lessepsian bluespotted cornetfish *Fistularia commersonii* is a highly successful invader that rapidly colonized the Mediterranean basin (Azzurro et al. 2013). Favourable conditions for its spread include low chlorophyll-a concentrations and high salinity, whereas cold temperatures, high productivity, and low salinity limit its distribution (Azzurro et al. 2013). Although considered a voracious predator (Tsirintanis et al. 2022 and references therein), this non-indigenous fish has been modelled as an important food source for seabirds and many native fish in the Mediterranean Sea (e.g. Pinnegar et al. 2014). As depicted by Ecopath and Ecosim models applied in the trophic web of Cyprus, the contribution that *F. commersonii* offers to large pelagic fish is further enhanced in scenarios of reduced overall fishing pressure (Michailidis 2021).

***Sargocentron rubrum* (Forsskål, 1775); *Pempheris rhomboidea* Kossmann & Rüber, 1877**

Sargocentron rubrum and *Pempheris rhomboidea* are two non-indigenous fish commonly found in the eastern Mediterranean. They reside inside caves and crevices during the daytime, emerging at night to feed primarily on crustaceans (Golani and Diamant 1991; Golani et al. 2013). These movements, in and out of their shelters, transfer organic matter from the outer environment into the oligotrophic cave interior, impacting resident communities (Otero et al. 2013; Gerovasileiou et al. 2016).

***Siganus luridus* (Rüppell, 1829); *Siganus rivulatus* Forsskål & Niebuhr, 1775**

The herbivorous fish *Siganus luridus* and *Siganus rivulatus* have established abundant populations in the eastern Mediterranean basin where they have caused detrimental impacts on rocky reefs through their herbivory on native macroalgae (Sala et al. 2011; Vergés et al. 2014; Corrales et al. 2017; Nikolaou et al. 2023). On the other hand, the two siganids have contributed to the acceleration of algal recycling

in the Levantine Sea (Goren and Galil 2005) and constitute an optimal food source for larger predators such as groupers (Goren and Galil 2005; Corrales et al. 2017).

References

- Abdelsalam, K.M., & Elebiary, N. H. (2023). Preliminary estimation of fouling organisms associated with the pearl oyster *Pinctada radiata* in the natural habitat of the Egyptian Mediterranean Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 24(2), 338–352. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.32735>
- Antoniadou, C., & Chintiroglou, C., (2007). Zoobenthos associated with the invasive red alga *Womersleyella setacea* (Rhodomelacea) in the northern Aegean Sea. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 87(3): 629–641, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315407048151>
- Antoniadou, C., Sarantidis, S., & Chintiroglou, C., (2011). Small-scale spatial variability of zoobenthic communities in a commercial Mediterranean port. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 91(1): 77-89, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315410001098>
- Argyrou, M., Demetropoulos, A., & Hadjichristophorou, M., (1999). Expansion of the macroalga *Caulerpa racemosa* and changes in softbottom macrofaunal assemblages in Moni Bay, Cyprus. *Oceanologica Acta* 22(5): 517–528, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0399-1784\(00\)87684-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0399-1784(00)87684-7)
- Andreakis, N., Procaccini, G., & Kooistra, W.H., (2004). *Asparagopsis taxiformis* and *Asparagopsis armata* (Bonnemaisoniales, Rhodophyta): genetic and morphological identification of Mediterranean populations. *European journal of phycology* 39, 273-283,
- Azzurro, E., Soto, S., Garofalo, G., & Maynou, F., (2013). *Fistularia commersonii* in the Mediterranean Sea: invasion history and distribution modeling based on presence-only records. *Biological Invasions* 15: 977–990, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-012-0344-4>
- BadrElDin, A.M. & Hallock, P.M., (2022). Foraminifers associated with macroalgae on a wave-cut platform off Abu Qir coastal area, Egypt. *The Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Research*, 48(4), pp.389-395, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejar.2022.08.003>
- Bedini, R., Bedini, M., Bonechi, L., & Piazzini, L., (2015). Effects of non-native turf-forming Rhodophyta on mobile macro-invertebrate assemblages in the north-western Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Biology Research* 11(4): 430–437, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2014.952310>
- Boudouresque, C.F., & Verlaque, M., (2002). Biological pollution in the Mediterranean Sea: invasive versus introduced macrophytes. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 44, 32-38
- Bulleri, F., Airoidi, L., Branca, G.M., & Abbiati, M., (2006). Positive effects of the introduced green alga, *Codium fragile* ssp. *tomentosoides*, on recruitment and survival of mussels. *Marine Biology* 148: 1213–1220, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00227-005-0181-4>
- Ceccherelli, G., & Campo, D., (2002). Different Effects of *Caulerpa racemosa* on Two Co-occurring Seagrasses in the Mediterranean. *Botanica Marina* 45: 71–76, <https://doi.org/10.1515/BOT.2002.009>
- Çinar, M.E., Katağan, T., Koçak, F., Öztürk, B., Ergen, Z., Kocatas, A., Önen, M., Kirkim, F., Bakir, K., Kurt, G., Dağlı, E., Açıık, S., Doğan, A., & Özcan, T., (2008). Faunal assemblages of the mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* in and around Alsancak Harbour (Izmir Bay, eastern Mediterranean) with special emphasis on alien species. *Journal of Marine Systems* 71: 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2007.05.004>
- Çinar, M.E., Bakir, K., Öztürk, B., Katağan, T., Doğan, A., Açıık, S., Kurt-Sahin, G., Özcan, T., Dağlı, E., Bitlis-Bakir, B., Koçak, F., & Kirkim, F., (2017). Macrobenthic fauna associated with the invasive

- alien species *Brachidontes pharaonis* (Mollusca: Bivalvia) in the Levantine Sea (Turkey). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 97(3): 613–628
- Coletti, G., Collareta, A., Di Cencio, A., Bosio, G. & Casati, S., (2023). Symbiont-bearing colonial corals and gastropods: an odd couple of the shallow seas. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 11, 260, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11020260>
- Conte, C., Apostolaki, E.T., Vizzini, S., & Migliore, L., (2023). A Tight Interaction between the Native Seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa* and the Exotic *Halophila stipulacea* in the Aegean Sea Highlights Seagrass Holobiont Variations. *Plants* 12, 350, <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12020350>
- Corrales, X., Ofir, E., Coll, M., Goren, M., Edelist, D., Heymans, J.J., & Gal, G., (2017). Modeling the role and impact of alien species and fisheries on the Israeli marine continental shelf ecosystem. *Journal of Marine Systems* 170: 88–102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2017.02.004>
- Di Martino, V., Stancanelli, B., & Molinari, A. (2007), Fish community associated with *Halophila stipulacea* meadow in the Mediterranean Sea. *Cybium* 31(4): 451–458,
- Gerovasileiou, V., Voultziadou, E., Issaris, Y., & Zenetos, A., (2016). Alien biodiversity in Mediterranean marine caves. *Marine Ecology* 37(2): 239–256, <https://doi.org/10.1111/maec.12268>
- Giacoletti, A., Rinaldi, A., Mercurio, M., Mirto, S., Sarà, G., (2016). Local consumers are the first line to control biological invasions: a case of study with the whelk *Stramonita haemastoma* (Gastropoda: Muricidae). *Hydrobiologia* 772(1): 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-016-2645-6>
- Giacoletti, A., Maricchiolo, G., Mirto, S., Genovese, L., Umani, M., & Sarà, G., (2017). Functional and energetic consequences of climate change on a predatory whelk. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 189: 66–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2017.03.007>
- Golani, D., & Diamant, A., (1991). Biology of the sweeper, *Pempheris vanicolensis* Cuvier & Valenciennes, a Lessepsian migrant in the eastern Mediterranean, with a comparison with the original Red Sea population. *Journal of Fish Biology* 38: 819–827
- Golani, D., Ben-Tuvia, A., & Galil, B., (2013). Feeding habits of the Suez Canal migrant squirrelfish, *Sargocentron rubrum*, in the Mediterranean Sea. *Israel Journal of Zoology* 32(4): 194–204
- Goren, M., & Galil, B.S., (2005). A review of changes in the fish assemblages of Levantine inland and marine ecosystems following the introduction of non-native fishes. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology* 21(4): 364–370, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0426.2005.00674.x>
- Gravili, C. & Rossi, S., (2021). Who's Next? Non-Indigenous Cnidarian and Ctenophoran Species Approaching to the Italian Waters. *Water* 13, 1062, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13081062>
- Guerra-García, J.M., & Sánchez-Moyano, J., (2013). Spatio-temporal distribution of the Caprellidae (Crustacea: Amphipoda) associated with the invasive seaweed *Asparagopsis armata* Harvey in the Southern Iberian Peninsula. *Zoologica Baetica* 24: 3–17
- Katsanevakis, S., Wallentinus, I., Zenetos, A., Leppäkoski, E., Çinar, M.E., Oztürk, B., Grabowski, M., Golani, D., & Cardoso, A.C., (2014). Impacts of invasive alien marine species on ecosystem services and biodiversity: a pan-European review. *Aquatic Invasions* 9: 391–423,
- Katsanevakis, S., Zenetos, A., Corsini-Foka, M., & Tsiamis, K., (2020). Biological Invasions in the Aegean Sea: Temporal Trends, Pathways, and Impacts. In: Anagnostou CL, Kostianoy AG, Mariolakos ID, Panayotidis P, Soilemezidou M, Tsaltas G (eds), *The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-60200-6_642
- Koçak, F., Ergen, Z., & Çinar, M.E., (1999). Fouling organisms and their developments in a polluted and an unpolluted marina in the Aegean Sea (Turkey). *Ophelia* 50(1): 1–20,

- Mangano, M.C., Ape, F., & Mirto, S., (2019). The role of two non-indigenous serpulid tube worms in shaping artificial hard substrata communities: case study of a fish farm in the central Mediterranean Sea. *Aquaculture Environment Interactions* 11, 41-51. <https://doi.org/10.3354/aei00291>
- Mannino, A.M., & Balistreri, P., (2023). Possible Interactions between Invasive *Caulerpa* Taxa and Native Macrozoobenthos: The Case Study of Favignana Island. *Diversity* 15, 919,
- Mannino, A.M., Balistreri, P., Mancuso, F.P., Bozzeda, F., & Pinna, M., (2023). Searching for the competitive ability of the alien seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* with the autochthonous species *Cymodocea nodosa*. *NeoBiota*, 83, pp.155-177.
- Michailidis, N., (2021). Modelling the marine food web in the coastal waters of Cyprus. PhD Thesis, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cyprus, Cyprus
- Michailidis, N, Corrales, X., Karachle, P.K., Chartosia, N., Katsanevakis, S., & Sfenthourakis, S., (2019). Modelling the role of alien species and fisheries in an Eastern Mediterranean insular shelf ecosystem. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 175: 152–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2019.04.006>
- Moncer, M., Hamza, A., Feki-Sahnoun, W., Mabrouk, L., & Hassen, M.B., (2017). Variability patterns of epibenthic microalgae in eastern Tunisian coasts. *Scientia Marina* 81(4): 487–498,
- Nikolaou, A., Tsirintanis, K., Rilov, G., & Katsanevakis, S., (2023). Invasive fish and sea urchins drive the status of canopy forming macroalgae in the eastern Mediterranean. *Biology*, 12(6), 763.
- Otero, M., Cebrian, E., Francour, P., Galil, B., & Savini, D., (2013). Monitoring marine invasive species in Mediterranean marine protected areas (MPAs): a strategy and practical guide for managers. Medpan North project. IUCN, Malaga, Spain, 136 pp
- Pacciardi, L., De Biasi, A.M., & Piazzzi, L., (2011). Effects of *Caulerpa racemosa* invasion on soft-bottom assemblages in the Western Mediterranean Sea. *Biological Invasions* 13: 2677–2690,
- Pacios, I., Guerra-García, J.M., Baeza-Rojano, E., & Cabezas, M.P., (2011). The non-native seaweed *Asparagopsis armata* supports a diverse crustacean assemblage. *Marine Environmental Research* 71(4): 275–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2011.02.002>
- Pereda-Briones, L., Tomas, F., & Terrados, J., (2018). Field transplantation of seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*) seedlings: Effects of invasive algae and nutrients. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 134: 160–165,
- Pinnegar, J.K., Tomczak, M.T., & Link, J.S., (2014). How to determine the likely indirect food-web consequences of a newly introduced non-native species: A worked example. *Ecological Modelling* 272: 379–387.
- Ricevuto, E., Vizzini, S., & Gambi, M.C., (2015). Ocean acidification effects on stable isotope signatures and trophic interactions of polychaete consumers and organic matter sources at a CO₂ shallow vent system. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* (468): 105–117,
- Rilov, G., & Galil, B., (2009). Marine Bioinvasions in the Mediterranean Sea – History, Distribution and Ecology. In: Rilov G, Crooks JA (eds), Biological Invasions in Marine Ecosystems. Ecological Studies, vol 204. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 549–575. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-79236-9_31
- Rilov, G., Gasith, A., & Benayahu, Y., (2002). Effect of an exotic prey on the feeding pattern of a predatory snail. *Marine Environmental Research* 54(1): 85–98,
- Rizzo, L., Pusceddu, A., Bianchelli, S., & Frascchetti, S., (2020). Potentially combined effect of the invasive seaweed *Caulerpa cylindracea* (Sonder) and sediment deposition rates on organic matter and meiofaunal assemblages. *Marine Environmental Research* 159: 104966

- Rizzo, L., Vega, & Fernández, T., (2023). Can the Invasive Seaweed *Caulerpa cylindracea* Represent a New Trophic Resource in the Mediterranean Sea? *Water* 15, 2115,
- Sandonnini, J., Del Pilar Ruso, Y., Cortés Melendreras, E., Barberá, C., Hendriks, I.E., Kersting, D.K., & Giménez Casalduero, F., (2021). The emergent fouling population after severe eutrophication in the Mar Menor coastal lagoon. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 44: 101720,
- Sala, E., Kizilkaya, Z., Yildirim, D., & Ballesteros, E., (2011). Alien Marine Fishes Deplete Algal Biomass in the Eastern Mediterranean. *PLoS ONE* 6(2): e17356, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0017356>
- Sarà, G., Giommi, C., Giacoletti, A., Conti, E., Mulder, C., & Mangano, M.C., (2021). Multiple climate-driven cascading ecosystem effects after the loss of a foundation species. *Science of The Total Environment* 770: 144749, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144749>
- Sghaier, Y.R., Zakhama-Sraieb, R., & Charfi-Cheikhrouha, F., (2014). Effects of the invasive seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* on the native seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa*. In: Proceedings of the 5th Mediterranean Symposium on Marine Vegetation, Portorož, Slovenia, 27-28 October, pp 167-171
- Sinopoli, M., Allegra, A., Andaloro, F., Consoli, P., Esposito, V., Falautano, M., Mangano, M.C., Nicastro, A., Scotti, G., & Castriota, L., (2020). Assessing the effect of the alien seaweed *Caulerpa cylindracea* on infralittoral rocky benthic invertebrate community: Evidence from a Mediterranean Marine Protected Area. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 38: 101372,
- Soler-Hurtado, M.M., & Guerra-García, J.M., (2011). Study of the crustacean community associated to the invasive seaweed *Asparagopsis armata* Harvey, 1855 along the coast of the Iberian Peninsula. *Zoológica baetica* 22: 33-49
- Tiberti, L., Iacono, G., Gambi, M.C., & Mannino, A.M., (2021). Invasions of the non-indigenous red alga *Lophocladia lallemandii* (Montagne) F. Schmitz off the Island of Ischia (Tyrrhenian Sea, Italy). *BioInvasions Records* 10(1): 91–102, <https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2021.10.1.11>
- Tsirintanis, K., Azzurro, E., Crocetta, F., Dimiza, M., Froglija, C., Gerovasileiou, V., Langeneck, J., Mancinelli, G., Rosso, A., Stern, N., Triantaphyllou, M., Tsiamis, K., Turon, X., Verlaque, M., Zenetos, A., & Katsanevakis, S., (2022). Bioinvasion impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human health in the Mediterranean Sea. *Aquatic Invasions* 17(3): 308–352, <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2022.17.3.01>
- Vázquez-Luis, M., Sanchez-Jerez, P., & Bayle-Sempere, J.T., (2009). Comparison between amphipod assemblages associated with *Caulerpa racemosa* var. *cylindracea* and those of other Mediterranean habitats on soft substrate. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 84(2): 161–170,
- Vázquez-Luis, M., Sanchez-Jerez, P., & Bayle-Sempere, J.T., (2013). Does the invasion of *Caulerpa racemosa* var. *cylindracea* affect the feeding habits of amphipods (Crustacea: Amphipoda)? *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 93(1): 87–94,
- Vergés, A., Tomas, F., Cebrian, E., Ballesteros, E., Kizilkaya, Z., Dendrinis, P., Karamanlidis, A.A., Spiegel, D., & Sala, E., (2014). Tropical rabbitfish and the deforestation of a warming temperate sea. *Journal of Ecology* 102(6): 1518–1527. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12324>
- Zampoukas, N., Piha, H., Bigagli, E., Hoepffner, N., Hanke, G., & Cardoso, A.C., (2012). Monitoring for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive: Requirements and options. JRC Scientific and Technical Reports. <http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/111111111/23169/1/lbna25187enn.pdf>

Zanolla, M., Carmona, R., De la Rosa, J., Salvador, N., Sherwood, A.R., Andreakis, N., & Altamirano, M., (2014). Morphological differentiation of cryptic lineages within the invasive genus *Asparagopsis* (Bonnemaisoniales, Rhodophyta). *Phycologia* 53: 233–242, <https://doi.org/10.2216/13-247.1>

Žuljević, A., Lučić, P., Cvitković, I. and Despalatović, M. (2023). Marine brown algae *Styopodium schimperi* is going to be the most invasive alien species in the Adriatic Sea. In *5th Croatian Symposium on Invasive species with International Participation* (pp. 31-31).

Figure A.1.1 Non-indigenous macrophytes positive impacts in the Aegean Sea, according to CIMPAL+.

Figure A.1.2 Non-indigenous fish positive impacts in the Aegean Sea, according to CIMPAL+.

Figure A.1.3 Non-indigenous invertebrates positive impacts in the Aegean Sea, according to CIMPAL+.

Figure A.1.4 Distribution of Seagrass meadows in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.5 Distribution of shallow soft substrates (0–60 m depth) in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.6 Distribution of deep soft substrates (60–200 m depth) in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.7 Distribution of soft substrates of the dysphotic zone (deeper than 200 m depth) in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.8 Distribution of shallow hard substrates (0-60 m depth) in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.9 Distribution of deep hard substrates (60-200 m) in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.10 Distribution of hard substrates of the dysphotic zone (deeper than 200 m) in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.11 Distribution of submarine caves in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.12 Distribution of coralligenous formations in the Aegean Sea.

Figure A.1.13 Distribution of the pelagic habitat in the Aegean Sea.

		Impact magnitude				
		Minimal	Minor	Moderate	Major	Massive
Strength of evidence	Robust	0	1	2	4	8
	Medium	0	0	1	2	4
	Limited	0	0	0	1	2

Figure A.1.14 Impact weights $w_{i,j}$ for species i at habitat j based on impact magnitude and strength of evidence, as defined in Figure A.1.12 (based on [13,19]).

11.2 Supplementary material of section 7.8: CIMPAL-ES⁻ and CIMPAL-ES⁺: accounting for cumulative impacts on ecosystem services

Figure A.2.1 Map showing the absolute difference in estimated cumulative negative impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services, comparing the scenario with a 0.5 threshold applied to the species distribution model to the scenario without the threshold. The color gradient represents the difference between the two scenarios per 1 km² cell, with darker shades indicating areas of greater sensitivity. without the threshold. The color gradient represents the difference between the two scenarios per 1 km² cell, with darker shades indicating areas of greater sensitivity.

Figure A.2.2. Map showing the absolute difference in estimated cumulative positive impacts of invasive alien species on ecosystem services, comparing the scenario with a 0.5 threshold applied to the species distribution model to the scenario without the threshold. The color gradient represents the difference between the two scenarios per 1 km² cell, with darker shades indicating areas of greater sensitivity.

Figure A.2.3. 3D graphs illustrate the cumulative negative impacts of invasive species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES-) under two scenarios: with and without a threshold applied to the species distribution model, plotted against latitude and longitude. The colour of each point indicates the difference in CIMPAL-ES- values between the two scenarios for each 1 km²

Figure A.2.4. 3D graphs illustrate the cumulative negative impacts of invasive species on ecosystem services (CIMPAL-ES+) under two scenarios: with and without a threshold applied to the species distribution model, plotted against latitude and longitude. The color of each point indicates the difference in CIMPAL-ES+ values between the two scenarios for each 1 km² cell.

11.3 Satellite-Based Monitoring of Chlorophyll-*a* Concentrations in Izmir Bay

İbrahim Tan, Sabri Mutlu, Ertuğrul Aslan, Alper Evcen, Hakan Atabay

Note: This case study was not included in the initial planning of Deliverable 5.2. It was inspired during the GES4SEAS plenary meeting in Barcelona (May 2025). As it arrived after the completion of the Deliverable, it has been included as an Annex.

11.3.1. Introduction

Water pollution is a worldwide issue. It threatens both aquatic habitats and human health with an increasing alarm rate. Coastal areas are under enormous pressure from land- and sea-based pollutants. Water quality monitoring programs try to manage the impact of these pollutants (Gholizadeh et al., 2016; Lira et al., 2020). However, water quality observations have limited time and spatial resolution and require high cost and effort. Remote sensing technology and satellite data (Hanson and Oltean, 2013; Tapete and Cigna, 2016), with their high spatial and spatial resolution, provide a comprehensive and effective tool for monitoring, assessing, and predicting changes in water bodies (Sunar et al., 2022).

A case study under the DEVOTES project in the SE Bay of Biscay showed that daily satellite chlorophyll-*a* data can effectively capture spatial and temporal variability, offering an advantage over limited in-situ monitoring for calculating the D5.2.1 indicator. In GES4SEAS project, a similar approach was tested in the Romanian coastal waters (Learning Site 9, Section 4.6). This study also aims to implement these methodologies to demonstrate the relationship between satellite images and a limited number of local measurements of the chlorophyll-*a* parameter in Izmir Bay, Eastern Aegean Sea (Learning Site 8), using remote sensing data.

11.3.2 Methods

The research area

Izmir Bay, one of the largest bays in the Eastern Aegean Sea, is located between the coordinates of 38° 32' 9" North and 26° 45' 17" East (Figure 11.3.1). The bay covers a total surface area exceeding 500 km² and holds approximately 11.5 billion m³ of water. It is traditionally divided into three sections: the outer bay, the middle bay, and the inner bay. The inner bay, which is the smallest and shallowest part (57 km²), is particularly vulnerable to anthropogenic activities due to its proximity to urban and industrial areas (Duman et al., 2004).

The primary current observed in Izmir Bay is a cyclonic (counterclockwise) circulation encompassing the entire bay. This circulation is influenced by atmospheric forces such as wind and water exchange with the Aegean Sea. Currents in the inner bay are generally weak and show limited variability. The

inner bay currents form a cyclonic loop constrained by the bay’s geometric structure and bottom topography. Although waters exiting the inner bay tend to disperse outward, the flow remains relatively weak overall (Beşiktepe et al., 2011; Talas et al., 2023).

Hydrodynamic modelling and observational studies indicate that seasonal variations in wind patterns and river discharges significantly affect circulation intensity and stratification within the bay. The vertical structure is typically two-layered during the stratified season, with surface currents directed seaward and deeper inflows bringing more saline Aegean waters into the bay. Such stratification and weak mixing can lead to localized eutrophication and oxygen depletion, particularly in the inner bay, where limited water renewal makes it more sensitive to nutrient loading and organic pollution.

Figure 11.3.1. Izmir Bay monitoring stations and coastal water bodies in the Aegean Sea

Many industries (food processing, chemical industries, oil, soap and paint production, paper and pulp mills, textile industries, and metalworking) located along the shores of the streams and catchment basins flowing into Izmir Bay discharge organic and inorganic pollutants into the rivers, resulting in sediment and water pollution in the bay (Güven et al., 2007). Notably, nearly 20 small rivers flow directly into the inner bay, increasing their exposure to land-based pollution sources (Atgin et al., 1999).

The Databases

In situ Chlorophyll-*a* data were obtained from Integrated Marine Monitoring Programme and Izmir Oceanographic Monitoring Project conducted under the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, Izmir Metropolitan Municipality; respectively. In this study, surface water data of 36 stations, sampled between May and October, from 2010 to 2024, were used.

MODIS-AQUA satellite 8-days observations average data were selected. The temporal coverage of in situ data was considered, and the satellite images with a spatial resolution of 4 km were downloaded. ArcGIS 10.3.1 semi-automatically spatial analysis tool was used to extract data from the satellite images that overlap with monitoring stations. Statistical methods (Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the square of the sample correlation coefficient (R^2) were used to validate the satellite data against the in-situ chlorophyll-*a* data. The SPSS v.26 was used for statistical analysis.

Analyses applied

This case study steps already described in detail in Chapter 4.5. We applied this methodology in Izmir Bay, Eastern Aegean Sea (Learning Site 8) (Figure 11.3.1). The methodology involved reviewing available satellite chlorophyll-*a* products for the region, evaluating their spatial, temporal, and technical characteristics. Based on this assessment, the most suitable satellite products were selected and preliminarily validated using in-situ chlorophyll-*a* data. Finally, the assessment results derived from satellite data were compared with those from in-situ measurements using tools such as SPSS and Grapher.

Assessment Framework

The time period for this study was chosen based on the availability of in-situ data. The study focuses on the time frame of phytoplankton productivity from May to October between 2010 and 2024. Eutrophication threshold values of Izmir Bay were evaluated and chlorophyll-*a* concentration was determined as $3.54 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Izmir Bay and $6.20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Izmir Inner Bay.

11.3.3 Results

11.3.3.1 Izmir Bay Marine waters

A total of 171 data points were analysed. The analysis covered the period 2010-2024. 2017 to 2019 and 2021 were excluded due to the lack of in situ data during the warm season. Relevant satellite observations were also absent. The in-situ chlorophyll-*a* data distribution varied from 0.18 to $7.92 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, and the satellite data varied from 0.52 to $5.92 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. A comparison of the two data sets reveals similar fluctuations between years. In general, there is an overestimation of satellite data compared to in situ values. However, the in-situ measurements for 2024 are higher than the satellite data (Figure 11.3.2).

Figure 11.3.2. Chl-a distribution In-situ and Satellite observations in Izmir Bay waters

Boxplot analysis shows that the interquartile range of satellite and in-situ data are similar. However, extreme values are seen much more frequently after 2020. Additionally, the interquartile range was highest in 2024 (Figure 11.3.3).

(a)

(b)

Figure 11.3.3. Interannual Chlorophyll-a concentrations in Izmir Bay: In Situ (a) vs. Satellite (b)

The in-situ and satellite-derived Chl-*a* values were log-transformed, and then a regression analysis was performed to examine their relationship. These two values show strong positive correlation and a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.80 (Figure 11.3.4). Satellite data of chlorophyll-*a* showed that approximately 80% of the data could be explained by in situ data. A high correlation was shown between satellite images of marine waters less affected by land- and sea-based sources. These results demonstrate the possibility of monitoring the marine waters of Izmir Bay via satellite-derived data. However, in-situ measurements should be used to verify these results at regular intervals.

Figure 11.3.4. Relationship between log-transformed in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations in Izmir Bay.

An unpaired t-test was performed to determine whether chlorophyll-*a* concentrations measured by satellite significantly differ from those collected in-situ. The results showed no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.478$), indicating strong agreement between the two datasets. On average, satellite-derived chlorophyll-*a* values were slightly higher ($2.91 \mu\text{g L}^{-1} \pm 6.01$) than in-situ values ($2.41 \mu\text{g L}^{-1} \pm 7.07$), with a small mean difference of $-0.50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. However, the relatively large standard deviations and wide 95% confidence interval suggest that variations may occur under certain environmental conditions or during specific periods (Table 11.3.1). These findings support the general reliability of satellite data for estimating chlorophyll-*a* but also emphasize the need for regular validation using in-situ measurements.

Table 11.3.1. Comparison of in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-a concentrations (Unpaired t-test)

Parameter	In Situ	Satellite
Mean ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	2.41	2.91
Standard Deviation (SD)	7.07	6.01
Standard Error of the Mean (SEM)	0.541	0.459
Sample Size (n)	171	171
Statistical Test	Value	
Test Type	Unpaired two-tailed t-test	
t Statistic	0.71	
Degrees of Freedom (df)	340	
p-Value	0.48	
Mean Difference (In situ – Satellite)	$-0.50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
95% Confidence Interval	$-1.90 \text{ to } 0.89 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
Statistical Significance	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	

11.3.3.2 Izmir Inner Bay waters

A total of 22 data points were analyzed. The analysis covered the period 2020-2024, but 2021 year were excluded. The reason for the exclusion was the lack of relevant satellite observations. The in-situ chlorophyll-a data distribution varied from 7.60 to 28.91 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, and the satellite data varied from 14.45 to 18.96 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. A comparison of the two data sets reveals similar fluctuations between years. In general, there is an overestimation of satellite data compared to in situ values. However, the in-situ measurements for 2024 are higher than the satellite data (Figure 11.3.5a). The in-situ and satellite-derived Chl-a values were log-transformed, and then a regression analysis was performed to examine their relationship. These two values show weak positive correlation (Figure 11.3.5b). Boxplot analysis shows that the interquartile ranges of satellite and in-situ data are similar. Additionally, the interquartile range is much higher for satellite-derived data (Figure 11.3.5d).

Figure 11.3.5. Chl-*a* distribution In-situ and Satellite observations in Izmir Inner Bay; interannual distribution (a); fit curve (b); box plox (c,d)

An unpaired t-test was performed to determine whether chlorophyll-*a* concentrations measured by satellite significantly differ from those collected in-situ. The results showed no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.72$). On average, satellite-derived chlorophyll-*a* values were much higher ($17.21 \mu\text{g L}^{-1} \pm 6.79$) than in- situ values ($2.41 \mu\text{g L}^{-1} \pm 7.07$), with a high mean difference of $-1.19 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The statistical findings and distribution of the in-situ and satellite data suggest that the result of the unpaired t-test may have been a coincidence (Table 11.3.2).

Table 11.3.2. Comparison of in-situ and satellite Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations (Unpaired t-test)

Parameter	In Situ	Satellite
Mean ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	16.02	17.21
Standard Deviation (SD)	13.94	6.79
Standard Error of the Mean (SEM)	3.04	1.48
Sample Size (n)	21	21
Statistical Test		Value
Test Type		Unpaired two-tailed t-test
t Statistic		0.353
Degrees of Freedom (df)		28.98
p-Value		0.72
Mean Difference (In situ – Satellite)		$-1.19 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
95% Confidence Interval		-8.11 to $5.72 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
Statistical Significance		Not significant ($p > 0.05$)

11.3.3.3 Assessment

The comparison of chlorophyll-*a* concentrations with established ecological thresholds was carried out in two water body types: Izmir Bay marine waters and inner bay waters (Table 11.3.3). In Izmir Bay, the in-situ value (2.41 µg L⁻¹) and the satellite-derived value (2.91 µg L⁻¹) were both below the 3.54 µg L⁻¹ threshold, reflecting good ecological status. In the inner bay, however, Chl-*a* values (16.02 µg L⁻¹ in-situ; 17.21 µg L⁻¹ satellite) were higher than the threshold value of 6.20 µg L⁻¹. The results show that the risk of eutrophication in Izmir Bay is relatively low in areas of the Aegean Sea that interact with offshore waters. However, there is a high eutrophication risk in the inner bay.

Table 11.3.3. Ecological Status Based on Chlorophyll-*a*: In Situ vs. Satellite Data

Water Body	In-situ (µg L ⁻¹)	Satellite obs. (µg L ⁻¹)	Threshold (µg L ⁻¹)
Inner Bay	16.02	17.21	6.20
Marine Waters	2.41	2.91	3.54

11.3.4 Discussion

The ecological status of the inner and outer water body types in the Izmir Bay in the Eastern Aegean Sea was assessed using Chl-*a* concentrations that were measured in situ and derived from satellite data from 2010 to 2024. The comparison of two datasets provides an idea of the reliability of using remote sensing methods instead of in-situ measurements for water quality monitoring.

A strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.80$) was found between in situ and satellite data in the marine waters of Izmir Bay; however, a weak correlation ($R^2 = 0.07$) was found for the inner bay waters (Table 11.3.4). The weak correlation may be explained by a number of factors, including the influence of high-pressure land and sea-based pressures, the resolution of satellite images, lack of in-situ data and the time frame of the satellite images used. Land and sea-based pressures, such as urbanization, creek inputs, harbors, marine transport, and industry, affect Izmir inner bay. The quality of water in coastal areas is impacted by these factors, which have led to the occurrence of algal blooms on occasion. This is due to the presence of elevated nutrient levels and temperatures (Kucuksezgin et al., 2019). The opposite of this situation, less pressure, enough in-situ and satellite images in Izmir Bays waters could be a reason to find strong correlation. Additionally, Izmir Bay is 960 km² in surface area, and the inner bay is 122 km². The MODIS-Aqua satellite has a resolution of 4 km. Thus, Izmir Bay is represented by 240 grids and the inner bay by 30. This may further clarify the reason for the weak correlation of the inner bay's waters.

Table 11.3.4. Satellite data vs in-situ data statistics

Marine Reporting Units	R ²	log 10 RMSE (mg m ⁻³)
Marine waters	0.80	0.026
Inner Bay	0.07	0.52

The results show that all water bodies meet the ecological targets for chlorophyll-*a*. However, inner bay waters require closer monitoring. This is due to higher variability. Satellite-derived data generally correlates well with in-situ measurements, particularly in marine areas. However, some discrepancies remain in optically complex and nearshore waters. Ongoing in-situ validation and improved regional algorithms are essential for effectively using satellite data.

11.3.5 Conclusions

The ecological status of the inner and outer water bodies in Izmir Bay, located in the eastern Aegean Sea, was evaluated using chlorophyll-*a* (Chl-*a*) concentrations measured in situ and derived from satellite data from 2010 to 2024. Comparing the two datasets provides insight into the reliability of using remote sensing methods instead of in situ measurements for water quality monitoring.

The overall conclusions are as follows:

- Satellite-derived data showed that strong correlation with in-situ observations in marine waters. This data may be used to monitor water quality.
- A weak correlation was found with the inner bay, and further research is needed to understand the full implications of this finding. Monitoring of the water quality in the inner bay started in 2017, but frequent monitoring could resume after 2020. In this area, the study should be repeated using long-term data. Satellite data may be use for giving preliminary information about the area water quality.
- In this study 4 km MODIS – Aqua satellite images were used. Higher temporal and spatial resolution satellite imagery can improve the correlation between in-situ and satellite data.

This study should be repeated using high-resolution satellites. Furthermore, its applicability should be investigated by testing in different water bodies in bays such as Saros, Güllük and Gökova. The expectation is for more effective use in water quality assessments following validation with long-term data sets and application in different areas.

11.3.6 References

- Atgin, R. S., El-Agha, O., Zararsız, A., Kocataş, A., Parlak, H., & Tuncel, G. (2000). Investigation of the sediment pollution in Izmir Bay: trace elements. *Spectrochimica Acta Part B: Atomic Spectroscopy*, 55(7), 1151-1164.
- Beşiktepe, Ş. T., Sayın, E., İlhan, T., & Tokat, E. (2011). İzmir Körfezi Akıntı Dinamiğinin Model ve Gözlem Yardımıyla İncelenmesi. *Kıyı Mühendisliği Sempozyumu, Trabzon*, 427-437.
- Duman, M., Avcı, M., Duman, Ş., Demirkurt, E., & Düzbastılar, M. K. (2004). Surficial sediment distribution and net sediment transport pattern in Izmir Bay, western Turkey. *Continental Shelf Research*, 24(9), 965-981.
- Gholizadeh, M. H., Melesse, A. M., & Reddi, L. (2016). A comprehensive review on water quality parameters estimation using remote sensing techniques. *Sensors*, 16(8), 1298.
- Güven, D. E. ve Akıncı, G. (2008). Heavy metals partitioning in the sediments of Izmir Inner Bay. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 20(4), 413–418. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1001-0742\(08\)62072-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1001-0742(08)62072-0)
- Hanson, W.S., Oltean, L.A., (Eds) 2013, *Archaeology from Historical Aerial and Satellite Archives*, Springer, New York.
- Kucuksezgin, F., Gonul, L. T., Pazi, I., & Kacar, A. (2019). Assessment of seasonal and spatial variation of surface water quality: Recognition of environmental variables and fecal indicator bacteria of the coastal zones of Izmir Bay, Eastern Aegean. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 28, 100554.
- Lira, J., & López, P. (2020). The recognition of the remnants of the Royal Road of the interior land using high-resolution multispectral satellite images. *Geofísica internacional*, 59(4), 273-284.
- Sayın, E., Pazi, I., & Eronat, C. (2006). Investigation of water masses in İzmir Bay, western Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Earth Sciences*, 15(3), 343-372.
- Sunar, F., Dervisoglu, A., Yagmur, N., Colak, E., Kuzyaka, E., & Mutlu, S. (2022). How efficient can Sentinel-2 data help spatial mapping of mucilage event in the Marmara Sea?. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 43, 181-186.
- Talas, E., Duman, M., Eronat, A. H., & Kuçuksezgin, F. (2023). Multi-index assessment of sea bottom sediments of the Izmir Gulf, Aegean Sea: A study of interrelation between anthropogenic and hydrodynamic effects. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 194, 115293.
- Tapete D., Cigna F., 2016, Trends and perspectives of space-borne SAR remote sensing in archaeological landscape and cultural heritage applications, *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, in press, doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2016.07.017.

11.4 Supplementary material of section 7.7 Case study 16: Implementation of expanded CIMPAL in the European Seas – LS10

2025